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A METHOD FOR SUPPORTING REQUIREMENTS CHANGE
MANAGEMENT IN SOFTWARE ECOSYSTEMS
BASED ON OPEN INNOVATION AND CROWDRE

Paulo Robson Campelo Malcher

Orientador

Rodrigo Pereira dos Santos

Coorientador

Davi Viana dos Santos

RIO DE JANEIRO, RJ - BRASIL

SETEMBRO DE 2024

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EXAMINADORA ABAIXO ASSINADA.

Aprovada por:

Rodrigo Pereira dos Santos, D.Sc. - UNIRIO

Davi Viana dos Santos, D.Sc. - UFMA

Gleison dos Santos Souza, D.Sc. - UNIRIO

Paulo Sergio Medeiros dos Santos, D.Sc. - UNIRIO

Carina Frota Alves, D.Sc. - UFPE

Igor Scalante Wiese, D.Sc. - UTFPR

Pablo Oliveira Antonino de Assis, D.Sc. - Fraunhofer IESE

RIO DE JANEIRO, RJ - BRASIL

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RESUMO

Ecossistemas de software (ECOS) são sistemas complexos e dinâmicos que compreendem vários componentes de software, plataformas e desenvolvedores que interagem entre si. Eles são parte integrante do desenvolvimento de software moderno e estão se tornando um contexto predominante. ECOS introduzem complexidade à gerência de requisitos devido à sua natureza aberta e dinâmica. Gerenciar mudanças de requisitos em ECOS é um desafio devido aos múltiplos atores que colaboram através de diversas fronteiras organizacionais e podem formar multidões distintas. Para preencher essa lacuna, propõe-se SECO-RCI, um método para auxiliar profissionais na identificação de mudanças de requisitos em ECOS baseado em inovação aberta e engenharia de requisitos baseada em multidão (do inglês, *crowd-based requirements engineering* - CrowdRE). SECO-RCI está fundamentado em um modelo conceitual para gerenciamento de requisitos em ECOS (SECO-RM), que foi construído a partir de um estudo terciário, um mapeamento sistemático da literatura e três estudos de campo e avaliado utilizando o método Delphi. SECO-RCI foi avaliado quanto à sua aceitação, considerando sua utilidade e facilidade de uso. Para isso, foi conduzido um grupo focal e um estudo de caso. No grupo focal, foram reunidos *insights* e sugestões sobre a estrutura e conteúdo do método de cinco especialistas com experiência prática em gerenciamento de requisitos em ECOS. No estudo de caso, foi envolvido um profissional que aplicou SECO-RCI a um cenário do mundo real dentro de uma empresa de software global. Os resultados mostraram que nosso método pode auxiliar os profissionais na identificação de mudanças de requisitos e apoiar a comunicação de mudanças de requisitos entre múltiplos atores de multidões distintas dentro de um ECOS.

Palavras-chave: Ecossistemas de Software, Gerência de Requisitos, Inovação Aberta, Engenharia de Requisitos baseada em Multidão.

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ABSTRACT

Software ecosystems (SECO) are complex and dynamic systems comprising several software components, platforms, and developers that interact with each other. They are an integral part of modern software development and are becoming a predominant context. SECO introduce complexity in requirements management due to their open and dynamic nature. Managing requirements changes in SECO is challenging due to multiple actors that collaborate across several organizational boundaries and can create distinct crowds. To bridge this gap, we propose SECO-RCI, a method to assist professionals in requirements change identification in SECO based on open innovation and crowd-based requirements engineering (CrowdRE). SECO-RCI is grounded in a conceptual model for requirements management in SECO (SECO-RM), built from a tertiary study, a systematic mapping study (SMS), and three field studies and evaluated using the Delphi method. We evaluated SECO-RCI regarding its acceptance, considering its usefulness and ease of use. To do so, we conducted a focus group and a case study. In the focus group, we gathered insights and suggestions on the method structure and content from five experts with practical experience in requirements management in SECO. In the case study, we involved one professional who applied SECO-RCI to a real-world scenario within a global company. The results showed that our method can assist professionals in requirements change identification in SECO and support requirements change communication among multiple actors of distinct crowds within a SECO.

Keywords: Software Ecosystems, Requirements Management, Open Innovation, Crowd-based Requirements Engineering.

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List of Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
BS	Backward Snowballing
CAP	Contribution Acceptance Process
CBSOft	Brazilian Conference on Software: Theory and Practice
CLEI	Latin American Computing Conference
CRD	Centre for Reviews and Disseminations
CrowdRE	Crowd-based Requirements Engineering
CTDSI	Thesis and Dissertation Contest on Information Systems
CTO	Chief Technology Officer
DARE	Database of Abstracts of Reviews of Effects
DBS	Database Search
DevOps	Development and Operations
DSRM	Design Science Research Methodology
DSR	Design Science Research
EBSE	Evidence-based Software Engineering
EC	Exclusion Criteria
FS	Forward Snowballing
GQM	Goal-Question-Metric
GSD	Global Software Development
GT	Grounded Theory
IC	Inclusion Criteria
ICSOB	International Conference on Software Business
IQR	Interquartile Range
KPI	Key performance indicator
LLS	Longitudinal Literature Studies

MSECO	Mobile Software Ecosystem
OSS	Open Source Software
OSSECO	Open Source Software Ecosystem
PDD	Process-Deliverable Diagram
PSECO	Proprietary Software Ecosystem
QC	Quality Criteria
RAMBO	Requirements Analysis and Management for Benefiting Openness
RCN	Requirements Communication Network
RE	Requirements Engineering
ReuseSEEM	Reuse-based Software Ecosystems Engineering and Management
RQ	Research Questions
RRC	Rational Requirements Composer
RTC	Rational Team Concert
SBES	Brazilian Symposium on Software Engineering
SBSI	Brazilian Symposium on Information Systems
SBQS	Brazilian Symposium on Software Quality
SD	Standard Deviation
SDK	Software Development Kit
SE	Software Engineering
SECO	Software Ecosystems
SECO-RM	Requirements Management in Software Ecosystems
SECO-RCI	Requirements Change Identification in Software Ecosystems
SIA	Stakeholder Influence Analysis
SOLAR	Online Learning System
SLR	Systematic Literature Review
SMS	Systematic Mapping Study
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
VLE	Virtual Learning Environment
WER	Thesis and Dissertations Workshop on Software
WTDSI	Thesis and Dissertation Workshop on Information Systems
WTDSOft	Thesis and Dissertations Workshop on Software

Chapter 1. Introduction

1.1 Context

In recent years, there has been a significant change in the way software companies function. Several concepts related to the reduction of organizational boundaries and the collaboration of multiple actors (internal and external to the organization) to build products over a common technological platform have emerged. In this context, software producers increasingly rely on other companies to deliver value to their customers. They use these platforms as a type of open innovation to expand their markets and as the foundation for forming software ecosystems (SECO) [1]. In SECO, the platform provider, also known as keystone, collaborates and innovates with other organizations, providing additional value on top of the platform core product while also sharing the risk of betting on the wrong requirements [2, 3].

SECO are complex and dynamic systems comprising several software components, platforms, and developers that interact with each other [1]. They have emerged as a paradigm for understanding dynamics and heterogeneity in collaborative software development [4]. According to Figalst et al. [5], one of the major differences between collaborative software development by distributed teams in the context of global software development (GSD) and SECO is the fact that the SECO actors are not within the same company or organization but instead spread across several organizations. This scenario entails several types of relationships between actors in an ecosystem, e.g., the actors can be competitors and/or share mutual benefits (“cooperation”) [6].

According to Bianco et al. [7], SECO emerged because companies realized that the functionality needed to satisfy customer needs was more than what their capacity could handle. Ghimire et al. [3] mentioned that companies such

as HubSpot¹, Salesforce², Xero³, Slack⁴, Shopify⁵, and Wix⁶ have thrived from their integration, marketplace, innovation, and other qualities that make a thriving SECO. Santos et al. [8] presented some examples of SECO as Eclipse Foundation⁷ and Apache Foundation⁸ (SECO based on a set of projects held by different actors and communities), SAP⁹ and Amazon¹⁰ (SECO based on source code and other artifacts protected by confidentiality agreements), and iOS¹¹ and Android¹² (SECO based on both proprietary and open source contributions). According to Fontão et al. [9], organizations such as Amazon, Apple, and Google have invested in platforms to engage a critical mass of external developers that help them develop and evolve contributions to these platforms.

The concept of SECO has impacted the platform business and research world, and over a short period, scientists and companies have conceptualized and realized SECO in a way that has significantly affected society and the software industry [1]. SECO are increasingly popular because of their economic, strategic, and technical advantages [10]. Companies are building SECO to gain competitive advantages by developing digital services together for customers [11]. For Damian et al. [2] and Ghimire et al. [3], SECO are becoming a predominant software development context and are an integral part of modern software development, with several stakeholders collaborating to develop, maintain, and evolve a complex software system.

SECO have become an active software engineering (SE) research field, gaining popularity over the last decades [12]. They introduced changes in how disciplines of SE are addressed in practice, including requirements engineering (RE) [13, 14, 15]. In SECO, a keystone should consider the requirements of three different types of users: users of their products, external developers who build applications and interact with the common technological platform, and users of these external

¹<https://www.hubspot.com/>

²<https://www.salesforce.com/>

³<https://www.xero.com/>

⁴<https://slack.com/>

⁵<https://www.shopify.com/>

⁶<https://www.wix.com/>

⁷<https://www.eclipse.org/org/foundation/>

⁸<https://www.apache.org/>

⁹<https://www.sap.com/>

¹⁰<https://www.amazon.com/>

¹¹<https://www.apple.com/br/ios/>

¹²<https://www.android.com/>

developers [2, 16]. According to Johnson et al. [16], the RE process in SECO now extends to the platform and has three major focuses: RE for the product, RE for the platform, and RE for the ecosystem.

1.2 Motivation

SECO introduces complexity in requirements management [1, 2, 17, 18, 19]. Requirements management is a key area within RE and an effective means to ensure the quality of software [20, 21, 22]. It is a continuous process that runs throughout software development and requires all stakeholders' participation to agree on potential requirements change [23]. However, the dynamic set of stakeholders in SECO introduces challenges to understanding and managing the different stakeholder requirements [17]. Moreover, the complexity and changing nature of SECO result in several new requirements based on ecosystem trends called emergent requirements. Emergent requirements make requirements management difficult in SECO [18].

According to Damian et al. [2], managing several requirements in SECO brings challenges to the partnerships between the keystone and external developers. For Linåker et al. [19], these challenges are related to the conflicting agendas and a lack of control over several requirements of the SECO's multiple actors, resulting in the misalignment of internal RE processes. Moreover, Vegendla et al. [14] performed a systematic mapping study (SMS) on RE in SECO and claimed that more research should be performed to investigate the current state of requirements management in SECO. Hence, investigating how requirements management is carried out in SECO can help professionals improve their practices and researchers better understand this field.

To illustrate the complexity of requirements management in SECO, we can mention the case of the Xero ecosystem. Xero is a software-producing organization that provides accounting software as a service to small businesses and their advisors. It also provides access to a service platform that allows other software developers to access their data and extend and enhance its product. Xero evolved from a company that primarily offered an accounting solution to a SECO that enables a full suite of small business solutions with its own offering at the core [2]. The RE process within

the Xero ecosystem has three major focuses: RE for the Xero product, RE for the Xero platform, and RE for the Xero ecosystem [16]. The multiple actors involved in the RE process include the Xero product users, app developers, and the users of the partner applications [16], as shown in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Requirement flow in the Xero ecosystem. Source: [16]

The requirements related to the Xero ecosystem (i.e., requirements of Xero product, requirements of Xero platform, requirements of Xero’s overall ecosystem) are identified through several communication channels used by multiple actors involved in SECO, which makes requirements management more complex [16]. For example, the requirements of Xero products are identified through a user forum with a feature request channel and direct communication with users through sales support and conferences. The requirements of the Xero platform are identified through communication with app developers. Developers also have channels for direct communication through conferences and the partner program. The requirements of Xero’s overall ecosystem are identified through the partner program by working directly with app partners and through the app marketplace. Additionally, Xero has a connected app section within its general user forum. Finally, partner apps also have their own RE processes that may differ from the keystone and have their own communication channels to identify requirements [16].

Given the inherent difficulty in managing requirements in SECO due to their open, dynamic, and distributed nature, an effective strategy to enhance the requirements management of a SECO involves requirements change management.

In other words, the focus is not on preventing requirements change from occurring but on identifying and managing them in the best possible way. Requirements change management is a critical activity of requirements management in SECO, as projects in a SECO co-evolve through inter-dependencies, i.e., changes to one project may cause ripple effects to many other downstream ones [24]. However, traditional software development approaches focus mainly on the engineering and adaptation of a single software system within the scope of a single project and a single organization, neglecting the SECO context [25].

1.3 Problem

Requirements changes are inevitable in software development [26, 27]. They may arise at any stage of the software development process due to different internal and external factors, e.g., customer needs, technological changes, market change, budget change, and global competition [28, 29]. Dynamic requirements change is among the principal difficulties that software businesses face [30]. According to Ali and Lai [31], the effect of requirements changes is beneficial for a project if changes are addressed appropriately at the right time; otherwise, they may result in project failure. Requirements changes naturally impact the project's cost, quality, and schedule, creating additional work in design and coding [26, 32]. Therefore, it is not just important but crucial for the success of the final product to understand and manage requirements change during software development [28, 29, 30, 33].

In modern software development, software projects are increasingly complex, and professionals encounter several challenges in handling requirements changes [34]. Studies highlighted these challenges in different software development contexts, such as agile development [35], GSD [29], development and operations (DevOps) [36], and SECO [37]. SECO are complex social systems that struggle with scale, mismatched priorities, heterogeneous levels and areas of expertise, and limits on communication and collaboration [38]. Any discernible (and sometimes even apparently trivial) software change will affect, for better or worse, its surrounding ecosystem [38]. In SECO, changes to one product can have ripple effects on several others, introduce conflicts, and be unexpected and disruptive, rippling through the ecosystem and triggering rework [37].

The ideal recipient for a given request usually changes over time in SECO, and it is necessary to periodically rethink the way requirements travel through the software organizations and which roles are responsible for seeking alignment of goals [18]. Moreover, how, when, and by whom changes are performed in a SECO is subject to (often implicit) negotiation among several ecosystem actors [37]. According to Bogart et al. [37], the multiple SECO actors can deal with changes in different ways: (i) keystone can decide how to make a change, may invest additional effort to make it easier to adopt the change, or may decide to accept opportunity costs for not making a change; (ii) external developers may regularly monitor changes in their dependencies and try to influence their development or may rework their own products; and (iii) users may encounter defects if changes are not made or installation difficulties if the repository's products have become incompatible.

Requirements change management is an important activity to requirements management, but it remains underexplored in the SECO field [14]. Problems related to incomplete and/or hidden requirements and requirements change management still affect requirements management in other software development contexts [39]. However, managing requirements change in SECO is challenging due to openness, scalability, mismatched priorities, heterogeneous levels and areas of expertise, and limits on communication and collaboration [2, 19, 38]. Moreover, there is a lack of guidelines for the RE process in SECO [14]. In summary, managing requirements changes in SECO is challenging due to the need to deal with inherent uncertainty and partner integration [40], and critical aspects still require investigation. In particular, **a significant gap exists regarding requirements change identification that can affect SECO.**

SECO enable interaction between multiple actors of the different organizations that form distinct crowds that can communicate relevant recent or upcoming changes on different communication channels [16, 37]. In practice, software professionals often face challenges in requirements change identification due to the openness and dynamism of SECO with the interdependence between multiple products and the integration between them and the common technological platform [18]. Bogart et al. [37] highlighted that traditional centralized change control or change management approaches (e.g., change control boards and roadmapping) break down with the

open, dynamic, and distributed nature of SECO. Moreover, tools for change impact analysis face challenges with the scale and openness of SECO [37]. Therefore, meeting the expectations of multiple users in SECO requires new approaches (e.g., models, methods, and tools) that involve this multitude of stakeholders in RE activities [41], ensuring the identification of these changes when considering the ecosystem.

Another challenge is understanding requirements management in SECO, which is an area still gaining maturity with researchers working in isolation to develop solutions to domain-specific problems [42]. Hence, even though research on this topic has grown in recent years, we still do not fully understand how managing requirements in SECO and all the details that come with it [14]. This understanding is essential to foster discussion within the research community, establish a common ground for communication, and promote the development of strategies for dealing with requirement changes in SECO. Given this scenario, we can formulate the research problems addressed by this thesis as follows:

- **Problem statement #1 - The lack of a shared understanding of requirements management in SECO:** Investigating requirements management in the context of SECO requires a shared understanding of the field. Such a shared understanding must encapsulate the specific characteristics of SECO, facilitating a common ground for discussion and advancement in the field. In summary, the problem is the lack of a shared and well-defined understanding of requirements management in SECO, which can hinder progress in the research and development of SECO;
- **Problem statement #2 - The need to improve the requirements change identification in SECO:** In light of the open, dynamic, and distributed nature of SECO, ensuring the requirements change identification poses a significant challenge. This challenge demands dealing with a crowd of multi-party actors, several feedback channels, and emergent requirements. Therefore, the problem is developing a strategy that can effectively accommodate the intrinsic openness of SECO, the dynamism of actors in this context and the identification of requirements change.

1.4 Objectives and Research Questions

Based on the problem statements, the objectives of this thesis can be defined as:

- To investigate what is known and how requirements management is carried out in SECO, including its key concepts and relationships;
- To develop a solution that helps professionals improve requirements change identification in SECO, considering their open, dynamic, and distributed nature.

Aiming to achieve these objectives, we defined the following research questions (RQ):

- **RQ1:** Which concepts are involved in requirements management in SECO, and how do they relate?
- **RQ2:** How to improve requirements change identification in SECO?

In summary, we present a conceptual model for requirements management in SECO, outlining related concepts and their relationships to address RQ1. According to Chazette et al. [43], a conceptual model helps abstract, understand, and communicate information regarding a given domain. For RQ2, we propose a method to help professionals improve requirements change identification in SECO based on open innovation and crowd-based RE (CrowdRE). This method is an artifact that advances the knowledge of requirements management in SECO. Figure 1.2 presents the research strategy used in this thesis that is detailed in Chapter 3.

1.5 Thesis Outline

This thesis is organized into nine chapters. This chapter presented the context of our work, outlined the motivation for this research, and identified the problems that represent gaps in both theory and practice.

Chapter 2 provides the theoretical background for understanding this thesis, introducing the fundamental aspects of traditional SECO, requirements management, open innovation, and CrowdRE, setting the groundwork for the discussions and analyses in the subsequent chapters.

Figure 1.2: Research strategy.

Chapter 3 presents the research method adopted in this study, based on Design Science Research Methodology (DSRM). This chapter explains how each step of the DSRM has been tailored to this research context.

Chapter 4 reports the state of the art on SECO and requirements management in SECO. Firstly, we performed a tertiary study on SECO and identified different aspects and subdomains investigated. We proposed a thematic map on SECO research topics and presented future research directions for the SECO field. Lastly, we performed an SMS on requirements management in SECO to identify its characteristics and existing approaches.

Chapter 5 reports the state of practice of requirements management in SECO. We conducted three field studies to better understand requirements management practices in SECO. The first field study aimed to investigate the stakeholders' perceptions of requirements management in a specific SECO. The second field study aimed to investigate the use of open innovation practices to support requirements management in SECO. The third field study aimed to investigate whether and how user feedback from a crowd is considered in requirements management in SECO.

Chapter 6 introduces a conceptual model for requirements management in SECO, referred as SECO-RM, derived from our SMS and field studies findings. It encompasses the key concepts and relationships relevant to requirements management in SECO.

Chapter 7 presents the proposed solution of this thesis. It introduces a method

to help professionals in requirements change identification in SECO based on open innovation and CrowdRE.

Chapter 8 details the studies we carried out to evaluate the method's acceptance. To do so, we conducted a focus group with experts with theoretical and practical experience in requirements management in SECO and a single case study at an application-oriented research institute in Europe.

Chapter 9 concludes this thesis. We present the final remarks, the contributions, and the limitations of this research. Finally, we point out future work.

Appendix A presents the links to supplementary materials of all studies performed in this thesis that are available in an open-access repository.

Chapter 2. Background

2.1 Introduction

This chapter provides a background on SECO, requirements management, open innovation, and CrowdRE. We present SECO definitions, characteristics, elements, and types. Next, we delve into the requirements management concept, emphasizing requirements change management. Moreover, we introduce the open innovation and CrowdRE concepts and present their importance for requirements management in SECO. Together, these concepts form the basis for understanding the contributions presented in this thesis.

This chapter is organized as follows: Section 2.2 presents the SECO concept and its inherent characteristics. Section 2.3 provides the fundamental concepts of requirements management. Section 2.4 explores concepts related to open innovation. Section 2.5 focuses on the CrowdRE. These two last sections present important concepts for our proposal, providing an overview of the central aspects of open innovation and CrowdRE (Section 2.4 and 2.5, respectively). Section 2.6 presents related work and Section 2.7 the final remarks of the chapter.

2.2 Software Ecosystems

Barbosa et al. [44] and Manikas [45] mentioned that research on SECO started in 2003 in the book by Messerschmitt and Szyperski [46]. According to Mens and Roover [12], since the seminal book by Messerschmitt and Szyperski [46], SECO have become an active topic of research in SE inspired by concepts from business and natural ecosystems. The identification of definitions, characteristics, elements, and types of SECO facilitates its understanding. We detail these aspects in the following subsections.

2.2.1 Definitions

In contrast to natural ecosystems, there is not a common definition of SECO [4]. SECO can be defined and interpreted from different perspectives [12]. Messerschmitt and Szyperski [46] proposed the oldest definition of SECO found in the literature. Since then, the research literature has provided different SECO definitions [12]. We identified 10 SECO definitions in the literature that are present in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: SECO definitions.

Year	SECO definition	Source
2003	<i>“collection of software products that have some degree of symbiotic relationships”</i>	Messerschmitt and Szyperski [46]
2004	<i>“sets of actors functioning as a unit and interacting with a shared market for software and services, together with the relationships among them”</i>	Iansiti and Levien [47]
2009	<i>“set of software solutions that enable, support and automate the activities and transactions by the actors in the associated social or business ecosystem and the organizations that provide these solutions”</i>	Bosch [48]
2009	<i>“set of businesses functioning as a unit and interacting with a shared market for software and services together with the relationships among them. These relationships are frequently underpinned by a common technological platform or market and operate through the exchange of information, resources, and artifacts”</i>	Jansen et al. [49]
2010	<i>“collection of software projects which are developed and evolve together in the same environment”</i>	Lungu et al. [50]
2012	<i>“a networked community of organizations, which base their relations to each other on a common interest in a central software technology”</i>	Hanssen [51]
2013	<i>“interaction of a set of actors on top of a common technological platform that results in a number of software solutions or services”</i>	Manikas and Hansen [6]
2013	<i>“collections of suppliers and buyers of software products, components, and technologies collaboratively create competitive value”</i>	Jansen and Cusumano [52]
2014	<i>“universe of shared assets centered around a common technical platform. In this universe, various roles, mainly suppliers and consumers, interact in order to develop, manage, and consume assets”</i>	Berger et al. [10]
2016	<i>“the software and actor interaction in relation to a common technological infrastructure, that results in a set of contributions and influences directly or indirectly the ecosystem”</i>	Manikas [45]

According to Mens and Roover [12], Manikas [45] combined all the perspectives used in the other SECO definitions into a single all-encompassing SECO definition. Hence, we considered the definition of Manikas [45] as the main SECO definition in this thesis.

2.2.2 Characteristics

There is a significant body of research on SECO, and their common characteristics have been identified in several works [5, 6, 44, 53, 54, 55]. According to Lettner et al. [53], there is a growing agreement about SECO’s general characteristics. We summarize the main SECO characteristics in Table 2.2 and present them next.

The interaction of **internal and external developers** over a common technological platform is a SECO characteristic. This interaction takes software

Table 2.2: SECO characteristics.

Characteristic	Source
Internal and external developers	[5, 44, 53, 54, 55]
Common technological platform	[53, 55]
Keystone	[44, 53]
Platform enabling external contributions	[44, 53, 55]
Variability-enabled architectures	[44, 53, 54, 55]
Shared core assets	[53]
Automated and tool-supported product derivation	[53, 55]
External contributions included in the common technological platform	[53]
Tools, frameworks and patterns	[53, 55]
Distribution channel	[53, 55]
Innovative processes	[44, 54, 55]
Co-evolution of software projects	[6, 44, 55]

development beyond the boundaries of organizations [44]. These internal and external actors also can include keystones, developers, and users, who work together to create several software solutions or services [53]. The existence of a **common technological platform** to support a specific technology and a class of applications is another SECO characteristic. Such a platform consists of a technological basis, an extensible and adaptable framework solution, a set of reusable core components, and often a set of ready-to-use standard solutions [53].

The existence of a **keystone** that provides a platform and collaborates and innovates with other actors is also a SECO characteristic [53]. Keystone is a central organization that provides the necessary support and resources to facilitate the development and growth of the ecosystem. Another SECO characteristic is the design and implementation of a **platform enabling external contributions**, i.e., it must have some degree of openness [53]. This external contribution can be achieved using different mechanisms such as distinctive interfaces for external developers, extension points allowing specific interventions, or even the complete source code opening.

Another SECO characteristic is that the common technological platform relies on a **variability-enabled architectures**, meaning external developers can build applications by selecting and configuring features and components from the core framework [53]. The common technological platform of a SECO has to facilitate the development of a set of applications customized to the customers' specific needs. The existence of reusable features and components in SECO, which are also called **shared core assets**, is also a SECO characteristic [53]. They are used to create products in a prescribed way for use by many actors.

The **automated and tool-supported product derivation** by external

developers or even users is also a SECO characteristic [53]. A set of generator mechanisms is provided actually to build products from configurations. **External contributions included in the common technological platform** is another SECO characteristic. Contributions and extensions provided by internal and external developers result in a pool of potentially reusable solutions that can serve as valuable assets for future development [53].

SECO rely on **tools, frameworks, and patterns** to manage the development and evolution of the variability-enabled architecture, the common technological platform, the shared core assets, and contributions. For instance, processes and guidelines may define how specific solutions can be built [53]. The existence of an accessible **distribution channel** for third-party developments is also a SECO characteristic. The organization building the core platform usually provides a distribution channel. It has a distinctive interface and process to support external developers in delivering their solutions and an easily accessible customer interface for obtaining the solutions [53].

Innovative processes enable both the keystone and the external actors to have opportunities to provide ideas to solve business problems in SECO, extending the organization's innovative strategy and supporting both reactive and proactive business innovations [54]. Another SECO characteristic is the **co-evolution of software projects** within the same environment. This environment can be organizational, such as a company, social, such as an open-source community, or technical, such as the Ruby ecosystem [3]. This co-evolution allows for the development of diverse solutions and services that meet the needs of the ecosystem's users [6].

2.2.3 Elements

Santos and Werner [56] identified three key elements for SECO: software, transactions, and relationships. The software element refers to the common technology platform, core software technology, software solutions, software platform, or product line. The transactions element includes profit or reward models, as well as non-financial benefits, e.g., something that an actor would obtain by engaging in open source communities. The relationships element involves connections between

actors based on software and transactions.

Regarding roles that the multiple actors in a SECO can take on, Lima et al. [57] stated that an actor can have specific roles in a SECO, being characterized as a company or other type of organization, a developer, an user, a supplier or a customer and, in general, can encompass any other involved or interested. Hanssen [51] identified three key roles: keystone (leading platform development), users (relying on the platform for their business), and external developers (creating related solutions). Damian et al. [2] reinforced these roles and claimed that there are three different, but sometimes overlapping, sets of stakeholders in SECO: the users of the own offering of keystone, the external developers (the third-party organizations that offer solutions and services), and the external developers' users.

It is possible to establish a SECO vision in three dimensions, initially distinguished by Campbell and Ahmed [58] and evolved by Santos and Werner [59], divided into technical, business and social. Regarding the technical dimension, the objective is platform openness and the development of third-party agents. The factors that guide this dimension are: development infrastructure, governance, and requirements management. In the business dimension, the objective is related to collaboration, competitiveness, stakeholder expectations and the environmental impact on productivity. The factors that guide this dimension are: environmental vision, innovation and strategic planning. Finally, the social dimension focuses on the organization's openness as a whole, the platform community and collaboration for development. The factors that guide this dimension are: usefulness, promotion and knowledge gain [59].

2.2.4 Types

According to García-Holgado and García-Peñalvo [60], SECO can be classified according to two dimensions, the first related to the type of license and the second to the type of device. Regarding the first classification dimension, Manikas [45] classified SECO into: (i) proprietary (PSECO): where confidentiality agreements protect the source code and other artifacts produced, as they are the products that would produce revenue for the ecosystem, e.g. platform as a service and e-commerce ecosystems; (ii) open source (OSSECO): where actors do not participate in obtaining

direct income from their activity in the ecosystem, e.g. Eclipse Foundation and Apache Foundation; or (iii) hybrid: that supports proprietary and open source contributions, e.g. iOS SECO can use proprietary strategies such as the app store and source code repository to drive policy on the technology platform and open source strategies for community engagement such as tools, submission, and publication contributions.

Regarding the second dimension, García-Holgado and García-Peñalvo [60] mentioned that a SECO can be: (i) mobile: where a set of collaborative systems, users and developers that create complex relationships driven by competition and cooperation and have their focus on the mobile application market; or (ii) embedded: where an organization synchronizes development between all parties involved and has full control of the final product software content. Software development within the ecosystem and the artifacts flow are hierarchically controlled by this organization and there is an independent operation for developing and deploying components on the platform.

2.3 Requirements Management

Requirements management is a process that accompanies the planning and development of a system, capturing and mapping the origin and context of changes [61]. It is an organized process that encompasses tasks that maintain evolving requirements such as requirements documentation, analysis (negotiation), traceability, prioritization, change control, and communication [23, 62]. It describes the elements that need to be accomplished during a project, including how to control and track requirements as well as requirements change [63]. The requirements management process must be continuous and occur during the entire project's life cycle [64, 63]. In addition, it must be iterative and refined over time [65].

Requirements management provides visibility for the development process of the software, which is a guarantee for the success of the software [22]. It establishes a baseline for the project management and aims to: (i) organize the identified requirements; (ii) control the requirements change; (iii) maintain requirements traceability; and (iv) manage the artifacts containing information regarding requirements [66]. Xu et al. [22] identified three

important requirements management activities: requirements baseline maintenance, requirements traceability, and requirements change management.

Requirement baseline maintenance is the activity that aims to maintain a summary of the results of the requirements development process that has been formally reviewed and agreed upon and will continue to play a role in the subsequent product life cycle [22]. Requirements traceability is the activity that aims to follow the life of a requirement in both a forward and backward direction, that is, from its origins, through its development and specification, to its subsequent deployment and use, and through periods of ongoing refinement and iteration [22]. Requirements change management is the activity that aims to manage requirements change during the RE process, system development, and maintenance process. It involves the requirements change identification, requirements change analysis, and requirements change cost estimation [22]. This thesis focuses on requirements change identification in SECO. Therefore, we detail the requirements change management activity next.

Change is an intrinsic characteristic of the SE compared to other engineering and a challenging aspect of the RE process [28, 67]. Jayatilleke and Lai [28] claimed that it is anticipated that requirements will change during a project life cycle, and such volatility constitutes one of the top ten risks to successful software project development. Requirements volatility is “the tendency of requirements to change over time in response to the evolving needs of customers, stakeholders, the organization and the work environment” [36, 68]. A requirements change is an addition/modification/deletion/bug fix or combination of these in terms of functional and non-functional requirements presented in any form [69].

Requirements change management is a collaboration-driven process that requires communication and coordination between several stakeholders to be successful [70]. It enables software development organizations to deliver quality products per clients’ expectations [70]. Jayatilleke and Lai [28] identified three key areas of the requirements change management: change identification, change analysis, and change cost estimation. According to the authors, it is important to understand how these areas can be practically implemented and what best practices are available in an organizational setting. Jayatilleke and Lai [28] highlighted that none of these areas are standalone and need to communicate with each other regarding updates

and verification.

Requirements change identification is an area that indicates why, by whom, and when a requirements change is required [28, 71]. The other requirements change management areas will be based on the correct requirements change identification [28]. Understanding what needs to be changed is a significant factor in the requirements change management process that helps clarify how the demanded change can be implemented [71]. According to Jayatilleke and Lai [28], there are two major activities within requirements change identification: requirements change elicitation, and requirements change representation.

Once a change has been identified, it must be further analyzed to understand its impact on the software system [28]. Requirements change impact analysis is an area that aims to “*identify the potential consequences, including side effects and ripple effects, of a change, or estimating what needs to be modified to accomplish a change before it has been made*” [72]. Software cost/effort estimation is an area of predicting the effort required to develop a software system [73]. Therefore, there is a need to estimate the additional cost/effort for implementation of the change [28].

2.4 Open Innovation

Chesbrough [74] introduced the concept of open innovation, highlighting how knowledge creation is linked to an open vision of the organization. Chesbrough [74] initially defined open innovation as “*a paradigm that assumes that firms can and should use external ideas as well as internal ideas, and internal and external paths to market, as the firms look to advance their technology*”. After three years, Chesbrough et al. [75] updated the definition as “*the use of purposive inflows and outflows of knowledge to accelerate internal innovation and expand the markets for external use of innovation, respectively*”. In a more recent definition, Chesbrough et al. [76] considered into account the possibility of non-pecuniary information circulation and defined it as: “*a distributed innovation process based on purposively managed knowledge flows across organizational boundaries, using pecuniary and non-pecuniary mechanisms in line with the organization’s business model*”. Two features stand out in all these definitions: (i) the existence of several parties (i.e., organizations); and (ii) the voluntary exchange of knowledge and ideas

(i.e., intellectual capital) in pursuit of innovation.

Previous studies have classified open innovation processes [77, 78]. Three different processes have been discussed in the literature: the inbound (or outside-in) open innovation process, the outbound (or inside-out) open innovation process, and the coupled open innovation process. The inbound process is characterized by knowledge flowing from the external environment to the organization. This process can increase innovativeness at organizations and enrich the company's own knowledge by introducing suppliers, customers, and external knowledge sourcing [77]. The outbound process involves the flow of internally developed knowledge to the external environment. This process refers to maximizing the return on investment by transferring ideas to the outside market with the purpose of bringing ideas to market much faster than they could through internal development [77]. In the coupled open innovation process, the inbound and outbound processes are combined to develop and commercialize innovation jointly. This process refers to co-creation with other partners, e.g., alliances, cooperation, and joint ventures, where give and take are necessary for success [77].

Software, with its flexibility in multiple aspects, is an excellent enabler for open innovation [79]. According to Munir et al. [80], software organizations have been exposed to new facets of openness that go beyond their experience and provide opportunities outside their organizational walls. The inherent flexibility of software, combined with the increase in software cost and value for new products and services, puts SE into the hotspot of open innovation [79]. Munir et al. [79] stated that there is unquestionable potential that open innovation can bring to the software industry. Open source software is the most straightforward application of open innovation to software development, although not the only one [81]. Other software development contexts, such as outsourcing, crowdsourcing and funding, GSD, and agile development, benefit from open innovation [79]. Munir et al. [79] concluded that open innovation provides several benefits that force these companies to re-think and often significantly change their current innovation strategies. According to the authors, it pushes the software industry into a new ground where well-known and checked software development and management strategies must be revisited.

2.5 Crowd-based Requirements Engineering

The rise of social media platforms has significantly increased the volume of feedback from software users. As a response, the RE community has initiated a shift toward data-driven and user-centered prioritization, planning, and management of requirements [82, 83]. Groen et al. [84] highlighted that performing RE with a crowd of stakeholders turns it into a participatory effort supported by automation, leading to better requirements and software quality. For Groen et al. [84], although any stakeholder can contribute, CrowdRE emphasizes one group whose role is often trivialized: users. CrowdRE is mainly founded on the assumption that it is important to collect up-to-date observations and experience of the “crowd” about a system and predict the future users requirements [85].

CrowdRE is an emerging paradigm that includes all approaches that engage a “crowd” of a software product’s current and potential users to perform RE tasks or provide requirements-relevant information [84, 86]. It is an umbrella term for all (semi-)automated RE techniques, including crowdsourcing, text mining and data mining, that can be utilized to actively involve a crowd of stakeholders, including users, in the RE process [84, 87]. CrowdRE enables the collection and analysis of information from a crowd to derive validated user requirements [84]. Crowd are the entities who will take part in the requirements processes in a CrowdRE context [85]. Therefore, it expands the reach of established RE approaches, which involve a selected sample of the stakeholders, extending the notion of market-driven RE toward the democratic participation of users in RE [87].

CrowdRE strives to mobilize as many crowd members as possible to communicate and discuss their needs regarding the evolution of existing software products [84]. Groen et al. [84] called this communication of “*user feedback*”, although such feedback can also come from other stakeholders. User feedback is an important resource in modern software development, often containing requirements that help address user concerns and desires for one or more software products [42]. According to Groen and Ochs [88] and Santos et al. [89], a promising approach in CrowdRE is considering user feedback about software products. Requirements management considers user feedback relevant because it validates and discovers requirements change during the continuous software evolution [90, 91, 92, 93]. Figure 2.1 presents

the proposed CrowdRE approach by Groen et al. [84]. The authors considered the crowd the sender of the feedback and a software company (represented in Figure 2.1 as a development team) the receiver.

Figure 2.1: CrowdRE approach proposed by Groen et al. [84].

2.6 Related Work

Few studies have addressed the topic of requirements change in SECO. Among them, we highlight the work of Bogart et al. [37], which performed a multiple case study of three SECO with different tooling and philosophies toward change (Eclipse, R/CRAN, and Node.js/npm) to understand how developers make decisions about change and change-related costs and what practices, tooling, and policies are used. The results of this work illustrate that there is value in making community values and accepted tradeoffs explicit and transparent to resolve conflicts and negotiate change-related costs. Another work was of the Matute et al. [38], which investigated software changes in SECO. According to the authors, managing changes in SECO is difficult because SECO are complex social systems that struggle with scale, mismatched priorities, heterogeneous levels and areas of expertise, and limits on communication and collaboration. Matute et al. [38] identified four social challenges of rolling out software changes in SECO: scale, priorities, expertise, and visibility. The results of this work illustrate that SECO produce several social barriers to deploying changes, but there are opportunities to automate and reduce duplicated effort in this software development context.

Several methods are available for different requirements change management phases in different software development contexts. Lim and Finkelstein [94] proposed a method to anticipate change in the traditional software development context. It separates requirements into layers that change at relatively different rates during requirements documentation. The results show that the method proposed by Lim and Finkelstein [94] accurately anticipates the relative volatility of the requirements. Jayatilleke and Lai [28] presented a method of requirements change analysis based on changes initiated at higher levels in the traditional software development context. It consists of analyzing the change using functions, identifying the change difficulty, and identifying the dependencies using a matrix. The results illustrate that the method proposed by Jayatilleke and Lai [28] contributes to the identification of conflicts and dependencies between requirement changes, allocation of priority to changes, and understanding of the difficulty of change.

Amaral and Franco Rosa [95] presented a method for assessing the potential impact of requirements changes of agile methodologies-based projects. This method consists of the use of requirement traceability and effort prediction on scope changes to benefit agile methodologies. The results illustrate that the method proposed by Amaral and Franco Rosa [95] provides a potential impact rate on scope changes in agile methodologies-based projects. Ali and Lai [31] presented a graph-based method for requirements change management in the GSD context. This method consists of understanding the changes required between different GSD sites to be established, performing a change analysis concerning the development work, which might be either directly or indirectly affected by the changes, and finalizing the changes that will be made between GSD sites. The results illustrate that the method proposed by Ali and Lai [31] facilitate stakeholders in managing requirements changes for GSD better than the existing methods could.

This thesis differs from other studies by proposing a method for requirements change identification in SECO. Previous studies that dealt with changes to requirements in SECO did not suggest any approach to dealing with requirements change in this context. They only analyzed requirements changes in SECO through case studies or identified related challenges. Furthermore, these studies highlighted that more research is needed to investigate requirements change management in

SECO. The other previous studies that proposed methods for requirements change management were related to different software development contexts and were not focused on identifying requirements change in SECO. We understand that these methods can be used in SECO. However, they were not created considering the SECO characteristics detailed in Section 2.2.

2.7 Final Remarks

This chapter presented the concepts used in this thesis. We introduced definitions, characteristics, elements, and types of SECO. We also presented concepts related to requirements management, focusing on requirements change management. We present the state of the art of requirements management in SECO in Chapter 4. Effective requirements change management is vital to the success of any software project. We noticed that requirements change identification is the first step in this process, necessitating a systematic approach to elicit and represent requirements change. This chapter also presented the open innovation and CrowdRE paradigms. These two concepts contribute to the solution presented as the final product of this thesis. In the following chapter, we provide detailed information about the research method employed in this thesis.

Chapter 3. Research Method

3.1 Introduction

This chapter provides details of the methodological approach employed in this thesis, detailing the approach taken to address RQ presented in Chapter 1. We characterized this research as both exploratory and experimental, allowing for the investigation of new ideas and the testing of innovative solutions within the domain. Moreover, we described the use of Design Science Research (DSR) and elucidated the specific method employed in this thesis, which is DSRM. DSRM is a specific methodology within the broader DSR paradigm. It provides a structured, step-by-step process for conducting DSR, guiding researchers through stages such as problem identification, artifact design, demonstration, evaluation, and communication [96].

This chapter is organized as follows: we characterize our research in Section 3.2. In Section 3.3, we provide an overview of the DSR and DSRM. Then, we delineate the steps carried out in our research in Section 3.4. Finally, Section 3.5 presents the final remarks of the chapter.

3.2 Research Characterization

This research is both exploratory and experimental. Exploratory research aims to gain insights into a problem that has not been clearly defined and to formulate propositions and hypotheses or more concrete research questions [97]. It helps to determine the best research design, data collection method, and selection of subjects. Experimental research aims to determine whether specific treatments have an impact on results [98]. It involves the creation, experimentation, and validation of artifacts. We carried out the experimentation from the conception of a method that helps

professionals to requirements change identification in SECO.

3.3 Design Science Research

Design science is a paradigm for conducting and communicating applied research, such as Information Systems and SE [99, 100]. According to Hevner et al. [101], DSR aims to create and evaluate artifacts designed to meet specific organizational needs. The approach is based on the premise that knowledge is generated by designing, constructing, and evaluating artifacts that address real-world problems [101]. Vaishnavi and Kuechler [102] claimed that the DSR could produce different types of artifacts through scientific research work, such as: constructs, models, frameworks, architectures, design principles, methods, instantiations, and design theories. Table 3.1 describes each type of artifact.

Table 3.1: Types of artifacts. **Source:** [102].

Artifact	Description
Constructs	The conceptual vocabulary of a domain.
Models	Sets of propositions or statements expressing relationships between constructs.
Frameworks	Real or conceptual guides to serve as support or guide.
Architectures	High level structures of systems.
Design Principles	Core principles and concepts to guide design.
Methods	Sets of steps used to perform tasks—how-to knowledge.
Instantiations	Situated implementations in certain environments that do or do not operationalize constructs, models, methods, and other abstract artifacts; in the latter case such knowledge remains tacit.
Design Theories	A prescriptive set of statements on how to do something to achieve a certain objective. A theory usually includes other abstract artifacts.

There are several methods for conducting DSR, and all share some common activities. These activities include defining the problem, reviewing existing literature or theories, proposing potential solutions, developing and evaluating the proposed solutions (the artifact), selecting the best solution, and communicating the results to the scientific community [103]. In this thesis, we utilized the DSRM as proposed by Peffers et al. [96], which has the following characteristics:

1. **Problem-solving orientation:** The approach focuses on addressing practical and relevant problems rather than only seeking explanation or description of existing phenomena;
2. **Artifact creation and evaluation:** DSRM involves the design, construction, and evaluation of artifacts that are designed to address specific problems;

3. **Rigor and relevance:** The methodology seeks to balance the rigorous application of theories and methods with the practical relevance of the created artifacts;
4. **Iterative cycle:** DSRM follows an iterative process of artifact development and refinement until they meet the desired requirements.

DSRM can be structured into six main steps, as proposed by Peffers et al. [96].

Figure 3.1 provides a visual representation of the DSRM process model.

Figure 3.1: DSRM Process Model. **Source:** [96].

1. **Identify Problem & Motivate:** This step involves identifying a practical and relevant problem that needs to be addressed and providing motivation for solving it through DSR. The researcher must establish the importance and significance of the problem within the research domain;
2. **Define Objectives of a Solution:** Based on the identified problem, the researcher defines the objectives of a solution in terms of desired functionalities, characteristics, and performance. This step includes setting clear and measurable goals for the artifact to be developed;
3. **Design & Development:** In this step, the artifact is designed and developed using appropriate theories, techniques, and tools. The process may involve creating models, prototypes, algorithms, or complete systems. The researcher must ensure that the design is grounded in existing knowledge and is guided by relevant theories and methods;

4. **Demonstration:** The developed artifact is demonstrated in one or more use cases, showing its applicability and effectiveness in addressing the problem. This step provides evidence of the artifact’s utility and its potential impact on the research domain;
5. **Evaluation:** The artifact is evaluated in terms of its effectiveness, efficiency, and utility using appropriate evaluation criteria and methods. This step is crucial for validating the artifact’s performance and establishing its contribution to the research domain;
6. **Communication:** The final step involves communicating the research process, the developed artifact, and the evaluation results to the target audience, which may include scholars, practitioners, and other stakeholders in the research domain.

3.4 Research Design Following DSRM

In the following sections, we elaborate on how each step of this research was designed and how the iterations were integrated into the DSRM. Figure 3.2 presents our research method design following DSRM, considering its steps and the iterations performed.

3.4.1 Identify Problem & Motivate

This step consists of understanding and describing the problem to be addressed [103]. It involves identifying the needs and challenges that motivate the research. This process includes observing and analyzing the current context and identifying gaps or opportunities for improvement that justify the need to create a new solution or enhance an existing one [103]. We conducted this process in six interactions. In the first iteration of this step, we carried out an informal literature review, which served as a starting point, helping us understand the main concepts and challenges in SECO, with a focus on requirements management.

In the second iteration, we carried out a tertiary study on SECO, which investigated the current state of research on SECO and its practice more broadly than possible with secondary studies. We adopted this method because it synthesizes

Figure 3.2: Research Method Design Following DSRM.

findings from secondary studies and offers a broad and consolidated view of the existing research landscape. Tertiary studies provide a holistic perspective on a research field, identifying underexplored research topics or where conflicting findings exist [104]. Our tertiary study identified the different aspects and subdomains of the SECO field, which are detailed in Chapter 4. Among the findings, our tertiary study revealed that aspects already investigated in other software development contexts, such as RE and their processes, are being investigated for SECO. This finding demonstrates the importance of understanding this SE discipline and its processes and proposing specific approaches to supporting them in SECO. This observation

aligns with the results of an SMS on RE in SECO published in 2018, in which Vegendla et al. [14] stated that research on RE has had increasing attention in SECO. However, the authors claimed that more research should be performed to investigate the current state of requirements management in SECO, which motivated the next iteration.

In the third iteration, we conducted an SMS on requirements management in SECO [105], which identified and analyzed the state of the art requirements management in SECO concerning its characteristics and existing approaches. We adopted this method because it allows survey the available knowledge about a research topic, synthesize this by categorization, identify where there are ‘clusters’ of studies that could form the basis of a fuller review, and identify where there are ‘gaps’ indicating the need for more primary studies [106]. Among the findings, which are also detailed in Chapter 4, our SMS revealed that requirements management in SECO: (i) has specific characteristics that make a difference in other software development contexts; (ii) requires specific support approaches for this software development context; (iii) usually uses open innovation practices; (iv) counts on the participation of the multiple actors that can form distinct crowds; and (v) still not well understood, and several issues remain open. These observations also align with the results of Vegendla et al. [14] that highlighted a lack of shared understanding of requirements management in SECO and the concepts and concerns involved. These findings motivated the next iterations (fourth, fifth and sixth iteration) that aimed to analyze them from a practical perspective.

In the fourth iteration, we performed a field study with professionals engaged in an educational SECO based on a virtual learning environment (VLE). This study obtained the stakeholders’ perceptions of requirements management activities in this SECO. We adopted this method in this iteration and in the fifth and sixth iterations because it allows real-world insights, identifies practical challenges, validates and refines theories, explores best practices, develops evidence-based recommendations, and enhances industry relevance [107]. Among the findings, which are detailed in Chapter 5, our field study revealed that: (i) there is no formal requirements management process in this SECO; and (ii) requirements management involves the participation of multiple actors (internal and external), e.g., the keystone and their

partners in this SECO. These findings align with the results of Knauss et al. [18] that stated that requirements management in SECO usually is informal and Vegendla et al. [14] that highlighted that requirements arise from multiple actors that may belong to different organizations in the SECO context.

In the fifth iteration, we performed another a field study with professionals involved in requirements management activities in different SECO. This study investigated the use of open innovation practices to support requirements management in SECO. Among the findings, which are also detailed in Chapter 5, our field study revealed that: (i) several communication channels are used to receive/provide requirements or requirements change from/to external actors in SECO; and (ii) several open innovation practices support requirements management in SECO. These findings align with the results of Linåker and Runeson [108] and Jansen [1]. Linåker and Runeson [108] mentioned open communication channels are resources to enable an open collaboration in SECO, and Jansen [1] defined that open innovation as a focus area of SECO governance that is concerned with sharing knowledge across the ecosystem to feed external developers with new possibilities for improvement.

In the sixth iteration, we performed a new field study with professionals involved in requirements management activities in different SECO. This study investigated whether and how user feedback from a crowd is considered in requirements management in SECO. Among the findings, which are detailed in Chapter 5, our field study revealed that the requirements management in SECO: (i) considers the user feedback from distinct crowds; (ii) uses several mechanisms to gather user feedback from distinct crowds; and (iii) uses several automated, semi-automated, and manual approaches to analyze user feedback from distinct crowds.

3.4.2 Define Objectives of a Solution

Taking insights from our earlier investigations, **we decided to tackle the requirements management issue in SECO**. More specifically, we aimed to propose a solution to help professionals in the requirements change identification in SECO. Such a solution must consider the intrinsic characteristics of SECO, especially its scalability, dynamism, and openness. Therefore, an essential requirement is

that our approach acknowledges the use of open innovation and CrowdRE to identify requirements change in SECO. This requirement is key as it reflects specific characteristics of requirements management in SECO, contributing to a more realistic and applicable solution. We defined it as another key requirement that our solution must be adaptable. Different SECO types have unique requirements, nuances, and specific characteristics. In this context, adaptability ensures that the solution can be customized regardless of the domain.

3.4.3 Design & Development

As with any technological artifact, the design of our solution required a comprehensive understanding of the theory it is grounded in. However, as previously highlighted, there is no shared understanding of the requirements management in SECO and the concepts and relationships involved in the subject. Therefore, we used the primary studies extracted from our SMS and the results of field studies to identify such concepts and relationships related to requirements management in SECO. In this iteration, we systematically analyzed the primary studies to identify relevant concepts and relationships and construct propositions that explain the subject. As a result, we proposed a conceptual model for requirements management in SECO, named SECO-RM, which was evaluated through a Delphi study [109] with 18 experts. We adopted this method because it offers several advantages, including the effective use of expert knowledge, consensus-building, model refinement and validation, and the generation of detailed qualitative insights [109]. SECO-RM guided the design of the solution proposed in this thesis. Chapter 6 details the design and evaluation of the conceptual model for requirements management in SECO.

Once we organized the concepts and relationships on requirements management in SECO in a conceptual model, we developed a method called SECO-RCI to achieve the solution objectives. A method is a set of steps used to perform a task [110] and may be understood as a procedure that provides a guide to the problem resolution [101]. It is based on the constructs and models previously defined [111]. Precisely, the outcomes of the method proposed in this thesis relate to requirements change identification in SECO, which is crucial for enabling requirements management in

this software development context. Chapter 7 details SECO-RCI.

3.4.4 Demonstration

SECO-RCI was demonstrated within the context of a SECO of an application-oriented research institute in Europe. This institute collaborates with others to conduct research and development, aiming to turn original ideas into innovations that benefit society and strengthen the European economy. It consists of more than 70 research units and has over 28,000 employees. This institute controls a SECO based on an open source platform for next-generation automation with projects related to asset administration shells. This SECO provides a free software platform that enables all stakeholders, large and small industries, research institutes, academia, and interested persons to participate in and shape the fourth industrial revolution. It provides common and re-useable Industrie 4.0 components and hosts a multitude of software development kits (SDK) for different programming languages (e.g., Java, Python, .Net, and C++).

3.4.5 Evaluation

In this thesis, we did not intend to compare distinct approaches as there are no other approaches with the same objectives as SECO-RCI. Instead, we focus on the method's acceptance of the method by experts with theoretical and practical experience and professionals. Hence, we aimed to understand how SECO-RCI is perceived by experts and used by professionals to gain insights into its usefulness and ease of use in this iteration. By gathering feedback and insights from experts and practitioners, we aim to investigate the feasibility of SECO-RCI as a novel artifact to improve requirements change identification in SECO.

We conducted two studies to evaluate SECO-RCI, one involving experts with different backgrounds and the other involving a SECO of an application-oriented research institute in Europe. The first study was performed through a focus group to gather the participants' feedback regarding SECO-RCI's acceptance. We adopted this method because it offers rich qualitative insights, explores diverse perspectives, facilitates dynamic interaction and feedback from experts, identifies practical issues and improvements, validates findings, and provides contextual understanding [112].

The second study was performed through a single case study. A single case study is an in-depth, detailed examination of a single subject or case within its real-world context [113, 114]. Unlike multiple case studies, which examine several cases to identify patterns and generalize findings, a single case study focuses on one case to gain a deep understanding of its unique characteristics, interactions, and outcomes [114]. We adopted this method because it offers several advantages, including in-depth exploration of contextual factors, practical validation, and rich qualitative data [113, 114]. In the first study, we introduced and demonstrated the method to the experts, who exposed their intuitive perceptions next. In the second study, a participant employed SECO-RCI based on a realistic case of an SECO operating in a European industry. For this study, the professional used a tool that supports the method utilization. Then, we interviewed the participant so that they could express their opinions from a practical perspective.

We recorded and transcribed the interviews for further analysis. We adopted open coding procedures [115] to support the analysis of participants' responses. Open coding is an essential part of the qualitative analysis of interview data. It allows researchers to dissect, examine, compare, conceptualize, and categorize the data, thereby uncovering emerging themes and patterns [116]. Through open coding, researchers can identify relationships between categories, further assisting in theory construction. Its approach improves the reliability and credibility of the analysis, minimizing the influence of bias and preconceptions. Its iterative nature also allows for multiple revisions, promoting a more nuanced data interpretation. Chapter 8 provides details on the study's planning, as well as the obtained results. Moreover, the chapter includes a discussion of the results, presenting the implications for both practitioners and researchers.

3.4.6 Communication

The results of this research have been disseminated via publications in academic journals and conferences in addition to this thesis, as listed in the following:

- A paper published in the Thesis and Dissertations Workshop on Software (WTDSOft) [117] held at the Brazilian Conference on Software: Theory and Practice (CBSOft), in which we outlined our initial solution. During the

presentation of this work, we received valuable feedback from researchers in the field. Their insightful contributions played a crucial role in the initial stages of our research;

- An article published in the Requirements Engineering (RE) journal [105] detailing an SMS on requirements management in SECO;
- A paper published in the main track of International Conference on Software Business (ICSOB) [118] detailing the findings of the field study on open innovation practices in requirements management in SECO;
- An article published in the Empirical Software Engineering journal [119], in which we presented the findings of the field study on user feedback from a crowd in requirements management in SECO;

Furthermore, we submitted the following articles:

- An article submitted to the Information and Software Technology journal (in the second round of review) [119], in which we presented our conceptual model for requirements management in SECO.
- An article submitted to the Journal of Systems and Software (in the first round of review) [120], in which we presented the findings of the field study on modeling and requirements management in a specific software ecosystem;

Finally, these articles are ready for submission:

- An article ready for submission to the ACM Computing Surveys [121], in which we presented the findings of the tertiary study on SECO;
- An article ready for submission to the Journal of Systems and Software [122], in which we presented the SECO-RCI method and outlined the studies conducted to evaluate it.

3.5 Final Remarks

This chapter presented the research details documented in this thesis, which was conceived from the perspective of DSR, adopting DSRM. In the following chapter,

we present the state of the art of SECO through a tertiary study and the state of the art of requirements management in SECO through an SMS. Carrying out these studies was essential in identifying the problem addressed in this thesis.

Chapter 4. State of the Art on Software Ecosystems and Requirements Management in the Context

4.1 Introduction

This chapter provides an overview of the current state of research on SECO and the state of the art of requirements management in SECO. We conducted a tertiary study to understand better research efforts in the SECO field and an SMS to identify characteristics and approaches of requirements management in SECO.

This chapter is organized as follows: Section 4.2 describes the tertiary study on SECO; Section 4.3 describes the SMS on requirements management in SECO; Section 4.4 lists the threats to the validity; and the final remarks are described in Section 4.5.

4.2 Tertiary Study on Software Ecosystems

Tertiary studies evaluate secondary studies and support the organization of an evidence-based body of knowledge [123, 124]. They help researchers and practitioners by reducing the individual effort of gathering and summarizing relevant literature [125]. This type of study also provides evidence to reinforce or reject widely held beliefs about the research domain under investigation [104]. The availability of a growing and continuous number of secondary studies covering different aspects and subdomains of SECO justifies our choice to conduct this study.

In this tertiary study, we provided an overview of research published in secondary

studies on SECO, identified the different aspects and subdomains investigated, proposed a thematic map on SECO research topics, assessed the quality of selected secondary studies, and presented future research directions for the SECO field. SECO can be investigated by analyzing several aspects and subdomains [60]. García-Holgado and García-Peñalvo [60] described an aspect as a particular characteristic, technique, or process associated with SECO (e.g., governance, health, quality) and a subdomain as a specific type of SECO (e.g., OSSECO, PSECO, or hybrid SECO - mobile SECO or MSECO).

This tertiary study followed the same methodological procedures of a systematic literature review (SLR) and was developed following the guidelines proposed by Kitchenham and Charters [125]. These guidelines are widely accepted in the evidence-based SE (EBSE) community and used in highly cited tertiary studies in the SE literature [104, 123, 126, 127, 128, 129], which also inspired this study. The following phases are proposed for this tertiary study according to Kitchenham and Charters [125]: planning, conducting, and reporting the results.

4.2.1 Planning

In the planning phase of the tertiary study, we defined a review protocol that details goals and RQ, search strategy, study selection process, quality assessment process, and data extraction and synthesis process.

4.2.1.1 Goals and Research Questions

The main goal of this study was to investigate the extensive research done on SECO after almost two decades since the term was introduced into SE and to present the current state of research in SECO, as evidenced by the increasing number of secondary studies identified in the literature. For this, we intended to answer the RQ defined in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Tertiary study research questions.

ID	Research questions	Rationale
TS-RQ1	What secondary studies have been published in the SECO field?	This question aims to characterize the secondary studies performed in the SECO field. For this, we will identify the number of published secondary studies on SECO per year and country, the publication type, the secondary study type, and the number of primary studies selected.
TS-RQ2	What research topics have been investigated in secondary studies on SECO?	This question aims to identify which research topics have gained the research community's attention. This question will identify the main themes covered and how each study has worked out these themes. In the end, the themes will be organized in a thematic map.
TS-RQ3	Is the quality of secondary studies on SECO improving?	This question aims to perform the quality assessment of the selected secondary studies using the DARE quality criteria.
TS-RQ4	What future research directions are described in the secondary studies on SECO?	This question aims to identify the implications presented in the selected secondary studies that can direct new research efforts.

4.2.1.2 Search Strategy

The search strategy involved database search [130, 131] in ACM Digital Library¹, Elsevier ScienceDirect², Engineering Village³, IEEEExplore Digital Library⁴, Scopus⁵, SpringerLink⁶, and Web of Science⁷. All the sources were used in several tertiary studies in SE [104, 123, 126, 127].

To define the search string used in this tertiary study, we identified terms used in relevant secondary studies on SECO and highly cited tertiary studies in the SE literature. Then, we generated a search string using boolean operators such as OR and AND to incorporate the terms. Finally, we performed searches in selected sources (application of search string). Table 4.2 provides the search string.

Table 4.2: The search string of tertiary study.

The search string
("software ecosystem" OR "software ecosystems") AND ("review of studies" OR "structured review" OR "systematic review" OR "literature review" OR "literature analysis" OR "systematic map" OR "systematic mapping" OR "mapping study" OR "longitudinal study" OR "scoping study")

4.2.1.3 Study Selection

We inserted all retrieved studies into the Mendeley tool⁸ and removed all duplicates to optimize the selection process. According to Kitchenham and Charters [125], for the selection of the retrieved studies, inclusion criteria (IC) and exclusion criteria

¹<https://dl.acm.org/>

²<https://www.sciencedirect.com/>

³<https://www.engineeringvillage.com/>

⁴<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/>

⁵<https://www.scopus.com/>

⁶<https://link.springer.com/>

⁷<https://webofknowledge.com/>

⁸<https://www.mendeley.com>

(EC) must be defined and applied (Table 4.3). These criteria were used to exclude studies that were not relevant to answer the research questions. We included studies that covered all IC and excluded if they were within at least one of the EC.

Table 4.3: Tertiary study selection criteria.

Inclusion criteria (IC)	
ID	Criteria
TS-IC1	The study describes secondary studies strategies about SECO, i.e., the study reports an analysis of the scientific literature with defined research questions, research process, data extraction, and presentation of results.
TS-IC2	The study is written in English.
TS-IC3	The study is peer-reviewed.
Exclusion criteria (EC)	
ID	Criteria
TS-EC1	The study does not satisfy all the inclusion criteria.
TS-EC2	The study is duplicate or reports similar results to another retrieved study.
TS-EC3	The study is unavailable for open access or cannot be accessed through legal sources (institutional access).

4.2.1.4 Quality Assessment

The quality assessment of studies selected is important in secondary and tertiary studies and determines to what extent the results of an empirical study are valid and bias-free [106, 132]. In this tertiary study, we used the quality criteria (QC) recommended by Kitchenham et al. [106], which are also the most commonly used ones in SE tertiary studies [104, 128, 129]. These criteria were defined by the Centre for Reviews and Disseminations (CRD) of York University and became known as the Database of Abstracts of Reviews of Effects (DARE)⁹. The criteria used are presented in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Tertiary study quality assessment criteria [106].

ID	Criteria	Score	Description
TS-QC1	IC/EC are reported	1	Explicit definition of IC/EC
		0.5	Implicit definition of IC/EC
		0	No IC/EC defined
TS-QC2	Search is adequate	1	4+ digital libraries searched and additional search strategies applied
		0.5	3-4 digital libraries searched, but no extra search strategies applied
		0	1-2 digital libraries searched or very restricted search
TS-QC3	Quality of studies is assessed	1	Quality criteria explicitly described and applied
		0.5	Implicit quality assessment
		0	No quality assessment
TS-QC4	Details of studies are presented	1	Complete information presented about primary studies
		0.5	Summary information presented about primary studies
		0	Results of primary studies not specified
TS-QC5	Synthesis of studies is performed	1	Explicit definition of the synthesis method
		0.5	Implicit definition of the synthesis method
		0	No synthesis method defined

Kitchenham et al. [106] refined DARE criteria by attributing points to each criterion, becoming a predominant scoring scheme in SE to assess secondary studies

⁹<https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/crdweb/ShowRecord.asp?ID=32004000332>

[104, 127, 128, 129, 133]. Thus, each QC has three possible values: 1, 0.5 or 0. The total quality score of each selected secondary study is the sum of the values of all five QC for that study (5). In this tertiary study, we considered the range of quality scores presented by Khan et al. [104], which varied from low ($0.5 \leq \text{quality score} \leq 2$) to medium ($2.5 \leq \text{quality score} \leq 3$) and to high ($3.5 \leq \text{quality score} \leq 5$). The spreadsheets with the complete quality assessment of each selected secondary study are available in the supplementary material¹⁰ (details in Appendix 9.5).

In this tertiary study, we decided not to use the quality assessment as a criterion to include or exclude the retrieved secondary studies. The reason for that is twofold: (i) we are interested in analyzing all selected secondary studies because SECO is still a recent research field, and (ii) we intend to draw an overall view of the quality of the selected secondary studies on SECO.

4.2.1.5 Data Extraction and Synthesis

The data extraction step comprises the design of forms for accurately recording the information obtained in the selected secondary studies [125]. We carried out the data extraction process of this study from the complete reading of the selected secondary studies and used a spreadsheet to store the data. The form used in the data extraction of this tertiary study is available in the supplementary material¹⁰.

Cruzes and Dyba [134] claimed that a research synthesis can be considered a collective term used to summarize, integrate, combine, and compare the findings of primary studies. We used descriptive analysis [134] to perform the data synthesis and answer this tertiary study's research questions. We used thematic analysis [126, 135] to identify, analyze, and report themes from data to help us conclude. Figure 4.1 illustrates the hierarchy of elements used in the thematic analysis.

4.2.2 Results

Figure 4.2 presents an overview of the study selection process. We performed the database search in seven digital libraries as detailed in Section 4.2.1. We retrieved 850 studies, removed 210 duplicate studies, and excluded 609 studies after applying IC/EC. Hence, we selected 31 secondary studies. We emphasize that we do not use

¹⁰<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10790626>

Figure 4.1: Hierarchy of elements of the thematic synthesis. Adapted from the works of Cruzes and Dybå [126] and Connelly and Peltzer [135].

date or search field filters (i.e., we searched only in title, abstract, and keywords). Table 4.5 presents the selected secondary studies in ascending order by year of publication and are referred to in this work as TS-S1 to TS-S31. The following subsections present the answers to the research questions, defined through data extraction and synthesis.

Figure 4.2: Secondary studies selection process.

4.2.2.1 Secondary Studies on SECO (TS-RQ1)

This RQ aimed to characterize the secondary studies performed on SECO. We identified the year, publication type, secondary study type, number of primary studies included, and country of each selected secondary study. This information represents, in some way, the extent of the search conducted by secondary studies of the area. Table 4.5 presents general characteristics of selected secondary studies.

About the number of secondary studies on SECO per year, we identified a

Table 4.5: Characteristics of the secondary studies selected in the tertiary study.

ID	Year	Publication type	Secondary study type*	N ^o of primary studies included	Country	Reference
TS-S1	2013	Book Chapter	SMS	44	Brazil	[44]
TS-S2	2013	Journal	SLR	90	Denmark	[6]
TS-S3	2014	Conference	SMS	34	Sweden	[136]
TS-S4	2015	Conference	SMS	260	Sweden	[137]
TS-S5	2015	Conference	SLR	17	Spain	[138]
TS-S6	2015	Conference	SMS	28	Brazil	[139]
TS-S7	2015	Conference	SLR	38	Finland	[140]
TS-S8	2016	Journal	SMS	6	Sweden	[17]
TS-S9	2016	Journal	LLS	231	Denmark	[45]
TS-S10	2017	Conference	SLR	23	Brazil	[141]
TS-S11	2017	Journal	SMS	82	Spain	[4]
TS-S12	2018	Journal	SMS	44	Norway	[14]
TS-S13	2018	Conference	SMS	12	Brazil	[142]
TS-S14	2018	Conference	SMS	13	Spain	[60]
TS-S15	2018	Conference	SLR	89	Brazil	[143]
TS-S16	2019	Conference	SMS	44	Brazil	[144]
TS-S17	2019	Conference	SMS	49	Brazil	[145]
TS-S18	2019	Conference	SMS	23	Brazil	[146]
TS-S19	2019	Conference	SMS	63	Brazil	[147]
TS-S20	2019	Conference	SLR	15	Brazil	[148]
TS-S21	2019	Journal	SLR	37	Spain	[149]
TS-S22	2019	Journal	SMS	23	Spain	[20]
TS-S23	2020	Conference	SMS	32	Brazil	[150]
TS-S24	2020	Conference	SMS	8	Brazil	[151]
TS-S25	2021	Conference	LLS	109	Brazil	[152]
TS-S26	2021	Conference	SMS	8	Brazil	[153]
TS-S27	2022	Conference	SMS	89	Finland	[154]
TS-S28	2022	Journal	SLR	42	Netherlands	[155]
TS-S29	2022	Journal	SLR	64	Finland	[156]
TS-S30	2022	Journal	SMS	13	Netherlands	[157]
TS-S31	2023	Journal	SLR	112	Netherlands	[158]

*SLR: Systematic Literature Review / SMS: Systematic Mapping Study / LLS: Longitudinal Literature Study

consistency in publications between 2013 and 2023 (at least one study per year). In 2019, there was the most significant number of publications of secondary studies on SECO (nine studies). This increase in publications corroborates the assertion of Khan et al. [104] about the rise in the number of secondary studies on SE in general. Regarding the countries that published secondary studies on SECO, we considered the country of the first author to perform the analysis. Figure 4.3 presents the distribution of countries and points to a significant number of secondary studies from Brazil (14 studies) and Spain (5 studies). We also observed that the number of SMS (19 studies) exceeds that of SLR (10 studies), and only two longitudinal literature studies (LLS) were published. It may be justified due to the emergence of the SECO field in the last decades. Moreover, Kitchenham et al. [106] stated that SMS have found wide acceptance in SE. Finally, we identified the main publication venues (book chapters, conferences, and journals) of secondary studies on SECO. Among the 31 selected secondary studies, 11 studies are from journals, 19 are from conferences, and one is a book chapter.

Figure 4.3: Distribution of secondary studies by country.

4.2.2.2 Research Topics Investigated in Secondary Studies on SECO (TS-RQ2)

To answer TS-RQ2, we analyzed the goals and research questions of the selected secondary studies. Hence, we identified five secondary studies that investigated SECO in a general form (TS-S1, TS-S2, TS-S9, TS-S14, TS-S29) and 26 secondary studies that investigated one or more aspects and subdomains of SECO. We highlighted that eight secondary studies focused on more than one research topic (TS-S5, TS-S15, TS-S20, TS-S21, TS-S22, TS-S23, TS-S25, TS-S26). For instance, TS-S25 investigated the aspects of governance and health in the subdomain PSECO. The aspects or subdomains more investigated are health (TS-S7, TS-S10, TS-S13, TS-S15, TS-S25), MSECO (TS-S6, TS-S19, TS-S20, TS-S23), OSSECO (TS-S5, TS-S11, TS-S26), and partnership (TS-S18, TS-S28, TS-S30). The number of secondary studies publications can demonstrate the emergent aspect of the field, the update of concepts, and, finally, its expansion to other domains. The research topics investigated in secondary studies on SECO can be visualized through the years in Figure 4.4.

We identified 19 research topics in the 31 selected secondary studies, including the general research topic. However, we noticed that several of these research topics were

Figure 4.4: Distribution of secondary studies by research topic over the years.

also mentioned or discussed in other selected secondary studies that did not address them primarily. For instance, the research topic “*health*” was cited or discussed in 25 of the 31 selected secondary studies. However, only five addressed health as a main research topic (TS-S7, TS-S10, TS-S13, TS-S15, TS-S25). Hence, we analyzed each research topic according to the results of the total set of selected secondary studies to obtain a broader view of each. This analysis allowed us to explore the different views on each research topic in the SECO literature and verify the main points of convergence and divergence between them. For this, we used thematic analysis. We adopted the hierarchical structure of themes from the works of Cruzes and Dyba [134] and Connelly and Peltzer [135] and defined one higher-order theme, three themes, and 18 subthemes. Figure 4.5 presents the themes and subthemes and their relationships in a thematic map.

When performing the thematic analysis, we defined the general research topic (SECO) as the higher-order theme and the SECO perspective in three dimensions (business, technical, and social) as the themes. We determined the other SECO research topics as subthemes (bottom part of Figure 4.5). The double arrow between items on the thematic map indicates bidirectional communication between themes and between themes and subthemes. We grouped the subthemes in a “*container*” to represent the bidirectional communication between all without overloading the

Figure 4.5: SECO thematic map.

thematic map with the arrow excess. Next, we detail our analysis only for the subthemes that contributed to identifying the problem of this thesis.

Social Aspects. We identified only one selected secondary study (TS-S20) with social aspects as one of their research topics. TS-S20 had social aspects and MSECO as research topics and selected 15 primary studies published between 2013 and 2017. TS-S20 aimed to identify the social factors influencing developers to participate in an MSECO. TS-S20 identified 11 social factors in this context and concluded that social aspects of a MSECO are important for its sustainability.

Another 12 selected secondary studies (TS-S1, TS-S2, TS-S3, TS-S5, TS-S8, TS-S9, TS-S11, TS-S17, TS-S19, TS-S20, TS-S29, TS-S31) cited social aspects in their results. TS-S1, TS-S2, TS-S5, TS-S9, TS-S11, TS-S17, TS-S19, and TS-S20 mentioned that the social dimension of an ecosystem focuses on SECO actors and involves collaboration between them and with the ecosystem. According to TS-S1, TS-S29, and TS-S31, the social dimension is strongly related to the success of a SECO. TS-S2 pointed out that a SECO cannot be created without the social aspect. TS-S2, TS-S3, TS-S8, and TS-S9 summarize different social aspects of SECO, for example, social networks, communities, collaboration, and actor-to-actor

or actor-to-ecosystem interaction. TS-S11 highlighted that the ecosystem's social behavior must be considered when analyzing OSSECO. TS-S17 presented the benefits that hackathons offer to the social dimension of a SECO. TS-S19 cited that the social aspect of MSECO is less explored than the technical and business aspects. According to TS-S31, from a social perspective, spreading knowledge among actors can increase SECO attractiveness and build trust.

Insight #1:

The social dimension of a SECO is crucial for its sustainability and success, emphasizing collaboration and interaction among actors and with the ecosystem, but remains underexplored when compared to technical and business dimensions.

Open Innovation. We identified only one selected secondary study (TS-S4) with open innovation as a research topic. TS-S4 selected 260 primary studies published between 1993 and 2013 and mapped the research on SECO and open innovation for embedded systems. However, their research questions are generic, not allowing for a clear discussion on SECO and open innovation. TS-S4 identified the need for more solutions to specific problems of open innovation in SECO, such as defining processes that promote open innovation and improving the way SECO actors can leverage the support of tools for open innovation.

Another seven selected secondary studies (TS-S1, TS-S10, TS-S11, TS-S12, TS-S15, TS-S17, TS-S30) cited open innovation in their results. TS-S1 pointed out that innovations no longer originate in a single organization and are co-innovations of different actors in SECO and emphasized that software co-innovation is one of the most common areas studied in SECO. TS-S10 and TS-S15 mentioned that SECO accelerates innovation while sharing its costs through co-innovations. TS-S11 highlighted the role of open innovation in OSSECO compared to PSECO. According to TS-S12, SECO and open innovation processes have been claimed as a way forward for the software industry. TS-S17 cited that holding hackathons is an open innovation trend and is a means of collecting feedback from the outside to innovate in SECO. TS-S30 presented open innovation as a trend in SECO, especially in MSECO.

Insight #2:

Open innovation is a growing trend in SECO, promoting collaboration and external feedback to innovate in SECO. However, further research is needed to address specific challenges.

Requirements Engineering. We identified only one selected secondary study (TS-S12) with RE as a research topic. TS-S12 selected 44 primary studies published between 2009 and 2017 and identified the RE activities specifically studied in SECO and how non-functional requirements are considered in this context. According to TS-S12, research on RE has had increasing attention in SECO, and the identification of stakeholders and roles for requirements elicitation and requirements analysis are the most studied activities in SECO. However, TS-S12 also pointed out that the requirements validation and requirements management activities are least addressed in SECO. According to TS-S12, without requirements validation and requirements management, the consistency and completeness of the requirements and the requirements changes are not ensured. TS-S12 stated that requirements management is challenging in SECO and that more research is needed on the topic.

Another four selected secondary studies (TS-S1, TS-S2, TS-S8, TS-S29) cited RE in their results. TS-S1 mentioned requirements coordination and communication as a challenge in SECO. TS-S2 highlighted that requirements elicitation is an exciting challenge in SECO, as the stakeholders are multiple and distant from the central management of the ecosystem. According to TS-S8, the requirements definition process is a challenge in SECO because normal stakeholders are complemented with the roles of keystone and niche players, and the challenges focus on the interactions between these two categories of actors, mainly on sharing and communicating requirements. TS-S29 mentioned that iterations and changes in requirements management in SECO are not necessarily coordinated or synchronized, thus creating long-term challenges in SECO.

Insight #3:

Requirements management is one of the least addressed areas in SECO, presenting significant challenges due to the complexity of coordinating multiple stakeholders and risking the consistency of requirements. More research is needed to improve requirements processes in this context.

4.2.2.3 Quality of Secondary Studies on SECO (TS-RQ3)

To answer TS-RQ3, we performed the quality assessment (discussed in Section 4.2.1.4) for all 31 selected secondary studies using the DARE criteria. These criteria are based on five questions (Table 4.4) that can be considered quality indicators for secondary studies [106]. Figure 4.6 presents the final score obtained by each study and the general classification of selected secondary studies according to the ranges of quality scores presented by Khan et al. [104] (low, medium, or high). The complete quality assessment with the scores for each indicator is openly available in the supplementary material¹¹ (details in Appendix 9.5).

Figure 4.6: Quality scores of the selected secondary studies.

The **first quality indicator** of secondary studies defined in the DARE criteria is related to the inclusion and exclusion criteria definition to select primary studies (TS-QC1). According to Kitchenham and Charters [125], secondary studies require explicit inclusion and exclusion criteria to assess each potential primary study and reduce the likelihood of bias in the selection process. From the 31 selected secondary studies, 26 defined IC/EC explicitly (TS-S1, TS-S2, TS-S3, TS-S4, TS-S6, TS-S7, TS-S10, TS-S11, TS-S12, TS-S13, TS-S14, TS-S15, TS-S16, TS-S17, TS-S18, TS-S19, TS-S20, TS-S21, TS-S22, TS-S24, TS-S25, TS-S27, TS-S28, TS-S29, TS-S30, TS-S31), one implicitly (TS-S8), and four did not provide evidence of the definition them (TS-S5, TS-S9, TS-S23, TS-S26).

The **second quality indicator** of secondary studies defined in the DARE criteria is related to carrying out adequate searches to select primary studies

¹¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10790626>

(TS-QC2). The guidelines provided by Kitchenham and Charters [125] recommend composing a string to find relevant studies by searching several digital libraries to find relevant studies. We identified that of the 31 selected secondary studies, 21 of them carried out searches in more than four digital libraries (TS-S1, TS-S2, TS-S3, TS-S4, TS-S7, TS-S8, TS-S9, TS-S10, TS-S11, TS-S12, TS-S13, TS-S15, TS-S16, TS-S17, TS-S19, TS-S20, TS-S21, TS-S23, TS-S24, TS-S25, TS-S26), seven carried out searches in three or four (TS-S5, TS-S6, TS-S14, TS-S22, TS-S27, TS-S30, TS-S31), and three carried out searches in one or two (TS-S18, TS-S28, TS-S29). Moreover, some of these selected secondary studies also applied additional search strategies such as manual search (TS-S1, TS-S5, TS-S6, TS-S8, TS-S10, TS-S11, TS-S12, TS-S15) and snowballing (TS-S10, TS-S17, TS-S18, TS-S20, TS-S23, TS-S24, TS-S30, TS-S31).

The **third quality indicator** of secondary studies defined in the DARE criteria is related to the quality assessment of the primary studies selected (TS-QC3). According to Kitchenham et al. [106], evaluating the quality of the primary studies can enhance the value of SLR and some types of SMS in several ways. Of the 31 selected secondary studies, nine described QC explicitly and performed quality assessment (TS-S3, TS-S10, TS-S12, TS-S14, TS-S20, TS-S21, TS-S22, TS-S28, TS-S31), one performed quality assessment implicitly (TS-S1), and 21 did not perform quality assessment (TS-S2, TS-S4, TS-S5, TS-S6, TS-S7, TS-S8, TS-S9, TS-S11, TS-S13, TS-S15, TS-S16, TS-S17, TS-S18, TS-S19, TS-S23, TS-S24, TS-S25, TS-S26, TS-S27, TS-S29, TS-S30).

The **fourth quality indicator** of secondary studies defined in the DARE criteria is related to presenting detailed information about the selected primary studies (TS-QC4). According to Kitchenham et al. [106], the strategy for data extraction needs to be defined and justified, and the data to be extracted are very closely related to the specific research questions. Of the 31 selected secondary studies, nine presented complete information about primary studies (TS-S12, TS-S7, TS-S8, TS-S11, TS-S15, TS-S21, TS-S23, TS-S24, TS-S31), 15 presented summary information (TS-S1, TS-S3, TS-S6, TS-S9, TS-S10, TS-S12, TS-S13, TS-S14, TS-S16, TS-S17, TS-S18, TS-S19, TS-S20, TS-S22, TS-S25), and seven not presented information about primary studies (TS-S4, TS-S5, TS-S26, TS-S27,

TS-S28, TS-S29, TS-S30).

The **fifth quality indicator** of secondary studies defined in the DARE criteria is related to synthesizing selected primary studies (TS-QC5). According to Kitchenham et al. [106], synthesis can consist mainly of classification of the material found, identifying where there are groups of studies addressing a particular issue, or equally, where there is a lack of studies. For the authors, it is necessary to specify in the review protocol the type of synthesis method you intend to use in secondary studies. Of the 31 selected secondary studies, 13 have explicitly stated the synthesis method and provided a reference to it (TS-S1, TS-S8, TS-S10, TS-S11, TS-S15, TS-S17, TS-S18, TS-S20, TS-S21, TS-S22, TS-S29, TS-S30, TS-S31), seven have only stated their synthesis method (TS-S3, TS-S4, TS-S6, TS-S7, TS-S9, TS-S19, TS-S23), and 11 did not describe their synthesis method (TS-S2, TS-S5, TS-S12, TS-S13, TS-S14, TS-S16, TS-S24, TS-S25, TS-S26, TS-S27, TS-S28).

4.2.2.4 Future Research Directions Described in the Secondary Studies on SECO (TS-RQ4)

To answer TS-RQ4, we analyzed the gaps, research agendas, discussion, implications, and conclusions presented in the selected secondary studies. Thus, we identified 105 future research directions to some of the SECO research topics discussed in Section 4.2.2.2 and also to other SECO research topics that have not yet been reviewed in secondary studies on SECO. From 31 selected secondary studies, 19 of them presented future research directions (TS-S1, TS-S2, TS-S3, TS-S4, TS-S7, TS-S8, TS-S9, TS-S10, TS-S11, TS-S12, TS-S14, TS-S18, TS-S23, TS-S24, TS-S25, TS-S27, TS-S28, TS-S29, TS-S30). Table 4.6 presents the research topics and the list of the selected secondary studies that pointed out future research directions for them. We detail the identified future research directions related to this thesis next.

General. We identified six future research directions that refer to: (i) examine research done in other types of ecosystems (TS-S2, TS-S9, TS-S29); (ii) investigate how openness in software affects and influences the success of a business in SECO (TS-S1); (iii) establish theories, methods, and tools specific to SECO problems (TS-S1, TS-S9); (iv) expand and evaluate existing SECO theories (TS-S9); (v) investigate SECO boundary conditions (TS-S9, TS-S29); and (vi) investigate

Table 4.6: SECO research topics with future research directions.

SECO research topic	Study ID
General	TS-S2, TS-S9, TS-S29
PSECO	TS-S2
OSSECO	TS-S1, TS-S2, TS-S11, TS-S15, TS-S18
MSECO	TS-S19
Health	TS-S2, TS-S7, TS-S10
Quality	TS-S1, TS-S2, TS-S8, TS-S12
Key performance indicator (KPI)	TS-S3
Governance	TS-S1, TS-S2, TS-S25
Social aspects	TS-S2, TS-S8
Partnership	TS-S18, TS-S28, TS-S30
Open innovation	TS-S4
Requirements engineering	TS-S1, TS-S8, TS-S12
Software architecture	TS-S1, TS-S8, TS-S14
Business processes management	TS-S24
Empirical research methods	TS-S1, TS-S27
Software evolution	TS-S1, TS-S2, TS-S8
Software verification & testing	TS-S8
Sustainability	TS-S29
Artificial intelligence	TS-S29

interdependent key contingency processes of value creation, value delivery, and value capture in SECO (TS-S29).

TS-S1 highlighted that a relevant question is how an SECO must be analyzed. TS-S2 mentioned that the investigation of the possible intersections or parallelization with other types of ecosystems would allow the use of theories from other fields or different perspectives on SECO problems. TS-S9 highlighted that when introducing theories from other ecosystem fields, one should be aware of how these theories fit, influence, and are influenced by the different aspects of SECO. TS-S29 pointed out the potential to investigate the interface between SECO and innovation ecosystems, SECO and platform-based ecosystems, and SECO and business ecosystems. For TS-S29, such studies would provide essential knowledge for the SECO research community.

Insight #4:

It is necessary to develop specific theories, methods, and tools specific to SECO, aiming to address their challenges.

Social Aspects. We identified one future research direction that refers to: (i) investigate the actor diversity and multiplicity in SECO (TS-S2). TS-S2 mentioned that no concrete studies have been provided on diversity, which is considered an important ingredient of the success of a SECO. Moreover, TS-S11 and TS-S19 pointed out the need for future investigations into social aspects in OSSECO and

MSECO, respectively.

Insight #5:

It is necessary to investigate the diversity and multiplicity of actors in SECO, as these factors are critical to the success of a SECO.

Open Innovation. We identified nine future research directions that refer to: (i) better understand mechanisms for primary innovations and its organizational and architectural aspects in SECO (TS-S4); (ii) better understand competitive architecture and organizational capabilities that foster open innovation in SECO (TS-S4); (iii) better understand transition from learning about existing products and markets to the definition of new competitive architecture in SECO (TS-S4); (iv) investigate the kinds of SECO processes that support software innovation across domains and players (TS-S4); (v) investigate procedures and techniques that support open innovation in SECO (TS-S4); (vi) identify best current practices for business innovation in the SECO domain (TS-S4); (vii) investigate business agreements that enable innovation and collaboration in SECO (TS-S4); (viii) understand how ecosystem processes and practices support business innovation and software innovation combined (TS-S4); and (ix) investigate extent to which hackathons contribute to SECO health (TS-S17).

TS-S4 identified areas related to ecosystems and open innovation that require additional research and presented them as a research agenda with items that are thus concerned with deriving knowledge about the competitive architecture and organizational capability for open innovation. TS-S17 highlighted that theoretical discussion about hackathons contributes to the open innovation literature and motivates future research.

Insight #6:

It is necessary to investigate procedures and techniques that support open innovation in SECO to better understand the SECO openness.

Requirements Engineering. We identified 11 future research directions that refer to: (i) better understand needs of niche players and defining the appropriate technical support to deal with them effectively; (ii) investigate how to communicate

quality requirements in SECO; (iii) investigate how to balance all ecosystem players' requirements, wishes and priorities; (iv) develop requirements elicitation tools and techniques for SECO (TS-S12); (v) define RE methods and guidelines for conducting the RE process in SECO (TS-S12); (vi) develop tools to analyze the requirements in SECO (TS-S12); (vii) define patterns to specify the users' requirements in SECO (TS-S12); (viii) develop tools to model the requirements in SECO (TS-S12); (ix) investigate requirements validation and management in SECO (TS-S12); (x) investigate requirements selection and prioritization in SECO (TS-S12); and (xi) perform empirical studies on RE in SECO (TS-S12).

TS-S8 presented a research agenda for quality assurance in SECO, with some research directions related to RE. TS-S12 presented several topics that could be the target of future RE research in SECO.

Insight #7:

It is necessary to define RE methods and guidelines for conducting the RE process in SECO that address challenges such as balancing requirements from multi-party actors, communicating requirements inside and outside the ecosystem, and managing requirements.

4.2.3 Discussion

In this section, we discuss the results presented in Section 4.2.2 and compare our results with other studies.

4.2.3.1 SECO Field Evolution (TS-RQ1)

The frequency of publications of secondary studies on SECO has been maintained since 2013, with at least one study published yearly. This frequency indicates a continued interest in publishing this type of study and, consequently, an increase in the publication of primary studies on the different SECO aspects and subdomains, contributing to the field's evolution. According to Kitchenham et al. [106], secondary studies motivate new primary studies.

We highlight that even with several secondary studies on aspects and subdomains of SECO, secondary studies on SECO, in a general form, continue to be published. TS-S1 presented an SMS published in 2013, TS-S2 presented an SLR published

in 2013, TS-S9 presented an LLS published in 2016, and TS-S29 presented a new SLR published in 2022. We noticed that: (i) TS-S1 and TS-S2 had different RQ; (ii) TS-S9 expanded on the results of TS-S2 and revised its RQ to consider the evolution of SECO research; and (iii) TS-S29 did not explicitly state its RQ but justified the need for a new SLR due to the significant increase in publications in the SECO field after the publication of TS-S9.

4.2.3.2 SECO Aspects and Subdomains (TS-RQ2)

We identified five selected secondary studies that investigate SECO in a general form, ten that investigate some subdomain of SECO, and 21 that explore one or more aspects of SECO. As presented in Section 4.2.2, some studies investigate more than one aspect in the same subdomain.

Regarding **SECO subdomains**, we identified: (i) one study that investigated PSECO and other SECO aspects (TS-S25); (ii) three studies that investigated OSSECO, where one investigated only OSSECO (TS-S11) and two investigated OSSECO and other SECO aspects (TS-S5 and TS-S26); (iii) four studies that investigated MSECO, where two investigated only MSECO (TS-S6 and TS-S19) and two investigated OSSECO and other SECO aspects (TS-S20 and TS-S23); and (iv) two studies that investigated only technological health ecosystems (TS-S21 and TS-S22).

We identified that there is no secondary study that investigates only PSECO. According to Santos et al. [8], PSECO require further investigation, as well as support for tooling and analytics. We noticed that OSSECO is the most cited/discussed subdomain in the selected secondary studies and has the largest number of published primary studies. According to Qi and Cao [159], the concept of the OSSECO has received attention from industry and academics. MSECO was the only subdomain of SECO investigated exclusively in two selected secondary studies (TS-S16 and TS-S19). Moreover, all selected secondary studies on MSECO are from Brazil and have a similar set of authors. According to Xiao et al. [160], the research on MSECO is still in the initial stage.

Regarding **SECO aspects**, we identified that health was the most investigated SECO aspect (TS-S7, TS-S10, TS-S13, TS-S15 and TS-S25). However, it did not

was investigated in the MSECO or OSSECO subdomains, despite there are several primary studies investigating health specifically for OSSECO [91, 159, 161, 162] and MSECO [160, 163, 164, 165]. Another SECO aspect investigated in different selected secondary studies was partnership. Jansen [1] defined partners in SECO as organizations that provide services and products that extend the capabilities of the orchestrator, such as consultancy, product, or knowledge partners. According to Valença and Alves [166], the successful evolution of the SECO is affected by how the partnerships are developed and nurtured in the ecosystem.

4.2.3.3 Quality of Secondary Studies on SECO (TS-RQ3)

We assessed the quality of the 31 selected secondary studies according to the DARE criteria. We ranked six selected secondary studies (TS-S5, TS-S9, TS-S26, TS-S27, TS-S28, TS-S29) with a low-quality score ($0.5 \leq \text{quality score} \leq 2$), 12 selected secondary studies (TS-S2, TS-S4, TS-S6, TS-S13, TS-S14, TS-S16, TS-S18, TS-S19, TS-S23, TS-S24, TS-S25, TS-S30) with a medium-quality score ($2.5 \leq \text{quality score} \leq 3$) and 13 selected secondary studies (TS-S1, TS-S3, TS-S7, TS-S8, TS-S10, TS-S11, TS-S12, TS-S15, TS-S17, TS-S20, TS-S21, TS-S22, TS-S31) with a high-quality score ($3.5 \leq \text{quality score} \leq 5$).

We identified among the secondary studies ranked with low-quality scores: (i) one study that presented a link to the full review protocol, but it was not accessible (TS-S5); (ii) one study that presented an LLS based on a previous SLR but did not detail their review protocol (TS-S9); and (iii) four studies presented only a summary of the review protocol without making the full version available (TS-S26, TS-S27, TS-S28, TS-S29). Moreover, none of these studies made open access to primary studies' data available. According to Kitchenham et al. [106], all the details of the review process, data extraction, and analysis/synthesis need to be reported, including the references for all the primary studies.

Among the selected secondary studies classified with high-quality scores, we noticed that: (i) there is no difference in the number of studies published in conferences (six secondary studies) and journals (six secondary studies), and there was only one study published as a chapter of book; (ii) there is no indication of improvement in the quality of selected secondary studies over time; (iii) there is a

slight difference between the number of SMS (seven secondary studies) and SLR (six secondary studies). Therefore, we realized that a high-quality score for a selected secondary study is unrelated to the form of publication, period, or type. According to Khan et al. [104], one of the approaches to increase the level of certainty of the results of a secondary study is to measure its quality meticulously.

4.2.3.4 SECO Future Research Directions (TS-RQ4)

We identified several future research directions (Section 4.2.2.4) for research topics identified in the selected secondary studies. Four of these research topics have not yet been investigated in secondary studies (software evolution, software verification/testing, sustainability, and artificial intelligence). We also identified that some future research directions in the field of SECO have persisted over time. We realized that the need to consider research carried out in the context of other ecosystems (e.g., natural ecosystems, business ecosystems, digital ecosystems) is a future research direction that was pointed out in 2013 (TS-S2), reinforced in 2016 (TS-S9), and maintained in 2022 (TS-S29). Moreover, clarifying SECO boundary conditions has not yet been fully achieved. We consider this analysis an important finding for the SECO field, as it allows the research community to reflect on the reasons for maintaining these research directions and how they have evolved.

We noticed that some future research directions converged in TS-S1 and TS-S11, such as those related to research topics, social aspects, quality, and software evolution. Hence, more research should be carried out on OSSECO considering the future research directions presented in TS-S1 and TS-S11 that can also be related to other SECO research topics, such as governance, social aspects, quality, RE, software evolution, software architecture, and software verification/testing.

This tertiary study identified the RE research topic in SECO and provided a better understanding of how RE has been investigated in SECO to date. Furthermore, it helped us identify a research direction related to understanding requirements management in SECO, which motivated the SMS presented in the next section.

4.3 Systematic Mapping Study on Requirements Management in Software Ecosystems

We carried out an SMS to identify and analyze the current state of requirements management in SECO in terms of its characteristics and existing approaches. We considered “*characteristics*” as process elements [167, 168] that differentiate requirements management in SECO from requirements management in traditional software development (i.e., concepts/definitions, activities, actors’ relationships, and artifacts). We consider “*approaches*” as types of contributions [169, 170, 171] cited/proposed in the selected studies (i.e., methods, techniques, tools, and practices). In addition, we aimed to verify if (and how) the approaches identified are assessed. Finally, we presented an overview of what has already been done and where contributions are still needed.

We adopted the guidelines provided by Kitchenham and Charters [125] and Kitchenham et al. [106] to carry out the SMS. Three main phases are proposed for this SMS: planning, conducting, and reporting the results [125, 106].

4.3.1 Planning

In the planning phase of SMS, we defined a review protocol that details goals and RQ, search strategy, study selection process, and data extraction and synthesis process.

4.3.1.1 Goals and Research Questions

We formalized the objective presented in Section 4.3 based on the GQM (Goal-Question-Metric) method [172] and defined as follows: **analyze** the requirements management **with the purpose of** characterizing **with respect to** elements (i.e., concepts/definitions, activities, actors’ relationships, and artifacts) and types of contributions (i.e., methods, techniques, tools, and practices) **from the point of view of** researchers **in the context of** SECO studies. Next, we formulated the research questions presented in Table 4.7.

Table 4.7: SMS research questions.

ID	Research questions	Rationale
SMS-RQ1	What are the characteristics (process elements, i.e., concepts definitions, activities, actors relationships, and artifacts) of requirements management in SECO context?	The answer to SMS-RQ1 can reveal the main characteristics of requirements management in SECO that differentiate from requirements management in traditional software development. We considered the technical, human, and organizational factors used by Luz et al. [173] to characterize requirements management in SECO.
SMS-RQ2	What are the approaches (types of contributions, i.e., methods, techniques, tools, and practices) used to support requirements management in SECO context?	The answer to SMS-RQ2 can reveal the approaches used in requirements management in SECO, as well as their status interest areas in the SECO research community, providing clues for summarizing future research directions. We defined approaches (types of contributions of the studies) according to the SE research results described by Shaw [169].
SMS-RQ3	How have the existing approaches to requirements management in SECO context been assessed?	The answer to SMS-RQ3 can summarize the evaluation methods applied in the approaches identified in SMS-RQ2 and provide a basis for measuring their effectiveness. We used the empirical research methods in software ecosystems described by Abdullai et al. [154] and empirical research methods in SE described by Wohlin et al. [174] to categorize our results.

4.3.1.2 Search Strategy

We applied a hybrid search strategy [175, 176] in our SMS. Wohlin et al. [176] defined a hybrid search strategy as “*the pre-planned integration of at least two systematic approaches to searching for articles for a systematic literature study*”. Mourão et al. [175] presented four hybrid search strategies used in SE: (i) database search (DBS) in Scopus followed by full backward snowballing (BS) and forward snowballing (FS); (ii) DBS in Scopus followed by BS and FS in parallel; (iii) DBS in Scopus followed by BS and then FS; and (iv) DBS in Scopus followed by FS and then BS. Wohlin et al. [176] compared and evaluated the four strategies and concluded that the full-fledged hybrid search strategy (i) is better than the other alternatives. For this reason, we applied strategy (i).

In the full-fledged hybrid search strategy (i), we must initially perform the DBS and then identify new studies by BS and FS based on the initial set of selected studies from the DBS. Our hybrid search strategy involved DBS in seven digital libraries: ACM Digital Library, ScienceDirect, Engineering Village, IEEE Xplore Digital Library, Scopus, Web of Science, and Wiley Online Library. Wohlin et al. [176] highlighted that BS and FS must be performed for all selected studies, i.e., they must be performed in several iterations until no new studies are selected. Figure 4.7 presents our hybrid search strategy.

The guidelines provided by Kitchenham and Charters [125] recommended composing a string to find relevant studies by searching several digital libraries or index databases. To conduct the DBS, we initially identified keywords from terms

Figure 4.7: SMS hybrid search strategy.

present in the research questions. Afterward, we gathered the keywords into the search string. Table 4.8 provides the search string.

Table 4.8: SMS search string.

SMS search string
(“software ecosystem” OR “software ecosystems”) AND (“requirements management” OR “requirements analysis” OR “requirements communication” OR “requirements traceability” OR “requirements documentation” OR “requirements prioritization” OR “requirements change” OR “requirements negotiation”)

To increase the reliability of our search strategy, we used control studies in the DBS. Control studies support evaluating the quality and comprehensiveness of the search string [177]. Control studies must be retrieved when searching in a given digital library and are essential for calibrating a search string [178]. We identified the two control studies [18, 179] in exploratory studies we conducted previously. The two control studies investigated requirements management in SECO and were retrieved in different digital libraries as we calibrated our search string.

4.3.1.3 Study Selection

Kitchenham and Charters [125] divided the study selection into two parts: (a) definition of study selection criteria; and (b) definition of the study selection process. We present our definitions for each part next.

According to Kitchenham and Charters [125], for the selection of retrieved studies, IC and EC (Table 4.9) must be defined and applied. We were inspired by the examples of IC and EC presented by Kitchenham et al. [106] in their reference book to define the set of IC and EC.

Table 4.9: SMS selection criteria.

Inclusion criteria (IC)	
ID	Criteria
SMS-IC1	The study presents characteristics of requirements management in SECO.
SMS-IC2	The study proposes or cites requirements management approaches in SECO.
Exclusion criteria (EC)	
ID	Criteria
SMS-EC1	The study does not meet at least one IC.
SMS-EC2	The study is duplicated.
SMS-EC3	The study is unavailable for free download or through institutional access.
SMS-EC4	The study is not peer-reviewed or is a Master's or Doctoral thesis.
SMS-EC5	The study is not written in English.

In our SMS, we divided the selection process into seven stages and explained each stage and its relationship with the IC and EC, according to Kitchenham and Charters [125], in Table 4.10. The selection process involved four researchers. Two researchers initially applied the IC and EC independently. Thereafter, the same two researchers compared the results and sought a consensus in case of divergence. Finally, the other two researchers, who have more than fifteen years of experience conducting and publishing secondary studies, assessed the results of each stage.

Table 4.10: SMS study selection process.

Stage	Description
Stage 1	We apply the search string in digital libraries to obtain the set of studies retrieved.
Stage 2	We apply the 1st filter (removal of duplicates) to the set of studies retrieved in stage 1. We frame all duplicate studies in EC2.
Stage 3	We apply the 2nd filter (application of IC and EC after reading the title, abstract, and keywords) in the set of studies analyzed in stage 2.
Stage 4	We apply the 3rd filter (application of IC and EC after reading the introduction and conclusion) in the set of studies analyzed in stage 3.
Stage 5	We apply the 4th filter (application of IC and EC after the complete reading) in the set of studies analyzed in stage 4.
Stage 6	We apply snowballing (BS and FS) in the set of studies analyzed in stage 5. Then, we perform stages 2, 3, 4, and 5 in the set of studies retrieved in snowballing. We iteratively repeat stage 6 until no new studies have been selected.
Stage 7	We extract data from the studies analyzed in stages 5 and 6.

4.3.1.4 Data Extraction and Synthesis

According to Kitchenham and Charters [125], the data extraction process must collect the data items needed to answer the research questions. The data extraction process in a secondary study comprises elaborating forms to record the information obtained in the primary studies accurately [125]. Our data extraction form¹² is openly available (details in Appendix 9.5).

During data extraction, we identified in each selected study: (a) specific characteristics of requirements management in SECO (SMS-RQ1); (b) approaches

¹²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8131745>

used for requirements management in SECO (SMS-RQ2); (c) whether or not there was an assessment of the approaches used for requirements management in SECO (SMS-RQ3); and (d) the method used for assessment (SMS-RQ3). We also extracted data that allowed us to do the demographic analysis of the studies selected in our SMS without referring to specific RQ. We identified in each selected study: (a) Title; (b) Year; (c) Authors; and (d) Country of 1st author.

To answer the research questions, we used data synthesis. Kitchenham and Charters [125] state that there are two main data synthesis methods: (i) descriptive (qualitative); and (ii) quantitative. We used the qualitative method to analyze the extracted data and answer our research questions, which led to descriptive data synthesis [134]. We applied open and axial coding procedures [116] to support the qualitative synthesis method. Open coding involves applying codes that are derived from the text, and axial coding categorizes the initial codes into key codes [116]. Qualitative methods such as content analysis, thematic analysis, and Grounded Theory (GT) use coding procedures.

4.3.2 Results

Figure 4.8 presents an overview of the selection process. We performed a DBS in the seven digital libraries. We retrieved 1,028 studies published up to March 2023 in the DBS. Then, we applied the filters defined in the stages of the selection process (Table 4.10). We selected 25 studies in the DBS. Thus, we applied BS and FS to the 25 studies selected from the search database and retrieved 1,300 studies. We selected three studies in the first snowballing iteration. Then, we applied BS and FS for the second time in 120 retrieved studies in the three selected studies in the first snowballing iteration. Thus, we selected one study in the second snowballing iteration. Finally, we applied BS and FS for the third time in 38 retrieved studies in the selected study in the second snowballing iteration. However, when we applied the filters defined in the selection process, we did not select any new studies. Hence, we got a total of 29 selected studies in our SMS.

Table 4.11 presents the selected studies in ascending order by year of publication and are referred to in this work as SMS-S1 to SMS-S29. Next, we present the analysis of demographic data and an overview of the results.

Figure 4.8: Study selection process.

Table 4.11: General characteristics of the primary studies selected in the SMS.

ID	Year	Country	Reference
SMS-S1	2009	Sweden	[180]
SMS-S2	2009	Switzerland	[181]
SMS-S3	2010	United States	[182]
SMS-S4	2012	Canada	[183]
SMS-S5	2013	Brazil	[184]
SMS-S6	2013	Brazil	[185]
SMS-S7	2013	Brazil	[186]
SMS-S8	2013	Netherlands	[187]
SMS-S9	2014	Brazil	[188]
SMS-S10	2014	Germany	[189]
SMS-S11	2014	Brazil	[190]
SMS-S12	2015	Sweden	[191]
SMS-S13	2016	Sweden	[192]
SMS-S14	2016	Sweden	[179]
SMS-S15	2016	Brazil	[166]
SMS-S16	2017	Sweden	[39]
SMS-S17	2018	Sweden	[18]
SMS-S18	2018	Brazil	[193]
SMS-S19	2018	Sweden	[81]
SMS-S20	2018	Germany	[194]
SMS-S21	2019	Germany	[5]
SMS-S22	2019	Germany	[195]
SMS-S23	2020	Netherlands	[1]
SMS-S24	2020	Sweden	[19]
SMS-S25	2020	Ireland	[196]
SMS-S26	2020	Canada	[16]
SMS-S27	2020	Sweden	[197]
SMS-S28	2021	Ireland	[198]
SMS-S29	2021	Canada	[2]

Figure 4.9 shows the distribution of selected studies over the years. We noticed that at least one study was published from 2012 to 2021. The selected studies had 87 different authors. However, to analyze the countries related to each study, we considered only the countries of the first author. Figure 4.10 presents the

distribution of publications by country. Sweden (9 studies) and Brazil (7 studies) are the countries that authored most of the selected studies.

Figure 4.9: Distribution of select studies by year.

Figure 4.10: Distribution of selected studies by country.

Figure 4.11 presents this study’s main findings and the summary of answers to research questions (Sections 4.3.2.1, 4.3.2.2, and 4.3.2.3). In addition, Figure 4.11 also shows other information discussed in Section 4.3.3, such as the main reasons requirements management in SECO is considered a challenge and what other activities of the RE are related to requirements management in SECO.

Figure 4.11: Requirements management overview in SECO.

4.3.2.1 Characteristics of Requirements Management in SECO (SMS-RQ1)

In our work, characteristics are process elements [167, 168] related to requirements management in SECO that differentiate it from requirements management performed in traditional software development. To define them, we considered the technical, human, and organizational factors in SECO used by Luz et al. [173]. Luz et al. [173] stated these factors can influence SECO technical and organizational elements. For example, the factor *multiplicity of organizations and relationships of a SECO* influences the requirements management in SECO.

We defined the characteristics of requirements management in SECO through the data synthesis process detailed in Section 4.3.1.4. We used the synthesis qualitative method [134] to analyze the extracted data and answer our research questions. To do so, we initially used an open coding approach. We coded the extracted data of the selected studies in an inductive (bottom-up) way [116]. We performed a detailed reading of selected studies and divided parts of the text of these studies into coherent units (sentences or paragraphs). Subsequently, we agreed on a set of

codes that captured the most frequent and relevant characteristics of requirements management in SECO cited in the selected studies (example in Table 4.12). The coding was done by two authors and reviewed over several iterative cycles by the other two authors (with more than fifteen years of experience with SE research).

After executing open coding, we used axial coding to group the codes into categories, as described by Charmaz [116]. We categorized the characteristics into (i) concepts/definitions; (ii) activities; (iii) actors' relationships; and (iv) artifacts. Table 4.12 shows examples of the coding process of the selected studies (the resulting codes and their categories). The complete coding process¹³ is openly available (details in Appendix 9.5). Finally, Table 4.13 presents the nine characteristics of requirements management in SECO (C1-C9).

Table 4.12: Illustration of the coding process for the definition of characteristics of requirements management in SECO.

C1 (Table 4.13)	
Category:	Concepts/definitions
Code:	Requirements management in SECO is open, informal, collaborative, and decentralized
Coherent units:	<p>SMS-S11: “Changes happen from a centralized to a <i>decentralized management</i>. It also involves new business models to support an <i>open RE</i>, with a <i>collaborative process</i> where clients suggest and vote for new features.”</p> <p>SMS-S13: “RE has moved to become more <i>decentralized</i> and <i>collaborative</i> with an evolving set of stakeholders.”</p> <p>SMS-S14: “Looking at OSS ecosystems, requirements practices are often <i>informal</i> and <i>overlapping</i>.”</p>
C4 (Table 4.13)	
Category:	Actors' relationships
Code:	Multi-party actors (i.e., users, external developers, and others) who are external to the keystone influence requirements management in SECO
Coherent units:	<p>SMS-S2: “Large-scale organizations need to consider the interplay of a <i>considerable number of stakeholders</i> for defining requirements of their commercial and technical products and product platforms.”</p> <p>SMS-S28: “Having too <i>many stakeholders</i> to manage completely is a problem that requirements managers of the technological base product of SECOs face.”</p> <p>SMS-S29: “In a SECO, the keystone has to consider the wishes and needs from not just its own end users, but also its ecosystem.”</p>
C7 (Table 4.13)	
Category:	Activities
Code:	Keystone usually conducts the requirements identification and prioritization in SECO collaboratively and involves multi-party actors (i.e., users, external developers, and others)
Coherent units:	<p>SMS-S5: “The majority of requirements are defined by participants of the ecosystem, rather than elicited from users.”</p> <p>SMS-S6: “Large-scale organizations need to consider the interplay of a <i>considerable number of stakeholders</i> for defining requirements of their commercial and technical products and platforms.”</p> <p>SMS-S14: “Requirements are commonly asserted through transparent discussions and suggestions. <i>Prioritization is commonly conducted by ecosystem maintainers.</i>”</p> <p>SMS-S24: “Practices such as <i>elicitation and prioritization overlap</i> and are done <i>collaboratively</i> through iterative discussions.”</p>

C1 (Concepts/Definitions) refers to the openness, informality, collaboration, and decentralization of requirements management in SECO. SMS-S13, SMS-S14, SMS-S17, SMS-S19, and SMS-S24 stated that requirements management in SECO is

¹³<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8131745>

Table 4.13: Characteristics of requirements management in SECO.

ID	Characteristics of requirements management in SECO	Selected Studies
Concepts/definitions		
C1	Requirements management in SECO usually is open, informal, collaborative, and decentralized and benefits from the open innovation paradigm.	SMS-S3, SMS-S11, SMS-S13, SMS-S14, SMS-S15, SMS-S16, SMS-S17, SMS-S19, SMS-S20, SMS-S22, SMS-S24, SMS-S29
C2	Emergent requirements originated by multi-party actors affect requirements management in SECO.	SMS-S3, SMS-S13, SMS-S17, SMS-S29
C3	Requirements management in SECO considers different types of requirements (i.e., platform, integration, and product requirements).	SMS-S3, SMS-S8, SMS-S9, SMS-S10, SMS-S15, SMS-S26, SMS-S29
Ators' relationships		
C4	Multi-party actors (i.e., users, external developers, and others) who are external to the keystone influence requirements management in SECO.	SMS-S2, SMS-S4, SMS-S6, SMS-S7, SMS-S8, SMS-S17, SMS-S20, SMS-S21, SMS-S24, SMS-S26, SMS-S28, SMS-S29
C5	Power relations among multi-party actors influence requirements management in SECO.	SMS-S9, SMS-S15, SMS-S17, SMS-S20, SMS-S21, SMS-S24
Activities		
C6	Keystone usually orchestrates the requirements negotiation in SECO and counts on the participation of multi-party actors (i.e., users, external developers, and others).	SMS-S2, SMS-S5, SMS-S7, SMS-S9, SMS-S13, SMS-S14, SMS-S17
C7	Keystone usually conducts the requirements identification and prioritization in SECO collaboratively and involves multi-party actors (i.e., users, external developers, and others).	SMS-S4, SMS-S5, SMS-S6, SMS-S7, SMS-S8, SMS-S9, SMS-S14, SMS-S15, SMS-S17, SMS-S21, SMS-S24, SMS-S25, SMS-S26, SMS-S28, SMS-S29
C8	Multi-party actors (i.e., keystone, users, external developers, and others) use multiple open communication channels for requirements communication inside and outside SECO.	SMS-S2, SMS-S3, SMS-S4, SMS-S5, SMS-S6, SMS-S8, SMS-S10, SMS-S13, SMS-S14, SMS-S15, SMS-S17, SMS-S20, SMS-S21, SMS-S26, SMS-S27
Artifacts		
C9	Requirements management in SECO manages requirements that may be spread across different types of artifacts and stored in more than one requirements repository (i.e., issue trackers, mailing lists, and source code repositories).	SMS-S8, SMS-S14, SMS-S19, SMS-S24

informal, has overlapping practices and uses informalisms [199]. SMS-S3, SMS-S11, SMS-S13, SMS-S15, SMS-S17, and SMS-S24 mentioned that the requirements management process in SECO is decentralized and collaborative. SMS-S15 highlighted that SECO require a collaborative and joint RE process. SMS-S24 defined requirements management in SECO as a lightweight and evolutionary process compared to more traditional processes characterized by heavy processes and supporting tools.

SMS-S11, SMS-S13, SMS-S14, SMS-S15, SMS-S16, SMS-S17, SMS-S20, SMS-S22, and SMS-S29 indicated that requirements management in SECO is open. SMS-S11, SMS-S16, SMS-S17, and SMS-S22 cited that the requirements management in SECO is cross-domain and benefits from the open innovation paradigm. SMS-S16 suggested that open innovation positively impacts requirements change management, quality requirements, and requirements communication.

However, open innovation negatively impacts identifying stakeholders' needs, requirements prioritization, and requirements traceability. SMS-S20 mentioned that SECO are, by nature, cross-domain and open. Then, requirements managers in SECO no longer deal with one domain at a time and must accept the openness inherent to SECO in requirements management activities. SMS-S11 pointed out that involving new business models to support open RE is necessary.

Insight #8:

Requirements management benefits from the open innovation paradigm with more flexible and cross-domain interactions, positively impacting requirements change management.

C2 (Concepts/Definitions) focuses explicitly on the concept of emergent requirements in requirements management in SECO. SMS-S17 mentioned that the complexity and ever-changing nature of SECO results in several new requirements based on ecosystem trends and defines them as emergent requirements. SMS-S3, SMS-S13, and SMS-S17 cited that emergent requirements originate from end users of consumers in the ecosystem, who find new ways to use existing services. SMS-S29 mentioned that new functionalities offered by external developers (complementors) can generate emergent requirements. SMS-S7 highlighted that multi-party actors who are not responsible for the requirements but contribute to discussing them beyond organizational boundaries originate emergent requirements. For SMS-S29, emergent requirements allow keystone to innovate further to grow platform offerings, creating a circular flow of requirements knowledge. According to SMS-S17, it is difficult to map emergent requirements to specific actors, especially since they are generally transversal to several SECO actors.

Insight #9:

Emergent requirements challenge requirements management in SECO. However, they also create opportunities for continuous innovation and platform growth.

C3 (Concepts/Definitions) refers to the types of requirements that affect requirements management in SECO. SMS-S3 bifurcated the requirements in

SECO into kernel requirements and periphery requirements. SMS-S8 ranked the requirements in SECO into partner requirements and customer requirements. SMS-S8 highlighted that partner requirements in SECO may be a higher priority than customer requirements. For SMS-S9, there are product, integration, and platform requirements in SECO. Integration requirements must be “*generic and reusable*” among partners as they are part of a shared infrastructure. Platform requirements are the basis of the development environment actors use to develop complementary products in SECO. SMS-S15 highlighted that most demands in a SECO are integration requirements involving data types exchanged and data dictionary, for instance. SMS-S29 mentioned that evangelists are a key source of feedback and provide several integration requirements.

SMS-S10 identified several requirements that the keystone communicated to other SECO members. SMS-S10 classified them into three generic categories of requirements: strategic, brand, and platform requirements. Strategic requirements ensure a particular function that is essential to the systemic product the customer will acquire. Branding requirements play a role in preserving SECO’s brand reputation. Platform requirements facilitate product design and development in SECO. SMS-S26 carried out a case study in a specific SECO. It suggested that the RE process in SECO should have three main focuses: RE for the product, RE for the platform, and RE for the ecosystem (holistic view to identify integrations between products). For SMS-S26, the developers of partner applications are direct users of the platform, and their needs are essential for the ecosystem’s health.

Insight #10:

Requirements management in SECO considers platform, integration, and product requirements. Dealing with these requirements is complex due to the multi-party actors of the ecosystem.

C4 (Actors’ Relationships) refers to groups of multi-party actors that influence the requirements management in SECO. SMS-S7 and SMS-S17 cited that requirements emerge and propagate through multiple stakeholders’ collaboration across a SECO. SMS-S2, SMS-S4, SMS-S6, SMS-S26, and SMS-S28 pointed out that in SECO, it is necessary to consider the interaction of several stakeholders to

define requirements for their products and platforms. For SMS-S6, it is necessary to identify requirements from several customers with different contexts of use and coordinate the work with several teams responsible for the products of the SECO. SMS-S8, SMS-S20, SMS-S21, SMS-S24, and SMS-S29 highlighted that requirements managers must consider external and interdependent stakeholders in SECO. For SMS-S21, one of the major differences between distributed teams in GSD and SECO is that the teams or actors are not within the same company or organization but instead spread across several organizations, whereby each actor contributes different elements to the system or product.

C5 (Actors' Relationships) focuses on power relations among different multi-party actors that influence requirements management in SECO. For SMS-S15, companies exercise their legitimate power by proposing new requirements for partners in SECO. SMS-S9 mentioned that power conflicts are frequent between partners in SECO. SMS-S17 cited that multiple stakeholders are susceptible to issues of stakeholder power affecting requirements management activities. Power relations strongly affect stakeholder identification (SMS-S17), negotiation (SMS-S9, SMS-S20, SMS-S21), prioritization (SMS-S20, SMS-S24), and requirements communication (SMS-S17) in SECO. For SMS-S9, the notion of power is a common problem affecting RE decision-making. SMS-S24 highlighted that power relations can result in misalignment with internal RE processes.

Insight #11:

Multi-party actors who are external to the keystone and with different power relations influence requirements management in SECO.

C6 (Activities) focuses on requirements negotiation activity that impacts requirements management in SECO. SMS-S14 highlighted that requirements negotiation in SECO is fundamental, as a consensus often is needed to make certain decisions. SMS-S2 and SMS-S9 mentioned that requirements negotiation in SECO establishes an agreement of interests and intentions between multiple stakeholders distributed globally. SMS-S5 stated that geographic distribution causes the inefficiency of negotiation activities that depend on face-to-face communication or require interaction between teams. SMS-S7 justified that since the stakeholders

are multiple and spread across the SECO, the requirements negotiation is complex, as it must consider shared objectives and relationships between the ecosystem actors. SMS-S5 pointed out that these actors have different and sometimes conflicting expectations.

SMS-S7 suggested using specific technologies or techniques to address requirements negotiation in SECO. However, SMS-S7 mentioned that these technologies or techniques do not have an in-depth view of the social dynamics of SECO. For SMS-S7, SECO introduce specific requirements negotiation questions, such as aligning interests and expectations among companies and its markets. SMS-S13 and SMS-S17 pointed out that emergent stakeholders from across the ecosystem and the relationship with partners are important in requirements negotiation in SECO. For SMS-S5, requirements negotiation involves a decision-making process conducted by several different actors along the SECO lifecycle. In traditional software development, requirements negotiation is often less complex, as it usually occurs between a limited number of customers and a limited set of organizations developing the software.

C7 (Activities) refers to requirements identification and prioritization that impact requirements management in SECO. SMS-S4, SMS-S6, SMS-S7, SMS-S15, SMS-S17, SMS-S25, SMS-S26, and SMS-S29 cited that keystone must consider interacting with several stakeholders to identify requirements. SMS-S15 highlighted that the requirements are not equally important and must be ranked or prioritized with a value. For SMS-S5 and SMS-S9, SECO provide products for a broad market, which means that requirements are often jointly defined by the suppliers of the ecosystem rather than elicited from users. SMS-S17 pointed out that traditional RE methods were reported as insufficient to support requirements elicitation in SECO. For SMS-S5 and SMS-S25, the high number of stakeholders in SECO presents challenges regarding requirements elicitation.

SMS-S14 and SMS-S24 mentioned that SECO maintainers (keystones) commonly conduct requirements prioritization, though care is often taken to the opinions of other developers and users. For SMS-S5 and SMS-S8, requirements prioritization in SECO should only be carried out by relevant stakeholders. According to SMS-S21, requirements prioritization can differ highly between SECO actors because

different stakeholders value different attributes when dealing with a requirement. Every partner contributes requirements to the ecosystem, which might result in a requirements overload, causing complications in the prioritization process. SMS-S24 cited that practices such as requirements identification and prioritization in SECO overlap and are done collaboratively through iterative and transparent discussions and negotiations. SMS-S5 highlighted that the requirements definition cannot be disconnected from business processes governing the SECO.

C8 (Activities) focuses on requirements communication activity, which is fundamental to requirements management in SECO. SMS-S10 and SMS-S17 highlighted that the requirements must be communicated inside and outside the SECO. For SMS-S5, requirements emerge through communications amongst the actors of the ecosystem. SMS-S20 and SMS-S26 cited that CrowdRE supports requirements communication through open and heterogeneous communication channels. According to SMS-S2, SMS-S6, and SMS-S8, a requirements communication network (RCN) enables the analysis and design of requirements communication between multiple stakeholders. An RCN describes the stakeholders and the structure of a SECO in terms of groups of actors and negotiation channels.

SMS-S4, SMS-S21, and SMS-S27 highlighted using multiple open communication channels to allow transparent communication between the multiple SECO actors. SMS-S4 cited that RE via open channels is an innovative process. The studies mentioned as examples of open communication channels the discussion forums (SMS-S3, SMS-S13, SMS-S15), problem/issue trackers (SMS-S13, SMS-S14, SMS-S27), mailing lists (SMS-S13, SMS-S14, SMS-S15, SMS-S27), ticket/helpdesk systems (SMS-S14, SMS-S15, SMS-S27), and version control systems (SMS-S27). This scenario diverges from requirements management in traditional software development, where the actors are usually well-defined, the view on requirements management tends to be more centralized, and communication channels are generally closed.

Insight #12:

Requirements management activities in SECO count on the participation of multi-party actors who use multiple communication channels for requirements communication inside and outside the ecosystem.

C9 (Artifacts) focuses on the requirements repositories in SECO. For SMS-S8, requirements sharing in SECO must be expanded with relevant and authorized external actors. SMS-S14, SMS-S19, and SMS-S24 mentioned that there is often no central repository with requirements defined, along with heavy processes and tools for examining the requirements for completeness and consistency in SECO. According to SMS-S19, decentralized repositories (i.e., issue trackers, mailing lists, and source code repositories) store the requirements in SECO. SMS-S19 and SMS-S24 highlighted that in OSSECO, several artifacts can represent a requirement, often complementing each other to give a complete picture, i.e., as an issue, in a mail thread, and/or as a prototype or a finished implementation.

Insight #13:

Requirements management in SECO involves requirements that may be spread across different types of artifacts and stored in more than one requirements repository.

4.3.2.2 Approaches Used to Requirements Management in SECO (SMS-RQ2)

To categorize the approaches identified in the selected studies, we used the taxonomy defined by Shaw [169] and the definitions of types of contributions cited by Paternoster et al. [170] and Dermeval et al. [171]. Shaw’s taxonomy used some research results in SE, such as procedure or technique; model (qualitative or descriptive, empirical, analytic); tool or notation; or a specific solution (i.e., practice).

Paternoster et al. [170] also used the taxonomy described by Shaw [169]. For Paternoster et al. [170], types of contributions can be divided into weak (advice and implications, lessons learned, tools and guidelines) and strong (theory, framework/method, and model) contributions. Dermeval et al. [171] mentioned that its classification of approaches (type of contribution) was based on the work of Petersen et al. [200]. Dermeval et al. [171] defined method, model, tool, and process as types of approaches. Finally, we also considered the classifications of approaches defined by the authors of the selected studies. For example, SMS-S23 mentioned the term “*practice*” to refer to the approach that the study cites. Table 4.14 presents

the definitions of each type of approach according to Shaw [169].

Table 4.14: Description of types of approaches.

Type of approach	Descripton by Shaw [169]	Descripton in our work
Tool	Implemented tool that embodies a technique; formal language to support a technique or model (should have a calculus, semantics, or other basis for computing or doing inference [169]).	“ <i>Tool</i> ” provides (semi-)automated support for some technique, method, or model to support requirements management in SECO.
Model	(a) Descriptive model: Structure or taxonomy for a problem area; architectural style, framework, or design pattern; non-formal domain analysis, well-grounded checklists, well-argued informal generalizations, guidance for integrating other results, well-organized interesting observations; (b) Empirical model: Empirical predictive model based on observed data; and (c) Analytic model: Structural model that permits formal analysis or automatic manipulation [169].	“ <i>Model</i> ” can be defined as a representation or abstraction of the activities characterized in the requirements management process in SECO.
Method	New or better way to do some task, such as design, implementation, maintenance, measurement, evaluation, selection from alternatives; includes techniques for implementation, representation, management, and analysis [169].	“ <i>method</i> ” is the procedure, technique, or way of doing some activity related to the requirements management process in SECO.
Practice	Shaw [169] does not define “ <i>practice</i> ”.	“ <i>Practice</i> ” is a less prescriptive way of doing some activity related to the requirements management process in SECO.

The results obtained show that requirements management in SECO has been performed with the support of Tool (SMS-S4, SMS-S6, SMS-S9, SMS-S12, SMS-S13, SMS-S14, SMS-S17, SMS-S19, SMS-S20, SMS-S23, SMS-S24, SMS-S26, SMS-S27, SMS-S29); Model (SMS-S5, SMS-S7, SMS-S14, SMS-S19, SMS-S25, SMS-S28); Method (SMS-S1, SMS-S18, SMS-S24); and Practice (SMS-S23). Figure 4.12 shows that most of the approaches found are related to the use of tools. In the context of SMS-RQ2, the selected studies propose or cite the identified approaches. Furthermore, a unique selected study may propose or cite multiple approaches. We presented more details about each type of approach next.

Tool. SMS-S4 presented a qualitative and quantitative investigation of RE in SECO. SMS-S4 conducted a case study on SECO IBM Collaborative Lifecycle Management (IBM CLM) and cited two tools related to requirements management in SECO: Rational Team Concert (RTC) and Rational Requirements Composer (RRC). SMS-S4 also cited issue trackers, discussion forums, and other open communication channels to the public as tools that support requirements management in SECO. SMS-S17 also conducted a study related to SECO IBM CLM and demonstrated requirements flow in SECO. SMS-S17 evidenced the use of RTC and cited that the tool facilitated the discussion of requirements and the

Figure 4.12: Types of approaches to support requirements management in SECO.

creation of bug reports and change requests.

SMS-S6 proposed a framework for dealing with various aspects of SECO, called Reuse-based Software Ecosystems Engineering and Management (ReuseSEEM). The study highlighted the need to create tools that map socio-technical networks to manage the needs, platform requirements, and SECO products and services. For SMS-S6, these tools allow communication and requirements management based on community participation, suggesting and solving customer needs on an extended social networking site.

SMS-S9 presented a case study of two software companies participating collaboratively and competitively in an SECO. One of the interviewers mentioned that one of the companies used the One Studio tool to record requirements change. Furthermore, client company stakeholders used a web-based request system to describe their new demands. Requests were automatically forwarded to the helpdesk service, which selected or discarded the requests. Then, company teams analyzed these demands and tracked their status in the tool, from registering the demand to fulfilling the requirements in a future release.

SMS-S12 presented a case study to analyze RE challenges in a specific SECO (AUTOSAR Ecosystem). One of the interviewees from the study pointed out that in their new project, they have started using an issue tracker for requirements management. He believed using the issue tracker has facilitated requirements management and communication. SMS-S13, SMS-S14, SMS-S19, SMS-S20, SMS-S24, SMS-S26, SMS-S27, and SMS-S29 mentioned issues trackers, discussion

lists, and a version control system as tools that support requirements management in SECO. SMS-S23 and SMS-S27 also cited requirements portals, SMS-S29 cited Stack Overflow and social media (such as Twitter and LinkedIn), and SMS-S24 mentioned source-code repositories and code reviews to support the requirements management in SECO.

Model. SMS-S5 and SMS-S7 proposed a requirements negotiation model in the SECO context to enrich the requirements management process. The proposal is associated with the management of the software platform and seeks to establish requirements for negotiation activities in this social context. SMS-S14 presented the Requirements Analysis and Management for Benefiting Openness (RAMBO) model. This model is used for requirements analysis and management to benefit open innovation. The model presented how the main stages of RE and requirements management processes can be adjusted to benefit from the new context's openness.

SMS-S19 presented the model called Contribution Acceptance Process (CAP). It aimed to help motivate the contribution of companies in OSSECO. Its operationalization in the organization is performed through a meta-model that integrates the requirements management infrastructure so that the contribution strategies of the primary model can be communicated and tracked. The meta-model enables inspiration and guidance on how developer organizations should implement necessary adaptations to their requirements management infrastructure or create a new one.

SMS-S25 and SMS-S28 proposed a reference process model to identify key stakeholders as part of requirements elicitation in SECO. According to SMS-S25, this model can be applied by requirements managers of the common technological platform of SECO to design a business process model to identify stakeholders. In this model, requirements managers identify stakeholders they already know and document their roles in SECO. After that, they open lines of communication with the identified stakeholders (or primary stakeholders) and ask them to identify others (secondary stakeholders). SMS-S28 suggested that requirements managers of the keystone use the reference process model in their activities. The model will provide a structured approach to identifying stakeholders in complicated environments. For SMS-S28, the existing stakeholder identification methods in the literature do not

take a comprehensive approach to consider all stakeholders while pinpointing only a subset from whom to elicit requirements and also with approaches that preserve SECO health, especially in SECO that include proprietary software.

Method. SMS-S1 mentioned three ecosystem elements that constitute agile methods: barely sufficient methodology, collaborative values, and chaordic perspective. Thus, the more volatile the requirements are, and the more experimental the technology, the more agile approaches increase the chances of success in SECO. The study cited that agile methods hold significant promise to deliver greater value to all main SECO actors. For SMS-S1, agile methods in the SECO context can help in (i) technical issues: requirements and tests management; and (ii) organizational issues: process adaptation, knowledge sharing, transfer, and culture change.

SMS-S1 highlighted the need for new approaches to requirements elicitation in SECO to ensure that the voice of the customer is accurately captured. SMS-S1 cited goal-oriented brainstorming and workshops as potential strategies to support agile requirements elicitation. Moreover, SMS-S1 suggested that visual specifications (high-fidelity prototypes) can be used as partial replacements for exclusively textual specifications, thus increasing the emphasis on requirements assessment. SMS-S1 also cited the user story-driven development for requirements management in SECO. According to SMS-S1, agile methods mitigate the impact of emerging changes between systems and embedded software that can unexpectedly increase the cost and duration of the development process.

SMS-S18 presented the results of an investigation into the effects of SECO in two software consumer organizations that conducted information technology management activities. In one of the cases, the study reveals that the demand management team faced challenges related to requirements management concerning the frequent “*re-prioritization*” of the project portfolio due to external issues. An agile method was adopted to mitigate this challenge. The study does not provide further details on use. However, it is possible to figure out that agile methods have been used to support requirements management in SECO.

SMS-S24 proposed the stakeholder influence analysis (SIA) method. SIA aimed to help companies analyze an OSSECO to identify its stakeholders’ influence by

their impact on the requirements implemented. The method SIA was based on social network analysis constructs that have proven useful in characterizing the influence of stakeholders but also effective when analyzing a company's participation in OSSECO and requirement-centric stakeholder collaborations.

Practice. SMS-S23 presented the Software Ecosystem Governance Maturity Model (SEG-M2). This model seeks to evaluate and classify, from the keystone, several elements of SECO in terms of governance. It is divided into seven focus areas, concentrating on a set of practices. SMS-S23 pointed out a practice related to requirements management, which is requirements sharing. It is evidenced at level 3 of the model when adopting a requirements portal is recommended. The study also mentioned that implementing an open requirements management system would face technical and cultural problems in the organization. A third-party system interfaced with the company is already used internally through an application programming interface (API) and manual data copying.

In the context of SMS-RQ2, we identified the approaches to support requirements management in SECO that were proposed or cited in the selected studies. Hence, we noticed that some requirements management tools used in traditional software development also are used in the SECO context. However, the selected studies highlighted several difficulties in using the SECO context. Additionally, when it comes to models, methods, or practices, none focus specifically on requirements management in SECO. The studies only cited that these approaches affect or benefit the requirements management in SECO and do not present much detail.

Insight #14:

In SECO, several approaches enable broad stakeholder participation and are essential for collaboratively managing requirements across the ecosystem. However, there is a need for approaches that address the specific characteristics of SECO.

4.3.2.3 Assessment of Approaches Used to Requirements Management in SECO (SMS-RQ3)

SMS-RQ3 aimed to identify if and how the approaches to requirements management in SECO identified in SMS-RQ2 were assessed. We classified the selected studies

into: (i) studies that do not cite or propose approaches (SMS-S3, SMS-S8, SMS-S10, SMS-S11, SMS-S15, SMS-S16, SMS-S21, SMS-S22); (ii) studies that only cite approaches (SMS-S1, SMS-S4, SMS-S9, SMS-S12, SMS-S13, SMS-S17, SMS-S18, SMS-S20, SMS-S26, SMS-S27, SMS-S29); and (iii) studies that propose approaches to requirements management in SECO (SMS-S2, SMS-S5, SMS-S6, SMS-S7, SMS-S14, SMS-S19, SMS-S23, SMS-S24, SMS-S25, SMS-S28). We identified multiple approaches in the same study (e.g., in SMS-S24, we identified a tool and method). We also identified that some selected studies (SMS-S14, SMS-S19, SMS-S23, SMS-S24) propose a certain approach while only citing others. Thus, we classified these studies as (iii). To answer SMS-RQ3, we considered only selected studies that proposed approaches (iii).

Among the selected studies that proposed approaches (iii), we classified them into (a) studies that present assessment (SMS-S19, SMS-S23, SMS-S24) and (b) studies that do not present assessment (SMS-S2, SMS-S5, SMS-S6, SMS-S7, SMS-S14, SMS-S25, SMS-S28). Among those that do not present an assessment, some mentioned the need for future assessment (SMS-S2, SMS-S6, SMS-S7, SMS-S25, SMS-S28).

We used the empirical research methods in SECO described by Abdullai et al. [154] and empirical research methods in SE described by Wohlin et al. [174] to categorize our results. Abdullai et al. [154] enumerated nine research methods used in SECO: (a) Case study; (b) Mixed methods; (c) Design science; (d) Survey; (e) Longitudinal study; (f) Experimental study; (g) Exploratory study; (h) Interview; and (i) Repository mining. Wohlin et al. [174] enumerated four research methods used in SE: (a) controlled experiment; (b) case study; (c) survey; and (d) postmortem analyses.

SMS-S19 defined the model described from the collaboration of Sony Mobile professionals. However, the authors conducted three exploratory case studies to evaluate it, verifying its usability and applicability. The companies that participated in the validation were: (i) a small company that creates a platform product in the agricultural domain, the Chief Technical Officer (CTO) was interviewed; (ii) a small business that creates games for mobile platforms, the founder was interviewed; and (iii) a large company in the field of telecommunications, a workshop with eight

participants was held. From the three evaluations, the study concludes that the model can be applied to a set of features, a product, or a complete project.

SMS-S23 assessed in six case studies with professionals from the following companies and/or platforms the model and practices presented: (i) platform for augmented reality that provides API through an extension from Unity; (ii) enterprise resource planning company; (iii) credit management company; (iv) network equipment manufacturer; (v) platform specifically designed to facilitate the ecosystem of the company mentioned in item iv; and (vi) a business-to-business platform that allows telecommunications providers to build their ecosystems. First, they applied the model to companies and assessed whether it was valid, functional, and effective. The overall conclusion of the evaluation showed that the model is a valuable collection of practices that enable decision-making regarding governance in SECO.

SMS-S24 conducted a case study on the Apache Hadoop OSSECO. SMS-S24 applied a proof of concept to demonstrate that the model is functional and practical. The Apache Hadoop OSSECO was chosen due to the high concentration of companies in the ecosystem and because it is the Apache project with the highest number of committers. The case study further helped to evolve and refine the model and its seven steps.

4.3.3 Discussion

The results presented in Section 4.3.2 provided some insights that will be discussed in this section. Initially, we discuss the results obtained with the RQ responses with the RE and SECO literature in other contexts. Next, we discuss how other RE activities influence or are influenced by requirements management in SECO. Finally, we discuss why the selected studies find requirements management challenging in SECO.

4.3.3.1 Characteristics and Approaches for Requirements Management in SECO

In Section 4.3.2, we identified nine characteristics of requirements management in SECO. Some of these characteristics relate to challenges and concepts emerging

from RE. C1 to C3 and C9 refer to the openness and informality of requirements management in SECO, among other aspects. According to SMS-S16, SECO are inherently open, to some extent, which influences requirements management activities. Openness in RE processes is also discussed in the context of open source software (OSS) projects, which can form OSSECO. Iyer and Lyytinen [201] pointed out that RE processes in OSS projects are less formal and reliant on online documentation and communication tools.

We noticed that the open innovation paradigm is explored in requirements management in SECO. In the literature, open innovation has been linked to both SECO and RE. Hanssen and Dybå [202] cited that the emergence of SECO relates to the inherent potential for open innovation. Linåker et al. [203] highlighted that RE needs to consider the implicit changes in open innovation and adapt to such a challenging context. Yin and Pfahl [204] cited that the application of open innovation strategies in RE is little investigated and that there is no support from proprietary tools for open innovation in RE.

Insight #15:

Open innovation has been linked to both SECO and RE, and RE needs to consider the implicit changes in open innovation and adapt to this new context.

We looked deeper at openness and open innovation in requirements management in SECO and identified their relationship to emerging concepts in RE. SMS-S20 and SMS-S22, for example, discussed the ubiquitous RE in the context of digital transformation involving the formation of SECO. SMS-S20 and SMS-S22 envisioned RE in multiple dimensions (i.e., RE everywhere, RE with everyone, RE for everything, automated RE, open RE, and cross-domain RE), resulting in the digital transformation of RE itself into ubiquitous RE. In these dimensions, SMS-S20, SMS-S22, and SMS-S26 highlighted the importance of the CrowdRE paradigm for requirements management in SECO. CrowdRE refers to an emerging paradigm that promotes the active involvement of a “*crowd*” of stakeholders, including current and potential software product users [84].

SMS-S26 mentioned that RE in SECO involves distinct crowds that includes different types of users, external developers, and the keystone. According to

SMS-S26, CrowdRE in SECO brings new opportunities and challenges for keystones and its partners. SMS-S22 highlighted that traditional requirements elicitation techniques, such as interviews or focus groups, present scalability problems in SECO. For SMS-S22, the CrowdRE paradigm addresses typical problems experienced in RE in SECO (i.e., involvement of multiple actors and the lack of scalability of RE) using global automation to perform with a crowd. According to SMS-S20, in heterogeneous and dispersed settings that include a crowd (such as SECO), allowing anyone to provide potential requirements can be more effective than involving only a selection of representative end users or applying personas. SMS-S20 stated that CrowdRE helps address RE challenges in a social context such as SECO.

Current works have investigated CrowdRE in different contexts. Abdullah et al. [205] presented research efforts and challenges in CrowdRE and concluded that researchers in CrowdRE continually explore the research area and propose new techniques and tools to improve it. Tizard et al. [42] stated that researchers found relevant information about requirements in feedback from multiple online communication channels, including app stores, social media, and product forums. For Wouters et al. [87], CrowdRE expands the reach of established RE approaches, which involve a selected sample of stakeholders, extending the notion of market-driven RE toward the democratic participation of users in RE. Gómez et al. [206] demonstrated that a SECO designed to leverage different types of crowds greatly benefits all actors in the ecosystem. The growing trend in CrowdRE research indicates that this field has more room to be improved and explored, including the context of SECO.

Insight #16:

CrowdRE can be explored in SECO because RE in ecosystems involves distinct crowds that include different types of users, external developers, and a keystone.

C4 to C8 highlight the existence of geographically distributed multi-party actors groups that influence requirements management in SECO. Geographical distribution has been studied in the context of the GSD. Ali and Lai [207] cited that organizations collaborate with software teams worldwide in GSD. GSD collaboration can be inter-organizational, intra-organizational, and of mixed nature

(inter+intra). The authors indicated a significant difference between the number of intra and inter-organizational collaborations due to management and communication processes, which often differ in inter-organizational setups. SMS-S21 identified one of the main differences between teams distributed in traditional organizations and SECO. In SECO, the teams or actors are not within the same company or organization but are spread across several organizations. Each actor contributes different elements to the system or product.

In SMS-RQ2, we identified approaches to support requirements management in SECO, and the most cited was “*tool*”. Several selected studies mentioned using “*issue trackers*” as a tool to support requirements management in SECO. CrowdRE explores the “*issue trackers*” as a source of feedback. Ali Khan et al. [208] proposed a CrowdRE framework. The framework can be applied in issue trackers to identify or respond to critical issues. Cleland-Huang [209] mentioned that the use of digital technologies as tools has brought about disruptive changes in all domains, widely known as “*digital transformation*”. For Cleland-Huang [209], disruptive change is a powerful force that explodes on the scene, introducing a new dominant solution or an unprecedented practice.

Regarding methods in SMS-RQ2, we identified that agile methods had been used to support requirements management in SECO. Cleland-Huang [209] highlighted that agility is just one example of a disruptive change that significantly impacts RE. Disruptive changes bring unprecedented opportunities for innovation. In addition, the author argued that the widespread adoption of agile methods across multiple project domains threatens many of the existing true practices associated with requirements management. However, for Cleland-Huang [209], there is an industrial tendency to move away from “*traditional*” requirements processes in the digital transformation scenario.

Jayatileke and Lai [28] differentiated requirements change management between traditional and agile software development. In addition, they cite challenges for these two contexts. In our work, we noticed that there are initiatives to use agile methods to help manage requirements in SECO despite the additional disruptions in new ways of software development and emerging contexts such as SECO. Hence, when discussing requirements management challenges in SECO, we related them to

some challenges identified by Jayatilleke and Lai [28]. For example, we highlighted the challenges related to requirements communication are different in SECO. We also noticed that the analysis of how organizations make decisions presented by Jayatilleke and Lai [28] focused on the context of a single organization. In the results of our work, we extended the analysis to a requirements management context that goes beyond the limits of organizational boundaries, as happens in SECO.

Santos and Werner [210] mentioned that SECO emerged to improve software reuse in the GSD industry, considering the relationships between companies and stakeholders worldwide. The authors also observed that the SECO vision has motivated the leading players in the sector to rethink their operational actions to open their platforms to external agents and keep their businesses alive. SMS-S29 pointed out that success no longer depends solely on keystone's efforts to manage user expectations of its offering. Instead, it works with a more complex set of business relationships within the SECO. The situation becomes even more complex when these relationships include collaboration between competitors, that is, a state of competition. SMS-S21 pointed out that in SECO, several types of relationships exist between actors, which can be competitors or share mutual benefits about requirements. The complexity of relationships and dependencies increases with the number of stakeholders in the ecosystem.

4.3.3.2 Requirements Engineering Activities Related to Requirements Management in SECO

Vegendla et al. [14] investigated RE activities in SECO and divided RE into five activities: requirements elicitation, requirements analysis, requirements specification, requirements validation, and requirements management. In our SMS, we characterize requirements management in SECO. We used the definition of ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148 [62], which considers requirements management an organized process of documentation, analysis, traceability, prioritization, change control, and communication of requirements. However, when answering our RQ, we noticed that other RE activities influence or are influenced by requirements management in SECO. Table 4.15 presents the citation frequency in the selected studies of other RE activities related to requirements management in SECO.

Table 4.15: RE activities in SECO related to requirements management in SECO.

RE activity	Selected Studies
Requirements elicitation	SMS-S1, SMS-S3, SMS-S4, SMS-S5, SMS-S7, SMS-S8, SMS-S9, SMS-S12, SMS-S13, SMS-S14, SMS-S15, SMS-S16, SMS-S17, SMS-S19, SMS-S20, SMS-S22, SMS-S24, SMS-S25, SMS-S26, SMS-S27, SMS-S28, SMS-S29
Requirements analysis	SMS-S1, SMS-S2, SMS-S5, SMS-S7, SMS-S9, SMS-S11, SMS-S12, SMS-S13, SMS-S14, SMS-S17, SMS-S20, SMS-S26, SMS-S27
Requirements specification	SMS-S1, SMS-S2, SMS-S6, SMS-S9, SMS-S12, SMS-S18, SMS-S19, SMS-S20, SMS-S24
Requirements validation	SMS-S12, SMS-S14, SMS-S17, SMS-S20

Requirements elicitation. SMS-S25 focused on one aspect of requirements management in SECO, identifying stakeholders as a preliminary step of requirements elicitation. SMS-S25 considered that the first step of requirements management is requirements elicitation, but it is imperative to know from whom the requirements should be elicited before that. According to Lim et al. [211], digital transformation has spawned new opportunities for requirements elicitation in different contexts. The authors highlighted that currently, requirements elicitation can consider an unprecedented and increasing amount of high-velocity and heterogeneous data. Vegendla et al. [14] highlighted that the platform’s openness in SECO allows everyone to provide the requirements without role identification.

According to Vegendla et al. [14], requirements elicitation involves identifying SECO members’ requirements according to their business goals and can be considered a challenging issue. Fricker et al. [212] mentioned that large organizations need to consider the interaction of several actors to define the requirements of their products and commercial platforms. However, conventional requirements elicitation techniques are not sufficiently scalable or capable of considering stakeholder groups that are becoming increasingly large and global [211, 213]. For SMS-S1 and SMS-S7, requirements elicitation requires new approaches that must provide mechanisms to capture the customer’s voice. We considered that the scalability that SECO requires in requirements elicitation approaches also affects requirements management, mainly concerning change control and traceability.

Insight #17:

The SECO platform openness allows everyone to provide the requirements without any role identification. In addition, new approaches must provide mechanisms to capture the voice of multiple actors in SECO, including those involved in the requirements change identification.

Requirements analysis. Our results showed that requirements management and analysis strongly relate to SECO. Vegendla et al. [14] cited that requirements analysis and management should be conducted in parallel to handle the conflicts and ambiguity in the requirements. However, SMS-S9 mentioned that companies participating in SECO perform requirements analysis differently. Alsanoosy et al. [214] mentioned the influence of culture on requirements analysis. For the authors, each culture relies on its context to interpret and understand information. Finally, Oriol et al. [162] stated that SECO health objectives are achieved as part of a requirements analysis and refinement process with the stakeholders.

We considered that requirements management and analysis must jointly and continually control changes and requirements status considering the open and dynamic environment of SECO. Nonetheless, SMS-S14 pointed out that the challenge of requirements analysis in SECO is the analysis of requirements with openness in mind. For the authors, from this broader perspective, requirements analysis should calculate the probability of completion if someone else in the ecosystem contributes to co-development or analyzes optimistic or pessimistic scenarios with or without other contributions within the same SECO.

Requirements specification. SMS-S24 pointed out that multi-party actors dispersed geographically collaboratively conduct the requirements specification at SECO. Vegendla et al. [14] cited several works on SECO modeling related to the requirement specification and highlighted the importance of GSD in SECO. In this scenario, SMS-S19 mentioned the difficulty of specifying requirements linked to different repositories of software artifacts within a global requirements management infrastructure in SECO. For Ali and Lai [215], social, linguistic, geographic, and cultural differences in GSD make it challenging to understand poorly written requirements specifications by introducing pauses and delays in communication. We considered that this is not different in the SECO context. However, we emphasized that SECO's open and inter-organizational environment makes this scenario even more difficult.

SMS-S18 mentioned the need to develop formal requirements specifications that consider the specificities of the ecosystem platform to assist in decision-making in SECO. Shahzad et al. [216] stated that it is necessary to consider the properties

of ecosystems, such as sustainability, contribution and incentives in requirements elicitation and specification. The authors justified that people usually have requirements for sociotechnical systems, and such a system consists of several different actors (e.g., other people and machines). In addition, according to the authors, most sociotechnical systems are operated for an extended period, and they should be improved and sometimes adapted to the current situation.

Requirements validation. SMS-S14 highlighted that informalism facilitates social interaction in requirements management in SECO and supports requirements validation. SMS-S20 mentioned that using crowdsourcing techniques that include crowd members was essential for collaborative and systematic requirements validation in SECO. Vegendla et al. [14] cited that there are few studies on requirements management and validation in SECO. Nevertheless, for the authors, without validation and management of the requirements, the consistency and completeness of the requirements and models and the changes in the requirements are not ensured. For Kamalrudin and Sidek [217], the requirements validation process in the context general of software development needs to consider consistency, completeness, and correctness for producing software specifications.

Cysneiros and Zisman [218] claimed that requirements traceability, an activity of requirements management, supports requirements validation in traditional software development. In turn, Vegendla et al. [14] stated that requirements traceability is a significant task to provide requirements changes in SECO. However, according to the authors, more research should be performed for requirements validation and traceability in SECO. Che and Perry [54] stated that SECO need efficient automated traceability between system drivers (such as requirements, business, and market needs) and architecture design decisions. Nonetheless, the authors also pointed out that extensive research is still required on architectural knowledge traceability to SECO.

4.3.3.3 Challenges of Requirements Management in SECO

During data extraction and synthesis to answer RQ1, we found that 16 of the 29 selected studies in our SMS (SMS-S2, SMS-S4, SMS-S5, SMS-S6, SMS-S7, SMS-S9, SMS-S14, SMS-S15, SMS-S17, SMS-S20, SMS-S21, SMS-S25, SMS-S26, SMS-27,

SMS-S28, SMS-S29) considered requirements management (or some related activity) a challenge in SECO. Thus, we realized that the main challenges pointed out by the selected studies are related to the characteristics of requirements management in SECO (Table 4.13). Table 4.16 presents the relationship between the identified challenges and the characteristics of requirements management in SECO. Table 4.17 illustrates some examples of coherent units we define to answer SMS-RQ1. The rest of the coherent units are available in the SMS-RQ1 complete coding process¹⁴ (details in Appendix 9.5). Then, we detailed and discussed the challenges.

Table 4.16: Relationship between challenges and characteristics of requirements management in SECO.

Challenge	Characteristic in Table 4.13	Selected Studies
Requirements communication	C8	SMS-S2, SMS-S4, SMS-S5, SMS-S6, SMS-S15, SMS-S20, SMS-S21, SMS-S26, SMS-S27
Requirements identification	C7	SMS-S5, SMS-S14, SMS-S25, SMS-S28
Multi-party actors	C4	SMS-S5, SMS-S17, SMS-S21
Openness	C1	SMS-S14, SMS-S17, SMS-S29
Requirements negotiation	C6	SMS-S5, SMS-S7, SMS-S9
Emergent requirements	C2	SMS-S17, SMS-S29

Table 4.17: Illustration of the process for defining challenges of requirements management in SECO.

Challenge related to C7 (Table 4.13)	
Challenge:	Requirements identification in SECO
Coherent units:	<p>SMS-S5: “SECO approach impacts on the traditional SE models and brings new challenges to RE. By putting together multiple and dispersed actors, SECO approach hampers requirements elicitation.”</p> <p>SMS-S25: “The number of stakeholders may become too large to manage completely. This presents challenges in the case of requirement elicitation.”</p>
Challenge related to C8 (Table 4.13)	
Challenge:	Requirements communication in SECO
Coherent units:	<p>SMS-S2: “Requirements communication is challenging, in particular when people and organizations need to collaborate over dispersed locations.”</p> <p>SMS-S6: “Requirements communication and management in SECOs is a challenge, especially in the distributed software development scenario.”</p> <p>SMS-S26: “We describe open challenges for SECOs in the context of CrowdRE. New communication mechanisms are needed that scale with the crowd.”</p>

SMS-S5 mentioned that the SECO approach brings new challenges to RE. SMS-S6 stated that **requirements communication** and management in SECO are challenging. For SMS-S2, SMS-S5, SMS-S6, and SMS-S20, requirements communication is challenging, especially when multiple actors must collaborate in dispersed locations in the GSD scenario. In the GSD context, Qureshi et al. [219] mentioned several challenges related to requirements communication as “*inadequate use of informal communication*” and “*inadequate transfer of information*”. Several

¹⁴<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8131745>

works consider the requirements communication between stakeholders in distributed geographic locations as a challenge [28, 220, 221, 222]. In addition, SMS-S4 pointed out that requirements need to be communicated and understood by all relevant stakeholders in SECO and identified this as a challenge. SMS-S15 reported that there are challenges in establishing centralized requirements communication in SECO. For SMS-S21, SMS-S26, and SMS-S27, requirements communication in SECO is challenging due to multiple communication channels.

Insight #18:

Requirements communication in SECO is challenging due to multiple communication channels.

SMS-S14 cited challenging aspects that open innovation brings to **requirements identification** in SECO. For SMS-S5, SMS-S25, and SMS-S28, the number of SECO stakeholders may become too large, which presents a challenge for requirements identification. Lim et al. [211] highlighted that conventional elicitation techniques are often time-consuming and not sufficiently scalable for considering stakeholder groups that are becoming increasingly large and global. For Lim et al. [211], CrowdRE is an excellent example of dealing with this challenge. The authors cite that the primary focus of CrowdRE is the requirements identification from explicit crowd users' feedback (e.g., app reviews and data from social media) by applying several techniques based on machine learning and natural language processing.

Insight #19:

CrowdRE is an excellent example of dealing with the number of SECO stakeholders that may become too large.

SMS-S5 cited that the existence of **multi-party actors** introduces challenges to requirement management in SECO. SMS-S17 pointed out that connecting the right actors to clarify requirements in SECO is difficult. SMS-S21 mentioned that the coordination between multi-party actors has already been identified as a significant challenge in agile and large-scale distributed teams. However, for SMS-S21, this challenge cannot be taken similarly in SECO because each actor has a way of working that can hardly be standardized. This results in several different practices being applied across the ecosystem. In addition, SMS-S21 highlighted that it is

necessary to consider that the actors in SECO do not belong to a single organization but to many organizations that share different, possibly competing relationships (coopetition). Roth et al. [223] explored open coopetition, i.e., open innovation cooperation between competitors that includes third parties such as networks, platforms, communities, ecosystems, or triple helices. The authors suggested using open innovation management principles to deal with open coopetition.

SMS-S14, SMS-S17, and SMS-S29 mentioned that **openness** brings RE-related challenges in SECO. SMS-S14 cited the challenge of analyzing requirements with openness in mind. For SMS-S14, in an open perspective, the requirements analysis should calculate the probability of completion of the implementation of the requirements if someone from the ecosystem contributes in co-development or analyzes optimistic or pessimistic scenarios with or without other contributions in the ecosystem. SMS-S17 pointed out that openness brings RE-related challenges in SECO, such as managing dynamic and emerging contributions from stakeholders and collecting their input while protecting their intellectual property. Zaggl et al. [224] ensured that finding the right degree of openness is challenging, especially in complex open innovation ecosystems. For the authors, being too open involves the risk of imitation and slippage of values, and users can gain a lot of influence on corporate decisions, leading to the challenge of requirements negotiation.

SMS-S5 pointed out that the SECO approach makes **requirements negotiation** difficult. SMS-S7 considered that the requirements negotiation in SECO is a relevant challenge for the social dimension of an ecosystem and states that it directly affects the success of a SECO. For SMS-S9, interacting with multiple partners in a SECO introduces challenges to requirements negotiation. Abdullahi et al. [222] cited the need for SECO actors to reach agreements effectively through requirements negotiation. However, for the authors, there is little understanding of how stakeholders make decisions in RE. Abdullahi et al. [222] also stated that decision making is the most challenging and difficult task in requirements negotiation in SECO. According to the authors, when making a decision, several challenges need attention before starting the negotiation. The authors cited some of them as the interaction between multiple actors in a SECO and the existence of incompatible objectives of these actors that require careful negotiation to avoid further conflicts.

SMS-S17 and SMS-S29 mentioned that managing **emergent requirements** in SECO is challenging. For SMS-S17, it is difficult to map emergent requirements to specific actors in SECO. Ailane et al. [225] cited challenges regarding emergent requirements and proposed a new attempt to define the emergence phenomenon from a SE perspective. According to the authors, the emergence phenomenon is an important phenomenon that is difficult to formalize and standardize in complex systems (such as SECO).

4.3.4 Research Agenda

Motivated by the results of this SMS, we suggest a research agenda inspired by the work of Santos et al. [226] and Santos and Carvalho [227], where some issues raised during the SMS can be investigated in the future:

1. How can CrowdRE, open innovation, and ubiquitous RE support requirements management in SECO?
2. How can the different requirements (product, platform, and integration) be managed for different types of SECO (OSSECO, PSECO, and hybrid SECO)?
3. Are the requirements management approaches identified in this SMS sufficient to support the problems and specificities of different types of SECO (OSSECO, PSECO, and hybrid SECO)? How to assess or adapt them?
4. How to carry out requirements traceability in SECO considering the characteristics of requirements management in this context?
5. How to monitor emergent requirements flows in SECO and manage such requirements in conjunction with other requirements?
6. How to manage requirements change in SECO considering the changes requested in multiple open communication channels by multi-party actors?

4.4 Threats to Validity

This section presents potential threats to the validity of the tertiary study and SMS, as well as our actions to mitigate them. The discussion builds on the guidelines for

addressing threats to the validity of secondary studies provided by Ampatzoglou et al. [228]. These threats are classified as study, data, and research validity.

4.4.1 Study Validity

Threats in this category are related to the study selection process and may lead to the omission of relevant studies or the inclusion of irrelevant studies. This potential threat includes (i) limitations in search strategy; (ii) ineffective search strings; and (iii) bias in the selection of studies that were selected in the tertiary study or SMS.

To mitigate (i) in the tertiary study and SMS, we applied a database search in seven digital libraries, including Scopus, which indexes works from several other digital libraries. Moreover, we applied a full-fledged hybrid search strategy (DBS + snowballing via BS and FS) in our SMS. Mourão et al. [175] mentioned that hybrid search strategies are efficient compared to the simple DBS strategy. According to Wohlin et al. [176], a full-fledged hybrid search strategy is better than other alternative hybrid strategies. To mitigate (ii) in the tertiary study and SMS, we used terms present in secondary and tertiary studies on SECO for the tertiary study and SECO and RE for the SMS highly cited in the SE literature. Moreover, we also used two control studies to evaluate the quality and comprehensiveness of our search string in the SMS. To mitigate (iii) in the tertiary study and SMS, we engaged in multiple discussions to resolve disagreements and clarify possible ambiguities. This approach aimed at ensuring as precise and unbiased an interpretation as possible within the constraints of the available information.

In this category, we emphasize the limitation regarding the generalization of the results. We know it is impossible to generalize the results by considering only studies published in academic databases. We did not consider all possible solutions created by the industry and possibly published in the grey literature (technical reports, white papers, web blog postings etc.).

4.4.2 Data Validity

The data extraction and synthesis process can threaten the data's validity, as it could lead to dubious results and conclusions. This potential threat includes (i) unverified data extraction; and (ii) researcher bias. To mitigate (i), we documented

all data transformations so that it is possible to trace the synthesis back to the corresponding selected secondary study. Concerning (ii), we performed a joint data analysis and, finally, condensed them. Two researchers experienced in conducting secondary studies in SE verified the result.

4.4.3 Search Validity

The lack of auditing and difficulty replicating the research threatens its validity. These threats are related to (i) lack of documentation on study planning; and (ii) lack of justification for changes made during the conduct of the study. To mitigate (i) and (ii), we defined a detailed protocol based on well-established guidelines of Kitchenham and Charters [125]. Finally, we analyzed, justified, and documented all necessary changes that occurred during the conduct of this study.

4.5 Final Remarks

This chapter presented the current state of research on SECO and its practice more broadly than possible with secondary studies through a tertiary study. In this tertiary study, we proposed a thematic map of the research topics on SECO. Moreover, we identified the need to investigate further research topics on SECO, such as RE, open innovation, and social aspects.

This chapter also presented the state of the art requirements management in SECO through an SMS. In this SMS, we defined characteristics of requirements management in SECO that differentiate it from requirements management in other software development and elaborated a research agenda for this field. We identified that: (i) there are still open questions about requirements change in SECO; (ii) the open innovation paradigm is explored in requirements management in SECO, and it positively impacts requirements change management; (iii) requirements management in SECO involves distinct crowds that include different types of users, external developers, and the keystone; and (iv) CrowdRE can help address requirements management challenges in SECO. Our conclusion from this chapter is that requirements management deserves recognition as a distinct SECO research field. In the following chapter, we intend to investigate requirements management characteristics in SECO from a practical perspective.

Chapter 5. State of the Practice on Requirements Management in Software Ecosystems

5.1 Introduction

This chapter provides an overview of the state of practice of requirements management in SECO. We conducted three field studies to understand requirements management practices in SECO better. A field study seeks to investigate how practitioners deal with their activities in practice and understand how they solve problems in their respective contexts [107]. According to Singer et al. [107], a field study may use different techniques for data collection, including questionnaires and interviews. Thus, we applied questionnaires and performed semi-structured interviews based on recommendations for field studies [107] with professionals involved in requirements management activities in SECO.

The first field study aimed to investigate the stakeholders' perceptions of requirements management in a specific SECO. The second field study aimed to investigate the use of open innovation practices to support requirements management in SECO. The third field study aimed to investigate whether and how user feedback from a crowd is considered in requirements management in SECO.

This chapter is organized as follows: Section 5.2 describes the first field study; Section 5.3 describes the second field study; Section 5.4 describes the third field study; Section 5.5 lists the threats to credibility and reliability; and the final remarks are described in Section 5.6.

5.2 Investigating Requirements Management in the SOLAR Software Ecosystem

Online Learning System (SOLAR) is a SECO based on a VLE designed to enable the creation of a virtual space to support face-to-face or online courses [229]. SOLAR SECO enables the publication of courses and interaction with them among its several users, and it consists of modules based on free software with an architecture that can be integrated with other environments [230]. According to Coutinho and Bezerra [230], requirements change impact SOLAR SECO and would have a beneficial effect on the development environment if they were modeled, documented, and analyzed for the impact of their implementation in different contexts. Therefore, we aimed to obtain the stakeholders' perceptions of requirements management in SOLAR SECO. To achieve this goal, we conducted a field study based on semi-structured interviews with one professional involved in requirements management activities in the SOLAR SECO and an experienced SOLAR SECO user. We detail the process of this field study next.

5.2.1 Planning

In the planning phase of this field study, we defined a protocol that details RQ, the semi-structured interview, the characterization of participants, and the coding process.

5.2.1.1 Research Question

The RQ for this field study aimed to obtain information about stakeholders' perceptions of SOLAR SECO requirements management. The RQ of the first field study was: *(FS1-RQ) What are the stakeholders' perceptions of requirements management in the SOLAR SECO?*

5.2.1.2 Semi-Structured Interview

We initially developed an interview guide¹ with interview planning (details in Appendix 9.5). The interview questions focused on topics related to requirements

¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13340212>

management activities. Although we approached the questions differently with the two interviewees, we explored the same topics. Moreover, we asked additional questions about specific aspects of requirements management for the professional interviewed.

We conducted the online interviews between July and August 2021. We did not define the maximum time for interviews, so their duration varied according to the interviewee's availability and exhaustion of possible answers. We used Google Meet² to record the interviews and Google Docs³ to transcribe them. We divided the interviews into three parts:

- **Characterization of the participants:** We collected information about academic background and experience in SOLAR SECO;
- **Presentation of the concepts used in the interview:** We presented the definitions of SECO and requirements management to ensure clarity and avoid any confusion or ambiguity about the meaning of each term;
- **Questions about requirements management activities in the SOLAR SECO:** We asked participants about requirements change identification, requirements change communication, requirements change prioritization, requirements change negotiation, requirements change control, requirements traceability, and requirements management challenges. Moreover, we asked additional questions about specific aspects of requirements management for the professional interviewed.

5.2.1.3 Characterization of Participants

We defined the target audience as SOLAR SECO requirements managers (or similar roles) and users. The keystone manager indicated two potential interviewees. Interviewee 1 is the development team coordinator with over six years of experience in the SOLAR SECO development. Interviewee 1 is responsible for receiving customer product and service demands in SOLAR SECO. Interviewee 2 is an experienced SOLAR SECO user with more than 10 years of use of the ecosystem

²<https://meet.google.com/>

³<https://docs.google.com>

platform. The choice of interviewing an experienced user was grounded on the fact that users are the main consumers of SOLAR SECO products and services and are often responsible for requesting change or new requirements.

5.2.1.4 Coding Process

We used the Card Sorting method presented by Spencer [231] to support the analysis and transcription of the data obtained from the interviews. We read the interview transcripts, marked relevant text excerpts, and divided them into coherent units (sentences or paragraphs).

5.2.2 Results

We identified stakeholders' perceptions of several activities related to requirements management in the SOLAR SECO. We detail our results next.

5.2.2.1 Requirements Change Identification in SOLAR SECO

Regarding requirements change identification in SOLAR SECO from the development team coordinator's perspective, we identified that requirements changes arise from multiple SECO actors, e.g., keystone, partners (external developers), and users. The development team coordinator mentioned that: *“the sources of requirements come from management who may pick up requirements from other departments in the university, through external partnerships, by faculty, by other users (students) and by the developers themselves who suggest new requirements, so several actors are involved”*.

Regarding requirements change identification in SOLAR SECO from the experienced user's perspective, we identified that the keystone offers different ways for users to submit requirements change in SECO. The experienced user cited that: *“usually, the SOLAR maintainers publish a questionnaire to get the user's perceptions of a feature or evaluate the interface. In addition, I use email to communicate with the team and send demands. These means of evaluating SOLAR have contributed a lot to improving the environment”*.

Insight #20:

In SOLAR SECO, requirements change identification is a collaborative and decentralized process involving multiple actors, including internal managers, external partners, users, and the development team itself.

5.2.2.2 Requirements Communication in SOLAR SECO

Regarding requirements communication in SOLAR SECO from the development team coordinator's perspective, we identified that email and questionnaires are the main communication channels used in the SECO. However, there is no central repository to store the requirements. The development team uses spreadsheets, project management tools, and bug tracker tools to store change requirements and requirements. The development team coordinator mentioned that: *“requirements changes usually arrive by email, but the requirements are not stored in a central platform. They are all organized in worksheets that are automatically generated through the forms received from the users. We used Pivotal Tracker and Trello tools to store new and old requirements”*.

Regarding requirements communication in SOLAR SECO from the experienced user's perspective, we also identified email and questionnaires as communication channels in the SECO. The experienced SOLAR SECO user described that these communication channels are sufficient but suggested the inclusion of a chatbot to make communication more automated. The experienced user cited that: *“usually, the SOLAR maintainers publish a questionnaire to get the user's perceptions of a feature or evaluate the interface. In addition, I use email to communicate with the team and send demands. These means of evaluating SOLAR have contributed a lot to improving the environment. I consider that the communication channels are sufficient, as I have direct contact with those responsible for the SOLAR SECO development team. However, those who do not have this direct contact may find it difficult to inform their demands. A chatbot could make communication more automated”*.

Insight #21:

In SOLAR SECO, requirements communication relies on specific communication channels with no centralized repository. This fact reflects a decentralized approach to requirements storage and management.

5.2.2.3 Requirements Prioritization in SOLAR SECO

Regarding requirements prioritization in SOLAR SECO from the development team coordinator's perspective, we identified that the SOLAR SECO development team does not apply any specific approach to this activity. However, they use urgency and deadline factors that affect decision-making in requirements prioritization. The development team coordinator mentioned that: *"the requirements prioritization considers the urgency of the demand. The requirement is prioritized if the demand can cause the platform to stop working. Another factor that is considered is deadlines. If a department requests a feature and defines a deadline, these requirements are prioritized automatically"*.

Regarding requirements prioritization in SOLAR SECO from the experienced user's perspective, we identified that users usually do not know the priority of their demands. The experienced user cited that: *"I don't know how my demands are prioritized"*.

5.2.2.4 Requirements Negotiation in SOLAR SECO

Regarding requirements negotiation in SOLAR SECO from the development team coordinator's perspective, we identified that it occurs in the requirements change analysis. After receiving demands, the platform development team communicates with the users to negotiate the requirements. The development team coordinator mentioned that: *"Requirements negotiation occurs after their identification. We talk with users or other actors. We interview to find out what this stakeholder specifically wants in their demand. We document all definitions"*.

Regarding requirements negotiation in SOLAR SECO from the experienced user's perspective, we identified that the users are involved in this negotiation. The experienced user cited that: *"the development team usually contacts me to negotiate my demands"*.

5.2.2.5 Requirements Traceability in SOLAR SECO

Regarding requirements traceability in SOLAR SECO from the development team coordinator's perspective, we identified that no specific approach is used to perform requirements traceability. The development team coordinator mentioned that: "*The team does not use a technique for requirements traceability. The closest to requirements traceability is to follow which communication channel requirements came from and who was the actor who requested the demand*".

Regarding requirements traceability in SOLAR SECO from the experienced user's perspective, we identified that users cannot track the status of their request. The experienced user cited that: "*It is impossible to track my demands' status. Sometimes I ask the team directly about the status*".

5.2.2.6 Requirements Management Challenges in SOLAR SECO

Regarding requirements management challenges in SOLAR SECO from the development team coordinator's perspective, requirements change prioritization and communication are challenging. The development team coordinator mentioned that: "*the requirements management difficulties in SOLAR are related to requirements prioritization and impact analysis of requirements changes. For this, it is necessary to consider what is being done and what should be done next. Requirements communication with the end-users also is one challenge*".

Regarding requirements management challenges in SOLAR SECO from the experienced user's perspective, the feedback on implementing demands by the development team is challenging. The experienced user cited that: "*As a user, a communication channel to receive feedback on the requested demands would be a way to improve and have more effective communication between the SOLAR team and the user*".

5.2.2.7 Specific Aspects of Requirements Management in SOLAR SECO

Regarding specific aspects of requirements management in SOLAR SECO from the development team coordinator's perspective, we identified that the SOLAR SECO team uses "*generic*" requirements management practices and has a team member with experience in requirements management for managing all requirements

throughout the platform development. The development team coordinator stated that: *“No specific technique is used for requirements management. A specific person with experience in requirements management is responsible for filtering and managing the requirements”*.

Insight #22:

In SOLAR SECO, requirements management activities present several challenges and lack systematic approaches to requirements prioritization, negotiation, and traceability.

5.2.3 Discussion

The results obtained in this field study pointed out that the SOLAR SECO does not have a formal requirements management process. However, this activity is carried out by a specific SECO actor (development team coordinator) and has the participation of other actors (managers and users). Knauss et al. [18] stated that requirements management in SECO usually is informal, has overlapping practices, and uses informalisms [199] in SECO. Regarding requirements change identification in SOLAR SECO, the development team coordinator pointed out that the demands of requirements change arise through requests from actors who belong to the organization that manages SOLAR (students, professors, and technicians) and through external partnerships that suggest requirements change. Vegendla et al. [14] identified that requirements arise from multiple actors that may belong to different companies in the open innovation context in SECO.

Insight #23:

Multi-party actors - including external actors (partners) in the open innovation context in SECO - can request requirements changes.

In the SOLAR SECO, closed communication channels (email and questionnaire) are a principal means to identify and communicate requirements. The interviewed experienced SOLAR SECO user highlighted that these communication channels are sufficient to share demands. However, Knauss et al. [18] emphasized that open communication channels facilitate the flow of information among users,

customers, and internal and external developers in SECO. These channels allow for transparent communication among stakeholders. For Knauss et al. [18], requirements communication in SECO requires a high level of transparency to meet the challenge of achieving a good representation of a large and heterogeneous set of stakeholders.

Although there is a defined number of communication channels for identifying requirements in SOLAR SECO, requirements can be found in different repositories, as stated by the development team coordinator. Vegendla et al. [14] identified that requirements usually are stored in several repositories decentralized in SECO. Regarding the challenges in requirements management in SOLAR SECO, requirements prioritization and communication are challenging from the development team coordinator's perception. In the experienced user's perception, the biggest challenge is the need for more communication to follow up and receive feedback on the status of the requests sent to the development team. Soltani and Knauss [191] corroborate the interviewees and highlight the challenge of communication in requirements management in the general SECO context.

Insight #24:

Requirements are usually stored in several decentralized repositories in SECO

This first field study investigated requirements management in a specific SECO. As a result, we identified the influence of external actors on requirements management activities in SECO. This result corroborates one of the open questions of the research agenda defined in our SMS, which is related to the use of open innovation practices in requirements management in SECO, such as collaboration and co-creation. This result (from both our SMS and first field study) motivated our second field study, as detailed next.

5.3 Investigating Open Innovation Practices to Support Requirements Management in Software Ecosystems

Professionals involved in requirements management activities in SECO have resorted to several open innovation practices such as co-creation, collaboration,

and crowdsourcing [179]. Several works have addressed the relationship between open innovation and SECO and RE [39, 179, 203, 232]. However, none identified which practices have been used to support requirements management in SECO. Implementing external requirements helps continuously to create more value for products and services in SECO [39]. Therefore, we aimed to investigate the use of open innovation practices to support requirements management in SECO. To achieve this goal, we conducted a field study based on semi-structured interviews with 21 professionals involved in related activities in SECO. We detail the field study process next.

5.3.1 Planning

In the planning step, we defined the RQ of the field study and presented the procedures for conducting the semi-structured interviews, the characterization of participants, and the coding process.

5.3.1.1 Research Question

The RQ for this field study aimed to obtain information about participants' experiences, opinions, and perspectives on how they receive/provide requirements or requirements change from/to external actors in SECO and how they manage these requirements in an open innovation context. The RQ of the second field study was: *(FS2-RQ) How do open innovation practices influence requirements management in SECO?*

5.3.1.2 Semi-Structured Interviews

We initially developed an interview guide⁴ with interview planning (details in Appendix 9.5). Afterward, we conducted a pilot interview with one professional involved in requirements management activities in SECO. The pilot checked the questions' clarity and understanding and the estimated time to complete the interview. The pilot participant encouraged us to add the definition of each open innovation practice presented to clarify possible doubts of the interviewees. We point out that we do not use pilot data in our analysis.

⁴<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038855>

We conducted 21 interviews between July and August 2023 with professionals involved in requirements management activities in SECO. Each interview lasted between 35 and 55 minutes. We used Google Meet to record the interviews and Google Docs to transcribe them. We transcribed the interviews iteratively, and the researcher coded the interviews, always watching the original video during the coding process even though we automatically transcribed each recording. Hence, we ensured the best and most accurate interpretation possible of each interview. We also fixed errors in the transcripts generated automatically during the coding process. We divided the interviews into three parts:

- **Characterization of the participants:** We collected information about academic background and experience in industry;
- **Presentation of the concepts used in the interview:** We presented the definitions of SECO, requirements management, and open innovation to ensure clarity and avoid any confusion or ambiguity about the meaning of each term;
- **Questions about open innovation practices to support requirements management in SECO:** We asked participants about their familiarity with open innovation, whether they receive/provide requirements or requirements change from/to external actors, and how this happens. Finally, we asked what open innovation practices they use to support requirements management in SECO. In this last question, we used the strategy adopted by Greiler et al. [233]. Such strategy consists of initially obtaining answers without presenting any examples of open innovation practices (unguided impressions) and so obtaining them after presenting a set of open innovation practices identified in our related work (guided impressions). This set of open innovation practices encourages deeper discussion as well as encourages participants to consider practices not immediately remembered.

We adopted the concept of “saturation” to establish the number of interviews required in our study. A study reaches saturation when conducting a new set of interviews does not produce new emerging data [234]. According to Guest et al. [235], saturation can usually be obtained with at least 12 interviews. In our study, we interviewed 21 professionals. We reached saturation with 18 interviews, in line with

the work of Guest et al. [235]. In each interview, we observed whether participants repeated the topics discussed earlier. Interview recordings and transcriptions were continually revisited in an iterative process. As no new codes or insights emerged in three consecutive interviews, we realized our codes and insights were fully saturated and stopped recruiting new participants.

5.3.1.3 Characterization of Participants

We used convenience sampling to select participants for our study based on their being nearby and available [236]. However, we looked for diverse participants in terms of experience and contacted professionals involved in requirements management activities in SECO from our network by email and other communication channels (WhatsApp and LinkedIn). We also used snowball sampling, where early participants referred other professionals to participate in the study. In addition, we applied a questionnaire with the consent form and some questions about the characterization of the participants⁵ (details in Appendix 9.5). All participants have experience in requirements management, SECO, and open innovation. This helps ensure that the selected sample is representative and relevant to the research goals. We assigned each participant a unique identifier (FS2-P1 to FS2-P21). Table 5.1 summarizes the information about the interview participants.

Six (28.6%) of the 21 participants have between 2 and 5 years of experience in requirements management, eight (38.1%) have between 6 and 10 years, and seven (33.3%) have more than 10 years of experience. Some participants answered “*No*” or “*I don’t know*” to questions about their engagement in SECO and participation in projects using open innovation. However, they confirmed involvement in these scenarios when we presented the concepts during the interviews.

5.3.1.4 Coding Process

To analyze the interviews, we initially performed an open coding approach inspired by the initial procedure of the GT [115]. During the open coding process, we divided the transcripts into coherent units (sentences or paragraphs) and added **preliminary codes** representing the key points each participant talked about.

⁵<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038855>

Table 5.1: Characterization of participants.

ID*	Academic background in computer science	Experience in requirements management	Engagement in SECO	Participation in projects that use open innovation
FS2-P1	Master's degree	15 years	Yes	Yes
FS2-P2	PhD	25 years	Yes	No**
FS2-P3	Specialization	10 years	No**	No**
FS2-P4	Specialization	10 years	Yes	Yes
FS2-P5	Specialization	3 years	I don't know**	I don't know**
FS2-P6	Master's degree	7 years	Yes	Yes
FS2-P7	Specialization	6 years	Yes	Yes
FS2-P8	PhD	9 years	Yes	Yes
FS2-P9	Specialization	10 years	Yes	No**
FS2-P10	Master's degree	12 years	Yes	Yes
FS2-P11	PhD	5 years	Yes	No**
FS2-P12	Master's degree	15 years	Yes	Yes
FS2-P13	Master's degree	8 years	Yes	No**
FS2-P14	Master's degree	5 years	Yes	Yes
FS2-P15	PhD	30 years	Yes	Yes
FS2-P16	Specialization	13 years	Yes	Yes
FS2-P17	PhD	2 years	Yes	Yes
FS2-P18	PhD	2 years	Yes	Yes
FS2-P19	Bachelor's degree	10 years	No**	No**
FS2-P20	PhD	3 years	Yes	No**
FS2-P21	Master's degree	15 years	Yes	Yes

*Field Study 2 - Participant [i], e.g., FS2-P1.

**Participants changed their answers to “Yes” at the beginning of the interview.

Subsequently, we defined a set of **focused codes** that captured the most frequent and relevant factors in the participants' perceptions. After performing open coding, we used axial coding described by Charmaz [116] to group the codes into **categories**. In these steps, we used the Atlas.TI tool⁶ as support to create the codes and categories. Table 5.2 shows the example of the coding process for one transcript with resulting codes and categories.

Table 5.2: Illustration of the coding process to second field study.

Example			
Coherent unit: “We have a collaborative flow in which cooperated members carry out this open innovation. They develop and ship the code to us. We can embed it in our code, but first, we understand, document, and specify that code.” (P11)			
Preliminary code	Focused code	Category	Core category
<i>We have a collaborative flow in which cooperated members</i>	Collaboration	Coupled	Open innovation practice

⁶<https://www.atlasti.com>

5.3.2 Results

We identified that most participants are familiar with open innovation, although some of them did not know it by such terminology. Moreover, participants use multiple communication channels to receive/provide requirements or requirements change and several open innovation practices to support activities related to requirements management in SECO. We detail our results next.

5.3.2.1 Communication Channels in Requirements Management in SECO

We initially asked professionals about their familiarity with the open innovation concept. This question aimed “*to break the ice*” and verify the participants’ perceptions about the subject. All participants rated their familiarity with the open innovation on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 meant less familiar and 5 meant more familiar. One participant considered himself/herself in level 1, four in level 2, eight in level 3, three in level 4, and six in level 5. We identified several participants were unfamiliar with the term “open innovation”. However, after we explained the concept at the beginning of the interviews, these participants reported they had already participated in projects that used open innovation. FS2-P13 highlighted: “*After your presentation, I realized I am quite familiar with the subject. I did not know it by that name, but I realized that we have this context of innovation in the ecosystem in which I participate*”.

We also asked participants if they usually receive/provide requirements from/to external actors to the projects they have been involved in SECO. If yes, we asked how they received/provided them. In response, 20 of the 21 participants stated that they received/provided requirements or requirements change from/to external actors. Only one participant claimed never to have provided/received requirements or requirements change from/to external actors. However, this participant mentioned during the interview that they use a tool provided by keystone to clarify doubts, report bugs, interact with SECO members from other organizations, and send suggestions for improvements.

Regarding how the participants receive/provide requirements or requirements change from/to external actors, we identified 14 communication channels. Communication channels are mainly used to improve and maintain a project’s

presence in a SECO and ensure that projects share knowledge at the ecosystem level with several contributors distributed geographically that possess different interests [237]. Moreover, communication channels help enhance open innovation practices, connecting key stakeholders, such as customers, suppliers, or business partners, and collaborating in the development of new products and services [238]. We classify these communication channels into three categories: (i) open online communication channels; (ii) closed online communication channels; and (iii) face-to-face communication channels. We also added the number of participants who cited each code. Table 5.3 presents the codes and categories resulting from our analysis.

Table 5.3: Communication channels to receive/provide requirements or requirements change from/to external actors in SECO.

Open online	Closed online	Face-to-face
App store (2)	Emails (7)	Face-to-face meetings (6)
Forums (6)	Feedback systems (5)	Hackathons (1)
Issue/bug trackers (1)	Forms (3)	Product demonstrations (3)
Software repositories (1)	Help desks (3)	Technical visits (1)
	Instant messaging apps (3)	

Open online communication channels facilitate information flows between the multiple actors in SECO [18]. The open communication paradigm in SECO provides opportunities for ‘just-in-time’ RE [239]. Participants cited the use of forums, app stores, issue/bug trackers, and software repositories to receive/provide requirements or requirements change from/to external actors in SECO. Forums, such as Stack Overflow⁷, were mostly mentioned by the participants. FS2-P8 highlighted: “*We are looking at the Stack Overflow and are mapping if there are any requirements around a tool, a product, or a software that we will need to change*”. According to Ververs et al. [240], to fully understand how a SECO works, the community needs to be studied as well, and this can be done by looking at issue/bug trackers and forums.

Closed online communication channels enable fast responses and can speed up decision making [241]. Participants also cited emails, forms, remote meetings, instant messaging apps, feedback systems, and help desks as channels to receive/provide requirements or requirements change from/ to external actors in SECO. Some participants highlighted the use of multiple closed online

⁷<https://stackoverflow.com/>

communication channels. FS3-P5 reported: “*For those who were not users of the tool, they contacted us in various ways, official letter, email, and even WhatsApp in an informal way*”. According to Johnson et al. [16], helpful information could be obtained through analysis of these multiple channels in SECO, both by the platform provider and the partner apps in their innovation processes.

Face-to-face communication channels are stimulus rich, i.e., enable the use of senses (auditory, visual, tactile, olfactory, and gustatory) in verbal and nonverbal activities [242]. Participants mentioned face-to-face meetings, product demonstrations at conferences or for other organizations, technical visits, and hackathons to receive/provide requirements or requirements change from/to external actors in SECO. Some participants conducted hackathons to identify requirements from external actors in SECO. FS3-P8 shared: “*We run hackathons to obtain requirements that may be important for new products or products already on the organization’s roadmap*”. According to Valença et al. [145], a hackathon can be seen as a strategy to support SECO evolution, enabling a company to gather new developers for its ecosystem, assess the software platform by identifying bugs, and verify to what extent the requirements for applications are fulfilled.

Insight #25:

In SECO, multi-party actors use several communication channels to request requirements change, contributing to a more open and decentralized requirements management.

5.3.2.2 Open Innovation Practices to Support Requirements Management in SECO

Our main goal was to identify open innovation practices to support requirements management in SECO through interviewing professionals. As described in Section 5.3.1.3, we iteratively coded their responses to the question: “*What open innovation practices have you used to support requirements management activities in software ecosystems?*” and grouped them into categories. Thus, we identified ten open innovation practices that support requirements management in SECO (Table 5.4). We identified eight open innovation practices in the unguided impressions, i.e., at least one participant mentioned the open innovation practice before we presented

the set of open innovation practices. Only two open innovation practices (open source and coopetition) were mentioned exclusively in the guided impressions.

We categorize open innovation practices according to open innovation processes (inbound, outbound, and coupled) [243]. Inbound open innovation seeks knowledge from external sources (e.g., suppliers, customers, competitors, and partners). Outbound open innovation explores internal knowledge externally. Coupled open innovation is a process where knowledge can flow inbound and outbound through active collaboration with partners to innovate. Table 5.4 shows the ten open innovation practices used to support requirements management in SECO, their categories, and the total number of participants that cited them. Next, we detail the open innovation practices identified in the study.

Table 5.4: open innovation practices to support requirements management in SECO.

Outbound	Inbound	Coupled
Open source (6)	Crowdsourcing (7)	Collaboration (17)
Venturing (1)	Hackathon (8)	Co-creation (6)
	University research grants (2)	Coopetition (3)
	Customer immersion (2)	
	Outsourcing R&D (2)	

Customer immersion is a collaborative innovation practice that focuses on the customer’s experience of using products or services [243]. Participants highlighted intense interaction with customers at events or agile ceremonies to identify requirements or requirements change. According to Gassmann [244], customer involvement is the principal constituent of open innovation. FS2-P18 mentioned: *“For more important customers, they sent invitations to events where they would expose the platform or software and received feedback them”*.

Hackathons are events with an element of competition, where participants work in teams over a short period to ideate, collaborate, design, rapidly prototype, test, iterate, and pitch their solutions to a determined challenge [245]. Some participants stated that hackathons are open innovation practices that support requirements management in SECO. These participants mentioned that they carry out or participate in hackathons to identify ideas, emerge and define requirements, create synergy between partners, and train different SECO actors. Hackathon is one key practice to enable open innovation [245]. FS2-P6 mentioned: *“When I want ideas or to understand a topic, I organize hackathons. Hackathon is cool because we listen to several ideas and select them”*.

Crowdsourcing consists of outsourcing processes, traditionally carried out internally, to an indefinite, generally large group of people [243]. Participants mentioned that crowdsourcing allows several SECO actors to contribute to requirements management. FS2-P1 stated: “*We have crowdsourcing when several groups come together. Our ventures come together to fund ideas*”. FS2-P18 commented: “*We used crowdsourcing to let the crowd say what was best about the system*”.

Outsourcing R&D consists of R&D services hiring from other organizations [246]. Participants said they worked in organizations that provided R&D services to keystone. FS2-P9 highlighted: “*The company I work for was hired as responsible for credit-related systems. When I need to request a change in systems not under our supervision, for example, customer or internal code systems. I speak with [omitted] (keystone), but not with the companies responsible for these systems*”.

University research grants consist of funding external research projects by researchers and scientists in universities to access external knowledge [247]. Some participants shared that keystone offered research grants for SECO members to carry out requirements management activities. FS2-P9 shared: “*The government has a digital transformation project that has injected resources into [omitted] (keystone). So, [omitted] (keystone) opened a call for grants for analysts and developers from the other organizations that are part of the ecosystem to work on the development of some module*”.

Venturing is defined as starting up new organizations drawing on internal knowledge, and possibly also with finance, human capital, and other support services from your enterprise [246]. Some participants reported that the companies they work for sometimes create new companies to meet specific requirements of the common technological platform or customers. FS2-P1 claimed: “*We have a group of ventures that support each other for innovation initiatives and initiatives to meet requirements and provide solutions for customers*”.

Open source aims to reveal internal technologies without immediate financial rewards for indirect benefits to the company [248]. Some participants highlighted that they identify changes to product requirements they develop by participating in open source initiatives. FS2-P14 reported: “*I participated in a project that used*

open source last year. We had an algorithm that made this automatic match between investors and startups. So, we helped other developers because it was something nobody could do, and our company got feedback”.

Co-creation refers to the contribution provided by the consumer to the process of creating value for the company, allowing the consumer to actively contribute to designing, analyzing, controlling, and evaluating products and processes [243]. Some participants commented on the active participation of customers in requirements management in SECO. FS2-P1 shared: *“We have some key customers who contribute to our activities and give us feedback”*. FS2-P14 stated: *“We are a design-driven company. Co-creation is what we do”*.

Collaboration involves internal resources operating in different business areas and extends to integrating external resources to define and develop innovative projects [243]. Several participants mentioned that collaborating with other organizations allows identifying requirements change, clarifying doubts, and implementing new features. FS2-P10 shared: *“A partner institution came to us so that we could clarify some doubts about the functioning of the systems and make some business comparisons to implement new functionalities”*.

Coopetition is characterized by a balance between cooperative and competitive forces [249]. Some participants reported that there are direct and indirect partnerships between competitors in SECO. Thus, some organizations need to compete in requirements prioritization. FS2-P18 mentioned: *“I observed coopetition when there were conflicting requirements between keystone’s partners. They were indirect partners because they evolved the platform and used each other’s solutions. However, they competed when it came to developing and sending add-ons”*.

Insight #26:

Open innovation practices play an important role in requirements management in SECO by supporting several approaches to identify and manage requirements.

5.3.3 Discussion

From the answers obtained in 21 interviews with professionals who carry out requirements management activities in SECO, we identified how these professionals

receive/provide requirements or requirements change from/to external actors and which open innovation practices are used to support these activities. We discuss our main results next.

Regarding the **communication channels** used to receive/provide requirements or requirements change from/to external actors in SECO, we identified that professionals use open online, closed online, and face-to-face communication channels. The relationship between open communication channels, requirements and SECO has already been investigated in the literature [18, 108]. Knauss et al. [18] stated that open communication channels allow transparent communication between developers and customers and are important for exploring RE practices in SECO. Linåker and Runeson [108] mentioned open communication channels, open requirements management, and active ecosystem engagement as resources to enable an open collaboration in SECO. Hence, open communication channels allow open innovation practices that influence open requirements management in SECO.

In our field study, FS2-P8 cited that he analyzes forums such as Stack Overflow to identify possible requirements. In the same direction, Knauss et al. [18] stated that some internal stakeholders even actively track open communication channels of other actors to identify crosscutting problems without this task being formally assigned to them. For the authors, open communication channels have shown their value for building communities over healthy ecosystems. Moreover, these channels offer an exciting opportunity to improve scalability by facilitating decentralized “just-in-time” RE and supporting agile development.

Insight #27:

The use of several communication channels is important in the requirements management in SECO to uncover new requirements and cross-cutting issues.

Regarding **open innovation practices** to support requirements management in SECO, we observed that SECO and open innovation are related mainly to collaboration between different actors (including external actors) over a common technological platform. Jansen [1] defines open innovation as a focus area of SECO governance. The open innovation focus area is concerned with sharing

knowledge across the ecosystem to feed external developers with new possibilities for improvement, also known as niche creation [1]. Hence, the open innovation focus area directly relates to requirements management.

Our results also show that open innovation practices influence how requirements management is carried out. Fernandez and Svensson [39] stated that open innovation as part of the RE process is becoming more and more fully explored from both the inbound and outbound. Several participants of our study highlighted open innovation practices to support requirements management in SECO, such as collaboration, co-creation, and crowdsourcing. argued that crowdsourcing has a high potential in most RE activities because a large network of both internal and external stakeholders can perform requirements elicitation, negotiation, and prioritization and contribute to requirements management, potentially leading to higher user satisfaction and open innovation.

Insight #28:

Crowdsourcing allows several SECO actors to contribute to requirements management, potentially leading to open innovation.

This second field study investigated open innovation practices in requirements management in SECO. As a result, we identified crowdsourcing as an open innovation practice. This result corroborates one of the open questions of the research agenda defined in our SMS, which is related to the use of the CrowdRE paradigm in requirements management in SECO. This result (in our SMS and second field study) motivated our third field study, as detailed next.

5.4 Investigating User Feedback from a Crowd in Requirements Management in Software Ecosystems

Multi-party stakeholders in a SECO form distinct crowds [16]. According to Johnson et al. [16], a crowd in SECO is a large heterogeneous user base providing requirements on multiple channels with multiple stakeholders. Hence, meeting multiple users' expectations in SECO requires new approaches that engage this crowd of actors in RE activities [41], such as those related to crowd-based RE (CrowdRE). Crowdsourcing has been used to support RE in capturing user feedback

from a crowd in SECO [16, 105, 118]. It is an evolving paradigm that helps to gather software requirements, enabling several stakeholders to claim their needs and expectations towards a particular software system [205]. Performing RE activities through crowdsourcing is part of CrowdRE, which includes all approaches that engage a crowd of mostly unknown people to perform RE tasks or provide requirements-relevant information [84, 86].

Despite the proliferation of SECO, growing a sustainable and healthy ecosystem remains a significant challenge [251]. According to Foundjem [251], one approach to mitigate this challenge is the analysis of feedback from the multiple stakeholders of a SECO. Several SECO actors rely on this feedback to make decisions and prioritize their actions [3, 252]. However, analyzing user feedback in SECO is difficult due to distinct crowds, multiple feedback channels, and the complex interplay with external developers' applications [3]. Previous works explored user feedback in SECO or cited its importance [1, 3, 158]. In this study, we aim to investigate whether and how user feedback from a crowd is considered in requirements management in SECO. To achieve this goal, we conducted a field study based on interviews with 20 professionals involved in related activities in SECO.

5.4.1 Planning

In the planning phase, we defined the RQ of the field study and presented the procedures for conducting the semi-structured interviews, the characterization of participants, and the coding process.

5.4.1.1 Research Question

The RQ aimed to allow a researcher to obtain detailed information about participants' experiences, opinions, and perspectives on how they consider user feedback from a crowd in requirements management activities in SECO. The RQ of the third field study was: *(FS3-RQ) How is user feedback from a crowd considered in requirements management in SECO?*

5.4.1.2 Semi-Structured Interviews

We initially developed an interview guide⁸ with the objective, the procedures for preparation, and carrying out the interviews (details in Appendix 9.5). Afterward, we conducted a pilot interview with one professional involved in requirements management activities in SECO that only helped us check the questions' clarity and understanding and the estimated time to complete the interview, not being used in our analysis. The pilot participant encouraged us to exemplify what could be considered a crowd in software development and which automated and semi-automated approaches are used in the context of CrowdRE.

We conducted 20 interviews between July and August 2023 with professionals involved in requirements management activities in SECO. Each of them lasted between 35 and 55 minutes. At the beginning of each interview session, we reinforced the consent form terms and requested permission to record it, explaining to the participant that the interview transcript would be used as research data. We divided the interviews into two parts:

- **Presentation of the concepts used in the interview:** We presented the definitions of SECO, requirements management, user feedback, crowd, and CrowdRE to ensure clarity and avoid any confusion or ambiguity about the meaning of each term;
- **Questions about user feedback from a crowd in requirements management in SECO:** we asked participants whether they considered user feedback from a crowd in requirements management activities in SECO and which mechanisms they used to do so. In addition, we asked if they know or have used automated or semi-automated approaches to deal with user feedback from a crowd in these activities. Finally, we asked if they agree with the fact that user feedback from a crowd brings benefits to requirements management in SECO.

We used Google Meet to record the interviews and Google Docs to transcribe them. We transcribed the interviews iteratively. Although we automatically

⁸<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13367845>

transcribed each video recording, the researcher coding the interviews had watched the original video during this process. Hence, we ensured the best and most accurate interpretation of each interview as possible and corrected errors in the automatically generated transcripts during the coding process. After transcription, we ratified the permission to share the transcripts from a specific authorization term to explicitly inform participants that we would make them available in an open-access repository as supplementary material for supporting a research manuscript. This authorization term and the anonymized spreadsheet with the responses of the 20 participants are available in the supplementary material⁹ (details in Appendix 9.5). All participants responded, to and agreed with, the authorization term.

We adopted the concept of “*saturation*” to establish the number of interviews required in our study. A study reaches saturation when conducting a new set of interviews does not produce new emerging data [234]. According to Morse [253] and Morse [254], saturation is the most common guiding principle for assessing the adequacy of purposive samples in qualitative research. For Hennink and Kaiser [255], saturation refers to the point in data collection when no additional issues or insights are identified, and data begin to repeat so that further data collection is redundant, signifying that an adequate sample size is reached. Moreover, saturation is “*the most frequently touted guarantee of qualitative rigor offered by authors to reviewers and readers*” [254].

According to Guest et al. [235], saturation can usually be obtained with at least 12 interviews. Hennink and Kaiser [255] conducted a recent SLR on sample sizes for saturation in qualitative research and identified that saturation can be reached within a narrow range of interviews (9–17 interviews). In our study, we initially identified 25 potential participants and interviewed 20 professionals as performed in similar studies in SE [233, 256, 257, 258, 259].

We reached saturation with 17 interviews, in line with the work of Guest et al. [235] and Hennink and Kaiser [255]. We highlight that the number of potential participants could increase according to the interviewees’ indications, considering snowball sampling. In each interview, we observed whether participants repeated the topics discussed earlier. Interview recordings and transcriptions were continually

⁹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13367845>

revisited in an iterative process. As no new codes or insights emerged in three consecutive interviews, we realized our codes and insights were fully saturated and stopped recruiting new participants.

5.4.1.3 Characterization of Participants

We used convenience sampling to select participants for our study based on their being nearby and available [236]. We contacted professionals involved in requirements management activities in SECO from our network via email and other communication channels (WhatsApp and LinkedIn). In addition, we used snowball sampling, in which early participants referred other professionals to participate in the study [236]. Even though we recruited participants through convenience and snowball sampling, we looked for diverse participants in terms of experience, engagement in different SECO, and different perspectives (keystone or external developer perspective). This helps ensure that the selected sample is representative and relevant to the research goals.

Before performing each meeting, we sent out a questionnaire to the participants in order to gather information on their profiles¹⁰ (details in Appendix 9.5). This questionnaire was shared via email to be responded to without supervision and also asked participants for their consent to be interviewed and permission to record the session. Some participants answered “*No*” or “*I don’t know*” to questions about their engagement in SECO and about receiving user feedback from a crowd. Most of these participants had been selected via snowball sampling. Therefore, other participants who had already participated in the interview indicated that these potential new participants were part of the study population. We realized participants might not have understood the “*SECO*” and “*crowd*” concepts well in the questionnaire. According to Jansen et al. [49], several practitioners do not fully recognize how their contributions fit into larger ecosystems that include other developers, users, and multiple organizations. Manikas and Hansen [6] highlighted that developers typically concentrate on their roles without considering the ecosystem’s dynamics. For this reason, we also invited these participants to interviews and confirmed their real understanding on the topics immediately after presenting and exemplifying

¹⁰<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13367845>

the concepts of SECO and crowd. Therefore, all participants have experience in requirements management, SECO, and receiving user feedback from a crowd.

Table 5.5 summarizes the information about the interviewees. We assigned a unique identifier (ID) to each participant, characterizing the first one as FS3-P1 and the last one as FS3-P20. We also kept the initial responses to the characterization questionnaire and marked the response change with an “*” in order to ensure data integrity.

Table 5.5: Characterization of participants.

ID*	Academic background in computer science	Experience in requirements management	Engagement in SECO	Receives user feedback from a crowd
FS3-P1	Master’s degree	15 years	Yes	Yes
FS3-P2	PhD	25 years	Yes	No**
FS3-P3	MBA (Specialization course)***	10 years	No**	No**
FS3-P4	MBA (Specialization course)***	10 years	Yes	Yes
FS3-P5	MBA (Specialization course)***	3 years	I don’t know**	I don’t know**
FS3-P6	Master’s degree	7 years	Yes	Yes
FS3-P7	MBA (Specialization course)***	6 years	Yes	Yes
FS3-P8	PhD	9 years	Yes	Yes
FS3-P9	MBA (Specialization course)***	10 years	Yes	No**
FS3-P10	Master’s degree	12 years	Yes	Yes
FS3-P11	PhD	5 years	Yes	No**
FS3-P12	Master’s degree	15 years	Yes	Yes
FS3-P13	Master’s degree	8 years	Yes	No**
FS3-P14	PhD	30 years	Yes	Yes
FS3-P15	MBA (Specialization course)***	13 years	Yes	Yes
FS3-P16	PhD	2 years	Yes	Yes
FS3-P17	PhD	2 years	Yes	Yes
FS3-P18	Bachelor’s degree	10 years	No**	No**
FS3-P19	PhD	3 years	Yes	No**
FS3-P20	Master’s degree	15 years	Yes	Yes

*Field Study 3 - Participant [i], e.g., FS3-P1.

**Participants changed their answers to “Yes” at the beginning of the interview.

***MBA (Master of Business Administration) with a specialization in Information Technology.

Five (25%) of the 20 participants have between 2 and 5 years of experience in requirements management, eight (40%) have between 6 and 10 years, and seven (35%) have more than 10 years of experience. We also asked participants which activities related to requirements management they had already performed. Table 5.6 presents the responses of some participants. The participants had

been engaged in 11 different SECO. We described and classified them into PSECO, OSSECO or Hybrid SECO in Table 5.7. Moreover, 10 participants had the perspective of requirements management activities in SECO performed by keystone (FS3-P1, FS3-P2, FS3-P7, FS3-P8, FS3-P11, FS3-P12, FS3-P14, FS3-P15, FS3-P16, FS3-P20) and 10 by external developers (FS3-P3, FS3-P4, FS3-P5, FS3-P6, FS3-P9, FS3-P10, FS3-P13, FS3-P17, FS3-P18, FS3-P19).

Table 5.6: Experience in requirements management activities.

ID	Requirements management activities
FS3-P8	<i>“I have had the opportunity to work in the discovery, elicitation, synthesis, change management, prioritization, and translation of requirements into stories/epics, mining review bases to extract requirements”</i>
FS3-P11	<i>“Requirements specification, client meetings, client validation, requirements prioritization, requirements change management”</i>
FS3-P15	<i>“Planning and monitoring requirements elicitation, prioritization, documentation and specifications, requirements negotiation, and communication (in delivering functionality to the user)”</i>
FS3-P18	<i>“Requirements elicitation, tracking and versioning, analysis of possible impacts to mitigate risks involved in new deployments, control of package versions (COBOL) and creation of change requests, control and management of customer needs backlog combined with formal documentation for analysis of estimated and realized function points. Elicitation, creation, and execution of test scenarios, as well as support and approval of demands with the management area”</i>

Table 5.7: Characterization of SECO in which study participants are engaged.

ID	SECO Type	SECO Description	Size	Participants
SECO01	PSECO	SECO formed around the development of solutions to digital transformation, artificial intelligence, automation, digital marketing, and cybersecurity, with several partners involved.	More than 250 available products	FS3-P1
SECO02	PSECO	SECO formed around the development of systems that aim to automate the management of institutional processes with several public partner organizations involved.	4 available products	FS3-FS3-P2, FS3-P14
SECO03	PSECO	Educational SECO formed around the development of solutions to administrative and academic project management with several public partner organizations involved.	25 available products	FS3-P3, FS3-P4, FS3-P5, FS3-P10, FS3-P13, FS3-P15
SECO04	Hybrid SECO	Mobile SECO formed around a platform that supports app development by several external actors with developer relations (DevRel) support.	More than 300,000 available apps	FS3-P6, FS3-P8
SECO05	PSECO	SECO formed around the development of federated information systems of a national public bank with several partners involved.	11 available apps	FS3-P7, FS3-P9, FS3-P18
SECO06	PSECO	Educational SECO formed around the development of a virtual learning environment and several add-ons with several public partner organizations involved.	3 available products	FS3-P11
SECO07	PSECO	SECO formed around the development of solutions offered by an innovation center with several partners involved.	More than 70 available products	FS3-P12

Continued on next page

Table 5.7 – Continued from previous page

ID	SECO Type	SECO Description	Size	Participants
SECO08	PSECO	SECO formed around the development of solutions that help to recover learning and reduce school dropout rates with several public partner organizations involved.	6 available products	FS3-P16
SECO09	OSSECO	SECO formed around the development of several products related to integrated development environments and a collection of modeling tools.	More than 1,000 available products	FS3-P17
SECO10	OSSECO	SECO formed around the development of a set of platforms and products for an operational system developed by an international community.	More than 200 available products	FS3-P19
SECO11	PSECO	SECO formed around the development of solutions for insurance in several segments (e.g., auto, property, health, capitalization, and open supplementary pension) with several partners involved.	More than 10 available products	FS3-P20

5.4.1.4 Coding Process

To start analyzing the interviews, we performed an open coding approach inspired by the initial procedure of the GT [115]. During the open coding process, we divided the transcripts into coherent units (sentences or paragraphs) and added **preliminary codes** representing the key points each participant talked about. Subsequently, we defined a set of **focused codes** that captured the most frequent and relevant factors from the participants' perceptions. After open coding, we used axial coding, described by Charmaz [116], to group the codes into **categories**. The categories resulting from this grouping were: *mechanisms* and *approaches*. Mechanisms are means by which CrowdRE approaches achieve their intended participation goal [85]. Approaches are methods, techniques, tools, and web-based platforms to support CrowdRE [205]. In these steps, we used Atlas.TI as a tool to support the creation of codes and categories. Table 5.8 shows the example of the coding process for one transcript with resulting codes and categories. The final report on how the coding process was carried out via Atlas.TI is available in the supplementary material ¹¹ (details in Appendix 9.5).

We have double-checked our coding results to ensure the reported results are accurate and consistent by analyzing the final report¹¹ generated in the Atlas.TI tool with quotes from the interviews, codes, and categories. Moreover, we continuously revisited the interview recordings and transcripts iteratively.

¹¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13367845>

Table 5.8: Illustration of the coding process to third field study.

Example 1		
Coherent unit: “we analyzed software repositories to identify and prioritize requirements. We implemented some scripts to identify and prioritize the requirements in these repositories” (FS3-P8)		
Preliminary code	Focused code	Category
<i>We analyzed software repositories to identify and prioritize requirements</i>	Software repositories	Mechanism
Example 2		
Coherent unit: “we use an artificial intelligence tool that does what the chatbot does but it is much more intelligent. We can identify this entire level of feedback in an omnichannel service through several channels” (FS3-P1)		
Preliminary code	Focused code	Category
<i>We use an artificial intelligence tool</i>	Artificial intelligence techniques	Approach

5.4.2 Results

We realized that user feedback from a crowd is more considered in requirements change identification than in requirements prioritization and negotiation. We also identify mechanisms and approaches used to reach and analyze user feedback from a crowd in requirements management in SECO, as extracted through open and axial coding. According to Charmaz [116], categories emerge from the data in the axial coding. Therefore, not all participants cited mechanisms for gathering user feedback from a crowd and/or approaches for analyzing it. Finally, we check that user feedback from a crowd brings benefits requirements management in SECO, according to most interviewed professionals. We detail our results next.

5.4.2.1 User Feedback from a Crowd in Requirements Management in SECO

We initially asked professionals whether they considered user feedback from a crowd in requirements management activities in SECO, such as requirements change identification, prioritization, or negotiation. We focused on the requirements management activities presented in ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148 [62], except the requirements version control and traceability, which refer to control activities performed by requirements managers that are not always directly related to gathering and analyzing user feedback in a crowd context. In the CrowdRE paradigm, users have a prominent role concerning other stakeholders [84].

Regarding **requirements change identification**, all professionals stated that they consider user feedback from a crowd to carry out this activity in requirements

management in SECO. FS3-P1 mentioned that: *“we have several possibilities here to consider user feedback to identify requirements”*. FS3-P15 responded that: *“yes, we have already considered. We do it when we are launching a new system, and we need to collect user feedback”*. Wouters et al. [87] highlighted that CrowdRE research has mainly investigated requirements elicitation. According to Lim et al. [211], a primary focus of CrowdRE has been eliciting requirements from explicit user feedback from crowd users. Vegendla et al. [14] highlighted that the requirements identification considering SECO characteristics is a challenging issue because: (i) involves identifying SECO members’ requirements with different business goals; (ii) software vendors have trouble distinguishing the particular SECO they are active in; (iii) software vendors have trouble using SECO advantages for their strategic planning; and (iv) the openness of the platform permits everyone to provide the requirements without role identification. The factors pointed out by Vegendla et al. [14] are directly related to distinct crowds in SECO.

Regarding **requirements prioritization**, 5 of 20 professionals stated they consider user feedback from a crowd to carry out this activity in requirements management in SECO. FS3-P1 mentioned that: *“we have another product whose prioritization is given by the end-user. This is really cool because he or she is the one who will use the system daily”*. FS3-P6 responded that: *“in prioritization, we try to measure the effort we have to make a change and, of course, we always try to start with the things that are mostly talked among users”*. For Kifetew et al. [92], information derived from user feedback can support software evolution activities, such as requirements prioritization. Moreover, requirements prioritization is pivotal in CrowdRE because a large number of stakeholders often results in a large set of requirements that cannot be implemented simultaneously [85].

Regarding **requirements negotiation**, 3 of 20 professionals pointed out user feedback from a crowd to carry out this activity in requirements management in SECO. FS3-P8 highlighted that: *“the negotiation phase is already difficult in small projects. However, this becomes more difficult when it involves a crowd with different perceptions and expectations. In app stores, for example, the acceptance criteria for that application to remain in the store or to be submitted and accepted is a form of negotiation with the crowd”*. FS3-P15 mentioned that: *“requirement con-*

licts occurred by the time to implement the requirements and the underlying cost. We resolved these conflicts by negotiating with such crowd and seeking a consensus between them". According to Snijders et al. [250], a crowd is involved in the initial requirements elicitation activity and can be part of other activities, such as requirements negotiation. For Khan et al. [85], requirements negotiation plays a pivotal role in CrowdRE.

Insight #29:

The user feedback from a crowd is acknowledged as important to requirements management activities in SECO.

5.4.2.2 Mechanisms to Gather User Feedback from a Crowd in Requirements Management in SECO

We also asked professionals how they got user feedback from a crowd in requirements management activities in SECO. The professionals mentioned several mechanisms to gather user feedback from a crowd in requirements management activities in SECO with answers to this question. Khan et al. [85] explained that mechanisms consist of the means by which CrowdRE approaches achieve their intended participation goals. According to the authors, these mechanisms include the media for communication or sources used to reach out to a crowd, the incentives to motivate a crowd to participate in RE activities, and crowd collaboration or aggregation mechanisms. Table 5.9 presents the mechanisms used to gather user feedback from a crowd in the requirements management activities in SECO according to participants. Next, we define the identified mechanisms to gather user feedback from a crowd in requirements management in SECO, present some excerpts mentioned by professionals in the interviews, and relate our results to the literature.

App stores/Marketplaces are mechanisms to gather user feedback from a crowd that allow continuous interaction between developers and users of mobile apps [260]. They are online software stores where users may browse, purchase, download, and install software applications [261]. In SECO, app stores/marketplaces play a crucial role by providing an online curated marketplace that allows developers to sell and distribute their software products [3, 262]. They are a rich source for software

Table 5.9: Mechanisms to gather user feedback from a crowd in requirements management in SECO.

ID	Mechanism	Requirements management activities		
		Requirements change identification	Requirements prioritization	Requirements negotiation
M01	App stores/Marketplaces	FS3-P6, FS3-P8, FS3-P17	FS3-P6, FS3-P8	-
M02	Built-in user feedback modules	FS3-P1, FS3-P4, FS3-P11, FS3-P15, FS3-P18, FS3-P20	-	-
M03	Forums	FS3-P1, FS3-P2, FS3-P4, FS3-P5, FS3-P8, FS3-P12, FS3-P13, FS3-P15, FS3-P17, FS3-P19	FS3-P8	-
M04	Gamification	FS3-P1	-	-
M05	Issue trackers	FS3-P4, FS3-P5, FS3-P7, FS3-P9, FS3-P12, FS3-P15	-	-
M06	Mailing lists	FS3-P4, FS3-P5, FS3-P10, FS3-P17	-	-
M07	Questionnaires	FS3-P1, FS3-P3, FS3-P4, FS3-P8, FS3-P13, FS3-P15, FS3-P16	FS3-P13	-
M08	Social media platforms	FS3-P10, FS3-P12, FS3-P13, FS3-P15, FS3-P18, FS3-P19	-	-
M09	Software repositories	FS3-P8	FS3-P8	-
M10	User feedback tools	FS3-P2, FS3-P4, FS3-P13, FS3-P14, FS3-P15, FS3-P18, FS3-P20	FS3-P4, FS3-P13, FS3-P15	FS3-P4, FS3-P14, FS3-P15

analysts to elicit requirements from user feedback from a crowd, describing bugs, requested features, and possible improvements [83].

From different perspectives (keystone and external developers), three participants who are engaged in different SECO types (hybrid and OSSECO) cited the use of app stores/marketplaces in the requirements change identification and prioritization. In the requirements change identification context, FS3-P6 (external developers’ perspective of a hybrid SECO) mentioned that: *“we use the app store to retrieve comments and then organize them into topics to analyze them”*. In the requirements prioritization context, FS3-P8 (keystone’s perspective of a hybrid SECO) commented that: *“we wanted to prioritize the requirements according to what was most important to users. We went to the app store to do so, but we did not have much confidence in whether we were covering what was needed within the ecosystem”*. FS3-P17 (external developers’ perspective of a OSSECO) claimed that: *“on the marketplace, there were general comments about the applications or the platform itself, a star rating”*.

Our results indicate that app stores/marketplaces are mechanisms that provide a source of user feedback from a crowd in SECO through reviews, ratings, and requirements change requests. According to Wang et al. [263], app reviews in app stores offer valuable insights into several activities in SECO, e.g., software development, app marketing, and security. Li et al. [264] claimed that app

stores/marketplaces are software crowdsourcing platforms demonstrating the success of software crowdsourcing processes regarding SECO expansion and product quality improvement. Dalpiaz and Parente [83] stated that analyzing the app stores/marketplaces can lead to a better understanding of how apps are actually used, fast detection of newly introduced bugs, and insights from a more diverse range of users from a crowd.

Built-in user feedback modules are mechanisms to gather user feedback from a crowd belonging to part of the software application where users can leave their opinions by filling out text boxes or ticking checkboxes [84, 265]. They enable users to communicate bug reports, feature requests, and praise [82]. Built-in user feedback modules generally provide one-way feedback communication, i.e., from sender to receiver only [266]. In SECO, built-in user feedback modules can include built-in surveys and interactive prompts, allowing users from a crowd to provide context-direct feedback without interrupting their workflow [16].

From the keystone’s perspective, six participants who are engaged in PSECO mentioned the use of built-in user feedback modules in the requirements change identification. FS3-P1 (keystone’s perspective of a PSECO) claimed that: *“one of our systems has a built-in feedback system. You can set the number of stars at the end of use and describe some improvements”*. FS3-P20 (keystone’s perspective of a PSECO) highlighted that: *“So, these demands you are talking about for changing requirements and new functionalities generally emerge through these [omitted]. If they want to send feedback, they use the feedback channel of our e-commerce”*.

Our results indicate that built-in user feedback modules are mechanisms that offer a continuous and immediate way for users from a crowd to communicate their experiences, issues, and suggestions directly in a product or the SECO’s common technological platform. Scherr [267] indicated that built-in user feedback modules, which are provided during the use of a software product, can lead to more detailed feedback about an encountered problem as well as about the product itself. According to Johnson et al. [16], they are channels to elicit user feedback from a crowd in SECO.

Forums are mechanisms to gather user feedback from a crowd through online discussion where people can post messages to exchange knowledge [211]. They

provide a place where the knowledge and experience of individual users anywhere in the world can be shared quickly and easily [268]. A well-structured forum can be a valuable source of requirements-related information [268]. In SECO, forums can be a feature request channel and direct communication with users and external developers from distinct crowds to elicit requirements [16]. Moreover, they allow the automatic extraction of requirements from the feedback of users and external developers [42]. Online discussions in forums are a more structured way of expressing and discussing the collected ideas in the CrowdRE context [87].

From different perspectives (keystone and external developers), 10 participants who are engaged in different SECO types (proprietary, hybrid, and open source) cited the use of forums in the requirements change identification. FS3-P2 (keystone's perspective of a PSECO) mentioned that: *"we received feedback from users on our forums"*. FS3-P4 (external developers' perspective of a PSECO) cited that: *"we always look for [omitted] to see how many people have experienced the same problem"*. FS3-P8 (keystone's perspective of a hybrid SECO) claimed that: *"we also used Stack Overflow and other discussion forums. We sorted the issue by reputation to get a better view of this"*. FS3-P17 (external developers' perspective of a OSSECO) highlighted that: *"Partners could send suggestions, not the users, but the partners, through the forums"*.

Our results demonstrate that forums are mechanisms that provide an open platform for users and external developers from distinct crowds to share their experiences, report issues, and suggest enhancements in SECO. According to Coutinho and Bezerra [230], new features and requirements change requests are registered in forums in SECO, allowing for detailed and asynchronous discussions where users and external developers can elaborate on their needs and preferences. For Albonico et al. [269], forums can discuss more complex topics and announce new projects and updates concerning the SECO community. Mens and Roover [12] highlighted that forums significantly improve mailing lists in SECO by providing browse and search functions and a platform for posting questions within a specific domain of interest and receiving expert answers to these questions.

Gamification is a mechanism to gather user feedback from a crowd that aims to increase the engagement of stakeholders in RE [270]. It establishes feedback loops

that reward the useful participants, i.e., those who provide valuable contributions (requirements) for the system being designed [270]. Gamification can result in some benefits to RE, such as an increase in the quality of the requirements, a greater number of requirements and test scenarios elicited, and an increase in stakeholder engagement [271]. In SECO, platforms often employ gamification elements to increase the participation of users and external developers that form distinct crowds [272]. It is a digital-motivation technique for boosting task completion and influencing positive behavioral changes in a crowd context [84].

From the keystone’s perspective, one participant who is engaged in a PSECO cited the use of gamification as a mechanism for requirements change identification. FS3-P1 (keystone’s perspective of a PSECO) mentioned that: *“we are also using gamification to reach this crowd and identify requirements”*.

Our results indicate that incorporating gamification elements such as points, badges, leaderboards, and challenges into the feedback process can enhance the participation of users and external developers from distinct crowds and the quality of feedback received in SECO. According to Snijders et al. [273], gamification complements crowdsourcing in collecting new requirements and gaining feedback on existing requirements by motivating users to participate more by rewarding users. Moldon et al. [272] suggested that gamification is a powerful channel for social influence in SECO and that a good gamification system can grow user engagement and increase social interaction and collaboration. Estefo et al. [274] recommended the use of gamification to motivate user participation from a crowd in SECO. The authors highlighted the format of Stack Overflow in this aspect, giving points for answers, which increases users’ karma (participation metric). Users can also gain badges for specific contribution achievements desired for an active and healthy community. According to Estefo et al. [274], these gamification techniques (points, badges etc.) have proven to be effective in Stack Overflow and can be effective in other SECO.

Issue trackers are mechanisms to gather user feedback from a crowd that allow software users and developers to submit bug reports and other change requests and track them until they are finally closed [275]. They are an important social part of software development and a hub of communication that significantly supports

collaboration within collocated teams [15]. In SECO, issue trackers are requirements repositories through which multi-party actors interact regarding the RE process [19]. They are standalone bilaterally communication channels that can help the project team elicit and analyze user feedback from a crowd [276].

From different perspectives (keystone and external developers), six participants who are engaged in PSECO mentioned the use of issue trackers in the requirements change identification. FS3-P7 (keystone’s perspective of a PSECO) commented that: *“users open a ticket with a bug report or suggestions for changes that reach our manager”*. FS3-P9 (external developers’ perspective of a PSECO) stated that: *“users open a ticket that is evaluated to see if it was really an error and then we analyzed this error”*.

Our results indicate that issue trackers are mechanisms that enable continuous and collaborative social interaction between the keystone and users and external developers from a crowd in a SECO. According to Jansen [1], they are one common mechanism companies use to collect, categorize, and prioritize user-reported issues in SECO. Chen et al. [15] highlighted that issue trackers enable the fixing process of a cross-project bug in SECO. For Ghimire et al. [3], companies can use information obtained in issues trackers to prioritize their development efforts and ensure that the most critical issues are addressed first.

Mailing lists are mechanisms to gather user feedback from a crowd that enable an electronic discussion forum via email messages [211]. They are an important communication channel between software developers and stakeholders [12, 277]. In SECO, mailing lists are a type of informalism that facilitates social interaction in requirements management [192]. They communicate regularly about the current status of requirements changes, including its technical and content development achieved with the help of a crowd [276].

From the external developers’ perspective, four participants who are engaged in different SECO types (proprietary and open source) cited the use of mailing lists in the requirements change identification. FS3-P4 (external developers’ perspective of a PSECO) highlighted that: *“these changes to requirements were mostly related to [omitted] and generally arrived via email”*. FS3-P17 (external developers’ perspective of a OSSECO) commented that: *“the platform had email contact and*

the partners could send suggestions via mailing list”.

Our results demonstrate that mailing lists are mechanisms that enable users and external developers from a crowd to communicate and discuss several aspects of the software, including feature requests, bug reports, and usage experiences in SECO. According to Shi et al. [277], mailing lists act as one of the most frequently used communication channels in a crowd context. For Shi et al. [277], they enable users to easily submit feature requests and greatly improve the efficiency of organizations when gathering new ideas. Foundjem et al. [278] stated that users and external developers use mailing lists to discuss feature updates, bug reports, and enhancement requests in SECO. Mens and Roover [12] highlighted that mining mailing list archives can reveal valuable insights into the factors driving requirements change in SECO. However, more modern communication technologies are gradually replacing mailing lists, according to Mens and Roover [12]. For Foundjem et al. [278], mailing lists are mechanisms of user feedback that are noisy and with many distractions in SECO.

Questionnaires are mechanisms to gather user feedback from a crowd that can support identifying how users use systems and what features they like or dislike [279]. In SECO, they can enable keystone to proactively seek feedback from both users and external developers, providing accessible and user-friendly channels for communication [3]. Moreover, questionnaires facilitate gathering immediate user perceptions and enable users from a crowd to communicate bug reports, feature requests, and praise [82].

From different perspectives (keystone and external developers), seven participants who are engaged in different SECO types (proprietary and hybrid) pointed out the use of questionnaires in the requirements change identification and prioritization. In the requirements change identification context, FS3-P3 (external developers’ perspective of a PSECO) commented that: *“we use questionnaires to identify requirements with this crowd, but I think these questionnaires fail because the vision of those who respond does not represent the whole”*. FS3-P8 (keystone’s perspective of a hybrid SECO) stated that: *“we also provided a link to a questionnaire in which people could send feedback about the systems. It was not just about requirements but also about how the entire process was conducted”*. In the

requirements prioritization context, FS3-P13 (external developers' perspective of a PSECO) mentioned that: *“sometimes, [omitted] sent some questionnaires about using a certain module or some questionnaire about a certain system, and then they shared the results. Feedback received through these questionnaires was used in prioritization”*.

Our results indicate that questionnaires are mechanisms that ensure the easy and systematic gathering of quantitative and qualitative data from a base of diverse users and external developers in SECO. According to Ghimire et al. [3], the multiple actors in a SECO can identify areas for improvement, identify any bugs or issues that may arise, and prioritize future updates through feedback received in questionnaires. For Laghari et al. [280], user feedback questionnaires are used in crowdsourcing platforms for users to enter feedback. Wüest et al. [266] highlighted that requesting user feedback with a simple feedback form is a useful approach for motivating users from a crowd to provide feedback.

Social media platforms are mechanisms to gather user feedback from a crowd that have relevant information about requirements [42]. They are important channels for software users to communicate with developers and other users [281]. In SECO, requirements change requests from users and external developers can be on social media platforms [2]. Social media platforms provide an excellent opportunity to motivate stakeholders to participate in a crowd [85] and are a fertile source for crowd-generated content [41].

From different perspectives (keystone and external developers), six participants who are engaged in different SECO types (proprietary and open source) cited the use of social media platforms in the requirements change identification. FS3-P15 (keystone's perspective of a PSECO) stated that: *“we have already received suggestions on Instagram. We have a communications team that is responsible for obtaining all these demands and directing them”*. FS3-P18 (external developers' perspective of a PSECO) mentioned that: *“we are starting to use WhatsApp channels now, and people are really sending their opinions through them”*. FS3-P19 (external developers' perspective of a OSSECO) claimed that: *“they also have conversations on social networks”*.

Our results indicate that social media platforms are mechanisms that provide

a vast and diverse source of user feedback from a crowd in SECO. According to Lim et al. [211], advanced analytical tools that mine social media platforms' data allow the requirement change identification and prioritization based on the frequency and intensity of user feedback. Chen et al. [15] cited that the use of social media in SECO facilitates the collaboration between the keystone, users, and external developers. For Khan et al. [282], stakeholders from a crowd frequently contribute requirements-related information on social media platforms.

Software repositories are mechanisms to gather user feedback from a crowd that enable sharing software packages or source codes and include datasets and information related to artifacts created during the software development process [211]. In SECO, open public software repositories have expanded the boundary and scale of who is involved in envisioning new features and functions of software so that ordinary consumers can inform software developers of their needs and preferences [283]. Software repositories can enhance the understanding of developer-user interactions during the creation of software artifacts in a crowd context [284].

From the keystone's perspective, one participant who is engaged in a hybrid SECO cited the use of software repositories in the requirements change identification and prioritization. FS3-P8 (keystone's perspective of a hybrid SECO) mentioned that: *"we analyzed software repositories to identify and prioritize requirements. We implemented some scripts to identify and prioritize the requirements in these repositories because we could not manage everything daily"*.

Our results indicate that software repositories are mechanisms that enable a collaborative environment where users and external developers can report bugs, propose new features, and discuss potential improvements in a SECO. Mens and Roover [12] highlighted that software repositories can provide the keystone and external developers with useful recommendations in SECO. For instance, Maruping and Matook [283] mentioned that Salesforce SECO has a software repository with a robust user community that generates ideas for new features and functionalities for applications sold on the keystone's AppExchange.

User feedback tools are mechanisms to gather user feedback from a crowd that allow users to submit proposals, issues, or ideas anytime actively [285]. These requests undergo a discussion and refinement process, to which everyone is eligible

to contribute and usually vote for or against the requests [285]. In SECO, these tools enable users and external developers from a crowd to provide meaningful feedback to the community [251]. Moreover, they can implement one or multiple methods for collecting, managing, and analyzing user feedback from a crowd [286].

From different perspectives (keystone and external developers), seven participants who are engaged in PSECO cited the use of user feedback tools in the requirements change identification, prioritization, and negotiation. FS3-P4 (external developers' perspective of a PSECO) mentioned that: “[omitted] was a system for sending feedback related to innovation, a new module, and even a new system”. FS3-P15 (keystone's perspective of a PSECO) commented that: “[omitted] is a system for internal employees and cooperative members to send suggestions for improvement”.

Our results demonstrate that user feedback tools are mechanisms that allow users from a crowd to submit detailed individual feedback, report issues, and suggest new features in SECO. Seyff et al. [287] highlighted that they are structured mechanisms that enable users to communicate individual feedback in SECO adequately. According to Knauss et al. [18], users can articulate their needs with the help of user feedback tools in SECO. For Tavanapour and Bittner [288], implementing user feedback tools serves as an additional motivational mechanism in the crowdsourcing context.

Insight #30:

Several mechanisms are used for gathering user feedback from a crowd in requirements management activities in SECO. Analyzing this user feedback in an integrated way ensures a comprehensive understanding of the needs of the multiple actors of SECO.

5.4.2.3 Approaches to Analyze User Feedback from a Crowd in Requirements Management in SECO

We asked professionals how they analyzed user feedback from a crowd in requirements management activities in SECO. The professionals mentioned several approaches to analyze user feedback from a crowd in requirements management in SECO. Abdullah et al. [205] highlighted that the current CrowdRE research

spans several approaches, such as methods, techniques, tools, and web-based platforms to assist the RE process while utilizing crowdsourcing benefits. Table 5.10 presents approaches used to analyze user feedback from a crowd in the requirements management activities in SECO according to the participants. Next, we define the identified approaches to analyze user feedback from a crowd in requirements management in SECO, present some excerpts mentioned by professionals in the interviews, and relate our results to the literature.

Table 5.10: Approaches used to analyze user feedback from a crowd in requirements management in SECO.

ID	Approach	Requirements management activities		
		Requirements change identification	Requirements prioritization	Requirements negotiation
A01	A/B testing	FS3-P1, FS3-P10	-	-
A02	Artificial intelligence techniques	FS3-P1, FS3-P6, FS3-P8, FS3-P12, FS3-P14	FS3-P8	-
A03	Multi-criteria decision-making methods	-	FS3-P1, FS3-P3, FS3-P14	FS3-P1, FS3-P14
A04	Social network analysis	FS3-P8	FS3-P8	-
A05	Voting	-	FS3-P10, FS3-P15	FS3-P10, FS3-P15
A06	WinWin	-	-	FS3-P1, FS3-P8

A/B testing is an approach to analyze user feedback from a crowd that commonly optimizes an existing feature, introduces a new feature, or builds a new product [289]. It significantly changed RE practice, showing different versions of the same product to different customer groups [290]. In SECO, A/B testing can target a specific group of users or external developers based on different criteria, such as location, language, age group, or users who have opted for testing beta versions of a product [17]. It is also a crowdsourcing mechanism in which two software variants, denoted as variant A and variant B, are compared by evaluating the merit of the variants through exposure to the users from a crowd [291, 292].

From different perspectives (keystone and external developers), two participants who are engaged in a PSECO cited the use of A/B testing as an approach to analyze user feedback from a crowd in requirements change identification. FS3-P1 (external developers' perspective of a PSECO) stated that: *“we also do A/B testing with different features to identify requirements. We make some features available to a specific group of customers and others available to another group”*. FS3-P10 (keystone's perspective of a PSECO) mentioned that: *“we gathered different groups of users and asked them to test different sets of features and present some improvement suggestions to us”*.

Our results indicate that A/B testing is an approach that supports the keystone and external developers to analyze user feedback from a crowd without disrupting users and make changes to a product in a SECO once they're satisfied with what they are rolling out. Axelsson and Skoglund [17] stated that A/B testing in SECO allows an external developer to test a business hypothesis before releasing the software publicly. For the authors, a keystone may orchestrate such a test, releasing software in stages to several subsets of users. According to Groen et al. [86], A/B testing, in combination with CrowdRE, may uncover implicit requirements and validate the derived requirements before they are implemented in a product.

Artificial intelligence techniques such as data mining, natural language processing, deep learning, and machine learning are approaches to analyze user feedback from a crowd that support uncovering 'unknown unknown' requirements [86]. In SECO, they can be used to reason about the large amounts of data collected, supporting automated RE activities [293]. Requirements management has successfully applied artificial intelligence techniques to large volumes of data and, in conjunction with crowdsourcing, these techniques obtain quality requirements from a crowd [294].

From different perspectives (keystone and external developers), five participants who are engaged in different SECO types (proprietary and hybrid) cited the use of artificial intelligence techniques as an approach to analyze user feedback from a crowd in requirements change identification and prioritization. In the requirements change identification context, FS3-P1 (keystone's perspective of a PSECO) highlighted that: *"we do not use a chatbot. We use an artificial intelligence tool that does what the chatbot does but it is much more intelligent. We can identify this entire level of feedback in an omnichannel service through several channels"*. FS3-P6 (external developers' perspective of a PSECO) claimed that: *"we have a tool to retrieve comments from the app store and summarize them by topic. It is an artificial intelligence tool"*. In the requirements prioritization context, FS3-P8 (keystone's perspective of a hybrid SECO) mentioned that: *"we used topic modeling algorithms and word clouds to identify the highest priority requirements [...] We started using data mining methods because we could not manage all comments daily"*.

Our results indicate that artificial intelligence techniques are an approach that supports the analysis of vast amounts of user feedback from distinct crowds in SECO elicited from several user feedback mechanisms, such as social media, app stores, and software repositories. According to Mens and Roover [12], artificial intelligence techniques in SECO provide a major opportunity to connect multiple sources of information. For the authors, these techniques can also be an interface between human developers and other software services, such as external developers' applications in SECO. Abdullah et al. [205] claimed that artificial intelligence techniques can analyze user feedback from a crowd to produce quality requirements descriptions. Kanchev et al. [295] mentioned that they are a promising research direction for CrowdRE.

Multi-criteria decision-making methods are approaches that can analyze user feedback from a crowd, providing an overall ranking of alternative solutions based on the most preferred to the least preferred solution [296]. They are particularly useful for different decision-makers interested in ranking a set of alternative requirements based on different criteria [297]. In SECO, multi-criteria decision-making methods consider the dependencies between alternatives and criteria while handling complex interactions among multiple actors [298]. They should consider different stakeholders' perspectives from a crowd in the requirements prioritization and negotiation, thus leading to a complex decision-making problem [299].

From the keystone's perspective, three participants who are engaged in PSECO cited the use of multi-criteria decision-making methods as an approach to analyzing user feedback from a crowd in requirements change prioritization and negotiation. As such, regarding the requirements prioritization context, FS3-P1 (keystone's perspective of a PSECO) mentioned that: *"we use the weighted shortest job first, a SAFe algorithm. We also created another alternating algorithm that uses weight and value in prioritization"*. In turn, in the requirements negotiation context, FS3-P14 (keystone's perspective of a PSECO) stated that: *"the requirements conflicts were about the time it would take and the cost it would have. To negotiate these requirements, we considered these factors and presented them to the partners – for example, time and cost that will be required, and we resolved conflicts this way"*.

Our results indicate that multi-criteria decision-making methods are a structured approach to evaluating and balancing multiple, often conflicting criteria when making decisions about requirements in SECO, considering several inputs and preferences of users from a crowd. Rani et al. [298] highlighted that a research gap exists concerning exploring and comparing multi-criteria decision-making methods specifically for decision-making in SECO. According to Morales-Ramirez et al. [299], this approach is particularly beneficial in a crowd context due to a large and heterogeneous group of users, each of them with different priorities and needs. Regarding the use of scaled agile framework (SAFe) in a crowd context, Köse and Aydemir [300] pointed out this framework as a support for continuous delivery, collaboration, and responsiveness, which are crucial in a crowd context where requirements emerge from a broad and diverse group of stakeholders.

Social network analysis are approaches that can be applied to investigate user feedback from a crowd based on the social structure of relationships in networks and the impact of the structure on the behaviors, attitudes, and performances of individual actors or groups [301]. In SECO, they can assist in the understanding of relationship patterns between multiple actors by studying the network structural aspects using a set of metrics and theories [302]. Social network analysis provides a useful framework for thinking about and measuring patterns of interaction between crowd members and project contributors [303]. It enables understanding the relationships among the nodes of interactions and can be an approach used to crowd identification in the CrowdRE context [304].

From the keystone's perspective, one participant who is engaged in a hybrid SECO pointed out the use of social network analysis to examine user feedback from a crowd in requirements change identification and prioritization. FS3-P8 (keystone's perspective of a hybrid SECO) stated that: *“we analyzed social networks to identify whether a person had the most influence in the crowd. We analyzed what he or she indicated and considered it when requirements identification and prioritization”*.

Our results indicate that social network analysis is an approach that can contribute to the visualization of 'big picture' of the relationships and interactions among users and external developers from a crowd in a SECO, highlighting the most influential users and their contributions. According to Teixeira et al. [305], social

network analysis enables a better understanding of competitive and collaborative issues in large and SECO. Moreover, Sun [306] mentioned that it can illustrate the relationship between developers and projects to support knowledge collaboration across projects in SECO. Ma et al. [24] also stated that social network analysis can identify cross-system-bug-fixings in SECO, and Robinson et al. [303] claimed that the stakeholder network structure can influence prioritization in a crowd context.

Voting is an approach that can analyze user feedback from a crowd, in which users can accept or reject collectively identified change requests or features and provide positive, negative, or indifferent feedback [307]. In SECO, voting is a social approach for communities of users and external developers to filter popular ideas among the myriad ideas submitted from a crowd [283]. It also is an approach to requirements prioritization and negotiation using the crowd [308].

From different perspectives (keystone and external developers), two participants who are engaged in a PSECO cited the use of voting as an approach to analyze user feedback from a crowd in requirements change identification and prioritization. In the requirements change prioritization and negotiation context, FS3-P10 (external developers' perspective of a PSECO) mentioned that: *“we have made a list of improvement suggestions available for voting. We wanted to share the responsibility for deciding what was a priority with our users, since they are the people who, in fact, use our systems”*. FS3-P15 (keystone's perspective of a PSECO) stated that: *“For example, all have access to [omitted], where they can search for ideas or register suggestions. If it's a feasible suggestion in our opinion, we can accept it and leave it open for voting, and then people will vote. Do you understand? So, the suggestions that receive the most votes are chosen”*.

Our results indicate that voting is a democratic decision-making approach that allows users and external developers from a crowd to express their preferences by voting on features, requirements change requests, or bug fixes they consider most important in SECO. Jansen [1] pointed out the use of platforms that implement voting to identify requirements based on user feedback from a crowd and enable the requirements management to be more open, such as UserVoice¹². According to Ali Khan et al. [208], voting helps decision making and identifies users' opinions

¹²<http://www.uservoice.com>

from a crowd about a topic under discussion, a new feature suggested, or an issue encountered in a scenario.

WinWin approaches refer to principles, practices, and tools that enable a set of interdependent stakeholders to work on a mutually satisfactory (win-win) set of shared commitments [309]. They help stakeholders prioritize their requirements and capture the rationale for their decisions [309]. In SECO, WinWin approaches seek to ensure mutual benefits for all multi-party actors [13]. Moreover, this approach emphasizes collaboration and mutual benefit in a crowd context [310].

From the keystone’s perspective, two participants who are engaged in different SECO types (proprietary and hybrid) cited the use of WinWin as an approach to analyze user feedback from a crowd in requirements change negotiation. FS3-P1 (keystone’s perspective of a PSECO) highlighted that: *“requirements conflicts are normal. We are already used to dealing with conflicts and offer criteria for their resolution. We offer WinWin approaches, considering weight and hierarchy”*. FS3-P8 (keystone’s perspective of a hybrid SECO) mentioned that: *“Everything is about establishing contracts in which all stakeholders win. It’s not the case that the person will sign a contract, but there are ways of making the person commit to the agreement”*.

Our results indicate that WinWin approaches help build trust and foster long-term relationships among multiple actors from a crowd in a SECO. According to Khan et al. [282], WinWin is one of the most used approaches to successfully achieve interaction between potential stakeholders in the requirements elicitation context. For Fricker [13], a WinWin approach involves several players and issues in the so-called secondary, hidden negotiation table in a SECO.

Insight #31:

Analyzing user feedback from a crowd in SECO involves several approaches that can be integrated into requirements management activities.

5.4.2.4 Benefits of User Feedback from a Crowd in Requirements Management in SECO

We asked professionals if they considered that user feedback from a crowd brings benefits requirements management in SECO. As an answer, 11 professionals (FS3-P3, FS3-P4, FS3-P6, FS3-P7, FS3-P10, FS3-P11, FS3-P12, FS3-P17, FS3-P18, FS3-P19, FS3-P20) corroborate such benefits without any reservations. Six professionals (FS3-P1, FS3-P2, FS3-P8, FS3-P14, FS3-P15, FS3-P16) reported that such feedback can benefit requirements management in SECO only if some important aspects are considered. Finally, three professionals (FS3-P5, FS3-P9, FS3-P13) responded that crowd feedback does not benefit requirements management in the SECO context in which they are involved.

Professionals who considered user feedback from a crowd beneficial for requirements management in SECO highlighted that it assists in: (i) crowd-based decision making; (ii) interaction between SECO members; (iii) definition and redefinition of priorities; (iv) improvement of rules business; and (v) identification of SECO trends. FS3-P4 (external developers' perspective of a PSECO) mentioned that: *"I believe that user feedback brings benefits because it allows interaction among the ecosystem members. For example, I can access a release from a member, find something interesting, and bring it as a new requirement to my fork as well"*. FS3-P6 (external developers' perspective of a hybrid SECO) claimed that: *"user feedback benefits requirements management because we can reprioritize, adjust, or improve things that have already been done or business rules related to requirements"*.

Professionals who considered that user feedback from a crowd only benefits the requirements management in SECO if some important aspects are considered highlighted that: (i) the crowd should not make the final decision; (ii) there be a small strategic control group of stakeholders to manage this feedback; (iii) there must be some statistical control that gives confidence to this feedback; (iv) the crowd must do not direct requirements management in SECO; (v) crowd feedback analysis must do not replace traditional RE methods; and (vi) there must be automated approaches to dealing with this feedback. FS3-P1 (keystone's perspective of a PSECO) mentioned that: *"the crowd is important, but the final decision does not belong to the crowd. We use the crowd to feed a system that provides indicators."*

The crowd is part of the decision making, but the final decision never belongs to the crowd". FS3-P2 (keystone's perspective of a PSECO) commented that: *"user feedback from a crowd benefits requirements management only if there is a small strategic control group of stakeholders to manage this feedback"*.

Professionals who considered that user feedback from a crowd does not benefit requirements management in the context of the SECO highlighted the following reasons: (i) the number of people in requirements management activities; and (ii) the manual way in which requirements management is carried out in a SECO. FS3-P5 (external developers' perspective of a PSECO) responded that: *"I believe that if this feedback were focused only on some sectors of the [omitted], such as [omitted], it would be more beneficial"*. FS3-P9 (external developers' perspective of a PSECO) mentioned that: *"I think it would be great to have this feedback from users, but at the same time, I don't see any real gain. Most of our demands represent the needs of a small group of people"*.

Insight #32:

It is important to balance the user feedback from a crowd with structured oversight to reach its benefits in requirements management in SECO.

5.4.3 Discussion

Based on the answers obtained from 20 interviews with professionals who carry out requirements management activities in SECO, we identified how they gather and analyze user feedback from a crowd in their activities. We discuss our results next.

Regarding the **mechanisms** used to gather user feedback from a crowd in SECO, we identified that professionals use app stores/marketplaces, built-in user feedback modules, forums, gamification, issue trackers, mailing lists, questionnaires, social media platforms, software repositories, and user feedback tools. Multi-party actors can use several of these mechanisms to capture user and external developers' feedback from a crowd in requirements management in SECO. This feedback can refer to the common technological platform, the products developed within a SECO, or the integration between the products and the platform. According to Wang et al. [263], practitioners gather user feedback mainly to identify new requirements,

prioritize features, and address bugs and common customer complaints.

Johnson et al. [16] described SECO in the CrowdRE context as a sizeable heterogeneous user base that needs to cooperate in eliciting requirements available in multiple channels and from distinct crowds across the ecosystem. According to Groen et al. [86] and Wang et al. [263], a crowd generates user feedback across multiple dimensions through a wide range of communication channels and media in a CrowdRE context. For Groen et al. [84], providing multiple feedback channels lets developers consider crowd members' individual backgrounds and needs regarding feedback communication.

Johnson et al. [16] also stated new and expanded mechanisms for collecting ecosystem user feedback that could benefit from CrowdRE are required. Khan et al. [85] highlighted that more scalable mechanisms are needed so that users can actively participate in different feedback channels, thus contributing to future system design decisions. Groen et al. [84] emphasized that user feedback appears in multiple channels in practice, such as app stores, product forums, and social media platforms. In this context, Ghimire et al. [3] highlighted that app stores, marketplaces, public review websites, and keystone platforms provide user feedback in the form of reviews in SECO. For Knauss et al. [18], multiple communication channels are important for exploring RE practices in SECO but also make requirements management difficult.

According to Johnson et al. [16], user feedback from a crowd on an external developer's product can also be useful for the keystone. This feedback can provide insights such as problems with the product integration, issues with features of the core product, or ways the platform could be extended to provide needed functionality in the external developer products. In SECO, external developers can give feedback on the common technological platform and application programming interfaces (API), forming a new crowd that must be considered [16]. For Johnson et al. [16], feedback from this crowd of external developers is often delayed since they need time to build new features using a newly delivered API before they can provide feedback. Foundjem [251] stated that SECO use feedback from external developers and users to coordinate the interests of all actors towards sustainable projects and a healthy SECO.

Insight #33:

Scalable mechanisms are needed so that users can actively participate in different feedback channels in SECO.

Regarding the **approaches** used to analyze user feedback from a crowd in SECO, we identified that professionals use automated, semi-automated, and manual solutions such as artificial intelligence techniques, multi-criteria decision-making methods, social network analysis, voting, and WinWin. Multi-party actors can use several approaches to analyze user and external developers' feedback from a crowd from different perspectives in requirements management in SECO. According to Astegher et al. [311], most practitioners analyze user feedback to validate and elicit new requirements to support alpha/beta testing and to maintain and evolve a software product.

User feedback analysis has become an additional elicitation technique [84]. Santos et al. [89] highlighted that research on CrowdRE has recently explored several approaches to analyze user feedback for RE. Glinz [312] presented a broader view of CrowdRE, from elicitation to any other RE activity and from automated or semi-automated approaches to any approaches, including manual ones. For Johnson et al. [16], new approaches to analyzing user feedback are required to scale with the crowd in SECO.

In the automated or semi-automated approaches context, several research efforts on CrowdRE that use of artificial intelligence techniques exist [89, 312]. Automation, a distinguishing feature of CrowdRE, reduces the effort required to cope with high volumes of feedback [83]. Moreover, classic crowd-based techniques such as questionnaires, stakeholder identification techniques, and crowd-based preference polling with A/B tests are also used in the CrowdRE context [312]. Wang et al. [263] concluded that several practitioners are aware of automated approaches for user feedback analysis from a crowd. However, they still prefer manual analysis due to the complex nature of the information. According to Dalpiaz and Parente [83], to make automated or semi-automated approaches useful for practitioners, the results of automation must be turned into requirements analytics tools built for use by human analysts. As such, Kifetew et al. [92] informed that these approaches support the decision-making of a software development team regarding requirements.

Insight #34:

User feedback analysis has become an additional elicitation technique and new approaches to analyze user feedback are required to scale with the crowd in SECO.

5.5 Threats to Credibility and Reliability

In contrast to quantitative studies, qualitative studies are more prone to threats to credibility than to validity [233]. The matters of validity and reliability in qualitative research rely on the meticulousness, thoroughness, and honesty employed by the researchers throughout the data collection and analysis procedures [313]. Thus, we outline the potential threats to external and internal credibility in the following.

Internal credibility refers to the credibility of interpretations and conclusions within the underlying setting or group [314]. When conducting interviews and transcriptions, we can incur risks when interpreting participants' responses according to our perspective instead of considering the participant's perspective. This threat is related to interpretative validity, which is a potential threat to the internal credibility of this study. To mitigate this threat, we defined an interview guide with clear and objective questions presented during the interviews, comprising all concepts related to these questions in the two studies. We also encouraged participants to reflect deeply on their answers.

External credibility refers to the degree to which the findings of a study can be generalized across different contexts [314]. The number and experience of interviewed participants are potential external threats to this study. To mitigate such threats, we followed the same strategy of other recent studies that conducted field studies with software developers [233, 256, 257, 258, 259]. These studies considered the recommendations of Guest et al. [235] on the fact that saturation in semi-structured interviews can be achieved with at least 12 interviews. In a recent study, Hennink and Kaiser [255] identified that saturation in qualitative studies can be reached within a narrow range of interviews (9–17 interviews). Hence, we conducted interviews until we reached saturation. In addition, we selected professionals with different backgrounds and experience in requirements management activities in SECO, which contributed to a more significant variety of

information with different perspectives.

5.6 Final Remarks

This chapter presented the state of practice of requirements management in SECO through three field studies. We better understand requirements management in SECO and investigated some findings from the literature reviews presented in Chapter 4 on the relationship between open innovation, CrowdRE, requirements management, and SECO. In the following chapter, we intend to contribute to this field by proposing a conceptual model for requirements management in SECO, facilitating a shared comprehension of the subject.

Chapter 6. A Conceptual Model for Requirements Management in Software Ecosystems

6.1 Introduction

This chapter presents SECO-RM, a conceptual model for requirements management in SECO. Our motivation for developing SECO-RM is to provide an understanding of several concepts and relationships of requirements management in SECO, enabling researchers and practitioners to discuss and create novel solutions and strategies for improving requirements management in this context.

This chapter is organized as follows: Section 6.2 presents our research method; Section 6.3 details the design of SECO-RM; Section 6.4 presents the results of the conceptual model evaluation and its final version; Section 6.5 depicts our main findings, perspectives for using the conceptual model, and implications of our this work; Section 6.6 lists the threats to the validity of this work and presents mitigation strategies; and, finally, Section 6.7 concludes presents the final remarks of this chapter.

6.2 Research Method

We followed the steps described in Figure 6.1 to build SECO-RM. The following subsections detail each step and sub-steps.

6.2.1 Step 1 - SECO-RM Design

We based this step on the theory-building framework proposed by Sjøberg et al. [315], which possess the sub-steps: (i) Step 2.1: Defining constructs (constructs are

Figure 6.1: Overview of the research method.

elements involved in a theory); (ii) Step 2.2: Defining propositions (propositions refer to the relationships among constructs); (iii) Step 2.3: Providing explanation (which provides the context and evidence for the propositions); and (iv) Step 2.4: Determining scope (in which the theory is valid).

6.2.1.1 Step 1.1: Defining Constructs

In Step 1.1, we examined the entire text of the 29 primary studies selected in our SMS to identify constructs, i.e., concepts associated with requirements management in SECO. After defining possible constructs, we analyzed the results of our tertiary study and field studies to verify the concepts' correspondence and also checked the work of Wouters et al. [316] to confirm SECO concepts. For example, we identified the *keystone* concept in the selected studies in the SMS. Next, we analyzed whether any field study interviewees had expressed it or any secondary study selected in our tertiary study had defined it. Additionally, we checked whether the meta-model of Wouters et al. [316] presented this concept. We reproduced this same process to other concepts. In some cases, there was no direct correspondence between the three studies, and what prevailed was the evidence identified in the literature. In the end, we identified a set of 57 concepts that we believed were constructs related to requirements management in SECO. The results of this step (i.e., the list of 57 concepts, their definitions, and studies used to identify them) are presented in Section 6.3, which concentrates all results of our research method.

6.2.1.2 Step 1.2: Defining Propositions

In Step 1.2, we described the SECO-RM propositions that are the relationships among their concepts [315]. Propositions can explain phenomena through the association among concepts and indicate how these concepts interact with each other [315]. According to Ferreira et al. [317], propositions are the essence of conceptual models. SECO-RM propositions describe a given fragment (the relationship among a subset of concepts) of the conceptual model and emerge from evidence extracted from primary studies of our SMS. We used propositions to better represent SECO-RM.

For instance, the proposition “*requirements management in SECO is based on a process that manages platform, products, and integration requirements*” (this is proposition 2 in Section 6.3) involves seven concepts (“*requirements management*”, “*software ecosystem*”, “*requirements management process*”, “*requirement, platform requirement*”, “*product requirement*”, and “*integration requirements*”). This proposition refers to the high-level categorization of the RE process in SECO [16]. Developing the propositions involved an intense discussion among the authors of this work until reaching a consensus. In the end, we defined seven propositions that together cover all 57 concepts identified in the previous step. To facilitate the visualization of our conceptual model, we also provided a diagrammatic representation using a UML class diagram. We presented the propositions and the diagrammatic representation of the conceptual model in Section 6.3.

6.2.1.3 Step 1.3: Providing Explanations

In Step 1.3, we provide evidence-based explanations from the literature for each of the SECO-RM propositions. For instance, for proposition 2, we provided the following explanation: “*There are product, integration, and platform requirements in SECO [188]. The most demands in a SECO are integration requirements involving data types exchanged and data dictionary [318]. The RE process in SECO should have three main focuses: the product, the platform, and the ecosystem (holistic view to identify integrations between products) [16]*”. Hence, the selected primary studies in our SMS are the key elements in such explanations. We presented the explanations for each proposition in Section 6.3.

6.2.1.4 Step 1.4: Determining Scope

In Step 1.4, we determined the conceptual model scope when supposing that SECO-RM is suitable for three types of SECO (PSECO, OSSECO, and hybrid) since the studies we conducted did not focus on a specific type of SECO.

6.2.2 Step 2 - SECO-RM Evaluation

This step evaluated whether the implemented solution to solve the problem (in our case, SECO-RM) meets the expected objectives [103]. We applied the Delphi method [319, 109] to evaluate the SECO-RM. The Delphi method uses an iterative process to reach an expert consensus to make decisions, evaluate, or conduct predictive research [320]. It involves collecting and analyzing data anonymously, as well as consulting several experts who can review their answers in different rounds until they reach a consensus [321].

Delphi studies contribute to evaluating RQ [322] and allow for the validation of propositions in scenarios that are not yet mature by leveraging experts' judgment [323]. In our study, we applied the Delphi method to evaluate the SECO-RM through judgment experts and obtain a consensus among them about understanding requirements management in SECO. To do so, we considered the steps presented by Olivero et al. [323], as described next.

6.2.2.1 Step 2.1: Planning the Evaluation

This step can be divided into the following activities: selecting subject, selecting experts, and statistical processing [323].

Selecting subject. A proper selection of the subject and the correct questionnaire design directly impact the quality of the results and the requirements to choose the experts [323]. This activity identifies research questions that define the purpose of the questionnaire and the development of the questionnaire itself. Hence, we defined two research questions that aim to evaluate SECO-RM:

- Delphi-RQ1: Do the experts (panelists) agree with the propositions presented for SECO-RM?

- Delphi-RQ2: Do the experts (panelists) agree that SECO-RM meets the criteria of ambiguity, explanatory power, parsimony, generality, and utility?

Based on the RQ, we defined the following purpose of the questionnaire: assess experts' agreement regarding the seven propositions of SECO-RM and compliance with the overall evaluation criteria presented by Sjøberg et al. [315]. Ferreira et al. [317] claimed that propositions can be used for evaluation purposes since they represent the entire conceptual model, i.e., the concepts, the association among them, and the diagrammatic representation of SECO-RM. According to Sjøberg et al. [315], the criteria ambiguity, explanatory power, parsimony, generality, and utility are the most relevant for evaluating empirically-based SE theories, as in the case of SECO-RM.

Regarding the questionnaire development, we divided it into three parts. Part I had five demographic questions to outline the experts' profiles. Part II comprised seven closed questions on the SECO-RM propositions, which experts could answer with “*I strongly agree*”, “*I agree*”, “*I neither agree nor disagree*”, “*I disagree*”, and “*I strongly disagree*”. Additionally, one optional open question for each proposition was available for additional contributions. We presented the SECO-RM propositions in Section 6.3. Part III had five closed questions related to the overall evaluation criteria of SECO-RM [315], which experts could answer with “*Yes*”, “*No*”, or “*Sometimes*” and five optional open questions associated with each closed question to additional comments. Table 6.1 presents the five closed questions of part III.

Table 6.1: Question-related to the set of five Sjøberg criteria [315].

ID	Question	Sjøberg criteria [315]
Cr1	Is the conceptual model free from ambiguities?	Ambiguity
Cr2	Are elements contained in the conceptual model understandable by the SECO and RE communities?	Explanatory power
Cr3	Was the conceptual model built with a minimum set of elements and relationships relevant for requirements management in SECO?	Parsimony
Cr4	Can the conceptual model include different scenarios regarding requirements management in software ecosystems?	Generality
Cr5	Do you think the conceptual model is useful for practice and/or theory?	Utility

We conducted a pilot to evaluate the questionnaire with three professionals with experience in requirements management and SECO to verify the questionnaire's clarity and effectiveness. The main suggestions obtained from carrying out the pilot were: (i) provide supplementary material with the definition of the areas of knowledge that are asked in Part I of the questionnaire; (ii) improve the quality

of the figures; (iii) add a note to explain the element of the conceptual model that represents the existence of other “*roles*” in SECO; and (iv) make the table that explains the UML representation of the relationships between elements also available in the supplementary material. After carrying out the pilot, we made the necessary adjustments, and the final version of the questionnaire is available in the supplementary material¹ (details in Appendix 9.5).

The questionnaire was available to the panel members using a Google Forms link. We did not disclose the panel’s composition and addressed all communications individually to ensure the anonymity of the study. We anonymized the results in each round’s report by eliminating references to panelist identities.

Selecting the experts. The selection of appropriate experts is essential to the success of the Delphi method, as it is directly related to the quality of the results generated [320, 322, 324]. However, selecting the appropriate participants is one of the most important challenges in Delphi studies [322]. There are no clear guidelines in the literature to define criteria to configure the profile of the most suitable participant [322]. Elements such as professional background, knowledge of the subject to be analyzed, and willingness to participate might be valid criteria to be a panel member [324]. Moreover, there is no consensus in the literature regarding the number of participants in a Delphi study [322]. Several works stated that most Delphi studies use a panel ranging from 15 to 20 members [320, 324, 325]. Torrecilla-Salinas et al. [324] recommended that the number of panelists be high enough to be representative and low sufficient to keep the process manageable.

As we aim to evaluate a conceptual model of requirements management in SECO (SECO-RM), the panel should ideally be composed of experts in both fields. However, finding people who are experts in both areas at the same time is not such an easy task. The community of researchers in SECO is not as large as in other more mature fields within SE area [12, 326]. This fact makes it difficult to find specialists who ideally fit this profile. For this reason, we followed the strategy used by Torrecilla-Salinas et al. [324] that designed a panel composed of experts in one of the fields involved in the evaluation with at least some theoretical knowledge about the other.

¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13369678>

We invite the experts between active members of the SECO and RE communities, members of the program committee, and organizers of SECO and RE-related conferences such as the International Workshop on Software Engineering for Systems-of-Systems and Software Ecosystems (SESoS)² and International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE Conference)³. We used convenience sampling based on being nearby as well as the availability of the experts [236]. Initially, we invited 50 experts to participate in this study, receiving a positive answer from 22 of them, who forwarded us answers during the different rounds of the method. Table 6.2 and 6.3 present the expert panel’s experience in requirements management and SECO. According to Alarabiat and Ramos [322], requesting the expert’s experience self-rating may be a suitable technique to identify participants with adequate expertise in the problem area of a Delphi study.

Table 6.2: Experience type of panel members.

Type of experience	Requirements management		Software ecosystems	
	Number of experts	%	Number of experts	%
Theoretical and practical	21	95.45%	18	81.81%
Only theoretical	1	4.55%	4	18.19%
No knowledge/No experience	0	0%	0	0%

Table 6.3: Experience level of panel members.

Degree of experience	Requirements management		Software ecosystems	
	Number of experts	%	Number of experts	%
Very high	10	45.45%	7	31.82%
High	8	36.37%	8	36.37%
Average	3	13.63%	3	13.63%
Low	1	4.55%	2	9.09%
Very low	0	0%	2	9.09%

Table 6.2 shows that all panel members possess theoretical experience in requirements management and SECO, with most having practical knowledge (95.45% and 81.81%, respectively). In turn, Table 6.3 presents a simple sum of the number of experts that marked their experience level in knowledge areas directly associated with SECO-RM (i.e., requirements management and SECO). For instance, considering the requirements management experience level, 10 participants informed that their level experience is “*Very high*”, eight informed “*High*” experience, and so on. The sum of each column related to the number of experts is 22, corresponding to the total of participants. In a broader view, we observe

²<http://www.sesos-wdes.icmc.usp.br/>

³<https://requirements-engineering.org/>

that most participants had “*Very high*” or “*High*” experience in requirements management or SECO.

Table 6.4 summarizes the experts’ work sectors. We identified that there is a balance between specialists who work exclusively in academia, exclusively in industry, and in both. Table 6.5 presents the academic degrees of the experts, revealing that 50% hold M.Sc. degrees, while the other 50% have Ph.D. We also highlight the geographical distribution of the panel, with experts coming from five different countries: Brazil, Canada, Germany, Netherlands, and Nicaragua. This geographical distribution provides different local interpretations of our conceptual model, bringing varied points of view to the panel. Hence, we believe that the expert panel of our Delphi study comprises a well-balanced group of people with suitable knowledge of two fields (requirements management and SECO), including practitioners with practical and theoretical experience.

Table 6.4: Type of work sector of the experts.

Type of work sector	Number of experts	%
Academy	8	36.36%
Industry	7	31.82%
Both academy and industry	7	31.82%

Table 6.5: Academic degree of the experts.

Academic degree	Number of experts	%
M.Sc.	11	50.0%
Ph.D	11	50.0%

Statistical processing. The statistical processing in Delphi studies includes defining the statistical approaches to analyze the experts’ responses in each Delphi round and defining the stopping conditions that determine when it is no longer necessary to launch additional rounds in a Delphi study [323]. Therefore, defining the statistical process before conducting the Delphi study prevents authors’ bias in determining the results.

Analysis of experts’ responses in each Delphi round aims to determine whether they have reached a consensus and identify response stability between successive rounds [323]. The consensus and the stability can be measured using several statistical approaches in Delphi studies [327, 328]. In our Delphi study, we applied descriptive analysis to analyze the consensus, Cronbach alpha [329] to measure the reliability of the questionnaire, and Kendall’s W [330] to measure the stability of

the responses among rounds.

Descriptive analysis measures data frequency distribution and central tendency [331]. We used the Likert scale 5-point and 3-point to measure the Delphi questionnaire items with values converted to numeric values. The 5-point scale was used where a more nuanced understanding of the panelists' opinions was needed (propositions), and the 3-point scale was applied where a simpler, more straightforward indication of agreement or disagreement sufficed (overall criteria), minimizing response fatigue and improving clarity. Hence, we calculated the median, mode, standard deviation (SD), interquartile range (IQR), and percentage of agreement and disagreement for each proposition or question related to the overall evaluation criteria. These values are often used as the basis of consensus assessment in Delphi studies [332]. In our Delphi study, such values helped us identify the experts' panel consensus and their agreement on each of the propositions and overall evaluation criteria.

IQR is often used to measure consensus in Delphi literature due to its robustness as a statistical measure [321, 333, 334]. IQR represents the distance between the 25th and 75th percentile values in opinions, with a smaller IQR indicating a larger consensus [335]. An IQR of less than 1 means that more than 50% of all opinions fall within one point on the five-point Likert scale, and an IQR of zero indicates that the experts are in complete agreement [320]. The median better measures the degree of panel support for each proposition or overall evaluation criteria. If it is high, we can conclude that the panel has a high level of agreement [332]. In turn, SD allows us to observe the dispersion of results, which is directly related to the IQR. An SD value of less than 1.5 indicates that the experts have reached a consensus [332].

Cronbach alpha measures a particular test's reliability level [336]. Torrecilla-Salinas et al. [324] explained that several works use the Cronbach alpha to determine the reliability of a questionnaire that includes Likert questions type. Its values range from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating better internal consistency among the questionnaire items [336]. Table 6.6 presents the interpretation recommendations for Cronbach's alpha values proposed by George and Mallery [337]. Several Delphi studies used this recommendation [323, 324, 338].

Kendall's' W is a statistical algorithm that measures the agreement among

Table 6.6: Cronbach’s alpha interpretation recommendations of George and Mallery [337].

Range of alpha	Meaning
> 0.9	Excellent
0.81 – 0.9	Good
0.71 – 0.8	Acceptable
0.61 – 0.7	Questionable
0.51 – 0.6	Poor
< 0.5	Unacceptable

several raters assessing a set of items [330]. The closer Kendall’s W to 1, the more similar the order of the sets of items is [330]. A high value of Kendall’s W can mean that experts apply the same standards when assessing the items [330]. We used Kendall’s W to calculate stability between two consecutive Delphi rounds. We calculate Kendall’s W for each item and then compute the general Kendall’s W by averaging Kendall’s W values for all items. Finally, we analyze the result to determine the level of stability between the rounds. According to Gisev et al. [339], the interpretation of Kendall’s W is often subjective. It may depend on the specific context of the Delphi study, including the number of experts, the nature of the items being rated, and the desired level of consensus. Table 6.7 shows the interpretation of Kendall’s W used by Gisev et al. [339] in the context of Delphi studies.

Table 6.7: Kendall’s W interpretation recommendations of Gisev et al. [339].

Range of Kendall’s W	Meaning
> 0.8	Almost perfect stability
0.61 – 0.8	Substantial stability
0.41 – 0.6	Moderate stability
0.2 – 0.4	Fair stability
< 0.2	Poor stability

Stopping conditions in Delphi studies can be reached by consensus, stability level, or when enough rounds have been conducted [323]. We defined the consensus based on IQR and SD as the stopping condition in our Delphi study, as in other Delphi studies [320, 321]. Therefore, we will consider that consensus has been reached in a round if the $IQR \leq 1$ and $SD \leq 1.5$. Furthermore, stability between Delphi rounds must be at least moderate according to the interpretation presented in Table 6.7. We also defined criteria for assessing the agreement or disagreement of experts for each proposition or overall evaluation criterion of the conceptual model according to the strategy of Olivero et al. [323]. This strategy defines that the experts agree with the propositions or overall evaluation criteria if more than 51% of experts gave it a score of 4 or 5.

6.2.2.2 Step 2.2: Conducting and Reporting Evaluation

This step comprises the following activities: first round, generating statistical data, and further rounds [323].

First round. It aims to introduce the questionnaire to the experts. According to Olivero et al. [323], there are two approaches to conducting the first round in Delphi studies: use a well-structured questionnaire or use a preliminary version for a test round. We chose the first alternative because we previously carried out a pilot with three practitioners with experience in requirements management in SECO, who helped us structure and review the questionnaire.

Generating statistical data. It analyzes and interprets experts' responses through previously defined statistical processing. Delphi study organizers produce an anonymous summary of the experts' panel opinion to determine if the Delphi method has reached a stopping condition [323].

Further rounds. It occurs as long as the Delphi study does not reach its stopping condition. In each round, Delphi study organizers send the experts the previous round summary containing statistical data with the expert's comments for each question in the study [323]. Based on this summary, the experts analyze the panel's general results and can modify or confirm their previous answers. Two or three rounds usually suffice to expert panel reach a consensus [323, 324].

6.2.2.3 Step 2.3: Determining Results and Conclusions

Once the stopping condition is met, a report is produced containing an analysis of the gathered information, and a Delphi study is finished.

6.3 SECO-RM Conceptual Model

This section introduces the first version of SECO-RM, composed of a diagrammatic representation, a glossary, and a set of propositions. Figure 6.2 presents SECO-RM in their representation through a UML class diagram with 57 concepts associated with requirements management in SECO and the relationships among them. Figure 6.3 depicts the UML elements we used to represent it. Table 6.8 presents the glossary that describes the 57 concepts related to requirements management in SECO.

Figure 6.2: First version of the conceptual model for requirements management in SECO.

	Represents an element "A" of the conceptual model.
	Represents a relationship between "A" and "B". The letter "R" represents the name of the relationship. The direction of the arrow represents the direction of the relationship.
	Represents that at least "M" instances of the element "A" have relationship with at least "X" instances of the element "B".
	Represents that exactly one instance of the element "A" has relationship with exactly one instance of the element "B".
	Represents that exactly one instance of the element "A" has relationship with at least "X" instances of the element "B".
	Represents an aggregation. "B" is part of "A".
	Represents that at least two instances of "B" are part of "A".
	Represents that one or more instances of "B" are part of one or more instances of "A".
	The arrow represents an inheritance. The elements "B" and "C" are subtypes of the element "A", which means that "B" and "C" inherit the properties of "A". However, "B" and "C" have particular properties.

Figure 6.3: UML elements used to represent SECO-RM.

Table 6.8: Concepts associated with requirements management in SECO.

Concept	Definition	Ref.
Activity	Action performed during the requirements management process in SECO with clearly defined objective, entry, and exit conditions.	[340]
Actor	Overlapping term for all legal entities in a SECO taking part in the ecosystem in some form.	[316]
Actors' relationship	Defines the valid relationships between actors in a SECO.	[59, 316]
Approach	Types of contribution identified in the SECO literature to manage requirements (i.e., methods, techniques, tools, and practices).	[169]
Artifact	Product created, used, or modified during the requirements management process in SECO.	[340]
Characteristic	Process elements (i.e., concepts/definitions, activities, actors' relationships, and artifacts) that differentiate requirements management in SECO from requirements management in traditional software development.	[105, 167, 168, 341]
Closed online communication channel	Online communication channels that enable fast responses for a restricted number of people and can speed up decision making in the requirements management in SECO.	[241]
Co-creation	Open innovation practice that refers to the contribution provided by the consumer to the requirements management process in SECO, allowing the consumer to actively contribute to designing, analyzing, controlling, and evaluating products and processes.	[243]
Collaboration	Open innovation practice that refers to the involvement of internal resources that extends to the integration of external resources to support requirements management in software ecosystems.	[243]
Collaborative	Characteristic of requirements management process in SECO that is carried out through a collaborative process where multiple actors suggest new requirements, contributing to new business models to support open RE.	[18, 19, 166]
Communication channel	Channels used to improve and maintain a project's or actor's presence in a SECO, as well as ensure that projects share knowledge at the ecosystem level with several actors distributed geographically.	[237]
Concept/definition	Characteristic of requirements management process in SECO related to the process's properties or their elements.	[167, 168]
Coopetition	Open innovation practice that refers to the combination of cooperation and competition among multiple actors involved in requirements management activities in SECO. It allows actors to collaborate in areas of mutual benefit while competing in areas where they wish to excel in the software market.	[249]
Crowdsourcing	Open innovation practice that refers to outsourcing processes or activities, traditionally carried out internally, to an indefinite, generally large group of people to support requirements management in SECO.	[243]

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Table 6.8 – Continued from previous page

Concept	Definition	Ref.
Customer immersion	Open innovation practice that refers to collaborative innovation, which focuses on the customer's experience of using products or services to support requirements management in SECO.	[243]
Decentralized	Characteristic of requirements management process in software ecosystems related to the participation of a growing set of geographically distributed multi-party actors belonging to different organizations.	[19, 166, 18]
Emergent requirements flow	Requirements flow resulting from local just-in-time RE activities and the open communication paradigm. It resembles the requirements practice in open-source projects where requirements emerge as informalisms (e.g., email and discussion forums).	[18, 199, 239]
Face-to-face communication channel	Communication channels that are rich in stimuli, i.e., enable the use of senses (auditory, visual, tactile, olfactory, and gustatory) in verbal and nonverbal activities in the requirements management activities in SECO.	[242]
Hackathon	Open innovation practice that refers to which refers to the holding of events with an element of competition, where participants work in teams over a short period to ideate, collaborate, design, rapidly prototype, test, iterate, and pitch their solutions to a determined challenge.	[245]
Hub	Role of an actor who owns the platform of a SECO.	[59, 316]
Hybrid software ecosystem	SECO that support both proprietary and open source contributions.	[45]
Informal	Characteristic of requirements management process in SECO related to the use of overlapping practices and open forums based on informalisms.	[18, 19, 81]
Integration requirements	Requirements generic and reusable among SECO partners that allow integration with a shared infrastructure. These requirements involve technical aspects such as database tables and mappings among systems, data dictionary, data types exchanged, and integration flows.	[188]
Keystone	Role of an actor who is responsible for creating and sharing value with all actors in a SECO.	[59, 316]
Method	Approach related to procedures, techniques, or ways of doing some activity related to the requirements management process in SECO.	[169]
Model	Approach related to representations or abstractions of the requirements management activities in SECO.	[169]
Niche player	Role of an actor in requiring the standard or platform technology provided by the hub to create business value in a SECO.	[316]
Open	Characteristic of requirements management process in SECO related to the opening provided by cross-domain and the use of innovation paradigm.	[2, 194, 195]
Open innovation practice	Practices that allow the use of external ideas as well as internal ideas in the requirements management activities in SECO.	[74]
Open online communication channel	Communication channels that facilitate information flows between the multiple actors in the requirements management activities in SECO, providing opportunities for 'just-in-time' RE.	[18, 239]
Open source	Open innovation practice that aims to reveal internal requirements or technologies without immediate financial rewards for indirect benefits to the company in a SECO.	[248]
Open source software ecosystem	SECO where contributions are typically open to the rest of the actors and the value typically refers to other than monetary compensations.	[45]
Outsourcing R&D	Open innovation practice that consists of research and development services hiring from other organizations to requirements management activities in SECO.	[246]
Platform	Central entity on which different actors can provide their products. Most of the time, the platform itself is a product that can be extended by apps or extensions produced by different actors in a SECO.	[316]
Platform requirements	Requirements related to development environment actors used to develop complementary products in SECO. These requirements involve technical aspects such as software libraries and content databases.	[188]
Practice	Approach related to a less prescriptive way of doing some activity related to the requirements management process in SECO.	[169]
Product	Software standard, hardware product, or software artifact that is part of a SECO.	[316]
Product requirements	Requirements necessary for the development of each of the multiple products developed in SECO. Product requirements must be intertwined and merged into a set of complementary features in a SECO.	[188]
Proprietary software ecosystem	SECO where value creation is based on proprietary contributions, typically protected by intellectual property management processes, and the value relates to monetary compensation.	[45]
Relationship	Interaction between actors that can determine the role of an actor in a SECO.	[316]
Requirement	Statements that translate or express a need and its associated constraints and conditions are to be considered for software development. In SECO, requirements are often jointly defined by the suppliers of the ecosystem rather than brainstormed by the stakeholders.	[19, 62]

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Table 6.8 – *Continued from previous page*

Concept	Definition	Ref.
Requirements change management	Requirements management process activity that deals with the requirements change from the multiple actors in SECO.	[28, 340]
Requirements communication	Requirements management process activity that deals with the communication of the needs from a given actor (customer) to another (supplier), which enables the latter to implement a solution that is accepted by the former in a SECO.	[18, 181]
Requirements flow	General information flows that introduce requirements to a SECO.	[239]
Requirements identification	Requirements management process activity that involves determining the needs of multiple actors in a SECO that must be met by the delivered artifact.	[184, 196, 342]
Requirements management	RE area that ensures that stakeholders' needs and expectations are continually monitored and evaluated to identify any changes or new requirements and that changes to requirements are appropriately managed and communicated to all relevant parties. In SECO, requirements emerge and propagate through the collaboration of multiple actors that are external, interdependent, and spread across several organizations.	[14, 62]
Requirements management process	Process performed throughout the software development lifecycle. In SECO, the requirements management process possesses specific approaches and characteristics and involves activities such as requirements identification, change management, communication, negotiation, prioritization, and traceability.	[14, 62]
Requirements negotiation	Requirements management process activity that involves discussion on the requirements conflict to have some compromise that will satisfy the participating stakeholders of a software project. In SECO, the multiple actors can have mismatching goals that need careful negotiation that establish an agreement of interests and intentions between multiple actors distributed globally.	[184, 186, 222]
Requirements prioritization	Requirements management process activity that deals with giving order or importance to requirements. In SECO, requirements prioritization can differ highly between the multiple actors because different stakeholders value different attributes when dealing with a requirement.	[5, 19, 343]
Requirements repository	Infrastructures where requirements are stored in SECO (i.e., issue trackers, mailing lists, and source code repositories).	[81]
Requirements traceability	Requirements management process activity that aims to establish and maintain the relationships between requirements and other project artifacts throughout the software development lifecycle. In SECO, requirements traceability is a significant activity to provide requirements changes.	[14, 344]
Role	Derivation of an actor's relationship with other actors in a SECO.	[316]
Software ecosystem	Software and actor interaction in relation to a common technological infrastructure that results in a set of contributions and directly or indirectly influences the ecosystem.	[45]
Strategic requirements flow	Requirements flow that considers business goals and global strategies, and it resembles traditional RE by focusing on a systematic analysis of business goals from stakeholders and their refinement to detailed requirements.	[18, 239]
Tool	Approach related to semi-automated or automated support for some technique, method, or model to support requirements management in SECO.	[169]
University research grants	Open innovation practice that consists of funding external research projects by researchers and scientists in universities to access external knowledge.	[247]
Venturing	Open innovation practice that aims to start up new companies drawing on internal knowledge and possibly also with finance, human capital, and other support services from their enterprise.	[246]

The seven propositions (P1 to P7) detail each portion of SECO-RM through the propositions themselves, the constructs involved (i.e., concepts contained in SECO-RM), and an explanation for each proposition grounded on studies from the literature. In the following sections, we detail each proposition.

6.3.1 Proposition 1 (P1) of the First Version of SECO-RM

- **Statement:** Multiple actors that may have one or more roles in software ecosystems, considering the type of software ecosystem, the products developed, and the platform's evolution, participate in requirements

management and influence other actors through power relations.

- **Concepts:** Requirements management, Software ecosystem, Actor, Relationship, Role, Niche player, Hub, Keystone, Platform, Product, Proprietary software ecosystem, Open source software ecosystem, Hybrid software ecosystem.
- **Explanation:** SECO are based on the collaboration of multiple actors [45]. Each actor can have one or more roles in a SECO [316]. These roles are grouped into two principal categories: hubs and niche players [59]. Requirements emerge and propagate through multiple actors' collaboration across a SECO [18, 186]. In SECO, it is necessary to consider the interaction of several actors to define requirements for their products and platforms [16, 198]. The multiple actors in a SECO are susceptible to power relations influencing requirements management activities [18]. However, the power relations are different in OSSECO and PSECO [258].

Figure 6.4: Diagrammatic representation of Proposition 1.

6.3.2 Proposition 2 (P2) of the First Version of SECO-RM

- **Statement:** Requirements management in software ecosystems is based on a process that manages platform, products, and integration requirements.
- **Concepts:** Requirements management, Requirements management process, Requirement, Platform requirement, Product requirement, Integration requirement.

- **Explanation:** There are product, integration, and platform requirements in SECO [188]. The most demands in a SECO are integration requirements involving data types exchanged and data dictionary [166]. The RE process in SECO should have three main focuses: the product, the platform, and the ecosystem (holistic view to identify integrations between products) [16].

Figure 6.5: Diagrammatic representation of Proposition 2.

6.3.3 Proposition 3 (P3) of the First Version of SECO-RM

- **Statement:** The requirements management process in software ecosystems has specific characteristics related to actor relationships', artifacts, concepts/definitions, and activities that differentiate it from traditional software development.
- **Concepts:** Requirements management process, Characteristic, Actor relationships', Artifact, Concepts/Definition, Activity, Informal, Decentralized, Open, Collaborative, Requirements identification, Requirements communication, Requirements prioritization, Requirements change management, Requirements negotiation, Requirements traceability.
- **Explanation:** Characteristics can be considered process elements [167, 168] and categorized as actors' relationships, artifacts, concepts/definitions or activities [341] of the requirements management in SECO. The requirements management process in SECO has specific multi-party actors' relationships from different organizations [18], requirements defined in several artifacts distributed in the ecosystem [81], concepts/definitions related to their openness [2], informality [18], collaboration [166], and decentralized [19] and activities related to requirements identification [5], change management [190],

communication [18], negotiation [186], prioritization [5], and traceability [14], which tend to differ from traditional software development.

Figure 6.6: UML representation of Proposition 3.

6.3.4 Proposition 4 (P4) of the First Version of SECO-RM

- **Statement:** The requirements management process in software ecosystems uses different support approaches such as methods, models, practices, and tools.
- **Concepts:** Requirements management process, Approach, Method, Model, Practice, Tool.
- **Explanation:** Approaches can be considered as the types of contributions of the published studies in SE [169, 170, 171]. The requirements management in SECO has been performed with the support of tools [16, 179, 183], models [81, 186, 198], methods [180, 193]; and practices [1].

Figure 6.7: UML representation of Proposition 4.

6.3.5 Proposition 5 (P5) of the First Version of SECO-RM

- **Statement:** The requirements management process in software ecosystems manages requirements that are not stored in a central repository but spread across different types of requirements artifacts, each with its own repository.
- **Concepts:** Requirements management process, Software ecosystem, Requirement, Repository, Artifact.
- **Explanation:** The requirements sharing in SECO must be expanded to multiple external actors [187], so there is often no central repository with requirements defined [19, 179]. Decentralized repositories (i.e., issue trackers, mailing lists, and source code repositories) store the requirements in SECO [81].

Figure 6.8: UML representation of Proposition 5.

6.3.6 Proposition 6 (P6) of the First Version of SECO-RM

- **Statement:** The requirements management process in software ecosystems manages requirements communicated in strategic and emergent requirements flows through several communication channels such as open online, closed online, and face-to-face communication channels.
- **Concepts:** Requirements management process, Software ecosystem, Requirement, Strategic requirements flow, Emergent requirements flow, Communication channel, Open online communication channel, closed online communication channel, Face-to-face communication channel, Face-to-face communication channel.
- **Explanation:** Requirements are largely introduced in SECO via two general information flows [18, 239]. The strategic requirements flow considers business goals and global strategies, while the emergent requirements flow results from local just-in-time RE activities and the open communication paradigm [18, 239]. Multi-party actors who are not responsible for the requirements but contribute to discussing them beyond organizational boundaries originate emergent requirements [186]. These requirements are communicated using multiple channels: online open, online closed, and face-to-face [183, 197].

Figure 6.9: UML representation of Proposition 6.

6.3.7 Proposition 7 (P7) of the First Version of SECO-RM

- **Statement:** Requirements management in software ecosystems uses open innovation practices.
- **Concepts:** Requirements management, Software ecosystem, Open innovation practice.
- **Explanation:** Requirements management in SECO is cross-domain and uses the open innovation paradigm [195]. Open innovation positively and negatively impacts requirements management in SECO [39]. The RE needs to consider the implicit changes in open innovation and adapt to this new context [203].

Figure 6.10: UML representation of Proposition 7.

6.4 SECO-RM Evaluation and Refinement

This section details the results of the SECO-RM evaluation that occurred through a Delphi study with 22 experts in requirements management and/or SECO providing their opinions. We carried out two rounds to reach a consensus among the experts. The study began in December 2023 [first round] and ended in April 2024 (second round). The study questions were measured using 3-point and 5-point Likert scales, later converted to numeric values to produce a statistical study of the results (Table 6.9).

Table 6.9: Likert scale interpretation.

5-points Likert scale	3-points Likert scales	Numeric value
I strongly agree	Yes	5
I agree	-	4
I neither agree nor disagree	Sometimes	3
I disagree	-	2
I strongly disagree	No	1

Inspired by the strategy of Olivero et al. [323], we defined two keywords to describe and summarize the decision of the expert panel: agreement and disagreement. We measured the agreement by calculating the percentage of experts who chose “*I strongly agree*”, “*I agree*”, or “*Yes*” to each proposition. Similarly, we measured the disagreement through the percentage of experts who chose “*I disagree*”, “*I strongly disagree*” or “*No*”. The following subsections describe the Delphi method execution round by round.

6.4.1 First Round

The first round of the Delphi study started in December 2023 and finished in February 2024. The experts evaluated the seven SECO-RM propositions and answered five questions related to the five criteria presented by Sjøberg et al. [315] for the overall evaluation of the model. We then carried out descriptive analyses of the responses related to the propositions and evaluation criteria, analyzed the reliability of the questionnaire, and presented conclusions for the round, as detailed next.

6.4.1.1 Evaluation of SECO-RM Propositions in the First Round

Table 6.10 presents the expert panel’s evaluation results for the SECO-RM propositions in the first round. It includes the median, mode, SD, IQR, and percentage of agreement and disagreement for each proposition.

Table 6.10: First-round results for SECO-RM propositions

Proposition	Median	Mode	SD	IQR	% Agreement		% Disagreement	
					Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
P1	4.5	5	0.67	1	50%	40.91%	0%	0%
P2	4	5	0.83	1	45.45%	40.91%	4.55%	0%
P3	5	5	1.02	1	54.55%	22.73%	9.09%	0%
P4	4	5	0.85	1.75	45.45%	27.27%	0%	0%
P5	4	4	1.06	0.75	27.27%	54.55%	9.09%	4.55%
P6	4	4	0.59	1	45.45%	50%	0%	0%
P7	4	5	1.22	2	31.82%	22.73%	13.64%	4.55%

In the first round, experts did not express strong disagreement with the SECO-RM propositions, except P5 and P7, receiving higher levels of disagreement. In addition, the experts' agreement on propositions seems to be high. Figure 6.11 presents the percentages of agreement and disagreement of the expert's panel about the SECO-RM propositions. We also highlight that the median and mode values were greater than 4 for all propositions, which means that “*I agree*” and “*I strongly agree*” were the options mostly selected by the experts.

Figure 6.11: Percentage of agreement and disagreement of the expert panel on SECO-RM propositions in the first round.

To identify the necessary adjustments to be made to SECO-RM, we conducted a qualitative analysis of the expert's responses to the open questions on propositions. We initially performed an open coding [116] to identify excerpts in these answers and create codes. Next, we used axial coding described by Charmaz [116] to group the codes into categories. The first author conducted the open and axial coding processes, and the other authors reviewed the codes and categories to ensure the reliability of the results. We organized the answers to the open questions, codes, and categories into a supplementary document ⁴ to track the results in several iterative cycles with discussions between the authors, always supported by the literature (details in Appendix 9.5). Table 6.11 presents examples of the coding process.

⁴<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13369678>

Table 6.11: Illustration of the coding process.

Excerpt on Proposition 1: “Multiple actors... participate in requirements management and ***may*** influence other actors through power relations”	
Code	Category
C1 - Multi-party actors can influence the requirements management and other actors in SECO.	Changes in SECO-RM (C)
Excerpt on Proposition 2: “Regarding integration requirements, I would like to be sure that it covers the process elements of a digital ecosystem (which do not only concern [technical] integration but money flow, asset flow, contract negotiation etc.)”	
Code	Category
NC5 - Integration requirements must cover digital ecosystems.	No changes in SECO-RM (NC)
Excerpt on Proposition 3: “The requirements management process in software ecosystems does indeed exhibit specific characteristics that differentiate it from traditional software development”	
Code	Category
R4 - SECO require approaches considering its specific characteristics and problems, such as those related to requirements management.	Reinforcement of the proposition (R)

As a result, we identified 30 codes related to the seven SECO-RM propositions. We categorized them according to the actions to be taken: R (Reinforcement of the proposition), NCh (No changes in SECO-RM), and Ch (Changes in SECO-RM). Eight codes reinforced the propositions (Table 6.12), eight did not require adjustments in the conceptual model as they would mischaracterize the propositions or were related to statements that conflict with the literature (Table 6.13), and 14 codes associated with adjustments to be made in the conceptual model (Table 6.14). We made simple adjustments to some propositions (P1, P2, P5, P6) and significant adjustments to others (P3, P4, P7). We deeply analyzed each change to improve the conceptual model.

Table 6.12: Codes associated with comments on SECO-RM propositions that reinforce (R) propositions in the first round.

Proposition	ID	Code	Reference
P1	R1	Influence is a type of power explored in SECO, which may be different according to the type of SECO.	[258, 345]
	R2	An actor can have one or more roles and influence other actors in a SECO.	[316]
P2	R3	There are product, platform and integration requirements in SECO.	[188]
P3	R4	SECO require approaches considering its specific characteristics and problems, such as those related to requirements management.	[45, 346]
P4	R5	Requirements management in SECO uses several approaches to deal with the SECO complexity.	[1]
P5	R6	Requirements are usually spread out over several requirements artifacts in SECO (each of them with its own repository).	[18, 19]
P6	R7	Multiple communication channels allow multi-party actors to share requirements in the SECO.	[237]
P7	R8	Requirements management in SECO can benefit from open innovation practices due to the inherent openness of SECO.	[2, 51, 179]

Table 6.13: Codes associated with comments on SECO-RM propositions that do not change (NCh) the conceptual model in the first round.

Proposition	ID	Code	Justification
P1	NCh1	Categorization of actor’s roles in SECO is incomplete.	An entity “...” represents the other roles in SECO. Additionally, a note associated with this entity explains it.
	NCh2	Keystone controls product in SECO.	Keystone is the role an actor takes when controlling the platform. In SECO, external actors can control products that are around the platform [316].
	NCh3	There must be a relationship between the concepts of actor and role.	An actor is associated with a role in SECO through the concept “ <i>Relationship</i> ” [316].
P2	NCh4	Integration requirements must cover digital ecosystems.	SECO-RM is limited to improving the understanding of requirements management in SECO.
	NCh5	It is necessary to include other types of requirements.	Product, integration, and platform requirements are the overall categories of requirements usually defined in SECO. [16, 188].
P3	NCh6	Requirements management in SECO is not different from that carried out in other software development contexts.	Requirements management in SECO has specific characteristics that differentiate it from other software development contexts [14, 18, 19].
P4	NCh7	It is necessary to include metrics/measures as requirements management approaches in SECO.	In SE, approaches usually refer to the methods, models, practices, and tools developed to support the software development processes [169, 170, 171].
P7	NCh8	Requirements management does not use open innovation.	Several works investigated open innovation in the requirements management context, including in SECO [118, 192, 204, 248].

Table 6.14: Codes associated with comments on SECO-RM propositions that change (Ch) the conceptual model in the first round.

Proposition	ID	Code	Action
P1	Ch1	Multi-party actors may influence the requirements management and other actors in SECO.	Add “ <i>may</i> ” in P1 and adjust the multiplicity.
	Ch2	Other social, technical, and business relations may influence requirements management in SECO.	Adjust P1 so that it is more comprehensive using only the term “ <i>influence</i> ”.
P2	Ch3	The definition of platform requirements is not clear.	Add the definition of platform requirements in the evidence for P2.
	Ch4	The definition of product requirements is not clear.	Add the definition of product requirements in the evidence for P2.
	Ch5	Actors must explicitly participate in requirements management in SECO.	Add the participation of multi-party actors in P3.
P3	Ch6	Requirements management in other software development contexts also can be collaborative and decentralized.	Present evidence of the characteristics that differentiate requirements management in SECO from that carried out in other software development contexts.
	Ch7	There are abstract concepts that need to be more specific to requirements management in SECO, such as “ <i>actor relationship</i> ”, “ <i>artifact</i> ”, “ <i>concept/definition</i> ”, and “ <i>activity</i> ”.	Better specify the concepts related to the characteristics of requirements management in SECO that differentiate it from that carried out in other software development contexts.
	Ch8	The relationship between requirements management in SECO and other RE activities is not detailed.	Clarify that a characteristic of requirements management in SECO is that its practices overlap with other cross-project RE activities in the ecosystem.
	Ch9	Requirements management in SECO can be centralized, depending on the type of SECO.	Remove the decentralized concept from P3.
P4	Ch10	There are abstract concepts that need to be more specific to requirements management in SECO, such as “ <i>method</i> ”, “ <i>model</i> ”, “ <i>practice</i> ” and “ <i>tool</i> ”.	Detail the specificity of the method, model, practice, and tool that support requirements management in SECO in P4.
P5	Ch11	There may be SECO with only one central requirements repository.	Add “ <i>may</i> ” in P5.

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Table 6.14 – Continued from previous page.

Proposition	ID	Code	Action
P6	Ch12	The use of multiple communication channels also occurs in other software development contexts.	Present more evidence about strategic and emergent requirements flows and highlight the role of multiple communication channels in SECO.
	Ch13	The communication channel concept is not clear.	Add communication channel definitions and examples in the evidence for P6.
P7	Ch14	Requirements management in SECO does not always use open innovation.	Modify the term “uses” to “benefits”.

6.4.1.2 Overall Evaluation of SECO-RM in the First Round

Table 6.15 presents the expert panel’s evaluation results for the questions regarding the overall evaluation of SECO-RM in the first round.

Table 6.15: First-round results for SECO-RM overall evaluation criteria [315].

Criteria	Median	Mode	SD	IQR	% Agreement	% Disagreement
Cr1	5	5	1.7	2	59.09%	22.73%
Cr2	5	5	1	0	86.36%	4.55%
Cr3	5	5	1.26	0	81.82%	9.09%
Cr4	5	5	1.18	2	63.64%	4.55%
Cr5	5	5	1.45	0	77.27%	13.64%

In the first round, experts also did not express strong disagreement about the achievement of overall evaluation criteria by the SECO-RM. The experts’ agreement appears to be high about the evaluation criteria. The median and mode value was 5 for all criteria, which means that “Yes” was the option selected by the experts the most. Only Cr1 (related to the utility) and Cr5 (related to the ambiguity) received higher levels of disagreement compared to others. Figure 6.12 presents the expert panel’s agreement and disagreement percentages.

To identify the necessary adjustments to SECO-RM, we also conducted a qualitative analysis of the expert’s responses to the open questions on overall evaluation criteria. As a result, we identified seven new codes, two related to no changes in SECO-RM (Table 6.16) and five related to changes in SECO-RM (Table 6.17). Moreover, we also identified codes previously related to the model’s propositions (Ch7, Ch8, Ch14).

Figure 6.12: Percentage of agreement and disagreement of the expert panel on overall evaluation criteria in the first round.

Table 6.16: Codes associated with comments on overall evaluation criteria that do not change the conceptual model in the first round.

Criteria	ID	Code	Justification
Cr1	NC9	Organize concepts related to characteristics at the same level.	The concepts were already organized at the same level.
Cr2	NC10	Tool is not an approach.	In SE, approaches usually refer to the methods, models, practices, and tools developed to support the software development processes [169, 170, 171].

6.4.1.3 Reliability Analysis in the First Round

We calculated Cronbach’s alpha for the reliability analysis using the “*psy*” package⁵ of R⁶. The value obtained was 0.7. According to George and Mallery [337], this Cronbach’s alpha value obtained indicates questionable reliability of the proposed questionnaire.

6.4.1.4 First Round Conclusions

As conclusions of the descriptive analysis of the propositions and overall evaluation criteria of SECO-RM in the first round, we identified that most experts indicated agreement with the conceptual model. However, two propositions (P4 and P7) and two overall evaluation criteria (C1 and C4) did not reach a consensus among experts. In other words, the stopping condition ($IQR \leq 1$ and $SD \leq 1.5$) defined previously was not reached (see Tables 6.10 and 6.15). Hence, considering the experts’ opinions

⁵<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=psy>

⁶<https://www.R-project.org/>

Table 6.17: Codes associated with comments on overall evaluation criteria that change the conceptual model in the first round.

Criteria	ID	Code	Action
Cr1, Cr2, Cr4	Ch15	The definition of keystone is not clear.	Add the definition of keystone in the evidence for Proposition 1.
Cr2, Cr3	Ch16	The definition of hub is not clear.	Add the definition of hub in the evidence for Proposition 1.
Cr1	Ch17	There are open innovation practices that are not directly related to requirements management in SECO.	Group more specific open innovation practices (e.g., hackathon and venturing) into more generic practices (e.g., collaboration, co-creation, and cooperation) to simplify the model.
Cr4	Ch18	The definition of scenarios in the Delphi questionnaire is not clear.	Change the question related to Cr4 in the Delphi questionnaire, adding scenario definition in the research context (different types of SECO).
Cr5	Ch19	The use of the model is not clear.	Change the question related to Cr5 in the Delphi questionnaire, adding explicitly the model purpose.

in the first round, we can state that there are still propositions and conceptual model elements to improve and/or clarify. Therefore, we concluded that our research requires a new Delphi round.

6.4.2 Intermediate Version of SECO-RM

We performed the following actions to create an intermediate version of SECO-RM: (i) we adjusted SECO-RM, considering the experts' recommendations (see Tables 6.14 and 6.17 for details); (ii) we rephrased the SECO-RM propositions, considering the adjusts performed; and (iii) we updated the glossary. Figure 6.13 presents the diagrammatic representation of the intermediate version of the SECO-RM after the modifications made based on the results of the first round. The model now contains 43 concepts and their relationships, all related to requirements management in SECO. Figure 6.13 also highlights (in gray) the changes performed in the model after its evaluation in the first round. All SECO-RM propositions were rephrased and are presented next.

6.4.2.1 Proposition 1 (P1) of the Intermediate Version of SECO-RM

- **Statement:** Multiple actors that may have one or more relationships that determine one or more roles in software ecosystems participate in requirements management and may influence other actors, considering the type of software ecosystem (proprietary, open source, or hybrid), the products developed, and the platform's evolution.

Figure 6.13: Intermediate version of the conceptual model for requirements management in SECO with refinements highlighted in gray after the first Delphi round.

- **Concepts:** Actor, Relationship, Role, Niche player, Hub, Keystone, Software ecosystem, Requirements management, Proprietary software ecosystem, Open source software ecosystem, Hybrid software ecosystem, Product, Platform
- **Explanation:** SECO are based on the collaboration of multi-party actors [45] where each actor can have one or more roles [316]. The relationship with other actors derives the role of an actor in a SECO [316]. In SECO, it is necessary to consider the interaction of several actors to define requirements for their products and platforms [16, 198]. Interaction between actors in SECO can lead to several relationships of influence that can affect the requirements management activities [18]. The influence of a social aspect is important in software development explored in SECO [345]. Influence is a type of power [166] that can differ in OSSECO and PSECO [258].

Figure 6.14: Diagrammatic representation of Proposition 1 after the first Delphi round.

6.4.2.2 Proposition 2 (P2) of the Intermediate Version of SECO-RM

- **Statement:** Requirements management in software ecosystems involves the participation of multiple actors and is based on a process that manages platform, product, and integration requirements.
- **Concepts:** Requirements management, Software ecosystem, Actor, Requirements management process, Platform requirement, Product requirement, Integration requirement.

- Explanation:** The RE process in SECO should have three main focuses: RE for the product, RE for the platform, and RE for the ecosystem, enabling a holistic view to identify integrations between products in the ecosystem [16]. Therefore, there are product, platform, and integration requirements in SECO [188]. Product requirements are related to a software standard, hardware product, or software artifact that is part of a SECO [316]. Platform requirements are the basis of a platform, a development environment actors use to develop complementary products in the ecosystem [189]. Integration requirements do not refer to feature specifications but are technical statements that establish the integration process in the ecosystem [188].

Figure 6.15: Diagrammatic representation of Proposition 2 after the first Delphi round.

6.4.2.3 Proposition 3 (P3) of the Intermediate Version of SECO-RM

- Statement:** The requirements management process in software ecosystems has specific characteristics that usually differentiate it from traditional software development, such as openness, multiple actors' relationships, activities impacted by other RE activities, and expanded requirements artifacts sharing.
- Concepts:** Requirements management process, Characteristic, Openness, Actors' relationships, Activity, Sharing requirements artifacts.
- Explanation:** SECO are, by nature, cross-domain and have inherent openness [194, 195]. Consequently, RE in this context must adapt to a more open context where requirements emerge and propagate through the different relationships of multi-party actors, possibly competing [2, 18,

19, 179, 186]. Moreover, RE activities as identification [5], negotiation [184, 186], prioritization [5, 192], and communication [18] overlaps with requirements management in SECO. These activities are complex in SECO, as they must consider shared objectives and relationships between multiple and spread actors across the ecosystem with different and sometimes conflicting expectations [18, 19, 192]. Finally, the requirements artifact sharing in SECO must be expanded to these actors through one or more requirements repositories (i.e., issue trackers, mailing lists, and source-code repositories) [19, 81, 187].

Figure 6.16: UML representation of Proposition 3 after the first Delphi round.

6.4.2.4 Proposition 4 (P4) of the Intermediate Version of SECO-RM

- Statement:** The requirements management process in software ecosystems uses support approaches that consider the software ecosystems' characteristics and usually differentiate it from traditional software development, such as actors influence analysis methods, models that benefit from openness, and use network theory, practices related to sharing requirements within and outside the ecosystem, and tools that allow community participation through several communication channels.
- Concepts:** Requirements management process, Approach, Method, Model, Practice, Tool.

- Explanation:** In SE, approaches usually refer to the methods, models, practices, and tools developed to support the software development processes [169, 170, 171]. The requirements management in SECO has been performed with the support of scalable methods that analyze multi-party actors' influence on the requirements implemented based on social network analysis [19, 180]. It also uses models to benefit openness based on network theory and the “*requirement value chain*” to analyze and design the requirements flow in a SECO [13, 181]. Moreover, requirements management in SECO uses collaborative practices and tools based on community participation to share requirements within and outside the ecosystem to support the requirements change [1].

Figure 6.17: UML representation of Proposition 4 after the first Delphi round.

6.4.2.5 Proposition 5 (P5) of the Intermediate Version of SECO-RM

- Statement:** The requirements management process in software ecosystems manages requirements that may be spread across different types of artifacts and stored in more than one requirements repository (i.e., issue trackers, mailing lists, and source code repositories).
- Concepts:** Requirements management process, Requirement, Artifact, Requirements repository.

- **Explanation:** The requirements sharing in software ecosystems must be expanded to multiple actors who may not belong to the same organization through one or more requirements repositories [187]. Hence, there is often no central repository with requirements defined [19, 192]. Usually, decentralized repositories (i.e., issue trackers, mailing lists, and source code repositories) store the requirements in software ecosystems [81]. Several artifacts may represent a requirement in a software ecosystem, often complementing each other to give a more complete picture, e.g., as an issue, in a mail thread, and/or as a prototype or a finished implementation [81].

Figure 6.18: UML representation of Proposition 5 after the first Delphi round.

6.4.2.6 Proposition 6 (P6) of the Intermediate Version of SECO-RM

- **Statement:** The requirements management process in software ecosystems manages requirements communicated by multi-party actors in strategic and emergent requirements flows through several communication channels (i.e., open online, closed online, and face-to-face).
- **Concepts:** Requirements management process, Requirement, Requirements flow, Strategic requirements flow, Emergent requirements flow.
- **Explanation:** Two general information flows largely introduce requirements in SECO: the strategic requirements flow and emergent requirements flow [18, 194, 239]. The strategic requirements flow systematically analyzes business goals from actors and their refinement to detailed requirements

[239]. Emergent requirements flow resembles the requirements practice in open source projects, where requirements emerge as “*informalisms*” [18]. Emergent requirements arise from multi-party actors who are not responsible for the requirements but contribute to discussing them across organizational boundaries in multiple communication channels [18, 186, 239]. The use of multiple communication channels improves and maintains these actors’ presence in an SECO and ensures they share knowledge at the ecosystem level [237]. The multi-party actors in a SECO often use open online (e.g., app store), closed online (e.g., emails), and face-to-face (e.g., technical visits) communication channels [18, 183, 197].

Figure 6.19: UML representation of Proposition 6 after the first Delphi round.

6.4.2.7 Proposition 7 (P7) of the Intermediate Version of SECO-RM

- **Statement:** Requirements management in software ecosystems can benefit from the use of open innovation practices.
- **Concepts:** Requirements management, Open innovation practice, Collaboration, Co-creation, Coopetition, Crowdsourcing, Customer Immersion.
- **Explanation:** SECO imply a shift from closed organizations and processes towards more open structures where external actors become increasingly

involved in the development [51]. External actors offer complementary products and services for the open (or semi-open) platforms in SECO [347]. One potential benefit of being a member of a SECO is the opportunity to exploit open innovation [51]. In SECO, the keystone has the unique opportunity to leverage open innovation through synergistic relationships with external actors who provide new requirements [2]. Therefore, RE can benefit from the implicit changes that open innovation offers in SECO and must adapt to this new context [203].

Figure 6.20: UML representation of Proposition 7 after the first Delphi round.

6.4.3 Second Round

The second round of the Delphi study started in March 2024 and finished in April 2024. This round aimed to clarify and refine the results obtained during the first round. We modified the Delphi questionnaire and sent this new version of the questionnaire and an anonymous report with aggregated results of the first round and all comments provided by the experts. After reading the report and analyzing the reformulated propositions, experts could maintain or modify their answers from the previous round. Only 19 of 22 experts participated in this round.

For experts who did not participate, we kept their first-round evaluation according to the strategy of Torrecilla-Salinas et al. [324].

6.4.3.1 Evaluation of SECO-RM Propositions in the Second Round

Table 6.18 presents the experts' evaluation results for the SECO-RM propositions in the second round. The experts' level of disagreement regarding most of the model's propositions decreased or remained the same as in the first round. The level of disagreement increased in only one proposition (P4). However, the level of disagreement ranged from 0% to 5.56%, which is not a significant increase. Figure 6.21 shows the percentages of agreement and disagreement of the panel of experts on the model's propositions in the second round.

Table 6.18: Second-round results for SECO-RM propositions

Proposition	Median	Mode	SD	IQR	% Agreement		% Disagreement	
					Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
P1	5	5	0.59	1	63.64%	31.82%	0%	0%
P2	5	5	0.5	1	59.09%	40.91%	0%	0%
P3	4.5	5	0.84	1	50%	36.36%	4.55%	0%
P4	4	4	0.96	1	40.91%	45.45%	0%	5.56%
P5	4	4	1.02	1	31.82%	50.00%	4.55%	4.55%
P6	4	5	0.72	1	45.45%	40.91%	0%	0%
P7	4	4	0.68	0.75	18.18%	54.55%	0%	0%

Figure 6.21: Percentage of agreement and disagreement of the expert panel on SECO-RM propositions in the second round.

The initial low disagreement from the first round and the clarifications provided by some other experts' comments might explain the reduction of disagreement. Moreover, the median and mode values remained above 4 for all propositions in the second round, meaning that “*I agree*” and “*I strongly agree*” remained the options most selected by experts. This result implies that the experts are convinced of the other panelists' arguments.

In the second round, the number of comments from experts decreased. Moreover, several of them were related to codes “*reinforce of proposition*” or “*no changes in SECO-RM*” previously defined in the first round as presented in the supplementary material⁷ (details in Appendix 9.5). Hence, we presented in this round only codes related to “*changes in SECO-RM*” (Table 6.19).

Table 6.19: Codes associated with comments on SECO-RM propositions that change (Ch) the conceptual model in the second round.

Proposition	ID	Code	Action
P3	Ch7	There are abstract concepts that need to be more specific to requirements management in SECO, such as “ <i>actor relationship</i> ”, “ <i>artifact</i> ”, “ <i>concept/definition</i> ”, and “ <i>activity</i> ”. [first round]	Better specify the concepts related to the characteristics of requirements management in SECO that differentiate it from that carried out in other software development contexts.
	Ch8	The relationship between requirements management in SECO and other RE activities is not detailed. [first round]	Clarify that a characteristic of requirements management in SECO is that its practices overlap with other cross-project RE activities in the ecosystem.
P4	Ch10	There are abstract concepts that need to be more specific to requirements management in SECO, such as “ <i>method</i> ”, “ <i>model</i> ”, “ <i>practice</i> ” and “ <i>tool</i> ”. [first round]	Better specify the concepts related to the approaches of requirements management in SECO that differentiate it from that carried out in other software development contexts.
P5	Ch23	Heterogeneity and integration between requirements repositories must be explicit.	Explain the heterogeneity and integration between requirements repositories in the evidence for P5.
P6	Ch25	The emergent requirements concept is not clear.	Better specify the concept of emergent requirements in the evidence for P6.

6.4.3.2 Overall Evaluation of SECO-RM in the Second Round

Table 6.20 presents the experts' evaluation results to the overall evaluation criteria of the model in the second round. The experts' level of disagreement regarding all overall evaluation criteria decreased or remained the same as in the first round. Figure 6.22 shows the percentages of agreement and disagreement of the panel of experts to the overall evaluation criteria in the second round. The median and mode values remained equal to 5 for all criteria in the second round, meaning that “*Yes*” remained the option most selected by experts.

⁷<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13369678>

Table 6.20: Second-round results for SECO-RM overall evaluation criteria [315].

Criteria	Median	Mode	SD	IQR	% Agreement	% Disagreement
Cr1	5	5	1.1	0	77.27%	4.55%
Cr2	5	5	0.85	0	95.45%	4.55%
Cr3	5	5	0.7	0	86.36%	0%
Cr4	5	5	0.85	0	95.45%	4.55%
Cr5	5	5	1.45	0	77.27%	13.64%

Figure 6.22: Percentage of agreement and disagreement of the expert panel on overall evaluation criteria in the second round.

We did not find comments related to changes in SECO-RM in the open questions on general evaluation criteria. We only found codes that were already identified in the first round, which were related to no changes in SECO-RM and the reinforcement of propositions. The second round coding process is available in the supplementary material⁸ (details in Appendix 9.5).

6.4.3.3 Reliability Analysis in the Second Round

The value obtained for Cronbach’s alpha in the second round was 0.71. Cronbach’s alpha value increased compared to the first round and continues to indicate acceptable reliability of the questionnaire [337].

6.4.3.4 Stability Analysis in the Second Round

We calculated Kendall’s W for the experts’ responses stability analysis between the first and second rounds using the “*psy*” package of R. The value obtained was

⁸<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13369678>

0.51. According to Gisev et al. [339], the value obtained indicates moderate stability between experts' responses in two Delphi rounds.

6.4.3.5 Second Round Conclusions

As a main conclusion of the second round, we can state that the experts' panel solved most of the uncertainties expressed in the first round. In this round, the descriptive analysis of the propositions and overall evaluation criteria of SECO-RM indicated that the experts' panel reached a consensus. In other words, the experts' panel responses achieved the stopping condition ($IQR \leq 1$ and $SD \leq 1.5$) defined in Section 6.2.2 (see Tables 6.18 and 6.20). Furthermore, the panel of experts agrees with all of the SECO-RM propositions and considers that the conceptual model met the general evaluation criteria proposed by Sjøberg et al. [315]. With consensus and a moderate level of stability reached, we concluded our research involving the Delphi method.

6.4.4 Final Version of SECO-RM

Figure 6.23 presents the diagrammatic representation of the final version of SECO-RM, containing 43 concepts and their relationships. The figure also highlights (in gray) the changes performed in the model after two evaluation Delphi rounds. Table 6.21 offers a definition for each concept (serving as a glossary of terms) and also lists references from the literature to support such definitions. The final version of the statement of SECO-RM propositions is presented in Table 6.22.

Figure 6.23: Final version of the conceptual model for requirements management in SECO (with refinements highlighted in gray after the evaluation).

Table 6.21: Definitions of the concepts contained in the conceptual model and associated with requirements management in SECO.

Concept	Definition	Ref.
Actor	Overlapping term for all legal entities in a SECO taking part in the ecosystem in some form.	[316]
Approach	Types of contribution identified in the SECO literature to manage requirements (i.e., methods, techniques, tools, and practices).	[169]
Artifact	Product created, used, or modified during the requirements management process in SECO.	[340]
Characteristic	Process elements (i.e., concepts/definitions, activities, actors' relationships, and artifacts) that differentiate requirements management in SECO from requirements management in traditional software development.	[167, 168, 341]
Closed online communication channel	Online communication channels that enable fast responses for a restricted number of people and can speed up decision making in the requirements management in SECO.	[241]
Co-creation	Open innovation practice that refers to the contribution provided by the consumer to the requirements management process in SECO, allowing the consumer to actively contribute to designing, analyzing, controlling, and evaluating products and processes.	[243]
Collaboration	Open innovation practice that refers to the involvement of internal resources that extends to the integration of external resources to support requirements management in SECO.	[243]
Collaborative practice	Approach related to a less prescriptive way of doing some collaborative activity related to the requirements management process in SECO.	[169]
Communication channel	Channels used to improve and maintain a project's or actor's presence in a software ecosystem, as well as ensure that projects share knowledge at the ecosystem level with several actors distributed geographically	[237]
Coopetition	Open innovation practice that refers to the combination of cooperation and competition among multi-party actors involved in requirements management activities in SECO. It allows actors to collaborate in areas of mutual benefit while competing in areas where they wish to excel in the software market.	[249]
Crowdsourcing	Open innovation practice that refers to outsourcing processes or activities, traditionally carried out internally, to an indefinite, generally large group of people to support requirements management in SECO.	[243]
Customer immersion	Open innovation practice that refers to collaborative innovation, which focuses on the customer's experience of using products or services to support requirements management in SECO.	[243]
Emergent requirements flow	Requirements flow resulting from local just-in-time RE activities and the open communication paradigm. It resembles the requirements practice in open source projects where requirements emerge as informalisms (e.g., email and discussion forums).	[18, 199, 239]
Expanded requirements sharing	Sharing requirements by cross-projects in SECO	[24]
Face-to-face communication channel	Communication channels that are rich in stimuli, i.e., enable the use of senses (auditory, visual, tactile, olfactory, and gustatory) in verbal and nonverbal activities in the requirements management activities in SECO.	[242]
Hub	Role of an actor who owns the platform of a SECO.	[59, 316]
Hybrid software ecosystem	SECO that support both proprietary and open source contributions	[45]
Integration requirements	Requirements generic and reusable among SECO partners that allow integration with a shared infrastructure. These requirements involve technical aspects such as database tables and mappings among systems, data dictionary, data types exchanged, and integration flows.	[188]
Keystone	Role of an actor who is responsible for creating and sharing value with all actors in a SECO.	[59, 316]
Model to benefit openness	Approach related to representations or abstractions of the requirements management activities that benefit openness in SECO.	[169]
Multi-party actors' relationship	Characteristic of the requirements management process in SECO that defines the valid relationships between multi-party actors.	[59, 316]
Niche player	Role of an actor in requiring the standard or platform technology provided by the hub to create business value in a SECO.	[316]
Open innovation practice	Practices that allow the use of external ideas as well as internal ideas in the requirements management activities in SECO.	[74]
Open online communication channel	Communication channels that facilitate information flows between the multi-party actors in the requirements management activities in SECO, providing opportunities for 'just-in-time' RE.	[18, 239]
Open source software ecosystem	SECO where contributions are typically open to the rest of the actors and the value typically refers to other than monetary compensations.	[45]

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Table 6.21 – Continued from previous page

Concept	Definition	Ref.
Openness	Characteristic of the requirements management process in SECO that increases innovation power in the information flows of SECO, supporting decentralized ways of facilitating the flow of requirements among stakeholders, similar to those found in open source projects.	[239]
Overlapping requirements engineering activity	Characteristic of the requirements management process in SECO that allows requirements management activities to overlap with other RE activities, including platform RE activities, product RE activities, and ecosystem RE activities.	[16, 18]
Platform	Central entity on which different actors can provide their products. Most of the time, the platform itself is a product that can be extended by apps or extensions produced by different actors in a software ecosystem.	[316]
Platform requirements	Requirements related to development environment actors used to develop complementary products in SECO. These requirements involve technical aspects such as software libraries and content databases.	[188]
Product	Software standard, hardware product, or software artifact that is part of a SECO.	[316]
Product requirements	Requirements necessary for the development of each of the multiple products developed in SECO. Product requirements must be intertwined and merged into a set of complementary features in a SECO.	[188]
Proprietary software ecosystem	SECO where value creation is based on proprietary contributions, typically protected by intellectual property management processes, and the value relates to monetary compensation.	[45]
Relationship	Interaction between actors that can determine the role of an actor in a SECO.	[316]
Requirement	Statements that translate or express a need and its associated constraints and conditions are to be considered for software development. In SECO, requirements are often jointly defined by the suppliers of the ecosystem rather than brainstormed by the stakeholders.	[19, 62]
Requirements flow	General information flows that introduce requirements to a SECO.	[239]
Requirements management	RE area that ensures that stakeholders' needs and expectations are continually monitored and evaluated to identify any changes or new requirements and that changes to requirements are appropriately managed and communicated to all relevant stakeholders. In SECO, requirements emerge and propagate through the collaboration of multi-party actors that are external, interdependent, and spread across several organizations.	[14, 62]
Requirements management process	Process performed throughout the software development lifecycle. In SECO, the requirements management process possesses specific approaches and characteristics and involves activities such as requirements identification, change management, communication, negotiation, prioritization, and traceability.	[62, 14]
Requirements repository	Infrastructures where requirements are stored in SECO (i.e., issue trackers, mailing lists, and source code repositories).	[81]
Role	Derivation of an actor's relationship with other actors in a SECO.	[316]
Scalable method	Approach related to procedures, techniques, or ways of doing some activity in a scalable way in the requirements management process in SECO.	[169]
Software ecosystem	Software and actor interaction in relation to a common technological infrastructure that results in a set of contributions and directly or indirectly influences the ecosystem.	[45]
Strategic requirements flow	Requirements flow that considers business goals and global strategies, and it resembles traditional RE by focusing on a systematic analysis of business goals from stakeholders and their refinement to detailed requirements.	[18, 239]
Tool based on community participation	Approach related to semi-automated or automated support for some technique, method, or model to support requirements management in SECO based on community participation.	[169]

Table 6.22: The final version of the statement of SECO-RM propositions.

Proposition	Statement
P1	Multi-party actors that may have one or more relationships that determine one or more roles (e.g., niche player, hub, and keystone) in software ecosystems participate in requirements management and may influence other actors, considering the type of software ecosystem (i.e., proprietary, open source, or hybrid), the products developed, and the platform's evolution.
P2	Requirements management in software ecosystems involves the participation of multi-party actors and is based on a process that manages platform, product, and integration requirements.
P3	The requirements management process in software ecosystems has specific characteristics that usually differentiate it from traditional software development, such as openness, multi-party actors' relationships, overlapping RE activities, and expanded requirements sharing.
P4	The requirements management process in software ecosystems comprises support approaches (i.e., scalable methods, models to benefit openness, collaborative practice, and Tools based on community participation) that must consider the characteristics of software ecosystems, differentiating it from that carried out in traditional software development.

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Table 6.22 – Continued from previous page

Proposition	Statement
P5	The requirements management process in software ecosystems manages requirements that may be spread across different types of artifacts and stored in more than one requirements repository (i.e., issue trackers, mailing lists, and source code repositories).
P6	The requirements management process in software ecosystems manages requirements communicated by multi-party actors in strategic and emergent requirements flows through several communication channels (i.e., open online, closed online, and face-to-face).
P7	Requirements management in software ecosystems can benefit from the use of open innovation practices.

6.5 Discussion

This section depicts our main findings and future perspectives on the use of SECO-RM.

6.5.1 Main Findings

SECO-RM building process was based on the execution of an SMS (Section 4.3) and a field study (Chapter 5), in addition to the analysis of a SECO meta-model [316]. Throughout this process, we gathered important observations and reflections on the requirements management in SECO, which we consolidated as a set of main findings. These findings help the SECO community identify and open new research directions regarding requirements management in SECO. The main findings are:

- Requirements management in SECO is a challenge:** Knauss et al. [18] claimed that SECO introduces complexity in requirements management, and studies published in recent decades have highlighted several challenges related to requirements management in SECO [183, 18, 198, 2]. In the literature (from our SMS) and in practice (from our field study with practitioners), we identified several reasons why requirements management in SECO is challenging. These reasons are related to: (i) the inherent openness of SECO; (ii) the interaction of multi-party actors across multiple organizational boundaries; (iii) the existence of emergent requirements flow; (iv) the relationship between platform, product, and integration requirements; (v) the storage of requirements in artifacts and repositories that can be spread across an ecosystem; and (vi) the requirements communication carried out through multiple channels. These reasons often refer to specific characteristics of requirements management in SECO that differentiate it from those performed

in other software development contexts. These characteristics are also the main findings of this work and are detailed later.

- **The inherent openness of SECO influences requirements management activities:** We noticed that it is necessary to consider the openness inherent to SECO [195] to better understand requirements management in this context. Therefore, requirements managers in SECO must have openness in mind [179], even in PSECO. An open platform is a prerequisite for a vibrant SECO [187]. Moreover, open interfaces are desirable, allowing for easier extensibility and integration in SECO [196, 198]. [17] Axelsson and Skoglund explained that SECO are based on an open environment and have a range of actors from different organizations, interacting around an open or semi-open platform, thriving among themselves cooperatively and competitively (“*coopetition*”). We also identified that several studies indicate that requirements management in SECO is open and can benefit from open innovation practices [2, 18, 39, 179, 192, 194, 195]. For example, Linåker and Wnuk [179] proposed a model that considers open innovation practices in the requirements management process in SECO.
- **Multi-party actors influence requirements management in SECO:** Better understanding the different roles that multi-party actors can have in a SECO helps to understand requirements management in this context. According to Wouters et al. [316], SECO consists of several actors, which can have one or multiple roles. Valença et al. [184] pointed out that the existence of multi-party actors introduces challenges to requirement management in SECO. Figalíst et al. [5] highlighted that coordination between multi-party actors in SECO could not be viewed similarly in large-scale, agile distributed teams because actors in a SECO do not belong to a single organization but to several organizations that share different and possibly competitive relationships (“*coopetition*”).
- **Requirements management in SECO must consider emergent requirements flow:** Emergent requirements are a reality in SECO and must be managed in this context. According to Knauss et al. [18], the complexity

and ever-changing nature of SECO results in several new requirements based on ecosystem trends and are defined as emergent requirements. They allow innovation and create a circular flow of requirements knowledge in SECO [2]. Emergent requirements originate users from consumers in the ecosystem in the ecosystem, who find new ways to use existing services [18, 192]. Moreover, new functionalities offered by external actors can generate emergent requirements [2]. However, it is difficult to map emergent requirements to specific actors, especially since they are generally transversal to several SECO actors [18].

- **Requirements management in SECO must manage product, platform and integration requirements:** The requirements management process at a keystone and its partners within a SECO often overlaps due to several user feedback channels available in the ecosystem. Johnson et al. [16] suggested that the RE process in SECO should have three main focuses: RE for the product, RE for the platform, and RE for the ecosystem. According to Damian et al. [2], two main sources of requirements knowledge exist for a SECO: users of keystone's core product and the external developers' products, and external developers, who are users of the platform itself. However, these two sources of requirements knowledge in SECO can often result in a large heterogeneous user base providing product, platform, and integration requirements across multiple channels that need to be managed [16].
- **Multiple repositories can store requirements in SECO:** We noticed that it is necessary to consider multiple requirements repositories in SECO to understand better requirements management in this context. According to Jansen et al. [187], the requirements sharing must be expanded with multi-party actors in SECO. Linåker and Wnuk [179] mentioned that there is often no central repository with requirements defined in SECO. Linåker et al. [81] claimed that decentralized repositories (i.e., issue trackers, mailing lists, and source code repositories) store the requirements in SECO. Moreover, several artifacts can represent a requirement, often complementing each other to give a complete picture [19, 81].
- **Requirements communication inside and outside SECO is fun-**

damental to requirements management: Requirements management in SECO must monitor multiple communication channels to identify requirements change and emergent requirements. According to Knauss et al. [18], the multiple actors in a SECO often use open online (e.g., app store, forums, and issue/bug trackers), closed online (e.g., emails and help desks), and face-to-face (e.g., product demonstrations and technical visits) communication channels. These communication channels are mainly used to improve and maintain a project's presence in a SECO and ensure that projects share knowledge at the ecosystem level with multi-party actors that possess different interests [237].

6.5.2 Perspectives for Using SECO-RM

Regarding the theoretical contributions, SECO-RM aggregates the long-term knowledge from the literature on requirement management in SECO. It enriches the SECO body of knowledge, providing a unified understanding of concepts and their relationships. Besides the diagrammatic representation of SECO-RM, a glossary of the associated concepts provides a unified and comprehensive description of each concept. Hence, we believe that the SECO community could benefit from this model and adopt it as a starting point for future research on requirements management in SECO.

SECO-RM contributes to the definition of practical strategies for requirements management in SECO and supports the development of tools and methods tailored to the challenges of SECO. It also contributes to the understanding of the dynamics of requirements management in SECO through: (i) identifying multi-party actors considering their influence in the developing strategies to manage requirements effectively; (ii) integrating OI practices that explore how requirements are sourced, selected, and integrated from external actors such as user communities and external developers; and (iii) understanding of how requirements emerge and evolve through emergent and strategic requirements flows in the ecosystem, considering ongoing interactions and feedback loops.

The integrating OI practices in SECO is related to identifying multi-party actors and understanding emergent and strategic requirements flow. Therefore, SECO-RM

supports the requirements sourcing by giving visibility to the requirements emergent flow and the use of the multiple communication channels by multi-party actors in SECO. It supports requirements selection by leveraging crowdsourcing techniques to assess and prioritize requirements based on contributions from the SECO community, helping to align requirements with ecosystem-wide needs. Additionally, SECO-RM emphasizes the integration of co-created and community-driven requirements, ensuring that requirements developed collaboratively with external actors, such as user communities and developers, are incorporated into the ecosystem.

Regarding the practical contributions, SECO-RM provides a holistic view of requirements management in SECO to professionals, as it comprises key concepts, definitions, and relationships. This view supports professionals in their requirements management activities in different SECO types. For instance, SECO-RM shows that requirements management in SECO should consider the strategic and emergent requirements flows, which can be adapted according to the SECO type. In proprietary SECO, SECO-RM can support structured requirements management processes with defined roles and workflows. In open source SECO, it can emphasize emergent flows driven by community contributions through collaborative practices, such as co-creation, to facilitate external contributions. Finally, in hybrid SECO, SECO-RM offers flexible concepts that blend closed and open practices to manage requirements as in mobile SECO. Another example is that SECO-RM provides an overview of the benefit of practices already used by professionals in requirements management in different SECO types, such as collaboration and competition in the context of OI, supporting requirements management strategies that fit the specific characteristics of proprietary, open source, and hybrid SECO.

SECO-RM can also serve as a practical tool for increasing the SECO multi-party actors' knowledge regarding requirements management in a complex field where empirical evidence may be limited. It can clarify the meaning of ambiguous terms, avoiding problems with different interpretations of the terms and concepts. Practitioners can use SECO-RM as a starting point to assess and refine requirements management practices in an SECO, ensuring that elements, such as multi-actor roles, integration requirements, and communication channels, are adequately addressed.

Furthermore, SECO-RM propositions offer a structure that can guide SECO design or re-evaluation of requirements management practices without prescribing mandatory actions.

6.6 Threats to Validity

This section discusses the threats to validity identified in this study. We recognize that this process is susceptible to several threats to validity, such as any process that uses a research method. Next, we present these threats according to the classification suggested by Wohlin et al. [348] (construct validity, internal validity, external validity, and reliability) and discuss how we mitigated them.

6.6.1 Construct Validity

Construct validity refers to the connection between a theory behind an investigation and its observations [348]. It is related to obtaining the correct measures for the concept studied.

To mitigate threats to construct validity in the SECO-RM design, such as the possibility of not identifying some concepts, we performed the following strategy: (i) we reanalyze the open coding process performed in the studies that grounded our conceptual model; and (ii) we carried out several rounds of discussion with advisors of this PhD thesis. This process helped us in the identification of the concepts and relationships among them. To mitigate threats related to construct validity in the SECO-RM evaluation, such as the inadequate design of the questionnaire, bias in expert selection, and overreliance on expert opinions, we performed a Delphi study with the following strategy: (i) we carried out a pilot to tune the questionnaire and reduce the ambiguities in the questions; (ii) we carefully selected experts based on their expertise, experience, and relevance to the study topic and ensured a diverse panel of experts representing different perspectives and backgrounds; (iii) we anonymized responses to reduce bias; and (iv) we supplemented expert opinions with empirical data whenever possible.

6.6.2 Internal Validity

Internal validity refers to uncontrolled factors that may affect the study results [348]. It consists of the results' equivalence with the reality or the degree to which the study minimizes bias.

To mitigate threats to internal validity in the entire process of building SECO-RM, such as the possibility of bias in the execution of the studies that grounded our conceptual model and in its design and evaluation, we carried out the following strategy: (i) we previously defined research protocols to all the studies that grounded our conceptual model and to our Delphi study; (ii) we carried out pilots to ensure the clarity of research instruments; and (iii) we provided references and definitions on requirements management in SECO and detailed instructions in the interviews and during the model evaluation.

6.6.3 External Validity

External validity refers to the capacity to generalize the results to other contexts, populations, or settings beyond those directly examined in the study [348]. It addresses whether the results obtained in a particular context hold in other situations or with other groups of people.

To mitigate threats to external validity in the entire process of building SECO-RM, such as the existence of non-representative samples of studies and participants in the conducted studies, we performed the following strategy: (i) we employ a search strategy to identify relevant studies; (ii) we used the convenience sampling to ensure diversity and representativeness in the sample; (iii) we considered the saturation as a criterion for sample size, ensuring that data collection continues until no new themes or insights emerge; and (iv) we carefully documented contextual factors and providing transparent descriptions of procedures carried out.

6.6.4 Reliability

Reliability refers to the consistency and repeatability of measurements or observations obtained in a study [348]. This aspect concerns the extent to which the data and analysis depend on the specific researchers.

To mitigate threats to reliability in the entire process of building SECO-RM, such as bias in interpreting the explanations extracted from studies that grounded our conceptual model and experts' comments in the model evaluation through the Delphi study, we performed the following strategy: (i) we carried out several cycles of review and discussion of the propositions among the authors of these studies; (ii) we performed the open coding of data extruded of each study; and (iii) we previously defined stopping criteria from analyzing consensus among experts and stability between model evaluation rounds.

6.7 Final Remarks

This chapter presented SECO-RM, a conceptual model for requirements management in SECO that contains key concepts, its definitions and relationships, and a diagrammatic representation. The main purpose of this chapter was to improve the understanding of requirements management in SECO, contributing to the advancement of the SECO body of knowledge. After evaluating the SECO-RM through a Delphi study with experts, we obtained a version of the model aligned with the state-of-the-art literature and opinions from industry and academia.

SECO-RM can guide researchers and practitioners in understanding the complexities of requirements management in SECO. Moreover, it can provide deeper insights into the challenges and dynamics of SECO, facilitating the generation of new knowledge and the advancement of theory in this area. By organizing the knowledge of requirements management in SECO, SECO-RM puts together several issues or concerns that must still be researched, including the benefits of open innovation for requirements management in SECO and the impact of emergent requirements flows in this context. In the following chapter, we introduce the SECO-RCI method, which is the main contribution of this thesis. Throughout the chapter, we explain how the activities of the method were grounded in SECO-RM.

Chapter 7. A Method for Supporting Requirements Change Management in Software Ecosystems

7.1 Introduction

This chapter presents SECO-RCI, a method to support requirements change identification in SECO, which is the main contribution of this thesis. In this chapter, we provide detailed information about the steps and activities of the method.

The chapter is organized as follows: Section 7.2 presents some fundamental observations of the research to support our proposal; Section 7.3 provides an overview of the method, explaining its objective and implications for SECO; Section 7.4 explain the activities of SECO-RCI; and, finally, Section 7.6 presents the final remarks.

7.2 Observations

The research cycles allowed us to outline the proposal presented in this thesis, a method¹ to assist professionals in requirements change identification in SECO based on open innovation and CrowdRE. Before proceeding with method's presentation, we highlight the main observations from our previous investigations that form the foundation of our proposal:

- **Observation #1 (related to Insights 1, 3, 5, 7, 11, 12, 14, 20, 22, 23,**

¹A method is an approach to perform a software/systems development project based on a specific way of thinking, consisting of guidelines, rules, and heuristics [349, 350].

25, and 30): In SECO, the dynamic set of multi-party actors contributing different elements to the ecosystem introduces challenges for managing the several requirements [5, 17]. A keystone must consider interacting with several stakeholders to identify requirements change [18]. Therefore, traditional RE methods were reported as insufficient to support requirements change elicitation in SECO [18];

- **Observation #2 (related to Insights 3, 4, 6, 7, 9, 12, 14, 17, 20, and 21):** The complexity and changing nature of SECO result in requirements change that emerge from ecosystem trends, which make requirements management difficult [18]. Requirements change can introduce conflicts in a SECO and can be unexpected and disruptive [37]. Traditional approaches to centralized change control or change management (e.g., change dashboards and roadmaps) break with the dynamic and distributed nature of SECO [37]. Furthermore, traditional tools for analyzing the impact of change face challenges due to the scale and openness of SECO [37];
- **Observation #3 (related to Insights 11, 16, 17, 19, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, and 34):** User feedback is an important resource in modern software development, such as in SECO, often containing requirements and requirements change that help address user concerns and desires for one or more software products [93]. User feedback from a distinct crowd helps several SECO actors to make decisions and prioritize their actions. However, in SECO, distinct crowds of users provide requirements, request requirements change, and report bugs through several feedback channels [3, 16]. Hence, meeting multi-party users' expectations in SECO requires new approaches that engage these distinct crowds of actors in RE activities [41]; Moreover, analyzing this feedback is an approach to mitigate the challenge of growing a sustainable and healthy ecosystem [251];
- **Observation #4 (related to Insights 13, 24, and 27):** Requirements management in SECO manages requirements that may be spread across different types of artifacts and stored in more than one requirements repository. Decentralized repositories (i.e., issue trackers, mailing lists, and source code

repositories) usually store the requirements in SECO and several artifacts can represent a requirement, often complementing each other to give a complete picture, i.e., as an issue, in a mail thread, and/or as a prototype or a finished implementation [81];

- **Observation #5 (related to Insight 9 and 25):** Emergent requirements make requirements management difficult in SECO [18]. Multi-party actors who are not responsible for the requirements but contribute to discussing them beyond organizational boundaries originate emergent requirements in SECO [186]. Emergent requirements allow keystone to innovate further to grow platform offerings, creating a circular flow of requirements knowledge [2]. It is difficult to map emergent requirements to specific actors, especially since they are generally transversal to several SECO actors [18];
- **Observation #6 (related to Insights 2, 6, 8, 15, 23, 26, and 28):** Requirements management in SECO is usually open, cross-domain, and uses the open innovation paradigm [2, 18, 195]. Requirements managers must consider external and interdependent stakeholders in SECO [2]. Implementing external requirements helps continuously to create more value for products and services in SECO [39]. Therefore, open innovation positively impacts requirements change management in SECO [39], i.e., requirements change management can benefit from open innovation in SECO [179];
- **Observation #7 (related to Insights 10, 17, 18, 25, 27, 30, 33, and 34):** Requirements change emerge and propagate through multiple actors' collaboration across a SECO [18]. It is necessary to consider the interaction of several stakeholders to define requirements for products and platforms in SECO [198]. Feedback channels are resources that enable collaboration in SECO [108]. Open feedback channels allow transparent communication between developers and customers and are important for exploring RE practices in SECO [18].

Several methods are available for different requirements change management phases in different software development contexts. Lim and Finkelstein [94] proposed a method to anticipate change in the traditional software development context. It

separates requirements into layers that change at relatively different rates during requirements documentation. The results show that the method proposed by Lim and Finkelstein [94] accurately anticipates the relative volatility of the requirements. Jayatilleke and Lai [28] presented a method of requirements change analysis based on changes initiated at higher levels in the traditional software development context. It consists of analyzing the change using functions, identifying the change difficulty, and identifying the dependencies using a matrix. The results illustrate that the method proposed by Jayatilleke and Lai [28] contributes to the identification of conflicts and dependencies between requirement changes, allocation of priority to changes, and understanding of the difficulty of change.

Amaral and Franco Rosa [95] presented a method for assessing the potential impact of requirements changes of agile methodologies-based projects. This method consists of the use of requirement traceability and effort prediction on scope changes to benefit agile methodologies. The results illustrate that the method proposed by Amaral and Franco Rosa [95] provides a potential impact rate on scope changes in agile methodologies-based projects. Ali and Lai [31] presented a graph-based method for requirements change management in the GSD context. This method consists of understanding the changes required between different GSD sites to be established, performing a change analysis concerning the development work, which might be either directly or indirectly affected by the changes, and finalizing the changes that will be made between GSD sites. The results illustrate that the method proposed by Ali and Lai [31] facilitates stakeholders in managing requirements changes for GSD in comparison to the existing methods.

So far, our research has identified that requirements management have been explored in SECO. Previous studies that dealt with changes to requirements in SECO did not suggest any approach to dealing with requirements change in this context [37, 38]. Furthermore, these studies highlighted that more research is needed to investigate requirements change management in SECO. Our contribution introduces an open and dynamic perspective to requirements change identification in SECO. While several studies propose approaches for managing requirements change in several software development contexts, we are focused on requirements change identification in SECO, considering their nature and characteristics. We understand

that these methods can be used in SECO. However, they were not created considering SECO characteristics detailed in Chapter 2. To address this challenge, this thesis introduces SECO-RCI, a method to assist professionals in requirements change identification in SECO based on open innovation and CrowdRE.

7.3 SECO-RCI Method

SECO-RCI is a method for requirements change identification in SECO based on open innovation and CrowdRE. This method is based on open innovation because it considers user feedback from external actors across multiple user feedback channels for requirements change identification in SECO and the involvement of external actors that may belong to distinct crowds (SECO niche players) in the review of SECO requirements change requests. This method is based on CrowdRE because it considers user feedback from distinct crowds (SECO niche players) obtained in multiple user feedback channels through (semi-)automated approaches for requirements change identification in SECO and active involvement of the distinct crowds (SECO niche players) in the review of SECO requirements change requests defined based on user feedback obtained in multiple user feedback channels.

SECO-RCI considers characteristics (e.g., keystone, internal and external actors, a platform enabling external contributions, and openness) [53], offering a more reasonable approach to handling requirements change in this context. Creating open requirements management systems and constantly listening to user feedback is an important task to incorporate wishes from partners into SECO products or platform [1]. Improving user feedback gathering and analysis from distinct crowds is important in a SECO context [3]. Analyzing user feedback is an approach to support the growth of a sustainable and healthy ecosystem [251]. Several SECO actors rely on this user feedback to make decisions and prioritize their actions [3].

SECO-RCI was built using method engineering, which is the engineering discipline of designing, constructing, and adapting methods, techniques, and tools for the development of information systems [349]. SECO-RCI is visualized with the use of a process-deliverable diagram (PDD) [351]. PDD is an approach to method visualization that attempts to combine process and product elements [351]. This diagrammatic approach combines a UML Activity Diagram and a UML class

diagram [350]. With the use of PDD, a clear picture can be presented of the processes of the method and the corresponding outputs of these processes. The corresponding notation to PDD is shown in Figure 7.1.

Figure 7.1: Notation to PDD.

7.4 SECO-RCI Activities

SECO-RCI consists of five activities described in Table 7.1 and presented through a PDD in Figure 7.2. SECO-RCI summarizes the findings obtained from our SMS and field studies and contains the main activities, sub-activities, and concepts relevant to requirements change identification in SECO. Two roles are mapped in the SECO-RCI method: (i) SECO requirements manager, i.e., professionals involved in requirements management activities in SECO, and (ii) SECO niche players, i.e., actors who create value in a SECO.

7.4.1 Identify SECO Open Innovation Practices and SECO User Feedback Channels

This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to identify SECO open innovation practices (e.g., collaboration, co-creation and crowdsourcing) and SECO

Figure 7.2: PDD of SECO-RCI method.

Table 7.1: The five activities of the SECO-RCI method.

Activity	Optional?	Description
Identify SECO open innovation practices and SECO user feedback channels	No	This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to identify SECO open innovation practices and SECO user feedback channels, including those allowing open innovation practices.
Perform pattern detection in SECO user feedback channels based on CrowdRE	No	This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to create a CrowdRE environment for SECO requirements change identification through pattern detection in SECO user feedback channels.
Define SECO requirements change requests	No	This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to analyze pattern detection results, extract SECO requirements change requests, and list them in priority order.
Review SECO requirement change requests	Yes	This activity allows SECO niche players to review (i.e., analyze, vote, and prioritize) the SECO requirements change requests list.
Redefine SECO requirements change requests based on SECO niche players' review	Yes	This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to redefine the SECO requirements change requests list based on SECO niche players' reviews.

user feedback channels (e.g., user feedback channels related to the platform and SECO products). User feedback channels can enable several open innovation practices, ensuring that feedback from external actors and their users is also analyzed. Therefore, it is positioned as the first activity in the execution of the method, preventing SECO user feedback channels from being neglected. Figure 7.3 shows the first activity of SECO-RCI.

Figure 7.3: Detailed PDD of the first activity of SECO-RCI.

7.4.1.1 Analyze SECO Open Innovation Practices

This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to identify SECO open innovation practices. Moreover, it can support the discovery of external actors who can contribute to identifying emergent requirements or requirements change across several SECO user feedback channels.

- **Example:** *To exemplify the use of SECO-RCI, we selected the SECO of the Free Computer Park Management project (from the French Gestionnaire Libre de Parc Informatique - GLPI), available on GitHub. GLPI is an open*

source system aimed at asset and IT management. The organization of this project includes the GLPI system repository, libraries to facilitate interaction with the application programming interface (API) provided by the GLPI system, plugins, documentation, and artifacts that consolidate the GLPI system. GLPI-SECO applies several open innovation practices such as collaboration, co-creation, crowdsourcing, and customer immersion through its partnership program, as Figure 7.4 exemplifies.

Figure 7.4: Partnership program and partners of GLPI-SECO.

7.4.1.2 Identify SECO User Feedback Channels

This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to identify SECO user feedback channels, including those used by external actors and their users through open innovation practices. These SECO user feedback channels can be related to the SECO platform, API, and SECO products. Hence, the user feedback provided through these multiple user feedback channels can be valuable to requirements change identification in SECO.

- **Example:** *GLPI-SECO has several user feedback channels, including the official GLPI forum, Github, Telegram, LinkedIn Group, IRC, Discord, Teclib Partners, UserEcho, and Questionnaire. Figures 7.5, 7.6 and 7.7 present examples of some of these SECO user feedback channels.*

7.4.2 Perform Pattern Detection in SECO User Feedback Channels Based on CrowdRE

This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to create a CrowdRE environment for SECO requirements change identification through pattern detection

Figure 7.5: GLPI forum (a user feedback channel identified).

Figure 7.6: GLPI project on GitHub (a user feedback channel identified).

Figure 7.7: GLPI feedback questionnaire (a user feedback channel identified).

in SECO user feedback channels. This environment uses semi-automated approaches to gather and analyze user feedback from distinct crowds (i.e., SECO niche players) available on SECO user feedback channels. This activity also aims to perform pattern detection in SECO user feedback channels selected by the requirements manager. Figure 7.8 shows the second activity of SECO-RCI.

7.4.2.1 Create CrowdRE Environment

This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to create a CrowdRE environment for SECO requirements change identification, considering pattern detection between user feedback obtained in SECO user feedback channels. To do so, the SECO requirements manager must select the user feedback channels to

Figure 7.8: Detailed PDD of the second activity of SECO-RCI.

perform the pattern detection and define filters (e.g., by keywords or not).

- **Example:** *The GLPI-SECO requirements manager creates a CrowdRE environment for SECO requirements change identification, selecting the SECO user feedback channels GitHub and UserEcho and choosing the filter by keywords to pattern detection. The GLPI-SECO requirements manager defines “feature request” and “password” as keywords.*

7.4.2.2 Execute Pattern Detection in SECO User Feedback Channels

This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to execute pattern detection in selected SECO user feedback channels. Using data mining techniques and considering the defined filter, user feedback is obtained from selected SECO user feedback channels. After obtaining SECO user feedback, non-relevant content (links, too many spaces, HTML tags, codes, stop-words) is removed. Moreover, lemmatization is applied to the set of user feedback obtained to encompass more texts that contain the keywords. Lemmatization is a process of finding the base morphological form (lemma) of a word [352]. Finally, topic modeling is performed on the obtained SECO user feedback set. After topic generation, the similarity analysis is carried out between user feedback on the same topic, aiming to identify the most similar ones, including user feedback from different projects/products in a SECO. Hence, providing a holistic view to the SECO requirements manager about requirements change requests described in multiple SECO user feedback channels is possible.

- **Example:** *The GLPI-SECO requirements manager executes pattern detection*

using data mining techniques in the selected user feedback channels (GitHub and UserEcho), considering the keywords “feature request” and “password”. The similarity between user feedback on the same topic is calculated. Hence, if there is user feedback about “password changes” in different user feedback channels of the projects that coevolve in GLPI-SECO, they will probably be part of the same topic and have a high similarity index.

7.4.3 Define SECO Requirements Change Requests

This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to analyze the results of pattern detection in SECO user feedback channels, extract SECO requirements change requests, and list them in priority order. Figure 7.9 shows the third activity of SECO-RCI.

Figure 7.9: Detailed PDD of the third activity of SECO-RCI.

7.4.3.1 Analyze SECO User Feedback Patterns

This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to analyze pattern detection results. The SECO requirements manager must analyze each topic generated and verify the similarity between user feedback on the same topic.

- **Example:** *The GLPI-SECO requirements manager analyzes pattern detection results to the selected SECO user feedback channels (GitHub and UserEcho) and evaluates the similarity between a bunch of user feedback on the same topic. In this example, user feedback related to “password change” identified*

in different SECO user feedback channels (Figure 7.10) will probably be on the same topic and have a high similarity index.

Figure 7.10: Example of user feedback that can be identified in different SECO user feedback channels.

7.4.3.2 Extract SECO Requirements Change Requests

This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to extract SECO requirements change requests based on the pattern detection results in the selected SECO user feedback channels. The SECO requirements manager can register SECO requirements change requests and relate them with a bunch of user feedback that determines them.

- **Example:** *The GLPI-SECO requirements manager registers the SECO requirements change request “password change flow update” and relates it with a bunch of user feedback obtained in GitHub and UserEcho (see Figure 7.10).*

7.4.3.3 List SECO Requirements Change Requests

This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to list registered SECO requirements change requests, manage this list (update or delete SECO requirements

change requests from the list), and define a priority order for listed SECO requirements change requests.

- **Example:** *The GLPI-SECO requirements manager lists registered SECO requirements change requests, updates the SECO requirements change request “password change flow update” to “password change process update” and orders “password change process update” as the first in priority order.*

7.4.4 Review SECO Requirements Change Requests

This activity allows SECO niche players (distinct SECO crowds) to review the SECO requirements change requests registered by the SECO requirements manager. This review consists of analyzing SECO requirements change requests, voting on whether or not they agree with them, and prioritizing them according to their perspective. Figure 7.11 shows the fourth activity of SECO-RCI.

Figure 7.11: Detailed PDD of the fourth activity of SECO-RCI.

7.4.4.1 Analyze SECO Requirements Change Requests

This sub-activity allows niche players to analyze the SECO requirements change requests list registered by the SECO requirements manager. SECO niche players can view the SECO requirements change requests list and a bunch of user feedback related to each registered SECO requirements change request. This bunch of user feedback may have been obtained from different SECO user feedback channels, related to multiple projects that coevolve in a SECO, and provided by different SECO actors.

- **Example:** *A GLPI-SECO niche player views the SECO requirements change request list registered by the SECO GLPI requirements manager and analyzes the SECO requirements change request “password change process update”, viewing a bunch of user feedback related to it (see Figure 7.11).*

7.4.4.2 Vote on SECO Requirements Change Requests

This sub-activity allows niche players to vote on the registered SECO requirements change requests. After analyzing them, SECO niche players can vote whether they agree (or not) with these SECO requirements change requests.

- **Example:** *A GLPI-SECO niche player chooses the option “Yes” from the options “Yes”, “No”, and “I don’t know” for the SECO requirements change request “password change process update”.*

7.4.4.3 Prioritize SECO Requirements Change Requests

This sub-activity allows niche players to prioritize SECO requirement change requests they previously voted “Yes” to. SECO niche players can list these SECO requirements change requests in order of priority.

- **Example:** *A GLPI-SECO niche player that chose the option “Yes” for the SECO requirements change request “password change process update” defines it as the first in priority order.*

7.4.5 Redefine SECO Requirements Change Requests Based on SECO Niche Players’ Review

This activity allows the SECO requirements manager to redefine the SECO requirements change requests list based on SECO niche players’ reviews. This redefinition is not mandatory but enables the SECO requirements manager to analyze SECO niche players’ reviews, manage SECO requirements change requests, and list them again in priority order. Figure 7.12 shows the fifth activity of SECO-RCI.

Figure 7.12: Detailed PDD of the fifth activity of SECO-RCI.

7.4.5.1 Analyze SECO Niche Players' Review Results of SECO Requirements Change Requests

This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to analyze SECO niche players' review results. The SECO requirements manager can analyze the results regarding the agreement (or not) to the SECO requirements change requests list and the different perspectives of the prioritization.

- **Example:** *The GLPI-SECO requirements manager analyzes the results of voting to the SECO requirements change request “password change process update” and identifies that most SECO GLPI niche players agreed with the SECO requirements change request and that it has high priority according to different perspectives.*

7.4.5.2 Manage SECO Requirements Change Requests Based on Niche Players' Review

This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to manage (update and delete RCR of the RCR list) the SECO requirements change requests list based on SECO niche players' reviews.

- **Example:** *The GLPI-SECO requirements manager updates the requirements change request “password change process update” to “password change process update with multi-factor authentication” based on SECO niche players' review.*

7.4.5.3 List SECO Requirements Change Requests Based on Niche Players' Review

This sub-activity allows the SECO requirements manager to list SECO requirements change requests in priority order based on SECO niche players' reviews. The SECO requirements manager can reprioritize registered SECO requirements change requests due to possible updates in SECO requirements change requests based on SECO niche players' reviews.

- **Example:** *The GLPI-SECO requirements manager lists the requirements change request “password change process update with multi-factor authentication” and updates their priority order based on SECO niche players' voting, defining it as the second in priority order.*

As a final result, SECO-RCI generates a SECO requirements change requests list, which may have undergone two validations. The first validation occurs because requests are generated from data obtained from user feedback channels used by the distinct SECO crowds (e.g., niche players). The second validation occurs because these requests can be reviewed by the distinct SECO crowds (e.g., niche players).

7.5 SECO-RCR: A Tool for instantiate SECO-RCI

SECO-RCR² is a free and open source web tool licensed under the MIT license³. The code of the tool is available in the supplementary material⁴ (details in Appendix 9.5). The tool aims to assist requirements managers and developers engaged in SECO in managing requirements changes. SECO-RCR instantiates the SECO-RCI method, using repository mining, natural language processing techniques and machine learning to support requirements change management in SECO. The tool uses data mining on interaction platforms between the central organization, external developers and users.

²<https://ecos-2024.vercel.app/>

³<https://choosealicense.com/licenses/mit/>

⁴<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11432155>

7.5.1 SECO-RCR Architecture

SECO-RCR was divided into modules for greater maintainability and separation of responsibilities, aiming to adhere to key concepts of modern SE, such as cohesion and coupling [353]. To meet this purpose, the tool is architected from four modules, as shown in Figure 7.13. The database management system (DBMS) used was PostgreSQL⁵.

Figure 7.13: Tool architecture.

7.5.1.1 Mining Module

This module is responsible for collecting and processing data initially. It allocates interactions with external tools, such as data mining in GitHub repositories and sending emails. Currently, the module only provides mining from open GitHub repositories, obtaining data from issues contained in the platform and, based on the user's selection of a keyword filter or not, performing a filter on the data obtained. This module was developed in Javascript using the NodeJS framework.

⁵<https://www.postgresql.org/>

7.5.1.2 Topics Module

This module is responsible for applying machine learning techniques to the mined data. It performs topic modeling (using Top2Vec [354]), with the goal of grouping the issues filtered in the Mining module into clusters of related topics. The premise is that they likely refer to the same subject if the issues frequently use the same words, they likely refer to the same subject. Another purpose of topic generation applied to the process implemented in the tool is to make the analysis performed by the requirements manager less laborious, providing a more homogeneous view of issues that may deal with related subjects.

After generating the topics, a comparison is made between each issue and the other issues within the same topic to identify which issues exhibit the highest similarity. To compute the comparative similarity value, the issue texts are converted into numerical vectors (using Sentence Transformers [355]), which are compared through cosine similarity calculation (using Scikit-Learn [356]). Cosine similarity uses the angle between vectors as a metric, disregarding their magnitude [356]. Thus, texts of different lengths that address the same topic can still be considered similar.

In the subsequent analysis carried out by the requirements manager, the objective is to highlight which issues stand out within a specific topic. This approach summarizes the topic's content without the need for an additional model to generate a summary. Consequently, the issue with the highest similarity to others tends to represent a potential requirement change effectively. This module was developed in Python.

7.5.1.3 Server Module

This module is responsible for direct interactions with the database and user authentication. It also has automated routines for processing votes. It interacts directly with the other two modules that comprise the system logic (Mining and Topics). This module aims to receive requests related to registering, updating, or reading data from the tool, validate them, and execute them. This module was developed in Javascript using the NodeJS framework.

7.5.1.4 Client Module

This module is responsible for the interface to be used by the user, in addition to the interaction with the database via the Server Module and mining requests via the Mining module. It allocates the web interface with which the user interacts directly. This module was developed in Javascript using the React framework.

7.5.2 SECO-RCR Functionalities

This section outlines the main functionalities of the SECO-RCR. The tool provides a comprehensive environment where a requirements manager can mine issues from repositories, classify topics, and engage stakeholders in voting processes to identify and prioritize requirements change. A systematic view of the process adopted in the tool is presented in Figure 7.14 through a UML activity diagram. The two actor roles involved in the process are the SECO requirements manager and the crowd, a large heterogeneous user base providing requirements in various communication channels in SECO [16]. The details for each activity mapped in the tool are described next:

Figure 7.14: SECO-RCR tool activity diagram.

- **Create analysis environment for requirements changes in SECO:** This functionality enables the requirements manager, who is authenticated in the system, to create an analysis environment. In the context of the tool, an analysis environment is considered an SECO, representing a set of projects that co-evolve within the same ecosystem, following the definition by Lungu et al. [50]. To create an analysis environment, the manager must provide a name, description, and type of mining (either from repositories of a single GitHub organization or from different GitHub repositories) and determine if the mined issues will be filtered based on predefined keywords;
- **Request mining of SECO repositories:** Once the environment is created, the Mining module is triggered to collect issues from the GitHub repositories associated with the environment. After retrieval, a text cleaning process is applied to each issue, including: (i) removal of non-relevant content (e.g., links, excessive whitespace, HTML tags, code snippets, and stop-words) and common textual elements in GitHub issues (e.g., [], [x]); and (ii) conversion of text to lowercase. Suppose the requirements manager opts to apply keyword filtering. In that case, only issues containing at least one of the predefined keywords within their body or labels will be stored in the database (via the Server module) for further steps, while other issues will be discarded. To expand coverage, lemmatization (a process of reducing words to their base form, or lemma [357]) is applied to both the keywords and the issues;
- **Request mining result classification of a SECO:** After performing repository mining, the requirements manager is notified via email and directed to the tool to request topic generation. The Topics module is then activated to perform topic modeling for the specified environment. Once topics are generated, comparisons are made between issues within each topic to identify the most similar ones. This processed data is subsequently stored in the database via the Server module;
- **Analyze possible SECO requirements changes and propose a set of SECO requirements change requests:** Upon completion of topic generation, the requirements manager is notified via email and directed to

the tool to begin manual evaluation of generated topics and associated issues. This evaluation involves determining whether the issues within a topic and related issues form a requirements change request, as well as defining and describing the identified requirements change;

- **Consult the crowd on the definition of SECO requirements change requests:** If at least one requirements change request is identified during analysis, the requirements manager can initiate a crowd consultation process focused on the SECO requirements change request definition. The manager selects which requirements change requests will be included in the voting process and sets a voting deadline. A link for requirements change requests voting is generated upon selection;
- **Vote on SECO's requirements change requests definition:** Members of the SECO community (e.g., end users or external developers) receive the voting link for RCR definition sent by the requirements manager of the keystone via several SECO communication channels. Voters indicate their agreement (approve, reject, or express uncertainty) regarding each requirements change request and can also provide comments (a comment is mandatory for rejection). To submit their vote, voters must have a valid email with a confirmation code sent to verify their input;
- **Define SECO requirements change request set:** At the requirements change requests definition voting deadline, the tool processes votes and notifies the requirements manager via email. This notification prompts the manager to access the tool to finalize the requirements change requests set for prioritization. Requirements change requests may be modified during this process, and any changes are recorded in a modification history;
- **Consult the crowd on SECO requirements change requests prioritization:** Once the final requirements change requests set is defined, the requirements manager can initiate another crowd consultation process for requirements change requests prioritization. The manager sets a voting deadline, after which a link for prioritization voting is generated, and an email containing the voting link is sent to all participants of the initial voting process;

- **Vote on SECO requirements change requests prioritization:** Voters receive the prioritization voting link from the requirements manager of the central organization through several SECO communication channels or via email from the tool. They rank each requirements change request priority using a scale where lower values indicate higher priority. To submit their vote, voters must provide a valid email and a confirmation code must be sent via email for verification;
- **Define a prioritized set of SECO requirements change requests:** When the voting period for prioritizing requirements change requests concludes, the tool processes the submitted votes and notifies the requirements manager. The manager is then prompted to access the tool to finalize the prioritization process. A suggested prioritization derived from the crowd votes is presented. However, the manager may adjust the prioritization before concluding the analysis;
- **Export final set of SECO requirements change requests:** Upon completion of the analysis, the requirements manager obtains the finalized requirements change requests set, marking the closure of the environment. The manager can export the requirements change requests as a comma-separated values (.csv) file.

7.5.3 SECO-RCR Demonstration

SECO-RCR provides a simplified way of performing the SECO-RCI method without relying on highly specialized approaches. The tool is demonstrated in a document and explanatory video in the supplementary material⁶ (details in Appendix 9.5), providing an in-depth walkthrough of the tool's functionalities and usage.

7.6 Final Remarks

This chapter presented SECO-RCI, a method designed to assist professionals in requirements change identification in SECO based on open innovation and

⁶<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14056341>

CrowdRE. SECO-RCI is closely related to SECO-RM since the conceptual model serves as a foundational theoretical model that delves into the intricacies of requirements management in SECO, particularly focusing on how the open, dynamic, and distributed nature of SECO impacts requirements change identification. This chapter also presented SECO-RCR, a tool for instantiating the SECO-RCI method. In summary, some conceptual insights of SECO-RM are translated into real-world applicability through the SECO-RCI method and SECO-RCR tool, enabling professionals to enhance requirements management in SECO.

In the following chapter, we detail the SECO-RCI evaluation through a focus group of experts and a single case study in the context of an SECO of a global application-oriented research institute. We evaluated the method's usefulness and ease of use, critical factors for its success and adoption.

Chapter 8. Evaluation

8.1 Introduction

This chapter details the evaluation planning and the results obtained. To the best of our knowledge, no other approaches serve the same objectives as SECO-RCI for comparison purposes. Therefore, our evaluation focuses on the acceptance of the method. By doing so, we seek to understand how SECO-RCI is perceived by experts and used by professionals, gaining insights into its usefulness and ease of use. By gathering feedback and insights from experts and professionals, we aim to investigate the feasibility of SECO-RCI as a novel artifact to improve requirements change identification in SECO.

This chapter is organized as follows: Section 8.2 presents the planning of the two studies, including their objectives, participant selection, interview guide, description of the evaluation scenario, and screenshots of the tool we developed for the second study; the results of the first study are described in Section 8.3, while the results of the second study are presented in Section 8.4; Section 8.5 discusses the results, including the implications for researchers and practitioners; the threats and limitations of the studies are described in Section 8.6; and finally, Section 8.7 presents the final remarks of the chapter.

8.2 Planning

We conducted a focus group with experts and a single case study in the software industry to evaluate SECO-RCI. In the first study (*Study #1*), the method was introduced to the participants, followed by a group discussion to collect their perceptions of the method from an intuitive perspective. In the second study (*Study #2*), a participant employed SECO-RCI based on a realistic case of SECO.

Then, they exposed their opinions from a practical perspective.

For both evaluation studies, we developed a guide with questions and topics that must be addressed available in supplementary material¹ (details in Appendix 9.5). We defined primary questions that could be answered objectively using a Likert scale to capture a general perception from the participant about a specific aspect. Such closed-ended questions served as gateways to facilitate open-ended responses. Therefore, with each participant's response, we prompted follow-up with questions such as "*Why?*", "*Why do you think so?*", "*Can you elaborate on that?*" and others to continue gathering information as needed. This approach helps us to deep into the participants' thoughts, providing richer context and understanding beyond the initial response. Moreover, it encourages participants to reflect upon their answers, revealing additional insights [358].

Our interview guide included questions to evaluate the method's usefulness and ease of use. By doing so, we address important factors that play a significant role in the acceptance of the method. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) [359] inspired us to do so. TAM is a well-established information systems model that explains how users accept and use a particular technology. It declares that perceived usefulness and ease of use primarily influence technology acceptance. As Davis [359] explained, perceived usefulness is the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular technology will enhance their job performance. On the other hand, perceived ease of use is the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular technology will be free of effort. Even if an individual perceives a technology to be useful, its use could be hindered if perceived as too complex or requiring excessive effort.

8.2.1 Study #1

The first study's dynamic involved introducing the method to participants and detailing all their activities in a focus group to obtain expert feedback. Focus groups are qualitative research methods that use group interviews to collect information based on participant communication and interaction [360]. We decided to adopt the focus group method since it is an efficient empirical approach for obtaining rich

¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13730925>

qualitative insights and feedback from experts and practitioners [112]. This method facilitates the exchange of ideas and experiences between participants, allowing people to explore their knowledge and perceptions on a given topic within a limited period [360]. Moreover, it enables the researcher to focus specifically on the research topic and has been successfully adopted in SE research [360]. To set up the focus group, we followed the activities proposed in Kontio et al. [360]: definition of the problem to investigate, selection of participants, data collection, execution of focus group, and data analysis.

8.2.1.1 Definition of the Problem to Investigate

The focus group aims to gather perceptions about the SECO-RCI method from an intuitive perspective. The SECO-RCI method must be presented and demonstrated to participants. In the focus group, we focused on understanding participants' perceptions of the method's clarity and understandability, ease of use, usefulness, potential to reduce effort, completeness, intended use, and adaptability. These criteria help assess the method's feasibility for the intended users and their context according to experts' perspectives. By gathering expert opinions, the evaluation can capture their subjective experiences and perspectives, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement. This feedback is crucial in guiding enhancements and adjustments to increase its chances of successful adoption. Hence, we defined the following RQ to Study #1: *(FG-RQ) How is the acceptance of the SECO-RCI method among experts in the field?*

8.2.1.2 Selection of Participants

A focus group is sensitive to the experience and perspective of the participants. For this reason, the participant selection process is critical to its success [360]. We established the following participant selection criteria: (i) participants must have a PhD; (ii) participants must have experience in requirements management and SECO. We used convenience sampling to select participants for our study based on their being nearby and available [236]. We contacted experts in requirements management in SECO from our network via email and other communication channels (WhatsApp and LinkedIn). We sent invitations to seven experts, and five of them accepted to

participate in the focus group. According to Shull et al. [361], the size of a focus group can vary from 3 to 12 participants. Hennink and Kaiser [255] conducted a recent systematic literature review on sample sizes for saturation in qualitative research and identified that saturation can be reached within a narrow range of 4–8 participants in focus groups.

In summary, all participants have PhD in computer science and more than nine years of professional experience in requirements management and SECO. Moreover, three participants have practical experience dealing with requirements change in SECO. Table 8.1 presents the participants' profiles.

Table 8.1: SECO characteristics.

ID	Academic degree	Experience in years in requirements management	Experience in years in SECO
P1	PhD	15	14
P2	PhD	10	10
P3	PhD	20	9
P4	PhD	25	10
P5	PhD	20	14

8.2.1.3 Data Collection

In addition to the data collected during the focus group session, we used an electronic questionnaire for data collection² (details in Appendix 9.5). We defined primary questions that could be answered objectively using a Likert scale to capture a general perception from the participants about a specific aspect. We formulated seven statements for this study, using a 5-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Partially Agree, Neutral, Partially Disagree, and Strongly Disagree) to gather participants' perceptions of the SECO-RCI method. Then, we will encourage the participants to delve deep into their answers by asking follow-up questions to gain a more comprehensive understanding. Table 8.2 lists the statements of this study.

8.2.1.4 Execution of Focus Group

Considering the different regional locations of the participants, the focus group was carried out using Google Meet³ as a video conferencing tool. This tool provides greater flexibility in participation and allows adaptation of the schedules of those

²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13730925>

³<https://meet.google.com/>

Table 8.2: Study #1 Statements.

ID	Statement	Aspect	Description
S1	The method and its activities are easy to understand.	Clarity and understanding	It refers to how easily a participant can understand the method and how clear its activities and related outputs are to them.
S2	The method activities are easy to perform.	Ease of use	It refers to the degree to which a participant believes that using the method would be free from difficulty.
S3	The method is useful.	Usefulness	It refers to the degree to which a participant believes that using the method would produce desirable outcomes.
S4	Using this method would reduce the effort to requirements change identification in SECO.	Potential to reduce effort	It refers to the perception of how much the method can decrease the amount of work or effort required to accomplish a goal.
S5	All method activities are necessary and enough.	Completeness	It refers to having all necessary activities needed to achieve a goal.
S6	I will use this method if I have the opportunity.	Intention of use	It refers to the likelihood that a participant plans to use the method in the future.
S7	The method is adaptable to all SECO types	Adaptability	It refers to the degree to which the framework can be adjusted to different SECO types.

involved, making collaboration between all participants more viable, regardless of their different time zones. As a previous step to the execution of the focus group, we sent a file with the SECO-RCI method description to the participants a few days before holding the focus group.

The focus group was held in a 90-minute virtual session. In addition to the five participants, the author of this thesis was present to be the moderator of the focus group. The session was recorded with the permission of the participants⁴ (details in Appendix 9.5). The structure of the session was as follows: (i) introduction of the moderator and participants; (ii) clarification about the study context; (iii) presentation of study goal; (iv) presentation of the structure and content of the SECO-RCI method; (v) analysis of the use of the SECO-RCI method to identify requirement changes in SECO; and (vi) discussion related to statements presented in Table 8.2.

8.2.1.5 Data Analysis

In this focus group, we aimed to evaluate the method's acceptance among experts with theoretical and practical experience. We drew inspiration from TAM constructs to formulate the statements and perform a qualitative analysis. By doing so, we benefited from robust theoretical foundations enriched by years of research and empirical validation. This approach allows us to capture the participants' perceptions while benefiting from TAM's theoretical solid grounding. We will record

⁴<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13730925>

and transcribe the focus group for further analysis. We will employ open coding procedures to support the analysis of participants' responses. This systematic approach allows us to analyze the responses and identify common themes and patterns. Open coding offers a structured way to understand the raw data, enabling us to categorize the responses based on their key elements, contributing to a proper data interpretation [115].

8.2.2 Study #2

The second study's dynamic involved applying the SECO-RCI method in a real SECO to evaluate its acceptance from a practical perspective through a single case study. Case studies are one of the most common approaches used in the SE domain to artifact evaluation [113]. They are empirical investigations that examine a contemporary event in depth and within its context [362]. The case study design must comprise case study selection and preparation to provide generalizations for the results of the evaluation [98].

The single case study approach has been applied both in social science in general and in SE in particular [363]. Single case studies have been used previously in SE research as they provide more flexible procedures and patterns of working that allow the researcher to find out how different issues hold different significance and focus on research identification and interpretation [51, 364, 365, 366]. To set up the case study, we followed the activities proposed in Runeson and Höst [98]: case study context, study design, execution and data collection, and data analysis.

8.2.2.1 Case Study Context

The study was conducted at an application-oriented research institute in Europe. This institute collaborates with others to conduct research and development, aiming to turn original ideas into innovations that benefit society and strengthen the European economy. It consists of more than 70 research units and has over 28,000 employees. The institute specializes in defense and security, information and communication technology, life science, light and surfaces, materials and components, microelectronics, and production. Over 70% of the research projects are collaborations with the private sector or publicly funded commissioned research

projects. The remaining projects rely on public funds from governments.

This institute controls a SECO based on an open source platform for next-generation automation with projects related to asset administration shells. This SECO provides a free software platform that enables all interested parties, large and small industries, research institutes, academia, and interested persons to participate in and shape the fourth industrial revolution. It provides common and re-useable Industrie 4.0 components and hosts a multitude of software development kits (SDK) for different programming languages (e.g., Java, Python, .Net, and C++). This case is suitable for SECO-RCI evaluation because it presents a real SECO with multiple actors involved requesting requirements changes in different feedback channels.

Two professionals of the institute participated in this study: the head of the department responsible for this SECO and the SECO project manager. We selected them due to their expertise in the SECO. The department head has more than 15 years of experience, and the SECO project manager has more than five years of experience. The department head holds a PhD, and the project manager holds an M.Sc. The SECO project manager is responsible for managing requirements change and has a deeper and more practical understanding of the problems and challenges faced in the requirements change identification in this SECO, which allows for a richer and more detailed analysis of the results. Table 8.3 provides the background information about each participant.

ID	Academic degree	Experience	Current position
P1	PhD	5 - 10 years	Head of Department
P2	M.Sc.	5 - 10 years	Project Manager

Table 8.3: Study #2 - Participants' profile.

8.2.2.2 Study Design

This study aimed to analyze SECO-RCI's acceptance from a practical perspective. We revisited some aspects addressed in *Study #1* and introduced new aspects that only those who employed the method could evaluate. Specifically, our focus was to gather information from participants about their learning experiences while using the method, their perception of clarity and understanding, ease of use, usefulness, and impact on job performance. Hence, we defined the following RQ to Study #2:

(CS-RQ) Is SECO-RCI feasible from a practical perspective?

For this study, we developed a tool called SECO-RCR⁵ that provides a simplified way of performing the method activities without relying on highly specialized approaches demonstrated in the supplementary material⁶ (details in Appendix 9.5). We made this decision because implementing specialized approaches would require a level of knowledge and experience that the participants currently do not possess. By doing so, we ensured that participants could effectively engage with the method's concepts and activities without being hindered by a lack of prior knowledge. Moreover, this approach allows the participants to focus on understanding the fundamentals of the method and its potential benefits in improving requirements change identification in SECO, setting the basis for improvements. The dynamics of this study initially involved an understanding of the case (where the method would be applied) with the department head and training on the method and the tool with the SECO project manager. After the training, the SECO project manager performed the method activities. The SECO project manager employed the tool to perform the activities of the SECO-RCI method, considering their experience with the SECO described and their knowledge about it.

8.2.2.3 Execution and Data Collection

The data were collected from June 2024 to August 2024 and emerged from the semi-structured interviews. All the group communications and semi-structured interviews happened online. We used Google Meet as the video conferencing tool and an online questionnaire to support the data collection. The data collection process was divided into three steps:

- Step 1: carrying out a semi-structured interview with the head of the department to define the best strategy to apply SECO-RCI.
- Step 2: application of a questionnaire to identify the SECO project manager's first impressions regarding the method's application.
- Step 3: carrying out a semi-structured interview with the SECO project manager to verify SECO-RCI's acceptance from a practical perspective.

⁵<https://ecos-2024.vercel.app/>

⁶<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13730925>

For step 2, we formulated five statements for *Study #2*, using a 5-point Likert scale (*Strongly Agree, Partially Agree, Neutral, Partially Disagree, and Strongly Disagree*) to gather the first impression of the participants. Then, in Step 3, we encouraged the participants to deep into their answers by asking follow-up questions to gain a more comprehensive understanding. Table 5 lists the statements of *Study #2*.

ID	Statement	Aspect	Description
S8	I found the process of learning to use the method to be a positive experience.	Learning experience	It refers to the participant's process of gaining knowledge related to the use of the method and how intuitive the method is perceived.
S9	The method's purposes and activities were clear and understandable.	Clarity and understanding	It refers to how easily a participant can understand the method and how clear its activities and related outputs are to them.
S10	I found the method to be easy to use.	Ease of use	It refers to the degree to which a participant believes that using the method would be free from difficulty.
S11	This method would be useful in supporting me to do my job.	Usefulness	It refers to the degree to which a participant believes that using the method would produce desirable outcomes.
S12	Applying this method would allow me to perform my job more efficiently.	Impact on job performance	It refers to the degree to which a participant believes that using the method would improve job efficiency or allow them to accomplish tasks more quickly.

Table 8.4: Study #2 statements.

8.2.2.4 Data Analysis

We followed the same qualitative analysis strategy used in *Study #1* (Section 8.2.1.5). We recorded and transcribed the interviews to analyze the responses⁷ (details in Appendix 9.5). We provide the complete results of the execution of semi-structured interviews and the questionnaire application in Section 8.4. The results of our data analysis are discussed in Section 8.5.

8.3 Study #1 Results

We conducted this study with five experts and introduced them to the method. We then asked for their opinions. Figure 8.1 shows a summary of the responses from participants about the statements we provided in Table 8.2. In short, participants generally had a positive perception of SECO-RCI. The upcoming sections contain detailed information about the participants' responses.

⁷<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13730925>

Figure 8.1: *Study #1* - Participants' responses.

8.3.1 Clarity and Understanding (S1)

The majority of participants (4 out of 5) demonstrated consensus regarding the clarity and understanding of the prescriptive activities contained in the method. They attributed this perception to the sequential logic of the activities, in which the output of one activity seamlessly informs the next, contributing to an overall coherent method. P2 stated: *“the activities are clear and understanding”*.

According to some participants, aspects related to how the method is modeled (PDD diagram) and the presentation of scenarios for using the method can impact its clarity and understanding. P3 stated that: *“yes, the activities are clear, but I agree with [omitted] that perhaps the use of BPMN makes the method more intuitive”*. P2 dismissed that: *“for me, the activities are clear, but I am an expert on the subject. I believe that the scenarios that appeared later on could have already appeared since the introduction”*. However, some points of attention were also highlighted by the participants. P1 and P3 reiterated that while the activities were clear, the use of BPMN diagrams might enhance intuitiveness. P4 noted that collaborative aspects of requirements need further exploration, particularly in the context of when voting is presented.

8.3.2 Ease of Use (S2)

The majority of participants (4 out of 5) expressed a partial agreement on SECO-RCI's ease of use, indicating a moderate level of ease in performing the activities. P5 claimed that: *“the method is very systematic and intuitive. It is interesting to provide examples like you did because you make the method more operational, explaining how to use each of the steps”*. However, some experts raised key points of attention during the focus group discussion that were: (i) calculation of similarity between user feedback; (ii) bias related to prioritization by niche players from their perspective; (iii) provision of more examples of how method can be adopted in different SECO.

Participants acknowledged the potential complexity and challenges inherent in niche players' prioritization in SECO (part of activity four of the SECO-RCI). P2 stated that: *“it was not clear to me how to deal with the bias in the sub-activity of prioritizing requests for changes to requirements carried out by niche players?”*. P5 claimed that: *“it would be interesting to provide more ecosystem examples on how the method can be adopted. Present examples for very different types of ecosystems”*.

8.3.3 Usefulness (S3)

All participants agreed on the usefulness of SECO-RCI. P1 stated that: *“I think that the contribution of the method is also to show a landscape of requirements management in complex environments, in large environments, which are ecosystems, and to show how these things can happen or can be systematized, perhaps even with tools and practices that already exist”*. The experts recognized the method's capability to support the requirements change identification in SECO. In this regard, the use of open innovation practices and CrowdRE to base the method for identifying requirements changes in SECO was perceived as positive for its role in addressing the complexities that can arise in such environments. P3 stated that: *“regarding the use of open innovation and crowd, collective intelligence, I think it's fantastic, super interesting, I think it's necessary in SECO”*.

Participants appreciated the comprehensive view SECO-RCI offers, recognizing its potential to support requirements change identification in SECO. P1 stated that: *“I think you systematized many things in the method. I think that in some specific sit-*

uation, someone will want to use the method”. Moreover, participants acknowledged that SECO-RCI is a valuable artifact that describes activities that help identify changes to requirements considering the open and dynamic nature of SECO. In this regard, P5 stated: *“it is important to have levels of abstraction in relation to the identified requirements changes and the authority in relation to them in the ecosystem”*.

Participants also argued that applying SECO-RCI in a real context is necessary. P1 claimed that: *“I agree with the method’s motivation, but there is a large gap between finding motivation and proposing something for the real world. Ideally, you would instantiate the method in a real context, with things that already exist, for example. I know it’s difficult to find a large ecosystem to apply it, but there’s open source too. For example, you can analyze SECO projects using GitHub Discussion, where people discuss requirements and changes”*.

8.3.4 Potential to Reduce Effort (S4)

Most participants (3 out of 5) agreed that SECO-RCI has the potential to reduce the effort required for requirements identification in SECO. An argument is that using SECO-RCI can help to identify requirements change of distinct crowds of a SECO. P3 stated that: *“open innovation and CrowdRE expand the scope of requirement change identification, which is important in SECO. Using automated approaches such as in the proposed method will probably reduce effort”*. P5 claimed that: *“niche players have demands that they would certainly love that were implemented on the platform, but often the platform will evolve in another direction”*. However, some points of attention were raised by the participants. P3 mentioned a perceived lack of risk mapping in the method, stating: *I felt the absence of risk mapping*”. P4 expressed skepticism about whether effort reduction could be achieved across different industry domains, noting: *I am not sure if the effort can be reduced in the industry across any application domains*”.

8.3.5 Completeness (S5)

Two participants agreed that carrying out all activities is essential to achieving the method’s objectives, two were neutral, and one disagreed. Participants who

agreed highlighted that the method may or may not consult the crowd. In other words, it is possible to identify requirements changes through user feedback available in user feedback channels, and it is also possible to validate them through crowd consultation and identify new requirements changes. P2 stated that: *“the method’s activities allow the identification of changes considering multiple actors and multiple projects in the ecosystem”*.

Participants who were indifferent about this statement mentioned that applying the method in different types of SECO is necessary to confirm that the activities are sufficient. P3 claimed that: *“Initially, I think they are sufficient, but it would be relevant to analyze them in other SECO”*. P4 stated that: *“they are necessary, but I don’t know if they are sufficient, especially concerning SECO domains and the tools used by organizations”*. The participant who disagreed (P1) highlighted that: *“I wonder if there aren’t similar and less “bureaucratic” alternatives regarding activities. For example, in open source, the list of requirements is listed and voted on by participants. Currently, on Github Discussion, if a feature is identified in the discussion (forum – mining pattern), it can become an issue that needs to be resolved by the community without the need to go through all these steps. As my basis of comparison is research, I tend to disagree that all activities are necessary”*.

8.3.6 Intention of Use (S6)

All participants agreed that they could use SECO-RCI in future opportunities. They highlighted that SECO-RCI is based on concepts that are important for SECO in literature and practice due to its open and dynamic nature. This suggests that SECO-RCI has the potential to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. P2 highlighted that: *“the method helps someone in the role of manager to identify changes to SECO requirements. It is based on Crowd and open innovation which are useful in many projects in SECO”*.

Participants also suggested activities that could improve the intention to use the method. P3 suggested that: *“it would be relevant to consider in the method a consultation of already consolidated requirements from other similar SECO, success and failure cases of these SECO. Together with the collective intelligence that you obtain with CrowdRE, obtain knowledge of similar SECO that may bring requirements and*

compare these requirements with success or failure cases of this SECO, which is super important". P1 complemented P3 and commented that: *"the day-to-day practices of an ecosystem are very specific. I'll give you an example, GitHub launched a tool called GitHub Discussion to discuss changes to project requirements, but not even 5% of large GitHub repositories use it. Why? Because they manage requirements differently"*.

8.3.7 Adaptability (S7)

Two participants agreed that the SECO-RCI method is adaptable across different SECO types, two were neutral, and one disagreed. Participants who agreed recognized the potential adaptability of SECO-RCI's generic activities and acknowledged the method's ability to address common challenges in requirements change identification in SECO. In addition, they highlighted the method's potential to provide systematic guidance to requirements change identification in SECO. P3 stated that: *"the method is generic, and I believe it could be used in proprietary, open, and hybrid ecosystems"*.

There was a certain skepticism among some participants regarding the universal applicability of SECO-RCI in all SECO types. P1 stated that: *"being adaptable to all contexts is something very strong in my opinion. There probably must be a counterexample where the method will not be useful"*. P4 mentioned that: *"I have doubts regarding the diversity of application domains, experiences and cultures of organizations"*. P5 claimed that: *"the artifact with the method description does not provide examples of different instantiations of the method in different ecosystems (proprietary, open source, mobile, safety-critical domain etc.), so it is impossible to verify the method's adaptability"*.

8.3.8 How is the Acceptance of the SECO-RCI Method Among Experts in the Field? (RQ - Study #1)

The overall reception of SECO among participants suggests a positive panorama, particularly in terms of its ease of use, usefulness and intention of use. The clarity and understandability of the activities and benefits of potential effort reduction were also considered positive points of the method. A key insight from participant

feedback is that SECO-RCI provides a systematic approach to requirements change identification that considers specific characteristics of SECO and is based on important paradigms in this context, open innovation and CrowdRE.

8.4 Study #2 Results

Study #2 involved two professionals: the head of the department and the SECO project manager. The department head explained how the requirements change identification worked in SECO, and the SECO project manager applied the SECO-RCI method in a real case.

We conducted a semi-structured interview with the head of the department to understand better the case to be studied and identify details about the process of identifying changes to requirements in SECO from the department's perspective. Initially, we asked them how the process of requirements change identifications worked at the SECO for which they was responsible. The head of the department explained that: *“there is no uniform approach to identifying changes in requirements. Each project carries it out in its own way”*. They also highlighted that: *“it is the project managers and the product owner who identify changes and document them as assignments on GitHub. If a bug or issue is identified, a notification opens on GitHub”*. Furthermore, the head of the department stated that: *“there is a professional who deals with specific SECO changes. The evolution of SECO is treated as a project and has its own team, whose components are involved in some of SECO's other projects”*.

We then ask the department head what problems he identifies in this process. They highlighted the problem of the lack of a broad view of requirements change requests in SECO that emerge from different projects in multiple SECO communication channels. According to them, the keystone has difficulty visualizing the origin of SECO requirements change requests. The head of the department stated that: *“I have difficulty seeing where the ends are tied. I would like to see it in different degrees of detail. If I want to see this, I have to go one by one to check. As a manager, I have to trust what my project manager seniors say”*.

Finally, we asked the department head what could change in this process, considering the open and dynamic nature of SECO. They responded that: *“the*

degree of dependence I have on different people to have a central vision of SECO and visualize possible changes. Some automatization could improve this”.

The SECO project manager applied the SECO-RCI method to a real case, using a tool that supports the instantiation of the method. As mentioned in Section 8.2.2, the tool offers a method instantiation. After the SECO project manager received training on the SECO-RCI method and the tool, we request that they:

1. Create an environment for requirements change identification by adding at least two GitHub repositories of inter-projects of their SECO;
2. Perform pattern detection in issues from selected repositories for the registered environment;
3. Analyze the results of pattern detection to identify requirement change requests that may have been requested in the different selected user feedback channels;
4. Register requirements change requests for the SECO analyzed;
5. List requirements change requests in priority order;
6. Export the CSV file from the list of registered requirements change requests.

In this study, the participant executed all activities to identify requirements change using open innovation practices (i.e., considering user feedback of external actors in open user feedback channels to identify requirements change) and CrowdRE (i.e., using a semiautomated approach to identify validated requirements change from distinct crowds of SECO). Therefore, consultation with distinct crowds of SECO has not been executed.

8.4.1 Learning Experience (S8)

The participant reported that learning the method was positive in several moments, but in some moments, they needed to refer to the description of the method to understand better what he really needed to do in each activity. For this reason, he/she neither agreed nor disagreed on the process of learning to use the method to be a positive experience. However, they also highlighted that the learning curve for

applying the method was not steep. The SECO project manager highlighted that: *“learning the method included a document describing the method that contained a practical example and a document demonstrating the tool. When I had difficulty understanding what needed to be done in the activity, I looked at the figures, an example of this activity being performed in the tool”*. Moreover, the participant identified opportunities for improvement that could make the method learning experience more positive. For example, they mentioned that the method description was long and contained content repeated in the text, which could confuse the user. The SECO project manager claimed that: *“there are activities that have three sub-activities, and there are texts that are repeated, and this left me a little confused about what I should do in each of them”*. The participant reported that it is important that whoever applies the method understands it very well and relates it to the context of their ecosystem. Moreover, they expressed optimism that familiarity with the method would be gained through continued use and experience.

8.4.2 Clarity and Understanding (S9)

The participant agreed that the purposes and activities of SECO-RCI are clear and comprehensive. However, they highlighted that it would be important for the activity and sub-activity to highlight what is expected as an input and output. The SECO project manager suggested: *“something that could be improved in the description of activities would be to present a short initial text informing what that activity needs as input and what its result will be, that is, what is expected from the output of that activity”*. This feedback offers practical considerations for refining the method and improving their clarity and understanding.

8.4.3 Ease of Use (S10)

The participant agreed that SECO-RCI is easy to use. They pointed out challenges that emerged in specific activities, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement in the method. As strengths, the participant highlighted that the tool helps apply the method, facilitating its use. Furthermore, they mentioned that the activities and sub-activities refer to practices with which they are familiar, e.g., analyzing issues in GitHub to identify requirements change. The SECO project manager claimed

that: *“I liked the way the pattern detection results can be visualized. This allowed me to easily identify which feedback was related to a requirements change and which was not”*. As areas for improvement, the participant mentioned that the method did not describe how pattern detection is carried out and how environment settings related to keyword filters and user feedback status can impact the analysis. The SECO project manager mentioned that: *“I did several tests to familiarize myself with the tool and the method’s activities. I realized that the keywords defined when creating the environment impact detecting patterns in the feedback retrieved, but it is not too clear in the method description”*.

8.4.4 Usefulness (S11)

The participant agreed with the method’s utility in their daily tasks. The SECO project manager acknowledged its role in supporting the requirements change identification in SECO and highlighted that: *“I believe it could be useful. However, it would require more interaction with the tool to learn the best way to use it, e.g., the filters and consequent results (grouping of tickets)”*. The participant also mentioned that the method often requires the manager to know more technical terms from SECO projects so that he can correctly direct the analysis by choosing keywords. The SECO project manager stated that: *“The manager needs to know the projects technically to define the most appropriate keywords. This works for small project groups, as was my case. However, for larger project groups in which the manager does not have this prior knowledge, it may be that the information generated is too generic”*.

8.4.5 Impact on Job Performance (S12)

The participant neither agreed nor disagreed that utilizing the method would enhance their job efficiency. They highlighted that the tool grouped feedback related to a specific problem that could generate changes to requirements in the ecosystem. However, the participant tried to configure the CrowdRE environment keyword filter to achieve this result. The SECO project manager stated that: *“see the potential, but I am not convinced if the tool would be able to classify and group the tickets/issues in the best way without the manager’s prior knowledge. I believe that if the tool*

also showed the number of occurrences of a certain term that could be related to a requirements change, it would be excellent. This would greatly help the manager to verify the importance of that change for SECO. The manager often looks for changes to requirements in GitHub issues to analyze them. If the tool could show this to him concerning the number of times that changes appear, it would be super interesting”.

8.4.6 Is SECO-RCI Feasible From a Practical Perspective? (RQ - Study #2)

Based on the findings of Study #2, we gained valuable insights into the practical feasibility of SECO-RCI. One key consideration that emerged is the crucial need for a specific tool to carry out the method activities successfully. Their use is important because of the open and dynamic nature of SECO, which involves user feedback from several communication channels. Acceptance of SECO-RCI by the participant and recognition of its usefulness can be seen as a positive aspect of its practical applicability. The participant emphasized the potential for continual improvement and refinement of results through consistent application of the method. This statement underscores the dynamic nature of SECO-RCI, suggesting that with ongoing use, it can address the identification of changing requirements in SECO and promote advancements in requirements management in SECO.

8.5 Discussion

In this section, we discuss our research’s main findings and implications and propose how researchers and practitioners can use SECO-RCI.

8.5.1 Main Findings and Lessons Learned

We gathered insights and reflections along the process of designing and evaluating SECO-RCI, as described next:

- **Requirements change identification in SECO requires the involvement of experts in the SECO domain and technical aspects of the projects.** Both evaluation studies highlighted the importance of a deep understanding of the SECO and the projects that coevolve in this environment

while dealing with requirements change identification. The participants stated that this is fundamental for adequately applying SECO-RCI. Bogart et al. [37] corroborate this finding by stating that changes to one product can have cascading effects on several others in SECO, and a holistic view of the SECO from domain experts is necessary to avoid conflicts. According to Matute et al. [38], any discernible (and sometimes even apparently trivial) change in a software product will affect, for better or worse, its ecosystem;

- **The value of SECO-RCI increases with continuous use.** From the participants' comments, it becomes apparent that the method's value increases with continual use. As the professionals gain more experience with the method, they can more effectively identify the requirements change in SECO, considering their open and dynamic nature. The continuous application of the method allows the constant identification of keywords related to the multiple projects that co-evolve in SECO, which can result in greater effectiveness in identifying changes to requirements. Bogart et al. [37] mentioned that technical debt, bugs, new features, or rippling upstream changes trigger breaking SECO changes. For the authors, central planning in SE is increasingly giving way to decentralized development in SECO, in which developers build on a rich set of external contributions, from libraries to community documentation;
- **The use of SECO-RCI increases with the scale of SECO.** Applying SECO-RCI to large SECO introduces a high level of complexity due to the multitude of user feedback spread in several user feedback channels. Such circumstances create a highly complex scenario requiring careful attention. Bogart et al. [37] stated that SECO actors (e.g., internal and external developers) can reuse and build upon others' contributions, often aided by package management tools that support finding, installing, and publishing third-party packages in the ecosystem. According to the authors, software development in such a decentralized environment can be challenging and expose friction among loosely organized parties.

Regarding **lessons learned**, during the conduction of the evaluation studies,

we recognized the importance of including more professionals in the evaluation process. Professionals with a background on Information Technology bring valuable technical expertise. However, we included domain experts in the evaluation, and with their specialized knowledge, they provided additional insights concerning specific particularities, which was important in evaluating the method's adaptability. Another important lesson was the need to develop a tool that can encompass all method activities clearly, allowing participants to express their opinions on SECO-RCI without limitations.

8.5.2 Implications for Practitioners and Researchers

This study presents implications for **practitioners**, as presented next:

- **Improvement of requirements change identification in SECO.** Using SECO-RCI can lead to an improvement in requirements change identification in SECO. Executing the activities of the method, professionals can identify requirements change and define requirements change requests, considering user feedback spread in multiple SECO user feedback channels;
- **Improvement of the holistic view of a SECO regarding changes.** SECO-RCI allows professionals to have a holistic view regarding requirements changes that may affect different projects in SECO or the common technological platform. By offering this comprehensive view of requirements change in SECO, SECO-RCI allows professionals to make well-informed decisions, prioritize actions more efficiently, and coordinate their efforts more effectively;
- **Improvement of requirements communication in SECO.** SECO-RCI was perceived as a facilitator of effective communication among multiple SECO actors. It can help promote a shared understanding concerning requirements change, collaboration and co-creation, improved decision-making, and stakeholder engagement.

During the conduction of this study, we also identified implications for **researchers**, as in the following:

- **Change-oriented perspective for future research in SECO.** The use of SECO-RCI provides a comprehensive view of the SECO concerning requirements change identification. This comprehensive perspective can also improve other requirements management subprocesses;
- **Adaptability to diverse SECO types.** SECO-RCI can serve as a foundation for future research on adaptability in different SECO types. Researchers can explore how the method can be tailored and customized to specific domains. This research can lead to developing domain-specific extensions or variations of the method, enabling its effective application in a more significant range of SECO.

8.6 Threats and Limitations

In this section, we discuss the potential threats to our study and how we mitigate them. We also outline the study's limitations.

8.6.1 Threats

In this section, we discuss the potential threats to the validity of our evaluation studies. We categorize these threats according to Runeson's framework [98], which includes conclusion validity, internal validity, construct validity, and external validity.

Conclusion validity refers to the degree to which the conclusions we draw are reasonable based on the data and analyses used [98]. The variability in responses due to different participant experiences or interpretations of questions in both the focus group and the case study can impact our conclusions. Moreover, participants may have felt pressure to conform to the group's dominant opinions. To mitigate these threats, we employed a structured interview guide, provided consistent explanations of the SECO-RCI method across all sessions, encouraged open discussion, and explicitly invited differing perspectives to reduce this risk.

Internal validity pertains to the causal relationships observed in our research setting [98]. Since the focus group and case study were moderated by the same researcher, there is a potential for unintentional bias during data collection

and interpretation. Moreover, there is a risk that researchers may impose their interpretations on participants' responses rather than accurately capturing the participants' intended meanings. To mitigate this threat, we defined an interview guide with clear and objective questions presented during the interviews, comprising all concepts related to these questions. We also encouraged participants to reflect deeply on their answers. In addition, while the author of this thesis performed the main coding, the advisors, with more than 15 years in SE, were extensively involved in verifying the results and ensuring the compliance of the final dataset.

Construct validity focuses on how well the evaluation measures align with the theoretical constructs being studied [98]. The clarity and applicability of SECO-RCI activities were a primary focus of evaluation, yet there is a risk that some constructs may have been misunderstood. Moreover, differences in participants' familiarity with SECO concepts, open innovation practices, and CrowdRE may have led to variations in their interpretations and responses. To mitigate these threats, we provided detailed explanations of all activities of the SECO-RCI method, defined selection criteria to ensure a baseline level of expertise, and used structured questions based on established models such as the TAM.

External validity addresses the generalizability of the study's findings [98]. The focus group involved a small number of participants with a shared background in SECO and requirements management. Similarly, the case study focused on a single organization and SECO scenario. Therefore, the number, experience, and the fact that all participants worked with a single scenario of SECO are potential external threats to this study. While these participants offered rich insights, our findings may not generalize to all SECO contexts. To mitigate such threats, we selected professionals and experts with different backgrounds and experience in requirements management in SECO. This strategy contributed to a more significant variety of information with different perspectives. We also carried out studies from distinct perspectives. The first study focused on participants' perceptions of the method through demonstration and explanation. In contrast, the second one took a more practical approach, with one participant using the method and offering their opinions based on a practical experience.

8.6.2 Limitations

Acknowledging that our evaluation is limited to only one specific scenario is essential. While our findings and conclusions provide valuable insights into that particular context, validating the results in other contexts is crucial. By conducting studies in multiple contexts, we can assess the robustness and applicability of our findings across several scenarios. This assessment helps establish a broader understanding of the method's effectiveness and potential limitations in different real-world situations. Furthermore, exploring different contexts can uncover insights and nuances our studies might not capture. It can shed light on new challenges and contextual factors that may influence the implementation and outcomes of the method. Hence, such additional validation can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the method's capabilities and limitations.

8.7 Final Remarks

This chapter presented the analysis of the results of the evaluation of SECO-RCI, which was designed to capture the method's insights from the perceptual and practical perspectives. By considering usefulness and ease of use, we aimed to assess experts's and professionals' acceptance of the SECO-RCI method. Acceptance is an important aspect of the potential adoption and success of the method, as professionals who perceive usefulness and ease of use are more likely to adopt and incorporate it into their job.

SECO-RCI's contribution relies on offering a systematic approach to requirements change identification in SECO. To the best of our knowledge, requirements management activities aiming at requirements change identification in SECO often lack a systematic approach to guide practitioners. By using SECO-RCI, professionals can better understand SECO characteristics that differentiate it from other software development contexts and the requirements change identification in this context. Moreover, SECO-RCI enables more effective requirements communication among the multiple actors of distinct crowds of a SECO regarding requirements change, ensuring everyone is on the same page. It also supports decision-making regarding the implementation of these requirements changes.

Chapter 9. Conclusion

9.1 Summary

The complex, dynamic, and distributed nature of SECO makes requirements management difficult in this context. In SECO, requirements can evolve rapidly due to changing market demands, technological advancements, or user feedback. Moreover, the open and collaborative nature of SECO means that contributions come from multiple actors that may have different or conflicting objectives, making it challenging to maintain a unified view of requirements. The continuous integration of new components or updates can introduce unforeseen dependencies or conflicts, difficulting the requirements change identification. Current literature partially addresses requirements change identification in SECO, highlighting the need to develop approaches to address this challenge. Therefore, the SECO-RM conceptual model can guide researchers and practitioners in understanding the complexities of requirements management in SECO. In turn, the SECO-RCI method can address this issue by providing structured activities based on open innovation and CrowdRE that enable requirements change identification, considering the open and dynamic nature of SECO.

SECO-RCI has five main activities that are related to: (i) the identification of open innovation practices and feedback channels that can contribute to requirements change identification in SECO; (ii) the detection of patterns related to requirements change in the identified SECO user feedback channels; (iii) the identification of requirements change, considering the holistic view of SECO; (iv) the voting of distinct crowds of SECO to confirm and prioritize identified changes to requirements; and (v) the possibility of redefining requirements change identified considering the results of voting of distinct crowds of SECO. SECO-RCI considers the open innovation practices used in SECO to identify the needs of external actors during

requirements change identification. Moreover, it uses the CrowdRE paradigm to consider the distinct crowds of SECO in this process.

To evaluate SECO-RCI, we conducted two studies to investigate the feasibility of SECO regarding its ease of use and usefulness. The evaluation studies involve experts and professionals with theoretical and practical experience in requirements management in SECO. The first, a perceptual study, involved presenting and demonstrating SECO-RCI to experts with theoretical and practical experience who provided their perceptions and insights regarding the method. In the second, a practical study, one professional used SECO-RCI with the support of a web tool we developed. Then, they exposed their opinions from a practical perspective.

Based on our evaluation studies' results, we observed that SECO-RCI could potentially advance the state of the practice by offering a systematic approach to requirements change identification in SECO. To the best of our knowledge, no other approaches adequately address requirements identification in SECO while considering the open innovation practices and CrowdRE. By using SECO-RCI, professionals can better understand SECO characteristics that differentiate it from other software development contexts and the requirements change identification in this context. Moreover, SECO-RCI enables more effective requirements communication among the multiple actors of distinct crowds of a SECO regarding requirements change, ensuring everyone is on the same page. It also supports decision-making regarding the implementation of these requirements changes.

Regarding RQ of this thesis, we revisited them as follows:

- **RQ1: Which concepts are involved in requirements management in SECO, and how do they relate?** To answer this research question, we conducted an SMS on requirements management in SECO and three field studies on the subject, which allowed us to identify and analyze the key concepts in this area. Through our SMS, we reviewed the existing literature and identified characteristics and approaches of requirements management in SECO. This comprehensive analysis gave us a clear understanding of the concepts involved in requirements management and their interrelationships. Based on the findings of the SMS and of the field studies, we developed a conceptual model for requirements management in SECO. This model

organizes the key concepts of requirements management in SECO in a structured manner, illustrating how they are interconnected. The conceptual model serves as a representation of a theory, providing a holistic view of the topic;

- **RQ2: How to improve requirements change identification in SECO?** The main objective of this thesis was to address the challenge of improving requirements change identification in SECO, considering their inherent characteristics. We noticed that using open innovation practices and CrowdRE could be a feasible approach to improve requirements change identification in SECO. Therefore, we developed a method for requirements change identification in SECO based on open innovation and CrowdRE called SECO-RCI. By following SECO-RCI activities, professionals have a systematic approach to requirements change identification in SECO. The development of SECO-RCI was grounded in both scientific literature and practical observations. We aligned the method with the SECO-RM conceptual model, drawing upon established concepts and relationships from the literature and the practice.

9.2 Contributions

The main contributions of this thesis are listed below:

- A conceptual model for requirements management in SECO (SECO-RM) in which we organized the concepts and relationships involved in requirements management in SECO. The propositions that ground the conceptual model were evaluated in a Delphi study with 22 experts who provided feedback to improve the model. Moreover, such experts also evaluated the complete conceptual model regarding ambiguity, explanatory power, parsimony, generality, and utility. According to Sjøberg et al. [315], these criteria are the most relevant for evaluating empirically-based theories in software engineering, as in the case of SECO-RM;
- A method to assist practitioners' requirements change identification in SECO (SECO-RCI). It encompasses structured activities based on open innovation

and CrowdRE;

- A web-based tool that supports the use of SECO-RCI (SECO-RCR).

Moreover, the knowledge produced during the course of this thesis was disseminated through the following publications:

Malcher, P., Viana, D., Santos, R.P. Uma Abordagem para Gerência de Requisitos em Ecossistemas de Software. *2021 Thesis and Dissertations Workshop on Software (WTDSOft) of Brazilian Conference on Software: Theory and Practice (CBSoft)*. Santa Catarina, Brazil, 2021, pp. 19-27.

Malcher, P., Silva, E., Viana, D., Santos, R.P. What do we know about requirements management in software ecosystems *Requirements Engineering*. 28 (2023), pp. 567-593.

Malcher, P., Viana, D., Antonino P.O., Santos, R.P. Investigating Open Innovation Practices to Support Requirements Management in Software Ecosystems. *14th International Conference on Software Business (ICSOB)*. Lahti, Finland, 2023, pp. 35-50.

Malcher, P., Viana, D., Antonino P.O., Santos, R.P. Investigating User Feedback from a Crowd in Requirements Management in Software Ecosystems. *Empirical Software Engineering*. 29, 152 (2024).

Condina, V., Malcher, P., Farias, F., Santos, R.P., Fontão, A., Wiese, I., Viana, D., An Exploratory Study on Developers Opinions about Influence in Open Source Software Ecosystems. *XXXIV Brazilian Symposium on Software Engineering (SBES)*. Natal, Brazil, 2020, pp. 137-146.

Gonçalves, R., Malcher, P., Santos, R.P. Investigando a Rastreabilidade de Requisitos em Ecossistemas de Software. *2022 Thesis and Dissertation Workshop on Information Systems (WTDSI)*. Paraná, Brazil, 2022, pp. 75-80.

Gonçalves, R., Malcher, P., Costa, L.A, Santos, R.P. Investigating Human and

Social Factors in Requirements Engineering in Software Ecosystems. *XXI Brazilian Symposium on Software Quality (SBQS)*. Curitiba, Brazil, 2022, pp. 1-10.

Barbosa, A., Malcher, P., Santos, R.P. ReQSI-CI: Um Catálogo de Requisitos Não-Funcionais para Sistemas de Informação em Cidades Inteligentes sob a Perspectiva de Ecossistemas Digitais. *XXVI Workshop on Requirements Engineering (WER)*. Porto Alegre, Brazil, 2023, pp. 1-10.

Gonçalves, E., Malcher, P., Moraes, L., Viana, D., Santos, R.P. SECO-RCR: A tool to manage requirements change in software ecosystems. *XXXVIII Brazilian Symposium on Software Engineering (SBES)*. Curitiba, Brazil, 2024, pp. 782-788.

Medeiros, C., Malcher, P., Gonçalves, R., Santos, R.P. Investigating Solutions for Social and Human Factors in Requirements Engineering. *XXII Brazilian Symposium on Software Quality (SBQS)*. Salvador, Brazil, 2024.

Submitted and awaiting review

Malcher, P., Viana, D., Antonino P.O., Santos, R.P. Towards an understanding of requirements management in software ecosystems. *Information and Software Technology* [In the second round of review].

Malcher, P., Gonçalves, O., Fernandes, J., Coutinho, E., Rivero, L., Viana, D., Santos, R.P. Investigating Stakeholders' Perceptions of the Software Supply Network Model and Requirements Management in the SOLAR Educational Software Ecosystem. *Journal of Systems and Software* [In the first round of review].

Ready for submission

Malcher, P., Barbosa, O., Viana, D., Santos, R.P. Software Ecosystems: A Tertiary Study. *ACM Computing Surveys*.

Malcher, P., Viana, D., Antonino P.O., Santos, R.P. A method for requirements change identification in software ecosystems based on open innovation and CrowdRE. *Journal of Systems and Software*.

Other Publications

Carvalho, R., Malcher, P., Santos, R.P. A Survey Research on the Use of Mobile Applications in Software Project Management. *XIX Brazilian Symposium on Software Quality (SBQS)*. São Luís, Brazil, 2020, pp. 1-10.

Antonio, N., Dias, R., Malcher, P., Horita, F., Santos, R.P. Mapping Organizational Tensions Using KIPO in Federated Information Systems: A Case Study in a Brazilian Bank. *XVII Brazilian Symposium on Information Systems (SBSI)*. Uberlândia, Brazil, 2021, pp. 1-8 (Article 24).

Barbosa, A., Malcher, P., Farias, V., Santos, R.P. Exploring Business Opportunities in the Domain of Smart Cities from Informal Systems. *XLVII Latin American Computing Conference (CLEI)*. Cartago, Costa Rica, 2021, pp. 1-10.

Barbosa, A., Malcher, P., Santos, R.P. SIGMA Net Zero: Um Sistema de Contabilização da Pegada de Carbono e Gestão das Emissões de Gases de Efeito Estufa. *XIX Brazilian Symposium on Information Systems (SBSI)*. Maceió, Brazil, 2023, pp. 81-83.

Barbosa, A., Malcher, P., Santos, R.P. Um Catálogo de Requisitos Não Funcionais para Sistemas de Informação em Cidades Inteligentes sob a Perspectiva de Ecossistemas Digitais. *V Thesis and Dissertation Contest on Information Systems (CTDSI)*. Maceió, Brazil, 2023, pp. 1-3.

Gonçalves, R., Malcher, P., Santos, R.P. Fatores Sociais e Humanos na Gerência de Requisitos em Ecossistemas de Software. *VI Thesis and Dissertation Contest on Information Systems (CTDSI)*. Juiz de Fora, Brazil, 2024, pp. 117-119.

Gonçalves, R., Malcher, P. Santos, R.P. Investigating Social and Human Factors in Requirements Management in Software Ecosystems. *Thesis and Dissertation Contest on Software Quality (CTDQS)*. Salvador, Brazil, 2024.

9.3 Limitations

In this section, we address the limitations encountered during this research. Recognizing these limitations sets the scope of our research and guides future studies toward potential improvements.

SECO-RCI's evaluation was primarily focused on its acceptance. While our initial evaluation of SECO-RCI produced promising results that encouraged its implementation, it demands further rigorous assessments. The focus group involved a specific set of experts whose perspectives, although valuable, may not fully represent the diversity of stakeholders in several SECO. Additionally, while providing in-depth insights, the single case study may not capture the complexities and variances present in different types of SECO. Therefore, evaluating the method's effectiveness in several scenarios with distinct challenges and specific characteristics is essential. A broader range of case studies across diverse SECO would be necessary to comprehensively validate the method's applicability and effectiveness. This approach allows for a rigorous assessment of its effectiveness based on hypothesis testing.

While theoretically sound, the conceptual model on which the method is based may not fully account for the dynamic and evolving nature of SECO in practice. Moreover, the reliance on open innovation and crowdRE assumes a certain level of engagement and quality in the contributions from external stakeholders, which may not always be consistent or reliable. These factors could affect the practical implementation and sustainability of the method in real-world scenarios, necessitating further refinement and continuous adaptation of the model to ensure its long-term viability in different SECO.

9.4 Implications

This section discusses the implications of the SECO-RCI method for both practitioners and researchers. By addressing practical and theoretical dimensions,

these implications provide insights into how SECO-RCI can influence industry practices in requirements change identification in SECO and contribute to the academic advancement of requirements management knowledge.

For practitioners, the focus is on the method's utility and potential to improve existing processes, while for researchers, the emphasis is on its value as a basis for further exploration and development of innovative concepts in SECO requirements management. Key implications for practitioners are as follows:

- **Enhanced efficiency in requirements management:** SECO-RCI provides a systematic approach to identifying and managing requirements changes, potentially reducing the effort involved in this process. Industry practitioners can benefit from more streamlined communication and coordination among the distinct crowds within a SECO, leading to faster decision-making and more efficient prioritization of changes;
- **Adaptability across diverse SECO:** The method is designed to accommodate the dynamic and collaborative nature of SECO, making it adaptable to various industry contexts. This flexibility can benefit companies operating within complex ecosystems that involve multiple stakeholders with different objectives;
- **Improved collaboration and stakeholder alignment:** By incorporating open innovation practices and CrowdRE, SECO-RCI encourages active collaboration among all stakeholders, enhancing the alignment between diverse actors in the SECO. This improved collaboration can lead to a more unified view of evolving requirements and a clearer understanding of collective priorities;
- **Enhanced data-driven decision-making:** SECO-RCI leverages data from various sources, including feedback from multiple stakeholders, to prioritize and confirm requirements changes. This data-driven approach allows practitioners to make more informed, evidence-based decisions, reducing the reliance on intuition or limited viewpoints and fostering a balanced consideration of different perspectives in an ecosystem.

For researchers, SECO-RCI presents a valuable foundation for understanding and advancing the research of requirements management in SECO. While practitioners may focus on practical utility, researchers can delve into its theoretical underpinnings, evaluate its broader implications, and explore new avenues for innovation. Key implications for researchers are as follows:

- **Advancement of knowledge in RE:** SECO-RCI addresses a key gap in the existing body of knowledge by providing a structured approach to requirements change identification that considers the complexities of SECO. Its integration of open innovation and CrowdRE paradigms expands the theoretical foundations of requirements engineering, emphasizing collaborative and participatory approaches in dynamic environments.
- **Comprehensive conceptual model:** The SECO-RM conceptual model that grounded the SECO-RCI method provides a well-structured framework that illustrates the interconnections between key concepts in requirements management specific to SECO. It serves as a tool for academics to better understand how requirements evolve within these ecosystems and how changes can be systematically managed.
- **Empirical insights into SECO management:** By documenting the development, evaluation, and application of SECO-RCI, this research provides empirical evidence and practical insights into managing requirements changes within SECO. Such insights deepen the understanding of how different factors—such as stakeholder diversity, collaborative dynamics, and feedback mechanisms—impact the requirements engineering process.
- **Exploration of open innovation and CrowdRE paradigms:** The method emphasizes the potential of open innovation and CrowdRE within requirements management, offering a foundation for exploring how these paradigms can improve engagement, capture diverse perspectives, and address the needs of various SECO actors. This has implications for research into participatory design, social computing, and collaborative software development.

9.5 Future Work

It is crucial to consider potential avenues for future research and development. These forward-looking perspectives promote the evolution and refinement of our work on the SECO-RCI and broaden the scope of its applicability.

Future work should consider conducting additional evaluation studies across diverse scenarios to identify potential refinements for the SECO-RCI method. It can involve multiple case studies across various domains to assess the method's robustness, adaptability, and effectiveness in different contexts. Additionally, it is important to acknowledge the potential of simulated environments in evaluating SECO-RCI. This approach enables manipulating variables and observing outcomes in a risk-free environment, paving the way to refine SECO-RCI for more complex real-world scenarios. By extending our research into several contexts, we can fine-tune SECO-RCI to handle a broader range of challenges in the requirements change identification in SECO and ensure its continuous evolution.

Additionally, future work should consider the refinement of the conceptual model that underpins the method. While the current model provides a strong foundation for requirements management in SECO, it may need to evolve due to its dynamic and rapidly changing nature. Future studies could investigate the model's scalability to enhance its utility and robustness, considering the impact of different SECO characteristics.

Another significant area of interest for future exploration involves the role of stakeholder engagement in the SECO-RCI's success. The method relies heavily on the assumption that stakeholders will actively and consistently contribute valuable input through open innovation and CrowdRE. However, engagement levels can vary widely, and factors such as motivation, expertise, and diversity of participants can significantly impact the quality of the requirements identified. Future research could explore techniques to enhance stakeholder engagement, such as gamification, incentives, or more effective communication channels, to ensure a steady flow of high-quality input. Understanding the social dynamics and motivations behind stakeholder participation will be crucial for optimizing the method's effectiveness.

Finally, future work should explore the integration of SECO-RCI with other activities and tools of requirements change management process in SECO. This

integration would facilitate a smoother transition from requirements change identification to requirements change analysis and cost estimation. Research could focus on developing tools, plug-ins, or API that promote this integration.

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Appendix A. Supplementary Material by Chapter

Table A.1: Supplementary Material by Chapter.

Chapter	Description	Link
Chapter 4	Supplementary material of tertiary study on SECO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10790626
Chapter 4	Supplementary material of systematic mapping study on requirements management in SECO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8131745
Chapter 5	Supplementary material of the first field study	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13340212
Chapter 5	Supplementary material of the second field study	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038855
Chapter 5	Supplementary material of the third field study	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13367845
Chapter 6	Supplementary material of SECO-RM conceptual model	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13369678
Chapter 7	Supplementary material of SECO-RCR tool (code)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11432155
Chapter 7	Supplementary material of SECO-RCR tool (demonstration)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14056341
Chapter 8	Supplementary material of the SECO-RCI method and SECO-RCR tool	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13730925